

UNIVERSITY OF THE WEST OF SCOTLAND

**BRAND ATTITUDE, PERCEIVED VALUE AND PURCHASE INTENTION
IN THE AUTOMOBILE INDUSTRY IN GHANA:
A COMPARATIVE AND MIXED METHODOLOGICAL PERSPECTIVE**

BY

FREDERICK OKYERE ASIEDU

DECLARATION

I declare that this thesis is original and was written by me and has not been submitted to any institution for an any award. The citations inherent are duly referenced as well.

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DATE

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TABLE OF CONTENT

DECLARATION	i
ACKNOWLEDGMENT.....	ii
TABLE OF CONTENT	iii
LIST OF TABLES	x
LIST OF FIGURES	xi
ABBREVIATIONS	xii
ABSTRACT.....	xiii
CHAPTER ONE.....	1
INTRODUCTION	1
1.0 Chapter Overview	1
1.1 Research Background	1
1.2 Research Aim.....	4
1.3 Research Objectives.....	4
1.4 Research Question	5
1.5 Research Process.....	5
1.6 Research Gaps and Problem Statement	5
1.6.1 Issue Gap.....	5
1.6.2 Context Gap	6
1.6.3 Methodological Gap.....	7
1.7 Academic Benefits	12
1.8 Practical Benefits to Companies	12
1.9 Thesis Structure	12
1.10 Scope of the Study	13
CHAPTER TWO	14
LITERATURE REVIEW	14
2.0 Introduction.....	14
2.1 The Concept of Branding.....	15
2.2 Key Components of a Brand.....	16
2.3 Requirements for Developing an Effective Brand.....	16
2.4 Benefits of Branding.....	17
2.5 Brand Development in the Automobile Industry.....	18
2.6 Product and Brands Life Cycle in the Automobile Industry.....	19

2.7 Perspectives of Branding	20
2.8 Brand Orientation.....	21
2.9 Brand Intangibles	21
2.9.1 Brand Past	22
2.9.1.1 History.....	22
2.9.1.2 Heritage.....	22
2.9.2 Brand Present.....	23
2.9.2.1 Brand Values.....	23
2.9.2.2 Brand Personality.....	23
2.9.2.3 Brand Character	24
2.9.3 Brand Future	24
2.10 The Influence of Brand Intangibles on Purchasing Decisions.....	24
2.11 Employees Role in Building Brands.....	25
2.12 Brand Equity.....	25
2.12.1 Brand Awareness	26
2.12.2 Brand Association.....	26
2.12.3 Perceived Quality.....	26
2.12.4 Brand Loyalty	27
2.13 Digital Branding.....	27
2.13.1 Social Media Branding	27
2.13.2 Online Reputation	28
2.13.3 E-Commerce Strategies	29
2.14 Brand Experience.....	29
2.15 Brand Purpose.....	30
2.16. Brand Authenticity.....	30
2.17 Brand Extensions	31
2.18 Challenges to Brand Building Success	31
2.19 Organisational Buying Behaviour.....	32
2.20 Branding and Business Markets.....	32
2.21 Conceptualisation of Attitude	33
2.22 The Concept of Brand Attitude.....	34
2.23 Components of Brand Attitude	35
2.24 Benefits of Brand Attitude	36
2.25 The Role of Pricing in Firms	37
2.25.1 Price Sensitivity	38
2.26 Perceptions.....	39

2.27 Definitions of Perceived Value.....	39
2.28 Importance of Perceived Value.....	40
2.29 Dimensions of Perceived Value.....	41
2.29.1 Functional Value.....	43
2.29.1.1. Functional Value, Perceived Quality.....	43
2.29.1.2 Functional Value, Perceived Price.....	44
2.29.2 Social Value.....	44
2.30 Relationships Among Perceived Value Constructs.....	46
2.31 Purchase Intentions.....	47
2.32 Brand Attitude and Purchase Intention.....	47
2.33 Brand Attitude and Perceived Value.....	49
2.33.1 Brand Attitude and Perceived Quality.....	50
2.33.2 Brand Attitude and Perceived Price.....	51
2.33.3 Brand Attitude and Social Value.....	52
2.34 Perceived Value and Purchase Intention.....	52
2.34.1 The Relationship between Perceived Quality and Purchase Intention.....	53
2.34.2 The Relationship between Perceived Price and Purchase Intention.....	54
2.34.3 The Relationship between Social Value and Purchase Intention.....	55
2.35 Brand Attitude, Perceived Value and Purchase Intention.....	56
CHAPTER THREE.....	58
THEORETICAL BACKGROUND.....	58
3.0 Introduction.....	58
3.1. Nudge Theory.....	58
3.2 The Theory of Reasoned Action.....	60
3.3 Theory of Planned Behaviour (TPB).....	60
3.4 The Expectancy Theory.....	61
3.5 Means-End Chain Theory.....	62
CHAPTER FOUR.....	64
CONTEXT OF THE STUDY.....	64
4.0 Introduction.....	64
4.1 The Vehicle Infrastructure.....	64
4.2 Impact of Automobiles on the Culture of Road Usage.....	65
4.3 Evolution of the Global Automobile Industry.....	66
4.4 The Value Chain within the Automobile Industry.....	69
4.5 The Global Automobile Value Provision (The Upstream and Downstream).....	71
4.5.1 Upstream Supply Chain.....	72

4.5.1.1 Supplier Selection Criteria in the Automobile Industry	73
4.5.1.2 Supplier Adaptation to Developments within the Automobile Industry	74
4.5.1.3 Additive Manufacturing and its Supply Chain implications.....	74
4.5.2 Automobile Marketing Channels (Downstream).....	75
4.5.2.1 Criteria for Selecting Marketing Channel Members.....	75
4.6 Productivity Analysis of Global Automobile Manufacturers	76
4.7 High Capital Intensity and Large Economies of Scale	77
4.8 Impact of Covid-19 on the Automobile Industry.....	77
4.9 Internationalisation Strategies in the Automobile Industry	78
4.10 The Role of the Automobile Industry in Economic Development	80
4.11 The World’s Major Global Automobile Producers	81
4.12 Vehicle Policies and Standards in Africa.....	81
4.13 Importation of Vehicle in Africa.....	83
4.14 Automotive Production in Africa.....	84
4.15 Automobile Manufacturing Challenges in Africa.....	86
4.16 Used and New Vehicle Adoption in Africa	86
4.17 Adoption of Electric Vehicles in Africa	87
4.18 Electric Vehicle in Ghana	87
4.19 Profile and Economy of Ghana.....	88
4.20 The Automobile Industry in Ghana	90
4.20.1 Importation of Vehicles into Ghana.....	91
4.20.2 Automobile Assembling Vehicles in Ghana.....	91
4.20.2.1 Volkswagen.....	93
4.20.2.2 Nissan.....	93
4.20.2.3 Toyota	94
4.20.2.4 Sinotruk.....	94
4.20.2.5 Kantanka Automobile	94
CHAPTER FIVE	96
RESEARCH METHODOLOGY	96
5.0 Introduction.....	96
5.1 Philosophical Assumptions and Research Paradigms.....	96
5.2 Research Approaches.....	98
5.3 Research Strategies	98
5.4 Methods.....	99
5.5 Research Population.....	100
5.6 Sampling Technique	101

5.7 Sample Size.....	102
5.8 Horizon	103
5.9 Techniques and Procedures.....	103
5.9.1 Data Collection Instruments	103
5.9.2 Validity and Reliability in Quantitative Studies	104
5.9.2.1 Validity	104
5.9.2.2 Reliability.....	105
5.9.3 Reliability and Validity of Qualitative Studies	105
5.9.3.1 Reliability.....	105
5.9.3.2 Validity	106
5.9.4 Pre-Testing of Data Collection Instruments	106
5.10 Data Analysis	106
5.10.1 Data Screening.....	106
5.10.2 Factor Analysis (FA).....	107
5.10.3 Structural Equation Modelling.....	107
5.11 Thematic Analysis	108
5.12 Data Integration	109
5.13 Ethical Consideration.....	110
CHAPTER SIX.....	111
QUANTITATIVE DATA ANALYSIS AND RESULTS	111
6.0 Introduction.....	111
6.1 The Demographic Profile of Respondents.....	111
6.2 Automobile Brands Preferences of Respondents.....	112
6.3 Exploratory Factor Analysis (EFA)	114
6.4 Confirmatory Factor Analysis (CFA).....	117
6.4.1 Measurement Model	117
6.4.1.1 Validity and Reliability Tests	120
6.4.2 Confirmatory Factor Analysis without Mediator.....	121
6.4.2.1 Significance Testing Results.....	122
6.4.3 Confirmatory Factor Analysis with Mediator.....	123
6.4.3.1 Structural Model Assessment Results.....	124
6.4.3.2 Relationships Among Variables and Constructs.....	124
6.4.4 Multi Group Analysis	125
6.4.4.1 Global Test.....	126
6.4.4.2 Local Test Results.....	126
6.4.5 Moderated Mediation (MyModMed) Relationship	127

6.4.5.1 Perceived Value	127
CHAPTER SEVEN	130
QUALITATIVE DATA ANALYSIS AND RESULTS	130
7.0 Introduction.....	130
7.1 Thematic Analytical Process.....	130
7.2 Demographic Profile of Participants.....	131
7.3 Attitude towards Automobile Vehicle Brands	132
7.3.1 Likability of Locally Assembled Vehicle Brands.....	132
7.3.2 Attractiveness to Locally Assembled Vehicle Brands.....	133
7.3.3 Favourability Towards Locally Assembled Vehicle Brands	133
7.4 The Role of Perceived Value in the Automobile Industry.....	133
7.4.1 Perceived Quality	133
7.4.2 Perceived Price.....	134
7.4.3 Social Value	135
7.5 A Stronger Preference for Locally Assembled Vehicle Brands	135
7.5.1 Economic Factors that Affect Marketing Environment.....	136
7.5.1.1 High Inflationary Rate	136
7.5.1.2 High Interest Rates.....	137
7.5.1.3 Foreign Exchange	138
7.5.2 Marketing Improvements.....	138
7.5.2.1 Competitiveness and Market Share within the Automobile Market.....	138
7.5.2.2 Good National Image.....	139
CHAPTER EIGHT	140
DATA INTEGRATION	140
8. 0 Introduction.....	140
8.1 Data Integration	140
CHAPTER NINE.....	146
DISCUSSION OF RESULTS	146
9.0 Introduction.....	146
9.1 Discussion of Quantitative Results	146
9.2 Discussion of Qualitative Results	151
CHAPTER TEN.....	155
CONCLUSIONS OF THE RESEARCH.....	155
10.0 Introduction.....	155
10.1 Research Contributions.....	159
10.1.1 Contributions to Theory.....	159

10.1.2 Contributions to Knowledge	159
10.1.2.1 Original Approach	159
10.1.2.2 Empirical (Understudied Area) Contribution	159
10.1.2.3 Method Contribution.....	160
10.1.3 Original Results Contribution	160
10.1.4 Contributions to Practice.....	161
10.2 Limitations of the Study.....	162
10.3 Directions for Future Research	163
REFERENCES	164
APPENDIX A.....	234
QUESTIONNAIRE	234
APPENDIX B	236
INTERVIEW GUIDE.....	236
APPENDIX C	238
MAIN RELATED STUDIES	238
APPENDIX D.....	270
PARTICIPANT CONSENT FORM.....	270
APPENDIX E	272
PARTICIPANT INFORMATION SHEET	272

LIST OF TABLES

Table 6.1: Descriptive Statistics: Demographic Profile of Respondents	111
Table 6.2: Descriptive Statistics: Automobile Brands Preferences of Respondents	113
Table 6. 3: KMO and Bartlett’s Test	114
Table 6. 4: Rotated Component Matrix	115
Table 6. 5: Cronbach Alpha Test	116
Table 6. 6: Improvement in Fit of Measurement Model.....	118
Table 6. 7: Validity Test	120
Table 6. 8: Reliability Test.....	121
Table 6. 9: Fit Indices for Final Measurement Model	122
Table 6. 10: Significance Results.....	122
Table 6. 11: Model Fit Indices	124
Table 6. 12: Structural Model Assessment Results	124
Table 6. 13: Structural Model Assessment Results	125
Table 6. 14: Global Test Results.....	126
Table 6. 15: Local Test Results.....	126
Table 6. 16: Perceived Quality, Moderated Mediation Relationship.....	128
Table 6. 17: Perceived Price, Moderated Mediation Relationship	128
Table 6. 18: Social Value, Moderated Mediation Relationship.....	129
Table 7. 1: Demographic Profile of Participants	131

LIST OF FIGURES

Figure 2. 1: Perceived Value Constructs for the Study.....	46
Figure 2. 2: Brand Attitude and Purchase Intention	49
Figure 2. 3: Brand Attitude and Perceived Value Constructs.....	50
Figure 2. 4: Perceived Value Constructs and Purchase Intention.....	53
Figure 2. 5: The Conceptual Framework of the Research (Brand Attitude, Perceived Value Constructs and Purchase Intention)	56
Figure 4. 1: Supply chain of Automobile Industry	72
Figure 4. 2: Upstream and Down Stream of Supply Chain in Automobile Industry.....	74
Figure 4. 3: Map of Ghana.....	90
Figure 6. 1: Measurement Model After Deletion.....	119
Figure 6. 2: Structural Model: Testing Independent and Dependent Relationship.....	121
Figure 6. 3: Structural Model: Testing Independent, Dependent and Mediating Variable Relationships.....	123
Figure 6. 4: Summary of Quantitative Results.....	129
Figure 8. 1: Steps in Conducting Quantitative Aspect of the Study	142
Figure 8. 2: Integrating Quantitative and Qualitative Findings	144

ABBREVIATIONS

AIDA Model: Attention, Interest, Desire and Action

EFA: Exploratory Factory Analysis

CFA: Confirmatory Factor Analysis

CFI: Comparative Fit Index

GFI: Goodness of Fit Index

NFI: Normed Fit Index

RMSEA: Root Mean Squared Error of Approximation

ABSTRACT

Behavioural patterns such as attitude towards brands, perceived value and purchase intention have received attention by businesses and scholars. The objectives of the research were to determine the impact of brand attitude and the purchase intention of automobile brands, the mediating role of perceived value in the relationship between brand attitude and purchase intention of automobile brands. Other objectives of the research were to ascertain the impact of brand attitude and purchase intention of locally assembled vehicle brands compared to imported vehicle brands and to determine if there was a significant difference of perceived value in the relationship between brand attitude and the purchase intention of locally assembled vehicle brands compared to imported brands. Based on the objectives, the research question was how perceived value influenced brand attitude and purchase intention in the automobile industry in Ghana. The gaps that necessitated the conduct of this study were issue based, context and methods. This research was underpinned by the Nudge Theory, the Theory of Reasoned Action, Theory of Planned Behaviour, the Expectancy Theory and Means-End Theory. These relevant theories have attained high recognition in marketing literature and therefore formed the basis for their choice. In terms of methodology, the research employed pragmatist paradigm and survey as strategy. The sample size for the study was drawn from trade firms within Greater Accra Region. Convenience and Purposive sampling techniques were used for quantitative and qualitative studies respectively. The sample size for the quantitative aspect of the study was 654 and 15 for the qualitative part of the research. The research was cross-sectional in nature and structured questionnaires and semi-structured interview guides were employed to collect quantitative data and qualitative data respectively. Data was analysed using Structural Equation Modelling and Thematic Analysis for the quantitative and qualitative aspects of the study respectively. Explanatory Sequential Model was employed to generate qualitative findings to explain the quantitative findings that were initially obtained. Ethics were also considered before, during and after data collection. The quantitative results revealed that, brand attitude affected purchase intention of automobile brands. In addition to that, perceived value mediated the relationship between brand attitude and purchase intention. Furthermore, there was a stronger impact of brand attitude and purchase intention of locally assembled vehicle brands than imported brands. In addition, there was no significant difference among the perception of value among locally assembled vehicle brands and imported vehicle brands. The qualitative research sought to explain the quantitative results. The respondents revealed that they had more likeness, attractiveness and had more willingness to act favourably towards locally assembled vehicles than imported vehicle brands. Another result indicated that, perceived value played a significant role in the automobile industry. In addition, businesses were particular about perceived quality attributes which satisfy their requirements such as durability and conformance to specifications in automobile vehicle brands. In terms of perceived price, businesses were interested in purchasing automobile brands that had pricing commensurate with the quality of the automobile vehicles and reflected value for money. The finding of social value dimension within perceived value indicated that family members, colleagues and friends influenced intention to buy automobile brands. The study also revealed that, economic issues which were high inflationary rates, high interest rates and attracting of foreign exchanges motivated the interviewees preference for locally assembled vehicles. In addition, marketing improvements, which were competitiveness, market share and enhancing national image were also identified as reasons why the participants favoured locally assembled vehicle brands. The study expanded the literature on organisational behaviour by drawing sample from the travel trade, provided findings that can influence government policies and shape the strategies and programmes of automobile firms.

CHAPTER ONE

INTRODUCTION

1.0 Chapter Overview

The first chapter presented an introduction to the research. This chapter provided information on the research background. The chapter also focused on the research gaps that necessitated the conduct of this study. These were contextual, issue based and methodological. The introduction also demonstrated the originality of the thesis through empirical (understudied area), method and research objectives and questions. It also highlighted on the significance of the study, chapter disposition and the scope of the research. The chapter ended with a summary.

1.1 Research Background

Businesses in both the manufacturing and service sectors must regard behavioural patterns as a pre-requisite for achieving competitive advantage. This is because, marketing activities are directed at consumers. It is therefore imperative that marketers understand and appreciate the behavioural patterns of consumers and answer pertinent questions such as why and how consumers behave in order to achieving competitive advantage (Ko and Megehee, 2012; Lim et al., 2023). Research into behavioural factors such as attitude, perception and purchase intention aid marketers produce products that are properly tailored to meet the needs and wants of consumers (Bian and Forsythe, 2012; Ko et al., 2011). The study by Mitchell and Olson (1981) revealed that, a person's attitude involves unchanging and continuing resolve to behave in a particular manner. Even though attitudes are considered stable, it has been demonstrated that they have the possibility to change overtime (De Pelsmacker and Janssens, 2007; Savolainen et al., 2022). Brand attitude is recognised as a crucial notion in understanding the consumers' behavioural patterns (Mitchell and Olson, 1981; Lee and Kang, 2013).

According to Yim et al. (2014), the attitudes of individuals towards objects are based on an individuals' knowledge which they have acquired through sources such as the family, social, cultural and global. Researchers have identified that, a positive attitude towards a brand in the long run will result in marketing benefits such as minimal costs and reduced risks of introducing a new product that has a brand name and is already in existence (Boone and Kurtz, 2002; He et al., 2016). Ajzen and Fishbein (1977) explained that consumers tend to form a lasting like or abhorrence for a product after consistently studying the brand for some time, which has a lasting implication on the purchasing behaviour towards the product. This means that in the event that consumers develop favourable attitudes towards a brand, they become favourably disposed towards purchasing the product of the brand. On the other hand, the development of negative attitudes towards a brand has an adverse effect on the product of the brand, as consumers become unwilling to buy the product (Neal, 2000).

One key variable or theme that has received attention in the purchasing behavioural literature is purchase intention. Schiffman and Kanuk (2000) and Zhang et al. (2018) have indicated that purchase intention involves customers' willingness to buy a particular commodity. Research has demonstrated that consumers tend to be affected by external factors when making decisions regarding the purchasing of a product. Some of these factors, as noted by Lin and Siu (2020) included advertising, reputation and the nature of the product they intend to buy. Dodds et al. (1991) added that, consumers demonstrate purchasing intent after thorough assessment and selection. Ajzen and Fishbein (1977) found out that consumers would shape a predictable pattern of likes, dislikes after researching, and analysing products, which will influence their buying behaviour. They will therefore prefer to purchase items from that brand when customers have a positive brand attitude.

Brand attitude aid marketers to determine the perceptions of customers as well as their readiness to buy (Wang, 2010). It is in this regard that Ajzen and Fishbein (1977) argued that customers' intention to buy a particular product is usually a reflection of their subjective behavioural patterns. Brand attitude therefore facilitates the acceptance of a product, and it affects its perceived value (Yang and Mattila, 2014). Thus, the attitude that customers exhibit towards a brand is a major determinant of the perception of value attached to that brand (Alden et al., 2013). Perceived value is a pre-requisite for the survival of firms in highly competitive atmosphere (Rintamäki et al., 2006). Businesses must therefore recognise that brand attitude directly affect its perceived value. Thus, a positive increase in brand attitude will lead to a resultant effect on its perceived value (Kang and Sharma, 2012). Firms must therefore develop marketing strategies that take into consideration the perception of value that customers have (Alden et al., 2013).

Customers whether businesses or individual buyers play a very pivotal role in the development of automobile business (Gupta and Raman, 2022). The automotive industry has been recognised among the world's most important industries (European Automobile Manufacturers Association, 2021; Cachon and Olivares, 2010). The industry has been given the cognition as a large sector which comprises other sectors including financial services, insurance, steel and plastic industries (Wong and Mo, 2013). The automobile industry's leading countries, including China, the United States of America, European countries, and Japan, have tried to develop their vehicles by integrating their technology and consumer demand (Hildebrandt et. al., 2015; Shigeta and Hosseini, 2020). Although many businesses have similar goals and ambitions, they have unique features and strengths that position them as key competitors (Shigeta and Hosseini, 2020). The automobile industry which has a global outlook involves developing economies with their own national vehicle brands. This means that there are countries noted for specific brands. For instance, Hyundai and Kia brands are linked to South Korea, while China is recognised with Chery, Dongfeng and Fengshen brands (Wong and Mo, 2013). Research has shown that the automotive industry has been the backbone or driving force for the growth of many economies in the world. As a result of this, the industry has become a very dynamic one due to the evolving nature of global economies (Kulkarni and Rao, 2014). The research findings of Bharadwaj (2015) reported that the automotive industry is constantly evolving in a rapid manner in the areas of technological innovation, adherence to sterner governmental guidelines and structural shifts, which have been influenced by unstable preferences of consumers. The nature of the automobile industry has made it a capital-intensive industry, with a lower labour ration when compared to many other industries, even in countries that are driven by manufacturing industries (Saber,

2018). It has also been noted through research that the automotive industry is a particular industry that exports the majority of its products to foreign markets, and this has made the industry greatly reliant on the conditions of its external market (Bharadwaj, 2015).

Decision-making process towards the purchasing of an automobile product is enormously complex. As a result, the decision to buy a particular vehicle by a consumer is often preceded by caution (Narteh et al., 2013). The majority of customers perceive the idea to own a new vehicle as a fundamental investment which requires a thorough review and analysis (Erasmus et al., 2014). Hence, a potential customer finally makes a decision to acquire a new automobile after the analysing and evaluating options available on the market (Brunello, 2015). Apart from customers who purchase for personal consumption, there are also businesses that are customers of automobile firms. These customers purchase products from businesses and other sources to produce goods or deliver services to firms, groups or individual consumers (Webster Jr and Keller, 2004). Before a decision is made in acquiring a particular vehicle, the potential customer consults various experts or automobile dealers in the industry who tend to provide the buyer with an established criterion hierarchy of options, which the buyer uses to review the various models that are available on the market (Nayeem and Casidy, 2013). This has made the process of choosing the right vehicle to purchase from the numerous vehicles on the market a very cumbersome task. Regarding this, Brunello (2015) indicated that knowledge of brands has become a crucial determinant or tool that is employed by potential buyers of vehicles in settling on the kind of vehicle to purchase. Consequently, automobile firms are presenting information on diverse brands of vehicles to persuade potential clients to accept their products as capable of meeting their ever-growing needs (Maheshwari et al., 2016). Wong and Mo (2013) asserted that to be competitive, it is necessary for automobile manufacturers to have knowledge of purchasing intentions. In this way, their marketing plan could be organised in a manner that could enable their firms generate more revenue, obtain market share and stay competitive in the worldwide automotive market.

In 1990, trade was liberalised across the world and as a result, restrictions on number of importations were removed and import duties were reduced (Ikome et al., 2022). Memedovic and Humphrey (2003) further explained that there was exponential increase in the number of automobile production facilities in developing economies due to economic growth and transformation. According to Alfaro et al. (2012), automobiles manufacturing figures was growing worldwide more than the number of humans. The liberalisation also threatened control measures and strategic approaches such as achieving local content demands and balance in foreign exchange (Ikome et al., 2022). As a result, vehicle manufacturers started prioritising developing economies and developed plans that will aid achieve their corporate goals and objectives. Vehicle manufacturers identified markets from developing economies and expanded their operations and obtained less expensive sites (Humphrey and Memedovic, 2003). This became necessary because the production of automobiles in Japan, Western-Europe and North America had witnessed saturated markets. The markets were also characterised with over-production with high price, low profits and a stagnation in demand (Barnes and Kaplinsky, 2000).

One of the emerging economies that has a growing automobile market is Ghana. In Ghana, the automobile industry is one of the most profitable market due to access to vehicle loans and

improved remuneration of workers (Sedzro et al., 2014). The situation of market liberalisation in the sub-Saharan Africa, including Ghana, has also created a novel economic structure where businesses compete to gain their customers' attention and attract them to their brands. As a result, customers have gained exposure to a variety of brands on a regular basis to fulfil their increasing needs (Narteh et al., 2013). The automobile industry in Ghana is characterised by many retailers who import used brands and a small number of distributors who market brand new vehicles. Statistics indicated that Ghana imports of an estimated 100,000 automobiles annually. The value of the importation is around US\$1.14 billion per year and about 90% of the automobiles are used (International Trade Administration, 2022). The country has introduced the Ghana Automotive Development Policy in 2019 to encourage the establishment of assembling and production of vehicles by automobile firms to minimise the enormous reliance on the high importation of used automobile firms (International Trade Administration, 2022).

1.2 Research Aim

The study employed a mixed methodological approach to determine how purchase intention within the automobile industry in Ghana was influenced by brand attitude and perceived value. Quantitatively, the study sought to generally, ascertain the effect of the causal relationships among the various variables (brand attitude, perceived value and purchase intention) in the automobile industry and specifically, tested the impact of these variables among locally assembled vehicle brands and imported vehicle brands. Qualitatively, the research sought to provide explanations on the quantitative results through exploring and providing deeper insights into issues of brand attitude, perceived value and purchase intention within the automobile industry in Ghana. This expanded the scope and provided multiple perspectives of the literature relating to brand attitude, perceived behaviour and purchase intention.

1.3 Research Objectives

The study objectives were highlighted below:

- i. To determine the impact of brand attitude and the purchase intention of automobile brands in Ghana
- ii. To determine the mediating role of perceived value in the relationship between brand attitude and purchase intention of automobile brands in Ghana
- iii. To ascertain the impact of brand attitude and purchase intention of locally assembled vehicle brands compared to imported vehicle brands in Ghana
- iv. To determine if there was a significant difference of perceived value in the relationship between brand attitude and the purchase intention of locally assembled vehicle brands compared to imported brands in Ghana
- v. To investigate the perspectives of attitude developed towards brands within the automobile industry (locally assembled and imported brands) in Ghana
- vi. To investigate the dimensions of perceived value that are relevant to the automobile industry (locally assembled and imported brands) in Ghana

- vii. To identify reasons for the quantitative outcomes of brand attitude, perceived value and purchase intention in the automobile industry in Ghana

1.4 Research Question

The research question was how does perceived value influenced brand attitude and purchase intention in the automobile industry in Ghana?

1.5 Research Process

The research process described the various stages that were implementation in the conduct of the study. The researcher reviewed extant literature to develop the topic and the gaps. The researcher then set objectives that were distinct from other scholars. Literature related to the topic were reviewed using key words. The review included peer-reviewed articles and credible websites. The context which entailed information related to the automobile industry, Africa and Ghana were developed. Methodological approaches that blended quantitative and qualitative approaches specifically structured questionnaires and semi-structured interview guides were used to collect data. Data was collected from travel trade and Structural Equation Modelling was employed to undertake quantitative data analysis. Thematic Analysis was then employed to undertake qualitative data analysis. This resulted in collection of qualitative data to explain the quantitative findings due to the choice of explanatory sequential modelling. Findings of the results were presented, and discussions of findings were also done. The researcher then developed the conclusion of the research.

1.6 Research Gaps and Problem Statement

This research issue, context and methodological gaps necessitated the conduct of this research. The identified gaps were categorised into issue, context and methods. This study contributed to the filling of the lacuna identified in the literature.

1.6.1 Issue Gap

This study contributed to dimensions of perceived value in relation to attitude towards brands, perception of value and purchase intention. Although researchers have studied attitude towards brands, perceived value and the purchasing intentions of customers, most of these studies approached perceived value from a unidimensional perspective. Research by Charton-Vachet et al. (2020) into regional food products in France for instance revealed that, perception of value played a very significant role in consumers attitude exhibited towards brands and their intention to buy food products in Vendee region. Another study by Balaji and Maheswari (2021) also discovered that, the features inherent in a store in India affected the attitude exhibited by individuals who embark on shopping which affected their intention to purchase. Gan and Wang (2017), however noted that, most of these studies have focused on the general perceived value,

with little attention devoted to the dimensions of perceived value. This research therefore contributed to the multi-dimensional perspective of analysing perceived value.

Furthermore, this study also examined the effect of brand attitude, perceived value and purchase intention in relation to imported vehicles brands and locally assembled brands. The result revealed that, there was a stronger impact of brand attitude, perceived value and purchase intention among locally assembled vehicle brands than imported brands. The study also concluded that, there was no difference among the perception of value among locally assembled vehicle brands compared to imported vehicle brands. These findings are novel and contributed to the behavioural literature regarding brand attitude, perceived value and purchase intention.

Generally, this study also contributed to the call for more studies in areas of brand attitude, perceived value and purchase intention to enhance the behavioural literature of customers. Salehzadeh and Pool (2017) for instance who researched luxury brands in Iran asserted that, one issue that managers of firms of which the automobile industry is of no exception face is the proper development of the concepts of brand attitude, perceived value and purchase intention. As a result, Molahoseini and Tajoddini (2015) who studied the clothing market in Iran made a call for further studies into brand attitudes, perceived value and purchase intentions to bring clarity to both researchers and managers and enhance knowledge in the area.

Furthermore, there are some studies on brands and business organisational buying behaviour. Alexander et al. (2009) study in South Africa revealed that, mining companies prioritised brand as the most important factor in purchasing tyres for business activities. This was followed by durability and price. Another research by Michell et al. (2001) revealed that, branding played an important role in charging premium price by accounting firms who provided services to other organisations in the United Kingdom. Hien and Nhu (2022) also conducted a study on business customers in Vietnam. The study revealed that, attitude towards digital marketing impacted on the purchase intention. Glynn et al. (2007) research in New Zealand among businesses revealed that, distribution channel members obtained financial, customer and managerial benefits from producers. The presence of these benefits resulted in the attainment of satisfaction, dependence, cooperation, commitment and trust of a producer's brand. Herbst and Merz (2011) researched into brand personality in industrial markets in Germany. The findings indicated that, brand personality was an important variable in measuring brand management activities in business markets. Chang et al. (2020) also studied the intention of procurement officers to buy for their organisations in Taiwan. The results revealed that, some members of the buying centre, specifically procurement personnel's intention to purchase for their firms are influence by perception of value held about the products. Despite the existence of these studies, there is a lacuna on the study of brand attitude, perceived value and purchase intention in the automobile industry from a business market perspective.

1.6.2 Context Gap

The automobile industry was previously dominated by manufacturers in developed countries who provided for home countries and engaged in export and foreign direct investment in host

countries in both developing and developed economies. In recent times, however, developing countries are also contributing immensely to the automobile industry (Mali et. al., 2022). Ghana's automobile industry was previously characterised by imported vehicles but the country in recent times is experiencing a surge in the number of automobile brands that aim to assemble vehicles in the country (International Trade Administration, 2022). Brands such as Nissan, Toyota, Suzuki and Renault are making progress at having assembling presence in Ghana. Other brands, which include Kantanka, a locally owned company and Volkswagen, have started producing vehicles for the Ghanaian market. Despite these developments, studies on automobile brands attitude and behavioural intentions in developing economies is sparse (Sedzro et al., 2014; Bera and Maitra, 2023; Zhang and Dong, 2023). Most studies in the automobile industry, including De Haan et al. (2009), Lieven et al. (2011) and Bigerna et al. (2016) have focused on developed economies. In their studies, researchers such as Simon and Reed (2007), Peters et al. (2011) and Thoburn (2022) have pointed out that the automobile industry is experiencing market saturation in developed economies but there is an increasing growth within the developing countries. There is therefore potential for developing countries to be a major market for automobiles. In addition, most of the studies in emerging markets about brands and behavioural patterns have focused on individuals who purchase for personal consumption but there are few studies on organisational buying behaviours. Kumar and Kapoor (2017) for instance investigated the role of labels in purchasing decisions. The research concluded that, labels influenced the purchasing intention of food among young Indians. Anaza et al. (2023) researched perceptions in organisations with regards to supplier brands in Nigeria. The study found that brands were the most important consideration in organisational buying behaviour. As a result of the scarcity of literature on branding and organisational buying behaviour, Anaza et al. (2023), made a call for further studies into brands and organisational behavioural patterns in emerging markets. This research aided to address contextual gap issues by focusing on Ghana, an emerging economy since most studies have focused on more developed context and researched into organisational purchasing behavioural specifically the travel trade in Ghana. This research is also motivated by rising competition in the automobile industry (Brunello, 2015; Fartade et al., 2023). This rivalry is reflected in the complex nature of purchasing decisions within the industry. As a result, purchasing decisions are characterised by high involvement (Mahfooz, 2015).

1.6.3 Methodological Gap

The methodological gap was identified as the widest lacuna among issue and context. Scholars have also researched the area of study from different methodological perspectives. There are various researchers who have investigated brand attitude from quantitative perspective. Ahn and Back (2018) online study in the United States employed multiple regression and revealed that, brand attitude impacted on brand reputation and customers' intention to visit a resort again. Pongjit and Beise-Zee (2015) also employed analysis of variance (ANOVA) and researched word-of-mouth incentivisation and consumer brand attitude among students in Thailand. The experimental study revealed that, likely customers might develop negative attitude towards a brand due to the impression that, a brand has enjoyed financial benefits from peers and family members through enticement. Another study by Lee et al. (2017) in South Korea among students employed partial least squares (PLS) structural equation modelling in relation to brand attitude and advertisement attitude and consumers' purchase intention of smartphones. The research revealed that, the context awareness about mobile phone advertisements had a strong influence on both advertising and brand attitude. Ahn et al. (2019) also studied a new dualistic approach to

brand attitude. The research employed structural equation modelling to analyse data among hospitality customers in the United States. The finding indicated that, while extrinsic motivation and obsessive passion minimised the impact on affective attitude, intrinsic motivation and harmonious passion increased affective attitude. The study further established a direct relationship between intrinsic and affective attitude. In another research, Park and Jeon (2018) explored the influence of mixed electronic word of comments sequence on the change of brand attitude from the perspective of cross-cultural differences. Park and Jeon's (2018) study was conducted in the United States and South Korea among students on varieties of products. The study which employed exploratory factor analysis (EFA) and analysis of variance (ANOVA) revealed that the order of presentation of information influenced attitude towards consumers in the United States but there were no significant differences among South Korea consumers. Rhee and Jung (2019) conducted their research by examining brand familiarity as a moderating factor in advertisements, brand attitude and advertising appeals. The sample was derived from students in the United States and regression was used to analyse the data. The findings revealed that, attitude exhibited towards advertisement tend to affect the development of consumers' attitude towards the advertised brand. Foroudi (2019) also studied attitude demonstrated towards brands in the hotel industry in the United Kingdom. The sample were hotel customers. In terms of data analysis, both exploratory factor analysis, and structural equation modelling were employed. The results of the study revealed that, brand signature had a positive relationship with brand attitude. Brand attitude also impacted on brand reputation and brand awareness also influenced brand attitude. Waiguny et al. (2013) also investigated the impact of advergaming content on brand attitude. The study which focused on game players employed analysis of variance (ANOVA) to analyse data. The findings showed that, game players exhibited negative content towards the game brand (Scion) that they were not familiar with. The study further demonstrated that, there was positive content for the brand that they were familiar with (LEGO).

Research works on brand attitude have also been conducted from the qualitative perspective. For instance, Renton and Simmonds (2017) research in New Zealand employed thematic analysis to explore the attitude of brands and the attainment of consumer goals online. The study which sampled young consumers aged 18 and 24 years concluded that, the strength of relationships were reflected in variations in attitude, the social media platforms selected and in brand usage. Banerjee and Pal (2023) also employed thematic analysis to study YouTube advertisements among students in the United Kingdom. The research revealed that, although consumers disliked YouTube advertisements, their displeasure did not extend to the advertised brand. Thus, the advertisements did not develop negative attitude towards the advertised brands. Another qualitative study by Danes et al. (2010) on brand image associations for large virtual groups employed thematic analysis. In assessing brand attitude among fast food consumers in the United States, the research concluded that more favourable brands received free association than brands that were less favourable.

In terms of mixed method study on brand attitude, Yoon and Park (2012) investigated the influence of sensory ad appeals on brand attitude among students. The research, which was conducted in South Korea utilised multiple regression, analysis of variance (ANOVA) for the quantitative part. Thematic analysis was also used to analyse quantitative aspect of the study as well. The quantitative result concluded that, olfactory and auditory senses significantly affected brand attitude. The qualitative result emphasised the stance that, brand logo and interior colour were important elements in developing brand attitude among consumers.

Scholars have also conducted quantitative studies in relation to attitude demonstrated towards brands and its effect on intention to buy. Research by Hsu et al. (2019) for instance investigated intention to buy using the Theory of Planned Behaviour. The researchers employed Structural Equation Modelling among green skincare consumers in Taiwan found that, attitude affected purchase intention. Abzari et al. (2014) study of brand attitude and purchase intention with a social media Khodro Company in Iran utilised structural equation modelling. The research concluded that the attitude of customers to brands influenced their willingness of customers to buy from Khodro Company. Also, a study by Singh and Banerjee (2018) in India which investigated scooter and motorbike brands also revealed that brand attitude formed based on celebrity endorsement positively affected customers intention to purchase. Another study conducted by Lee et al. (2017) in South Korea compared advertising attitude and purchase intention. The finding which was attained through the application of partial least squares (PLS) structural equation modelling revealed that, attitude exhibited by smartphone consumers was stronger on their willingness to purchase than advertising attitude.

In another study, Augusto and Torres (2018) applied structural equation modelling derived sample from bank customers in Portugal. The findings indicated that, brand attitude influenced the purchase intention of customers.

In terms of mixed methodological approach, scholars have investigated attitude towards brands and intention to purchase. Park et al. (2015) for instance investigated how consumer brand attitude and purchase intention were affected by visual merchandising in fashion retail shops, a study that was conducted among South Korean customers. The qualitative part of the study employed Thematic Analysis in order to identify themes that were incorporated into the questionnaire development. structural equation modelling was undertaken, and the result indicated that, consumers' demonstration of favourable attitude toward visual merchandising directly and positively impacted on their willingness to buy.

Quantitative studies related to perceived value have also been conducted. For instance, Karjaluoto et al. (2019) researched on how the use of mobile financial apps was driven by perceived value. Partial least squares (PLS) of structural equation modelling was the analytical technique and the sample was drawn from mobile banking application users in Finland. The research concluded that, the perception that consumers held in terms of value had a stronger positive effect on satisfaction and commitment level exhibited by banks customers. Lee et al. (2007) research of Japanese tourists in South Korea which utilised structural equation modelling indicated also that perceived value played an influential role in achieving satisfaction.

Literature also revealed some qualitative studies on perceived value. Research by Lo and Lee (2011) conducted in Hong Kong which relied on thematic analysis concluded that, one of the reasons of volunteering by travellers was to obtain value based on their perceptions. Another study by Choppy et al. (2015) that applied inductive content analysis in the United States concluded that, individuals subscribed to the Oley Foundation due to the perception of value which manifested in the programmes, capabilities, inspiration, normalcy and advocacy. Research

by Coutelle-Brillet et al. (2014) in France which employed thematic content analysis revealed that, the elements of value inherent in-service innovation were not restricted to economic and functional but there were other components which deserved attention. These components are interactional, emotional, symbolic and altruistic.

Quantitative studies have focused on purchase intention as well. Sedzro et al. (2014) assessed the factors that determine people's choice of brand and the kind of automobile they purchase in Ghana by using the multinomial logistic model. The findings indicated that, automobile owners were interested in safety, value for money, interior satisfaction, modernity and affordability when determining to buy a specific vehicle. In another study, Zhu et al. (2019) explored willingness to buy regarding cross-border E-commerce by adopting a three-stage model in China. The sample was derived from purchasers via an online platform, e DHGate.com. Exploratory factor analysis and Mplus 7.0 software's bootstrap method were applied. The research results indicated that, platform situational involvement, trust beliefs as well as platform enduring involvement influenced the willingness of consumers to purchase. Osei-Frimpong et al. (2019) also studied consumer behavioural patterns in Ghana and employed partial least square (structural equation modelling). The research which sampled university students revealed that, celebrity characteristics such as attractiveness, trustworthiness and familiarity affected consumers' intention and loyalty towards brands.

Another research by Yuan et al. (2020) among hotel customers in Taiwan which utilised exploratory factor analysis and hierarchical regression analysis revealed that, electronic word of mouth and Internet risk avoidance influenced consumers' willingness to buy. Watanabe et al (2019) employed structural equation modelling to research the influence of culture, store image and satisfaction towards customers intention to buy in supermarkets in Brazil. The findings concluded that, apart from culture, store image and satisfaction influenced customers intention to buy again in supermarkets. Wang et al (2022) also conducted systematic literature to study trust and purchase intention. The research employed Pearson correlation coefficient and concluded that, trust had an influential effect on the intention of consumers to buy. Hosseinikhah Choshaly (2019) who studied innovative features and their impact among consumers in Malaysia. Partial least squares, structural equation modelling was used to analyse data. The research found that relative advantage, trialability and observability influenced the willingness of consumers to buy eco-friendly products.

Literature also revealed qualitative studies on purchase intention. Kazancoglu and Aydin (2018) researched the willingness of students to purchase clothing from omni-channel. The thematic analysis results concluded that, performance which included expectancy and effort influenced consumers' willingness to purchase. In addition to this, enabling conditions, motivation based on hedonism and habit were identified as influencers of willingness to buy. Other themes that influenced consumers' willingness to purchase were the value attached to product prices and the perception of trustworthiness. In addition to that, the perception of risk, interactive activities, the quest to address privacy issues played influential roles in forming the intention of customers in Turkey.

Brand attitude and perceived value have been studied quantitatively as well. Salehzadeh and Pool (2017) study which employed structural equation modelling among consumers in shopping malls in Iran revealed that, the attitude exhibited by brands were influenced by the perception of value (quality, price and social value) of luxury brands. Another study by Hwai Lee and Yuen Han (2002) in Singapore among students employed analysis of variance (ANOVA) and found that, the attitude exhibited towards computer and stereo brands also influenced perceived value in terms of prices.

Other researchers had undertaken quantitative studies on perceived value and purchase intention. Gan and Wang (2017) studied social commerce of Chinese customers and employed partial least squares, structural equation modelling to test the various constructs and variables. The results indicated that, various components of perceived value which were utilitarian, hedonic and social values positively affected purchase intention of customers. Zhang et al. (2021) also researched online reviews of customers in China. The research concluded that, customers had the intention to purchase accommodation services again due to the perceived value obtained from the services.

There were also qualitative studies on perceived value and purchase intention. Liu and Murphy (2007) study of wine consumption revealed that, Chinese consumers drank made-in China alcoholic beverages regularly but reserved red wine for special occasion such as holidays or New Year. Drinking red wine was considered trendy and more acceptable because it contained less alcohol compared to Chinese alcoholic beverages. Thus, Chinese culture played an influential role in the purchasing behaviour towards wine. Amatulli and Guido (2011) content analysis study among Italians who patronised luxurious fashion products also concluded that, consumers were likely to patronise fashion brands in order to satisfy their perception of value, specifically their lifestyle. Sharma et al. (2021) research also revealed that, perceived value themes which were functional, social and emotional values significantly influenced purchase intentions of India young consumers among luxury brands.

There have been quantitative studies about perceived value and purchase intention in the consumer behaviour literature. Hung et al. (2011) studied Taiwanese customers and used exploratory factor analysis and multiple regression. The findings revealed that, although functional value influenced purchase intention, symbolic value did not. Eunju et al. (2008) researched the sportswear market in relation to perceived value and purchase intention in two countries using linear structural relation. The findings showed that although perceived value specifically price had an influence of intention to buy in the Chinese market, it did not influence intention to purchase in the South Korean market.

Researchers have also studied perceived value and purchase intention from a mixed methodological perspective. Roy et al. (2020) researched the antecedents that form the willingness of ageing consumers to buy online in India. Content analysis was used to conduct qualitative data analysis. The results indicated that, social influence, a component of perceived value encouraged online purchases. The quantitative aspect of the study which employed exploratory factor analysis and structural equation modelling also revealed that, brand loyalty

and social influence which were constructs of electronic word-of-mouth had a significant impact on the willingness to buy online.

Despite the existence of these studies, there was a lacuna on brand attitude, perceived value and purchase intention that focused on organisational buying behavioural patterns, compared imported and locally assembled vehicles, employed mixed methodological perspective (structural equation modelling and thematic analysis) and adopted the explanatory sequential approach (utilising qualitative results to explain quantitative findings).

1.7 Academic Benefits

The study added to the knowledge in the literature regarding brand attitude, perceived value and purchase intention. This research therefore contributed to the expansion of extant literature. The research was undertaken from different perspectives to contribute to the literature. Quantitative findings revealed causal relationships between brand attitude, perceived value and purchase intention in the automobile industry. The study also revealed themes based on the qualitative research. These themes can be converted into variables and used for other studies. Thus, this research will encourage scholars to conduct more studies in the area.

1.8 Practical Benefits to Companies

The automobile industry is undergoing transformation and is attracting a lot of investment in Ghana. The government of Ghana is also creating a conducive environment for the establishment of locally assembled vehicles. The country has introduced the automobile policy and providing incentives such as tax holidays to automobile firms to engage in automobile assembling and manufacturing (Ghana Automotive Policy, 2023). Ghana previously relied solely on imported vehicles, but the country has attracted firms to locally assemble various brands of vehicles in recent times. This has led to fierce competition in the automobile industry. This study will aid automobile industries better understand the behavioural patterns of businesses to develop strategies that will aid in the attainment of marketing goals and objectives. The findings of this study can shape policies and programmes within the automobile industry.

1.9 Thesis Structure

The first chapter provided an introduction of the thesis and therefore formed the basis for the development of subsequent chapters. The second chapter discussed extant literature that were related to the research. Chapter three highlighted on the contextual issues of the research. The fourth chapter focused on relevant theories that underpinned the research. Chapter five was the methodology that was adopted to answer the research question. Chapter six highlighted on the quantitative aspect of data analysis and results. The seventh chapter focused on the quantitative aspect of data analysis and results. Chapter eight discussed the findings of the research from the qualitative perspective. The ninth chapter provided insights into the integration of both

quantitative and qualitative data. Chapter ten, the final chapter provided detailed conclusion of the research.

1.10 Scope of the Study

The study of brand attitude, perceived value and purchase intention was conducted within the automobile industry and was in relation to new automobiles only. The study focused on the automobile industry because the industry is a fast growing within the Ghanaian environment. Data for the study was collected from travel trade firms within the Greater Accra Region, the capital of Ghana. Greater Accra is the region with the highest number of travel trade firms which included vehicle rentals, travel and tours and tour operating agencies (Ghana Tourism Report, 2021). The sample was drawn from vehicle trade due to their knowledge and experiences gained from automobiles which is an important component in their business activities and service delivery to their customers.

CHAPTER TWO

LITERATURE REVIEW

2.0 Introduction

In this chapter, the research presented a review of the extant literature. The review highlighted on the concept of branding, key components of a brand, requirements for developing an effective brand, benefits of branding, brand development in the automobile industry, product and brand life cycle in the automobile industry, brand orientation, brand intangibles, the influence of brand intangibles on purchasing decisions. Other literature reviewed included the role of employees in brand building, brand equity, digital Branding, brand experience, brand Purpose, brand authenticity, brand extensions, The literature of the study also covered internal brand management, challenges to building brand success, organisational buying behaviour, branding and business markets, conceptualisation of attitude, the concept of brand attitude, components of brand attitude and benefits of brand attitude. The chapter also highlighted on the role of quality in organisations, the role of pricing in firms, perceptions, definitions of perceived value, importance of perceived value, dimensions of perceived value, relationship among perceived value constructs and purchase intentions. The literature reviewed also included the relationships between brand attitude and purchase intention, brand attitude and perceived value, brand attitude, perceived value, and purchase intention as well as the theoretical background of the research and a summary of the chapter.

Brand attitude, perceived value and purchase intention play a major role in the behavioural patterns of individuals and business markets. A review of extant literature revealed some studies on the subject. The literature review relied on peer-reviewed articles and publications from authentic sources. The search terms were 'brand', 'attitude', 'perception', 'value', 'purchase' and 'intention'. Other search terms were 'brand attitude', 'perceived value' and 'purchase intention'. The search terms were narrowed to cover 'brand attitude and perceived value', 'brand attitude and purchase intention' as well as 'perceived value and purchase intention'. Further search terms revealed the linkages among the three variables. These were 'brand attitude, perceived value and purchase intention'. Despite the existence of literature, a number of observable research gaps were identified. Hence, the conduct of this study was to contribute to the fill of the gaps. The findings of the current study contributed empirically to branding and organisational purchasing behaviour within the automobile industry in a developing country. Extant literature revealed that most studies have focused on developed economies and studied from individual consumer perspective with little focus on organisations. In addition, most studies on perceived value have applied the concept from a uni-dimensional perspective. This study also compared locally assembled and imported automobile brands in relation to brand attitude, perceived value from a multidimensional perspective and purchase intention by drawing sample from the travel trade.

Methodological contributions also made the study novel. The research adopted comparative method and utilised convenience and purposive sampling techniques. The mixed methodological approach was used, and explanatory sequential design was employed to connect quantitative and qualitative data with the application of structural equation modelling and thematic analysis. The

study was also original in approach because new research questions related to the topic were answered. The questions asked pertained to attitude of towards brands, perception of value and purchase intention towards local assembled vehicle brands compared and imported brands.

2.1 The Concept of Branding

The concept of branding is believed to have originated from marks made on cattle for differentiation purposes. It has its roots in the Norse word *brandr* which means the branding of cattle (Hart and Murphy, 1998; Riezebos, 2003). Branding in olden times was regarded as the conduit that generated conflicts among firms seeking to be identified as the obvious preference among competitors (Butler, 1914). Cherington (1920) regarded branding as a new concept that was employed and formed an integral part in advertising and selling. The role of branding was called “aggressive sales methods”. Cherington (1920) further asserted that brands will only thrive if they possessed quality.

The concept of branding was not widely used in ancient times. Products were sold in retail outlets to consumers without any indication of their sources. There were generic products without specific brand names. Some of these products included cheese, pickles and coffee (Bastos and Levy, 2012). Branding started gaining acceptability in the late nineteenth and early twentieth centuries when packaging and labelling of products aided to identify the firms responsible for their manufacturing. Manufacturers began exhibiting a sense of pride by inscribing their names on their products which provided value addition (Bastos and Levy, 2012). Firms such as Folger in 1872 started branding their cheese. In 1903, Kraft followed with cheese brand and Vlasic branded their pickles in 1942. As the field of branding was evolving, some brands became dominant to the extent of being associated almost to the generic product before World War II (Carpenter and Nakamoto, 1989). The transformation that characterised branding was largely influenced by the growing popularity of the media which comprised of television, radio and print advertising among others (Moore and Reid, 2008). World War II also increased competitiveness among brands. There was wide availability of goods and increased consumer demand in the late 1940s and 1950s which was called “consumer revolution” (Bastos and Levy, 2012). The era witnessed a surge in the number of brands in various industries. As a result, new brands together with existing brands intensively challenged the market leaders. Pepsi aggressively competed against Coca Cola who was the market leader. The entry of Starbucks into the coffee market led to the demise of Maxwell House and B/G (Bastos and Levy, 2012).

A brand is a differentiator among competitors. A brand can be a name, term, mark, or design or two more of these which identifies and distinguishes a firm from others (Kotler, 1991). The definition of brand has broadened in scope over the years (Dinnie, 2015). Primarily, brand has its meaning applying to products, services, and corporations, which include brands of products and corporate brands. The concept brand also applies to events, institutions, government agencies, associations, individuals, non-governmental organisations and even nations (Kerr, 2006). Bajde (2019) contended that the widening of the meaning of the notion brand has compounded the complexity of the elusive definition. Literature revealed that numerous attempts by researchers have been made to provide a convincing definition for the terms brand and branding. From historical perspective, it has been noted that branding has its various definitions clustering

around identification of products and entities (Bajde, 2019). Based on this, Dinnie (2015) considered brand from the perspective of identity markers, including symbols, names, among other forms of identification, by which marketers are allowed to make a distinction between their products or organisations from that of their competitors. According to Kapferer (2012), brand as a concept refers to a name that has the capacity to influence. A brand has also been regarded as a strategic tool that organisations employ in their attempt to build industrial barriers when competitions are identified within the same industry (Anees-ur-Rehman et al., 2018). There is therefore no consensus on the conceptualisation of the concept of brand and its applicability has been used in diverse manner.

2.2 Key Components of a Brand

The first aspect of a brand that is the main pillar for creating and engaging in marketing activities is the brand name (Keller et al., 1998). After a brand is named, another aspect which constitutes the visual representation termed as the brand mark is developed (Klink, 2003). A trademark is also another aspect of a brand. Trademark gives firms the legal right to use brand name and brand mark as well as protection from imitation (Flikkema et al. 2019). Trademark offers an opportunity to trace the source of products and therefore protects both firms and customers (Greer, 1979). Trademarks also serve as protection against deception and fraudulent activities as well as a firm's monopoly (Flikkema et al., 2019). Trademark safeguards a firm's investment towards developing quality and building reputation (Nam and Barnett, 2011). Although trademarks can be restricted to country, there are opportunities for firms to extend it beyond their country-of-origin (Madsen and Servais, 1997). Companies that subscribe to Community trademarks (CTMs) for example can venture into other countries with an existing brand name and brand mark (Madsen and Servais, 1997). Firms innovate and expand to other markets with the same brand to diversify risks and generate more profits (Flikkema et al., 2019).

2.3 Requirements for Developing an Effective Brand

Branding experts have identified some qualities that a brand name should possess to be effective in attaining desirable marketing outcomes. Robertson (1989) asserted that, when naming a brand, a firm must ensure that the names should be pronounced with ease. Brand names should also be easily remembered and should be unique. Other scholars such as Keller et al. (1998) and Pavia and Costa (1993) have also argued that names should communicate important information about the characteristics inherent in a product. It should therefore have a meaning.

Brand marking, which is also an integral part of the branding strategy of firms should be considered. Brand mark facilitates the identification and speeds consumer choice for a particular product (Morrow, 1992). Brand marks can be found on important communication materials such as letterheads, business cards, signs, annual reports, and designs of products. Firms can also exhibit brand marks on radio and television campaigns (Henderson and Cote, 1998). Sales promotional packages that are offered to customers such as t-shirts, mugs and pens can also have brand mark or logo (Hayes, 1995). Scholars have proposed some criteria for brand marking. Firms should ensure that the chosen brand mark can be recognised without difficulty. It should be meaningful and should generate positive feelings (Henderson and Cote, 1998; Cohen, 1986;

Robertson, 1989; Vartorella, 1990). There are a number of brand mark items that marketers need to consider in developing their brands. These are colours, shapes, and sizes of the product. Colours tend to provide communication signals and form perceptions about brands. Gold for instance was used to communicate caffeine free products (Gimba, 1998). Scholars such as Henderson and Cote (1998) mentioned that the shape of a product forms an integral part of developing a brand. Consumers might develop attachment towards a brand not only because of the benefits but the likability of the manner a product is shaped which could be angled, rounded or straighter lines. Sizes also play a key role in developing brand marks. Nike for instance ensures that, the “swoosh” appears larger on billboards and clothing (Klink, 2003).

Firms can gain an edge over competing brands by capitalising and carefully integrating performances and aspirations of brands. Brands can be related in their previous or past occurrences based on the historical and heritage stance and achievements. Brands can leverage their present position based on their values that are upheld, personality that is exhibited and the character that has been developed (Keller, 2023). The present position of brands influences the thinking, feeling and action towards that brand. Brands can also be used as a competitive advantage to project the future by carefully designing a meaningful and insightful mission, vision and purpose that produces a differentiation effect (Keller, 2023). Strong brands must present a persuasive narration in terms of their roots, growth, and destiny. Marketing oriented firms who employ this strategy are likely to have customers that demonstrate strong loyalty (Keller, 2023). Keller and Swaminathan (2020) also postulated that, to build strong brands, firms must ensure that brands are well-positioned in the memory of consumers. There is also the need to develop the appropriate associations of a brand to occupy the hearts of buyers as well. Pecot and Barnier (2018) and Pfannes et al. (2021) asserted that, these inputs are essential in developing an effective communications strategy.

2.4 Benefits of Branding

Branding aids in associating a particular product from a manufacturer or a retail outlet and therefore aids customers to recognise what is on offer. It therefore acts as an identifier (Roper and Parker, 2006). Brands also act as a differentiation from competitors. Customers can ascertain the differences that products have in order to make choices. This is because branding clearly differentiates based on product features that are more appealing to customers (Roper and Parker, 2006). Branding also provides human features to a firm’s products. Aaker (1997) attributed human qualities to brands and termed it as brand personality just like psychologists identifying personality traits of mankind. Hanby (1999) described the personification of a brand as “manipulable artifact (to) living entity.... the machine and the organism”. Brands can also be developed in a manner that fits the known and credible personality of a Chief Executive Officer of a firm. Chrysler for instance, inherited the personality of charisma to dependability from its Chief Executive Officer, Lee Iacocca (Roper and Parker, 2006).

Brands are also regarded as valuable assets for an organisation in many ways. Jacoby and Chestnut (1978) concluded that branding aids customers loyalty to an organisation due to the value inherent in its products. Branding is also used to generate sales and profitability of businesses. Accountants also use brands to ascertain the financial position and determine the

financial worth of a business (Penrose and Moorhouse, 1989). Low and Blois (2002) further postulated that organisations that have strong brands receive more value when they are put for sale.

Organisations benefit from branding in other various ways as well. Branding aids to enhance the perception of quality of a firm's offerings (Cretu and Brodie, 2007). Branding also enables products to be associated with consistency in image building (Michell et al., 2001). Michell et al. (2001), Low and Blois (2002), Ohnemus (2009) also asserted that, strong brands are in high demand and as a result, firms use it as a basis for charging higher prices. Due to immense competition from strong brands, competitors' brands may become less attractive and receive less patronage (Low and Blois, 2002; Ohnemus, 2009). Branded products are more receptive than non-branded products during bidding situations. The decision-making body of an organisation is more likely to embrace branded products than unbranded products during tender events or bidding situations (Wise and Zednickova, 2009). Branding also tends to provide more credibility due to identification of sources of products and association of quality among others. As a result, consumers are more receptive to information from branded products (Michell et al., 2001; Low and Blois, 2002; Ohnemus, 2009). Hutton (1997) identified that existing brands with strong identities can easily transfer goodwill to new brands introduced by a firm. A brand that is strong has the potential of attracting distributors and enjoying expansion into new markets or territories (Low and Blois, 2002; Ohnemus, 2009). The presence of a strong brand also serves as a barrier for new entrants due to market acceptability (Michell et al., 2001). Customers are more likely to recommend friends, family members, work colleagues and others to purchase products that have strong brands (Hutton, 1997; Bendixen et al., 2004). Customers tend to have confidence in purchasing strong brands due to the values associated with it (Michell et al., 2001; Low and Blois, 2002). Strong brands tend to enhance the satisfaction levels of consumer purchases (Low and Blois, 2002) and the "feel good" level (Mudambi, 2002). Branding also aids minimise the challenges inherent in choosing products and therefore reduces the perceived risks and uncertainties associated with purchases (Mudambi, 2002; Bengtsson and Servais, 2005; Ohnemus, 2009).

Chen et al. (2023) asserted that, brands names played an influencing role in the goods and services that consumers buy. Statistics indicated that more than 70% of purchases are based on brand directions. The research further indicated that 50% of acquisitions of products are really driven by brands. In addition, 72% of purchasers mentioned their readiness to pay an extra 20% to purchase the brands of their choice than the brand of the closest rivalry (Lim and Tan, 2010). Due to the attachment to brand names, consumers book market leading types of electric automobiles such as Tesla's Model Y, BYD Song, Volkswagen ID.4 ahead and pay a premium price because of the power that these brands have (Chen et al., 2023).

2.5 Brand Development in the Automobile Industry

Automobile firms mostly use between three to five years in developing their brands (Kearney, 2001). In developed countries, the average lifespan of a typical car model has halved in the past decade, reducing from around eight years to four years (Bogorin-Predescu et al., 2023). Moreover, there has been a notable reduction in the average time required for brand

development, decreasing from an average of 48 months to approximately 25 months recently (Bogorin-Predescu et al., 2023). For instance, Toyota's product development cycle comprises an initial design phase spanning 2-3 years, followed by a production planning phase lasting approximately 15-20 months (Moon, 2005). Brand development plays an essential role in achieving organisational objectives and outcomes (Kearney, 2001). Research by Štrach and Everett (2005) in the automobile industry adapted Goodyear (1996)'s brand development steps. The first stage of Goodyear (1996)'s brand development is when products are unbranded. The next stage is the usage of brand as a source of reference. The third step is regarding brand as a personality. The fourth stage is the development of brand to iconic status. The next stage is when the brand is recognised as company and the final stage is when the brand is identified as policy.

The unbranded stage is where a product is regarded as commodities and such products do not play a major role in countries that are advanced. The next step is the brand as reference. At this level, brands identified with names and advertising is employed to focus on the cognitive features associated with the products. The brand names are used as assurance of quality inherent in a product. Štrach and Everett (2005) linked automobile brands which included Acura, Hummer, Infiniti, Land Rover, Lexus, and Lincoln to this level. Brand as a personality is the next step. At this stage, the brand has the potential to be regarded as a separate entity or a "stand alone". Marketing activities are employed to assist in emphasising benefits and emotionally attracting customers. The next stage is brand as an icon. Goodyear (1996) postulated that, such brands appeal to the upper echelon in the societal ladder and consumers have a sense of "ownership" of brands. Such brands have an international presence and advertising tends to build relationships. Štrach and Everett (2005) identified Audi, BMW, Cadillac, Lamborghini, and Mercedes-Benz as having attained this stage. The next stage according to Goodyear (1996) is brand as company. Brands at this level have complicated identities which are subjected to evaluation by customers. Organisations employ integrated marketing communications to achieve clear, unified and consistent communication. Firms at this level are required to concentrate on providing benefits to customers as a corporate entity. According to Štrach and Everett (2005), automobile firms that have attained this level are Ferrari, Bugatti, Bentley, and Maybach. With brand as policy, Goodyear (1996) viewed businesses having interested in political and social issues. Consumers are identified as those who have "ownership" of firms, brands, and politics.

2.6 Product and Brands Life Cycle in the Automobile Industry

The concept of product life cycle encompasses various phases, each marked by significant shifts in product behaviour within the market, including factors such as demand and profitability (Sabadka et al., 2019). In the realm of automotive systems and software engineering, effective product life cycle management has become a critical task in contemporary processes (Eigner and Stelzer, 2009). It involves the comprehensive management of a company's products from their initial conceptualisation to eventual retirement and disposal. At its core, product life cycle management aims to enhance product revenues, reduce associated costs, and increase the overall value of the product portfolio, benefiting both customers and shareholders (Stark, 2022). Consequently, it can be viewed as a digital archive that facilitates the seamless integration of all information generated throughout a product's life cycle (Möller et al., 2019). Simon (1979) postulated that, just like products, brands also experience various stages of life. These include introduction, growth, maturity, and decline. Literature on brands has focused on the elasticity of

price at the various stages of brands. Simon (1979) identified a decline in price elasticity when brands are introduced to the market and experience growth as well. He further revealed price elasticity was at the lowest level when products mature but identified a rise during the decline stage. Tellis (1988) study concluded that customers are sensitive to price when products are the decline stage of its cycle.

Carmody (2015) asserted that, about 96% of all businesses established fail within the first ten years of operations. One of the identified reasons is poor communications. There is therefore the need for businesses to conduct studies in order to ascertain how new brands can communicate properly during the introductory stages to their target audience to be established in the minds of consumers (Riedel et al., 2021). The channels identified as media for communication purposes are traditional, online and in-store. The traditional channels are television, radio and catalogues while the online channels are firms' websites and social media platforms. Some businesses also blend both traditional and online channels (Riedel et al., 2021). There are studies which stress that brands tend to derive a lot of benefits from the usage of online channels during their introductory phase (Huang et al., 2014). Morra et al. (2018) indicated that, marketing activities conducted online are more effective than traditional marketing. Lee and Hoffman (2015) added that firms must consider adopting the AIDA Model in communications at the various stages of a brand. AIDA is an acronym which stands for Attention, Interest, Desire, and Action. At the introductory stage of the life of a brand, communication should be targeted at creating more awareness and interest. At the growth stage, firms should develop communication that will create more desire and encourage prospects to take action (Riedel et al., 2021).

2.7 Perspectives of Branding

The extant literature showed three perspectives in understanding the notion of brand. Lin and Siu (2020) reported that the three perspectives of a brand are evolutionary, managerial, and competitive perspectives. In terms of evolutionary perspective, De Chernatony (2009) noted that a brand is multifaceted in nature, which is transformed from a functional stance to a stage of value addition. The functional stance of a brand has been equated to the product paradigm level. This, according to Louro and Cunha (2001) is based on the differentiating and positioning abilities of brands because of its emphasis on brands as identifiers. In the contexts of business-to-business (B2B), the evolutionary view regarding brand aims at providing an explanation for the roles of B2B in the creation of the value of brands. The managerial perspective to the understanding of the notion brand has been projected by Aaker (1991) and Bendixen et al. (2004) who argued that the notion brand originally developed from consumer markets. This perspective deals with management tends to provide the various implications of branding practices (Lin and Siu, 2020). In terms of the competitive perspective of a brand, scholars such as Cretu and Brodie (2007) and Lee et al. (2017) have construed brand as an exceptional competitive advantage tool that has the ability to positively influence potential and actual customers' perceived product and service quality irrespective of whether the market is for individuals or businesses. From the perspective of competitive advantage, Lin and Siu (2020) pointed out that it seeks to illustrate the perceived benefits that stakeholders hold of a brand in relation to its competitors. Researchers, including Lin and Siu (2020), have argued that these three perspectives to the understanding of brand, provide the bases or foundation for the understanding of the various interpretations that have been provided on the notion of brand and branding.

2.8 Brand Orientation

The term brand orientation is noted to have been coined by Urde (1994). Brand orientation involves initiating, developing, and protecting the identity of a brand to obtain sustained competitive advantages recognised by its customers (Urde, 1999). It is observable that Urde's (1999) definition of brand stresses the prioritisation of a brand among the numerous strategic choices of a firm and their organisational culture. Scholars such as Hirvonen and Laukkanen (2014) and Anees-ur-Rehman et al. (2016) have argued that a firm whose organisational culture is brand-oriented tends to integrate its branding activities into its organisational beliefs, values, and vision. According to Urde et al. (2013), the situation whereby a firm integrates its branding mechanism into its vision and values could be described as an inside-out approach, due to its ability to offer guidance that provides the necessary action for brand survival. Various research findings, including Huang and Tsai (2013) and Zhang et al. (2016), have shown that brand orientation is crucial in ensuring that firms improve upon their brand performance. Other empirical studies conducted on brands, including Baumgarth (2010) and Reijonen et al. (2015), have also reported that the orientation of a firm's brand contributes significantly to improving market performance. Urde (1994) argued that three main factors force organisations to be brand oriented. According to Urde (1994), decreasing product divergence, integration of markets and increasing media costs are the main factors that move firms and organisations towards becoming brand oriented. It has been posited by Anees-Ur Rehman et al. (2016) that for firms and organisations to become brand oriented, there is the need for them to emphasise their efforts on the creation of added value, and this can be achieved through adequate coordination of branding activities and placing the quest of creating enviable brand on the top of management priority scale.

In the study of Baumgarth (2010), four layers of brand orientation have been identified. These layers comprise of norms, values, behaviours, and artefacts. In literature, two main perspectives, philosophical and behavioural, have been identified by researchers such as Urde et al. (2013) as approaches to understanding brand orientation. Urde et al. (2013) argued that brand orientation could be considered as a philosophy that shows the values, beliefs and attitudes a firm or an organisation has regarding branding. On the other hand, the behavioural perspective emphasises the degree to which the marketing practices of a firm or an organisation offer support for building brand value. In the research of Evans et al. (2012), evidence of criticism has been observed where the failure of the behavioural perspective in acknowledging the fact that a firm's brand must first be contained in its philosophy is considered a flaw. It has been noted that brand-oriented values serve as the foundation for brand supporting behaviours.

2.9 Brand Intangibles

According to Keller (2023) brand intangibles refers to the past of brands, its present and future as well. Below was a discussion on the various elements of brand intangibles.

2.9.1 Brand Past

Brands have previous activities associated with it even if it was short-lived. The brand past acts as a source of reference and forms part of its Deoxyribonucleic Acid (DNA) (Balmer, 2017; Balmer and Burghausen, 2015; Paharia et al., 2011; Preece et al., 2019). Brands that have existed within a short time or a long period of time whether positive or negative contribute to the development of attributes associated with them (Balmer, 2017; Balmer and Burghausen, 2015; Paharia et al., 2011 and Preece et al., 2019). These attributes are classified as history and heritage of the brand. Even though these two concepts are intertwined, focus should be given to each concept distinctively (Burghausen and Balmer, 2014). Below was a discussion on the history and heritage that contribute to the brand past.

2.9.1.1 History

The historical part of the brand past embodies what the brand has achieved over its period of existence whether significant or insignificant and the errors or the defects that are attributed to the brand (Keller, 2023). Scholars such as Rindell and Iglesias (2014) have emphasised that history is factual but there is the possibility of differences in perceptions that consumers hold about various organisations (Rindell and Iglesias, 2014). Although histories are factual in nature, various individuals may distort or place value on some historical happenings based on certain perceptions that have been developed (Keller, 2023). Firms must be guided and carefully identify which historical perceptives to focus on and the more appropriate manner to project the history and influence the interpretation that is attributed to its brands by consumers and other stakeholders (Iglesias et al., 2020). The history of a firm also includes the formation of the firm, its branches and the markets that it is serving. Directors, managers and employees who have played various roles throughout the existence of the company are also part of the historical narrative (Keller, 2023). The various corporate brands that are offered to customers, important events such as launching of new products, advertising campaigns and other events that are memorable or have created a favourable outlook for a firm must also be taken into consideration (Balmer, 2011; Santos et al., 2016). History therefore aids in providing a deep imagery imprint on the minds of consumers and other stakeholders of a firm's offerings (Balmer, 2011; Santos et al., 2016).

2.9.1.2 Heritage

According to Rindell et al. (2015), Urde et al. (2007) and Wiedmann et al. (2011), heritage is derived from history. It is the persistent and enduring aspect of brand history that is attached with deeper significance. Brand heritage constitutes selective aspects of a brand that provide in-depth relevance and importance in contemporary times which can be assessed (Keller, 2023). The heritage of a brand is firmly based on the products and services that a firm provided at the early stages of business to the current offerings to customers. The heritage may also include notable personalities that have played instrumental roles in creating, shaping and continuously developing an organisation. Brand heritage is more concerned about brand developments that did not get truncated during a brand's cycle but is still of relevance to a brand in contemporary times (Keller, 2023). Heritage is usually deeply rooted in the culture of organisations (Miller and

Vaugh, 2021) that have undergone changes overtime to suit contemporary times, rejuvenate brands and add more value to a firm and its offerings (Keller, 2023).

2.9.2 Brand Present

The brand present is the updated and recent knowledge that exists in relation to a brand. Knowledge is formed based on the ideas, features and characteristics, attitudes, images and the experiences that customers linked to a brand (Keller, 2003). These aspects of a brand are key towards building successful enterprises. Businesses in developing brand present must ask key questions that evolve around the values inherent in brands, the personality that a brand possess and character of the brand as well as the behavioural patterns of the brand (Keller, 2023). Scholars such as Aaker (1997) and Mathur et al. (2012) have urged firms to adopt various communication approaches in enhancing their brand presence. Keller (2023) recognised the presence of overlapping of the elements inherent in brand present but called for a clear separation to properly define their uniqueness and distinguishing features (Keller, 2023).

2.9.2.1 Brand Values

Brand values are deemed to be difficult to conceptualised and is regarded as the most complicated and abstract in nature. Brand values are the beliefs that provide a guide to an organisational functionality within a firm and its relationship with the external environment (Keller, 2023). Some firms have taken into consideration political, social and environmental issues in approaching and handling brand values (Torelli et al., 2012). Torelli et al. (2012) further revealed that, the extent to which a firm is politically and socially active and the level of environmental consciousness and friendliness are all inherent in brand values. Other aspects of brand value include the extent of the relationship and cordiality that exists between a firm and its employees.

2.9.2.2 Brand Personality

Brand personality is more specific unlike brand values which are broad in perspective. Brand personality is providing human attributes to describe a brand (Keller, 2023). One notable scholar in the field of brand personality is Aaker. Aaker (1997) developed five dimensions that are used for measuring brand personality. Brands must demonstrate competence, be sincere, bring about excitement, be sophisticated and regarded as tough. Brand personality for corporate brands may not only limit descriptions to the product but also highlighted on the distinguishing features of employees of a firm that aid to develop various product brands (Keller, 2023). In describing brand personality of corporate brands, Keller and Richey (2006) asserted that three dimensions need to be taken into consideration. The first is the “heart” which represents passionate and compassionateness. The second is the “mind” which stands for creative and discipline and the third is the “body” highlighted agile and collaborative. These three dimensions appear contradictory to each other but firms that are poised towards establishing strong brands identify “sweet spots” in the middle (Keller, 2023).

2.9.2.3 Brand Character

Brand character has been conceptualised differently by researchers (Spanenberg, 2021). One popular and widely used conceptualisation of brand character is by Keller (2023). According to Keller (2023), although brand character is linked to brand values and personality, it is a concept that is distinct. Brand character is recognised as the moral attributes, ethics and behaviour of not only the brand but also the individuals and groups that create, develop, promote and work towards success (Keller, 2023). Brand character together with brand values and personality aids in creating the right pictorial version of a brand that is imperative for creating customer loyalty (Malär et al., 2011). A combination of these will aid a firm to go beyond establishing transactional marketing to building customer relationships which does not only favour a firm but also provides a win-win situation that rewards customers and lead to repeat business (Fournier 1998; Keller, 2001). Apart from the brand past and the brand present, customers are also interested in identifying the future of brands (Keller, 2023).

2.9.3 Brand Future

The future of the brand provides directions on the way forward. It is embodied in the mission, vision, and purpose of a brand (Keller, 2012). The mission, vision and the purpose of a brand aids to ascertain the current position of a brand and what it intends to achieve in the future (Keller, 2023). The mission, vision and purpose of a firm is a futuristic aspiration, or it is what a brand hopes to attain in future which will involve transition or transformations. For consumers to believe in the futuristic aspirations of a brand, there should be a wide acceptance of the historical narrative, the heritage, values, personality, and character associated with a brand (Keller, 2023). The likelihood for consumers to accept the prospects of a brand is based on positive previous and current happenings (Beck et. al., 2020).

2.10 The Influence of Brand Intangibles on Purchasing Decisions

Brand history, heritage, values, personality, and character which form part of the composition of brand intangibles play an influential role in the decisions that consumers make whether directly or indirectly towards a firm's brands (Keller, 2012). Consumers tend to directly choose brands and make other decisions based on brands because of the knowledge of the past and present which form the basis for deciding to buy a particular brand. Intangibles can indirectly lead to the creation of certain impressions about the offerings of a brand. Thus, the availability of information from appropriate sources serves as an avenue for interpreting information (Hovland and Weiss, 1951; McGuire, 1985). The knowledge of a customer about the past of a brand in terms of its performance is likely to affect the reception of brand information about its futuristic expected performance (Balmer, 2012). The brand past and brand present are also used as yardstick to ascertain the credibility of a brand and it is therefore key in forming judgments about a brand. Keller and Aaker (1998) and Keller (2012) asserted that customers tend to assess the credibility of a brand based on three criteria which are the expertise associated with the brand, its

trustworthiness and likeability. Customers view brand as having the required expertise based on previous achievements. A brand that has also been able to instil values, personality and character that are receptive can positively influence the manner in which trust, and likeability are perceived. The presence of knowledge that supports a brand because of satisfactory intangibles lead to the creation of a more respectable and authenticated brand (Beverland and Farrelly, 2010; Fritz et al., 2017; Grayson and Martinec, 2004). Consumers are likely to also adopt deeper and more consistent feelings towards a brand that has been accepted as having brand intangibles (Batra et al., 2012; Pham et al., 2013). Such brands instil socially accepted benefits into customers. Thus, customers are likely to embrace offerings due to the social approval that a brand commands (Keller, 2023).

2.11 Employees Role in Building Brands

Workers are recognised as significant contributors to building brands within an organisation (King, 2010). As a result, Yang et al. (2015) asserted that, employees are not only identified as a key resource within an organisation but play an integral role in the product offered to customers. An organisation is expected to demonstrate competence in its work, and this can only be achieved through employees (Piehler et al., 2016). Viitala et al. (2022) were of the view that organisations can only be successful if the roles that employees play are identified as strategically significant. This is because, to fulfil the promises that brands make, employees must perform their duties to meet expectations of customers (Piehler et al., 2018). The employees' perceptions that are held about brands tend to influence the behavioural patterns of other internal and external stakeholders through their communications (Boukis and Christodoulides, 2020). King and Grace (2010) added that, to achieve organisational goals, management must ensure that employees have important information relating to the brands of their firms. Burmann and Zeplin (2005) further advocated that employees should not be linked only mentally but emotionally and behaviourally to a brand. Piehler et al. (2018) also proposed categorisation of these three aspects as the cognitive outcome which stress on understanding the brand, demonstrating dedication towards the brand which is referred to as the affective outcome and the third aspect called brand citizenship which emphasises on the behavioural outcomes of a brand. Behavioural patterns that are more likely to be predicted than attitude based on less elaboration are also referred to as the peripheral processing route.

2.12 Brand Equity

There have been varied definitions of brand equity by researchers. Brand equity has been defined as the assets and liabilities that brands possess. It includes the name and symbol that add value or minimise the value of a brand to customers (Aaker, 1991). Keller (1993) defined brand equity as “the differential effect of brand knowledge on consumer response to the marketing of the brand”. According to Farquhar (1989), brand equity is the power that a brand, whether name, symbol or logo possesses in the marketplace. Customer based brand equity comprises of brand awareness, brand association, perceived quality and brand loyalty.

2.12.1 Brand Awareness

Brand awareness is one of the components of brand knowledge. It focuses on the ability of consumers to have high memory of a brand under varied situations (Keller, 1993). Thus, it emphasises on the memory strength of a brand among consumers (Rossiter and Percy, 1987). Brand memory consists of two aspects. These are brand recognition and brand recall performance (Keller, 1993). Brand recognition deals with the capacity of consumers to identify brands among competing brands due to previous exposure (Keller, 1993). Brand awareness is key in forming purchasing decisions of consumers due to three reasons. It helps consumers to identify brands as options that will be purchased (Baker et al. 1986; Nedungadi, 1990). In addition to this, Jacoby, Syzabillo and Busato-Schach (1977) and Roselius (1971) argued that brands that are well-established and more familiar are likely to be purchased among competing brands. The third reason according to Bettman and Park (1980), Hoyer and Brown (1990) and Park and Lessig (1981) is that consumers are more likely to purchase brands that are not well-known when the purchase decision is low involvement even in situations where attitudes are not properly developed.

2.12.2 Brand Association

Aaker (1991) defined brand associations as linkages to a brand stored in the memory of purchasers. This is consistent with Keller (1993) asserted that, information-related to brands stored in the minds of consumers was termed as brand association. Keller (1993) categorised brand association as having three main aspects which are brand attributes, brand benefits and brand attitude. Attributes are the characteristics that consumers favour in a brand. The benefits are the gains or the advantages that consumers derive from the purchase or usage of a brand. These benefits can be functional, experiential or symbolic (Aaker, 1991). The functional benefits are product-related and are concerned with the solutions that a brand offers to a consumer. Experiential benefit is also product-related and is concerned with the feelings derived from the usage of a brand. Symbolic benefit on the other hand is non-product related and is directed towards attaining approval within the social circle of consumers due to usage of specific brand or brands (Keller, 1993). Brand attitudes are the consumers' total assessment of brands (Wilkie, 1986). Brand attitude is significant because it is the backbone for consumer behavioural patterns in issues such as brand choice. Brand attitude can be linked to the attributes inherent in products which include functional and experiential benefits as argued by Zeithaml (1988) research on perceived quality. Scholars such as Rossiter and Percy (1987) have also argued that brand attitudes can be related to non-product-related attributes and symbolic benefits.

2.12.3 Perceived Quality

Perceived quality is defined as the customer's perspective of the superiority that a brand possesses compared to competing brands (Selase Asamoah, 2014). The perception of quality is regarded as a key influence in an organisation that provides competitive advantage (Baldauf et al., 2003). Urde (1994) further argued that perceived quality does not only provide competitive advantage but also provide brand attractiveness among the target market. Organisations must therefore communicate effectively to the target audience to position brands that have been developed to be recognised as the brand of choice.

2.12.4 Brand Loyalty

Brand loyalty is the dedication that consumers have for a brand that results in repeat business and purchase regardless of marketing campaigns by competing brands (Keller, 1993). Loyal consumers have brands that they prioritise or identify as the most preferred option despite the existence of brands that provide similar or same benefits (Tong and Hawley, 2009). Consumers become loyal to brands by purchasing and using products of their preferred brands (Baldauf et al., 2003). The attainment of brand loyalty, which is a key component of brand equity, will be based on the development of strategic directions that are geared towards not only attracting customers but retaining them as well (Atilgan et al., 2005; Tong and Hawley, 2009; Aaker, 1991). Delgado-Ballaster and Munuera-Aleman (2005) postulated that, benefits derived from brand loyalty are enormous. These include greater market share, premium prices, minimised marketing costs and increased trade advantages.

2.13 Digital Branding

Digital brand is the technique that blends digital marketing and internet branding to create brands that are visible across digital channels which entails device centered applications or media content and internet-centered platforms (Jaiswal and Upadhyay, 2018). Developing social media branding, building online reputation and e-commerce branding strategies are notable channels for building digital brands.

2.13.1 Social Media Branding

Social media is defined as information that is generated by users and shared among individuals who have interests in the topics under discussion (Blackshaw and Nazzaro, 2004). Social media has transformed the existing media landscape from reliance on traditional marketing where communications only originated from marketers to consumers to a situation where consumers can generate communications targeted at marketers as well (Kohli, Suri and Kapoor, 2015). Social media can also influence the crafting and delivery of products due to consumers ability to provide information that can easily be accessed by firms. Social media users obtain information, get familiarised with brands and provide their views (Yan, 2011). Firms can also leverage on social media to enhance their reputation (Barwise and Meehan, 2010).

Kohli, Suri and Kapoor (2015) identified strategies for managing brands on social media. The first is to accept the new paradigm. This is because social media has provided power to consumers in managing and disseminating information in a manner that did not previously exist (Divol, Edelman and Sarrazin, 2012). Firms must therefore accept and embrace the reality that social media has come to stay and should adapt their activities to meet changing trends and needs (Kohli, Suri and Kapoor, 2015). In addition, firms should support brands with quality products and effective and efficient distribution systems. Furthermore, social media is a source of word-of-mouth comments for establishing the quality inherent in a brand. Firms must pay attention to interactions about brands and establish relationships (Kohli, Suri and Kapoor, 2015). Marketers should craft good messages on social media to enable advocates disseminate brand-related

information (Kohli, Suri and Kapoor, 2015). Mercedes for instance, utilised real-life stories to demonstrate the lifesaving potentials of its vehicles (Lamb, 2012).

Social users engage in behavioural patterns such as liking, sharing, commenting and forwarding posts (Sheth, Newman and Gross, 1991). Gao et al (2018) postulated that, brand positioning strategies in advertising as proposed by Alden, Steenkamp, and Batra (1999) should be implemented in social media circles in international marketing. First, brands as a symbol should be recognised as global culture which is termed as global consumer culture positioning. Foreign consumer culture positioning should also be employed. It is the placing of brands to suit other markets abroad. Local consumer culture positioning which is the third strategy is concerned with placing brands to suit locality needs. Businesses that utilise global consumer culture positioning employ global icons as endorsers, adopt globally spoken languages and implement logos and stories to relate to global values (Kjeldgaard and Askegaard, 2006). Foreign consumer culture positioning entails the use of foreign endorsers who possess understanding of national features, logos and stories that are in sync with foreign identities. Local consumer culture positioning on the other hand is concerned with the usage of local symbols or endorsers who are appealing to a particular area or locality (Gao et al., 2018).

2.13.2 Online Reputation

Online reputation is reputation that is generated from electronic communication channels (Chun and Davies, 2001). Research on online reputation is scarce, despite this, some scholars have concluded that, reputation built by firms in online situations are significant than that of offline (Jarvenpaa et al., 2000). Two areas that have attracted research into online reputation are its role and significance among markets. Researchers have also identified some impediments in the usage of online as a means of generating reputation. These are the absence of interacting on a face-to-face basis and the challenges inherent in the security of providing sensitive information (Milne and Culnan, 2004). Siano et al. (2011) also identified lack of credibility and doubts about the real identity of users of online platforms. These factors result in risk and uncertainties in adopting online modes of communication.

Despite these challenges, scholars have identified some characteristics inherent in online communication that aid in developing brand reputation. Kotha et al. (2001) argued that minimum cost of searching for information and enhanced opportunities of sharing information among relevant individuals and groups are some of the positive effects of online reputation. Reputation established online have other positive impacts as well. Online reputation can serve as a reason to purchase offerings (Siano, Vollero and Palazzo, 2011). On the contrary, reputation can also act as a stumbling block to developing relationships with customers when it is bad (Kollock, 1999; Keser, 2002). Kotha (1998) and Kotha et al. (2001) also argued that brands with good reputation have the capacity to transfer such goodwill to online platforms. Thus, consumers who have trust in the reputation of brands can influence future customers through their online activities to act favourable towards those brands (Siano, Vollero and Palazzo, 2011).

Scholars have identified some challenges inherent in building online reputation. Friedman and Resnick (2001) for instance, questioned the honesty of the opinions and the authenticity of those

who conduct the reviews online. Despite setbacks, scholars such as Kotha et al. (2001) have called on firms to channel their investments in building online reputation due to its contribution in building strategic partnerships.

2.13.3 E-Commerce Strategies

E-commerce has been conceptualised by many authors from different perspectives. The definition that has received wide acceptance is the buying and selling of goods and services via online platforms (Gupta et al., 2023). E-commerce is conducted using electronic gadgets such as mobile phones and computers. E-commerce allows the buying and selling of a plethora of goods and services ranging from publications, music, tickets and financial services (Kalakota and Whinston, 1997). The introduction of e-commerce has transformed the business sector and provided easy access to goods and services at appropriate times (Zhang et al., 2020). E-commerce has eliminated queuing in certain markets and at certain places and overcome obstacles inherent in obtaining parking space to engage in business transactions and the stress inherent in engaging in purchases before closing times of firms. E-commerce also provides customers with an interface where a wide range of goods and services can easily be identified and accessed (Antoniou and Batten, 2011). The advent of e-commerce can be attributed to creating more job opportunities in roles such as digital marketers, customer service personnel and software providers (Gupta et al., 2023).

The success of E-commerce stems from flexibility and immediate pleasure. This is reflected in the procedure which includes identifying products in a speedy manner, speedily finalising the check-out procedures and distributing products to customers. Firms must develop strategies to be successful in e-commerce activities. Businesses must incorporate live chat to quickly address customer complaints and questions. This serves as a conduit for meeting customer expectations (Gupta et al., 2023). Guarda et al. (2012) and Liu et al. (2021) advocated for the need to obtain feedback from customers to improve e-commerce websites and applications before they are launched onto the market. Customer concerns must also be incorporated in the design stage of the e-commerce platforms. Gupta et al (2023) highlighted that, the involvement of customers in the design and implementation of e-commerce platforms will prevent frustrations in its usage and curb negative word-of-mouth comments. Businesses must also ensure that various technological advancement tools such as chatbots, quick response times are utilised for meeting customer expectations (Hamad et al., 2018).

2.14 Brand Experience

Brand experience is defined as the total involvement with a particular product which include the emotions, mental and behavioural responses that consumers elicit based on dealings and engaging with a particular product and its environment (Moedeen et al., 2024). Scholars such as Nyer (1997) and Iglesias et al. (2011) have emphasised that, the experience derived from a brand

is a broader concept and should not be restricted to the cognitive or the affective aspects but should include both aspects to elicit responses from consumers. The engagement with a brand can be in the form of interactions during shows, in stores and focusing on product features such as design (Brakus et al., 2009; Chen and Qasim, 2021). Consumers therefore purchase products that they perceive will provide maximum satisfaction both emotionally and mentally (Ding and Tseng, 2015). Consumers that perceive that brands have had positive impacts tend to have positive judgment of such brands (Koay et al., 2020). As a result, scholars such as Brakus et al. (2009) and Yu and Yuan (2019) argued that firms direct their activities towards ensuring that customers have positive experiences and achieve positive judgments which leads to repeat business and customer loyalty in the long term. Moedeen et al. (2024) have identified brand experiences that are desirable as a key determinant in building long-term relationships between firms and consumers. Dwivedi et al. (2018) added that, consumers with favourable brand experience, keep such experiences in memory and develop positive associations which can lead to the creation of high-quality perception of brands.

2.15 Brand Purpose

Brand purpose is one of the underpinnings of brand identity. It is the reason why a brand exists which transcends beyond the profit motive (Kramer 2017). Brand purpose is identified as one of the essential approaches that an organisation employs to attract and bond with users of their offerings (Mirzaei, Webster and Siuki, 2021). Studies have concluded that, consumers choose brands that are consistent with their personal and social identities. These brands have an impact on their activities, assessments and usage experiences (Escalas and Bettman, 2005; Scaraboto and Fischer, 2013). Brand purpose when combined with brand personality influences the strategic direction, vision and goals developed by an organisation (Gartenberg et al., 2019). Brands are being constantly encouraged to go beyond their profit motives and develop other motives that shape and influence the lives of people and satisfy societal interests (Aaker, 2014; Quinn and Thakor, 2018). The purpose of a brand can serve as a backbone for determining the significant influence that firms should have on the society in which it operates (Hollensbe et al., 2014). Firms that have crafted more significant purposes achieve competitive advantages and tend to enjoy future expansions (Vila and Bharadwaj, 2017).

2.16. Brand Authenticity

Brand authenticity is one of the topical issues that merit the attention of consumers in contemporary times (Tran and Nguyen, 2022). Despite its importance, the understanding of authenticity lacks clarity among brand professionals although the concept has been highly linked to the field of branding (Beverland and Luxton, 2005; Brown et al., 2003) and consumer behavioural patterns (Belk and Costa, 1998; Holt, 1997 and Kozinets, 2002). According to Mason (2011), authenticity is concerned with approved products that have value addition for the target markets. Tran and Nguyen (2022) highlighted that, the term authenticity relates to the genuineness and originality inherent in a specific offering. Other scholars have also conceptualised authenticity as genuineness, accuracy, honesty and reliability (Beverland, 2006; Grayson and Martinec, 2004).

Kumail et al. (2022) revealed three aspects of brand authenticity which were objective, constructive, and existing. Morhart et al. (2015) developed three dimensions of an authentic brand which were honesty, credibility and symbolism. Research by Ilicic and Webster concluded that, authenticity inherent in brands positively impacted brand attitudes. Wang (1999) research found that, one of the motivations for tourist visit to a particular site was the authenticity inherent in the brand. A study by Kumail et al. (2022) also revealed that, authenticity influenced purchase intention of hospitality services.

2.17 Brand Extensions

Firms are increasingly adopting brand extensions as a major component in their marketing strategies for their brands. Parent brands leverage on their favourable image and create other categories (Albrecht et al., 2013). This strategy leads to expanding markets and gaining more users (Dens and Pelsmacker, 2016). Scholars have identified brand extension as a strategy that minimises the risks levels inherent in specific products offered to the market. In addition to that, this strategy aids minimise the costs of marketing activities (Keller and Sood, 2003). Despite these identified benefits, scholars such as Volckner and Sattler (2006) have doubted the successful impact that brand extensions have on businesses. However, Michel and Donthu (2014) argued that brand extensions are gaining wide acceptance, and this has led to lack of reliance on single brand categories. Michel and Donthu (2014) further argued that the successful implementation of brand extension strategies was based on possessing a good match between the parent brand and the extension product, developing an efficient and effective marketing assistance services, parent brand conviction, experience of the parent brand and acceptability by distribution channel members. Evangeline and Ragel (2016) and Klink and Smith (2001) also added that, customers favour brands that have been extended if it is a good fit of the parent brand.

Researchers such as Keller and Sood (2003) argued that parent brands can also achieve benefits such as high sales, enhance image and equity if extension brands programmes are successfully implemented. Contrarily, an unsuccessful extension brand can result in destroying the goodwill, image and sales of a successful parent brand (Riley et al., 2013). It is imperative that marketers develop messages that have association between the parent brand and the extension brand to obtain improved communication with target audience (Kim and Yoon, 2013).

2.18 Challenges to Brand Building Success

It is imperative that organisations develop strong brands as part of a strategic focus to be competitive and survive through turbulent situations within the business environment (Keller, 2023; Kay, 2006). This is therefore an indication that the success of a firm is largely linked to the success that its built brands have attained (Chapleo, 2015). Thus, brand management should be recognised as an important topic and attached with the needed attention and interest in both nonprofit and commercial firms (Buil et al., 2016). To successfully manage brands, different resources must be harnessed and there should be a committed to achieving brand objectives (Wang, 2022).

Branding experts such as Keller (2001) have developed six elements that should form the basis for the attainment of successful branding outcomes. Keller (2001) proposed that there are elements that firms should have presence in their activities to realise their branding objectives. These are performance, imagery, salience, judgments, feelings, and resonance. Another scholar, Krake (2005) developed criteria for brand building success which was more focused on factors within an organisation. Krake (2005) first criteria was that firms should develop fewer brands that can be managed to develop the requisite associations with those brands. There should also be proper co-ordination of elements of brands to create awareness and project image. In addition, firms should have a systematic approach towards policy and have clear and unified communication that does not send conflicting signals. In addition, there should be consistency inherent in a firm's character and the brand's character. Lastly, the firm must be passionate about the brand. The success of a brand rests on various brand focused factors that are taken into consideration within a firm (Ewing and Napoli, 2005). According to Chapleo (2015) these factors within a firm can also be referred to as 'brand infrastructure'.

2.19 Organisational Buying Behaviour

Organisational buying behaviour entails patterns geared towards purchasing to meet the objectives of a firm or business and not towards the attainment of individual objectives of those involved (Baker and Parkinson, 2016). The purchasing processes inherent in businesses are complicated which involve many individuals and different objectives and criteria (Johnston and Lewin, 1996). The buying situations in businesses involve various departmental relationships and information from various sources. The length involved in organisational purchases is based on the number of individuals involved and the complicated nature of the purchasing decision (Afif et al., 2020). The various roles and expertise of individuals within a business play a very important role in achieving the desired outcomes of a purchasing situation (Howard and Doyle, 2006). Some researchers argued that businesses are encouraged to buy offerings that aid in profit generation while maintaining limited budgets (Webster Jr and Keller, 2004) while other firms engage in purchases based on their features such as size, structure, orientation, and technology. Other considerations are the type of buying situation such as nature of risk and product types as well as the value that the seller provides in the form of product, price, and quality (Lewin and Donthu, 2005). Another reason that is receiving much focus in business purchasing literature is the country that the product originated from (Dobrucali, 2019).

2.20 Branding and Business Markets

Business markets have more than one individual that undertake a buying decision. The criteria that are used are different due to the roles performed by members within the decision unit of organisations. A study by Bendixen et al. (2004) revealed that, individuals who possess technical expertise within the decision-making unit in an organisation regarded "brand name" as the most important attribute with 24% together with price (Leek and Christodoulides, 2011). Users within the decision-making unit prioritised brand name as the most important factor to consider with 28% (Leek and Christodoulides, 2011). Buyers and gatekeepers within the decision-making unit regarded brand names as relatively important with 16% and 7% respectively. Price was regarded

as the most prioritised attribute among all the roles within the decision-making centre (Leek and Christodoulides, 2011). Another study by Alexander et al. (2009) also identified that 48% of the deciders regarded brand as the most important factor while 42% of users prioritised price as most important. The significance attached to branding in a business market is also based on the characteristics inherent in the purchasing situation. In situations where purchases by businesses are more complicated, branding is prioritised (Mudambi et al., 1997). Members of a firm's buying centre will prioritise brands over other criteria when the purchasing decision has a high degree of uncertainty. The level of risk is also another factor that influences organisational purchasing decisions. Branding receives higher priority in situations where the risk identified in a purchase situation is higher (Bengtsson and Servais, 2005).

2.21 Conceptualisation of Attitude

Allport (1968) contended that attitude played a significant role in research and is applicable across diverse domains of life. Ajzen (2011) explained that the attitudes people have concerning an act, or a behaviour serve as an element that revealed a particular belief of a person and evoked positive or negative contributions to the life of that person. The research of Ajzen (1991) viewed attitude in two different components. Attitude has been considered as feelings that are evoked in a person. Secondly, attitude is considered as knowledge that an individual has pertaining to a specific behaviour. Research has demonstrated that attitude serves as a yardstick which can be used to assess individual behavioural patterns. Consistent with this, Conner and Armitage (1998) stressed on the principle of compatibility which mentioned that performance of certain behaviours evokes specific attitudes. According to the principle of compatibility, there is a difference between attitude and behaviour. It is argued that attitudes become better as a measure for predicting an individual's behaviour when the measures of attitude serve as the individual's expected behaviour (Conner and Armitage, 1998). Cheung et al. (1999) and Lam et al. (2004) have noted that anytime there is high level of attitude toward behaviour, an individual tends to develop a strong intention for the commitment of a particular behaviour.

Attitude formation is based on the level of participation of individuals towards brands. A consumer is regarded to have higher attitude strength when there is an active involvement and as a result, information is processed via a central path (Luttrell and Sawicki, 2020). Luttrell and Sawicki (2020) further asserted that, higher attitude is "an attitude of durability and impact". A low level of involvement in a firm's brand leads to the processing of information via the peripheral path which leads to a weaker attitude strength in terms of consumers projecting behavioural patterns, developing opposing stance to change, and staying resolute with a brand (Petty et al., 1983). The level of involvement of consumers in the offerings of an organisation indicates whether the central or the peripheral path will be activated to process information (Petty and Cacioppo, 1986; Zotos et al., 1992) and through online media (e.g., Peng et al., 2019; Eslami and Ghasemaghaei, 2018; Han and Kim, 2017; Martín et al., 2011; Ha and Lennon, 2010). The use of the central path processing allows customers to generate a lot of thoughts about a firm's offerings unlike using the peripheral path (Rucker et al., 2007; Petty and Cacioppo, 1986; Laurent and Kapferer, 1985).

Attitude is recognised as the total assessment of an object (Rucker et al., 2007) which provides behavioural directions, demonstrates stability for a long time and is constantly in mind (Blankenship and Wegener, 2008). Attitudes are strong and can have an impact. Thus, attitudes that have stability for a long period of time, can be used to determine immediate behavioural patterns and have partiality in thinking are called “strong attitudes”. The strength of attitude is critical for explaining why consumers with similar attitude when it comes to content and valence may develop varied behavioural patterns. Consumers that developed positive attitudes because of greater elaboration, which is also referred to as the central processing, are regarded as having stronger attitudes. Consumers who do not put in less thoughts and efforts towards stimuli are likely to develop weak attitudes (Barden and Petty, 2008; Horcajo and Luttrell, 2016). The development of attitudes occurs based on prior knowledge and current knowledge obtained and the significance that a customer attaches to a product (Howe and Krosnick, 2017). Customers base on previously formed attitudes about existing products as bases for developing new attitudes of about new products (Palla et al., 2023).

2.22 The Concept of Brand Attitude

Attitude towards brands is regarded as a critical concept in the field of individual and organisational behavioural patterns (Lee and Kang, 2013; Marticotte and Arcand, 2017). Park et al. (1986) contended that brands enable firms to make higher profits and render products of firms unique in their customers’ minds. Yoo and MacInnis (2005) considered brand attitudes as customers’ holistic evaluation of a specific brand. In their study, Spears and Singh (2004) intimated that brand attitude involved the persistent and consistent evaluation activity carried out by customers of a product. Brand attitude is the ability to consistently respond and react favourably or unfavourably to a specific brand (Yim et al., 2014). The attitude of customers concerning a particular brand serves as a reflection of positive or negative evaluation of the brand; and this tends to affect the behavioural patterns that is evoked towards the product by the customers (Bartsch et al., 2016). Therefore, positive evaluations of brands stem from consumers’ positive brand attitudes. Meyer (2008) added that customers form attitude based on information and experiences with a brand. The family, social, cultural, and global sources are recognised as the means through which individuals obtain knowledge to form attitude towards objects (Hamid, 2014). Aaker and Jacobson (2001) also concluded that, brand attitude formation is based on new products, issues surrounding products, changes in senior managerial positions and legal actions. According to Liu et al. (2020) factors that influence brand attitude may be categorised into two. These include consumer-side factors and brand-side factors. It has been noted that internal driving factors, self-concept and consumer knowledge constitute the category of consumer-side factors. According to Gonzalez-Jimenez (2017), brand attitude is affected by the overall process involving the consumer self-concept life cycle. On the other hand, the name of the brand and the platforms where the brand is presented served as the brand-side factors that affected brand attitude. For instance, the findings of Kachersky and Carnevale (2015) have shown that diverse personal pronouns (first vs. second vs. third person) found in the name of a brand have the propensity to influence the decision-making preferences of consumers concerning the product of a brand. In another study, Mukherjee and Banerjee (2019) reported that a brand’s presentation on various social networking platforms influences the attitude of a consumer towards the brand. Other researchers, including Kotler and Keller (2006) have established that if customers express positive attitudes towards a brand, the positive brand experience increases. On the other hand,

the possibility of consumers using a specific brand tends to decrease anytime a negative attitude is expressed towards the brand by customers.

2.23 Components of Brand Attitude

There is no consensus on the constructs of brand attitude. While some scholars regard brand attitude as uni-dimensional which is emotion (Um and Yoon, 2020) or individualist assessment (Mitchell and Olson, 1981), others recognised the concept as multidimensional (Um and Yoon, 2020). Researchers also integrate two defining features of attitude, which as indicated by Giner-Sorolla (1999), appear constant among the various 20th century definitions in the literature. The first of these two features is the idea that attitude is centred or directed at an object, which in this regard, reference is made towards a brand. The second feature is the consideration of attitude as an evaluative element whereby it is construed possess a certain level of goodness or badness (Eagly and Chaiken 1993). The last section of the definition of Mitchell and Olson (1981), which is internal evaluation is also very important and appears noteworthy. That aspect of the definition implies that an attitude is an internal state. Spears and Singh (2004) agreeing with Eagly and Chaiken (1973), added that attitude has the ability to endure at least for a brief duration and has the potential to lead to behaviour. This means that the manner in which consumers' attitude towards brand is the conceptualised is a summary assessment which is uni-dimensional in nature can result in behavioural tendencies (Spears and Singh, 2004). From the definition given above, Giner-Sorolla (1999) followed the assertion of Machleit et al. (1993) and Zanna and Rempel (1988), in treating attitude as a "summary evaluation" to enable them to differentiate it from an evaluation that is based on beliefs, feelings, behavioural tendencies and others. In their conceptualisation, attitudes toward a brand are different from feelings that are elicited by the same brand. Whereas feelings towards a brand are transitory, consumers' attitude towards the brand are comparatively stable (Batra and Ray, 1986). Spears and Singh (2004) also added that, consumers' affective responses / feelings / moods should not be considered emotional responses. They explained that consumer feelings appear mild, general, pervasive. They are not evoked directly towards any specific object. Regarding this, researchers including Gardner (1985), Petty et al. (2001), and Schwarz and Clore (1996) have established that, unlike feelings, emotions are more intense and tend to relate directly to a specifiable behaviour.

Other scholars have also identified brand attitude as a multi-dimensional construct. For instance, in the research of Lee and Back (2008), consumer brand attitude was categorised into three aspects. The categorisation consists of brand image (general brand impressions), Word of Mouth (WOM) and brand commitment. According to Kotler and Keller (2006), consumer attitude comprises behavioural tendencies, likes or dislikes and passionate feelings. Fishbein (1967), Hossien (2011) and Yoon and Park (2012) identified brand attitude as multidimensional concept with three components. These are cognitive, affective and conative. The consumers' beliefs about or the kind of knowledge they have regarding a product or service of a particular brand constitutes cognitive attitude (Um and Yoon, 2020). It includes the cognition or knowledge the consumers have regarding a brand after they have acquired and integrated the direct experiences with the product or accessed credible information on the product. The affective component is regarded as the emotion or affective reaction (Wu and Wang, 2011). The other component, conation, or mental component involves the likelihood or propensity of a consumer to exhibit a specific action or behaviour towards a brand (Wu and Wang, 2011). It has been pointed out by

Walsh et al. (2010) that the attitude of consumers towards a product could serve as the basis for explaining consumers' intention regarding their future purchase behaviours, especially in situations whereby consumer attitude is directly expressed towards a particular brand.

In this study brand attitude is treated as a uni-dimensional construct. This is in agreement with findings in literature. For instance, in the findings of Zanna and Rempel (1988), Spears and Singh (2004), Salehzadeh and Pool (2017), and Charton-Vachet et al. (2020), brand attitude was treated as a "summary evaluation" from the uni-dimensional perspective. This study adopted the conceptualisation of brand attitude as an emotional construct (Fishbein, 1967; Um and Yoon, 2020). This is consistent with the assertion by Ajzen (1991) that, the emotional construct is solely considered by researcher to ascertain the impact of attitude on purchase or behavioural intention. The uni-dimensional nature of attitude conceptualisation provides the basis on which other variables in the study are separated and tested. The study adopted the definition of attitude as an emotional construct defined by Um and Yoon (2020). Attitude in this study is defined as the degree of positive or negative emotions exhibited towards a specific object (Um and Yoon, 2020). Attitude is therefore acquired and makes individuals react to a specific object (Allport, 1933). Spears and Singh (2004) scale for measuring brand attitude was adapted for the study. This is because Spears and Singh (2004) conceptualisation of brand attitude as a uni-dimensional construct is consistent with this study. In addition, Spears and Singh (2004) scale is well accepted among scholars. As a result, a conceptual study by Naseem et al. (2015) which involved the variables of brand attitude, perceived value and purchase intention advocated for the empirical testing of brand attitude using the Spears and Singh (2004) scale. Other more recent scales (Peters and Slovic, 2007; Ahn and Back, 2018; Zhang and Chen, 2022) similar to Spears and Singh (2004) which were used in measuring brand attitude quantitatively were also considered.

In terms of the qualitative section, the interview questions on brand attitude were guided by Coelho et al. (2018) brand related study and research by Edbring et al. (2016) on brand attitude. Aspect on perceived value was guided by Lim et al (2014) and Coutelle-Brillet et al. (2014) interview guide related to perceived value. The study of Lim et al. (2014) who conducted an exploratory study guided the development of purchase intention section of the interview guide.

2.24 Benefits of Brand Attitude

Attitude is regarded as a key component in the evaluating process of a brand (Collins-Dodd and Lindley, 2003; Arachchi and Samarasinghe, 2023). Brands are viewed based on the influences that they possess and the ability to be meaningful to consumers. Consumers are therefore interested in brands that will aid in achieving their goals (Park et al., 2010). As a result, consumers develop attachment to brands based on their impact on their lives (Rammile, 2015). In their study, Yin Wong and Merrilees (2008) also asserted that brand attitude serves as a crucial factor in determining a brand's success in a market. Researchers have identified that, when consumers develop a positive attitude towards a brand in the long run, it will result in marketing benefits such as minimal costs and reduced risks of introducing a new product that has a brand name and is already in existence (He et al., 2016). According to Soltani et al (2013), consumers are more likely to purchase a new product that has an existing brand name because they are

likely to associate the quality and benefits enjoyed from the product with existing brand name with the new product. Brand attitude as explained by Papadimitriou et al. (2016), is very important in the development of solid brand equity outcomes, which entails high awareness and perception of quality. From the argument of Behaviour Theory, the chance to toughen a brand and enable it to gain a competitive advantage serves as a benefit a brand obtains from consumer attitude (Faust, 2013). It has been noted that the attitude of consumers of luxury goods towards a brand has the propensity to make them consider brand monopoly as something that cannot be lost because of inaccessibility on the part of majority of consumers (Salehzadeh and Pool, 2017). McLean et al. (2020) revealed that attitude of consumers exhibited towards brands enables businesses enjoy a surge in the number of purchases of their products. Trang et al. (2019) study of mobile commerce also found that, the development of positive attitude towards brands have resulted in increasing revenues and the loyalty of customers. Firms are continuously engaging in activities targeted towards the enhancement of brand attitude in other to gain more profits and not only attract customers but retain them in the long-term (Kim et al., 2016). Aaker and Jacobson (2001) research in products that are highly driven by technology revealed that, brand attitude is regarded as asset and as such can be utilised to project the futuristic earnings of a business. Aaker and Jacobson (2001) further indicated that, brand attitude is used to determine financial performance due to its ability to increase return on stocks.

2.25 The Role of Pricing in Firms

In the marketing and branding literature, price has been considered as one of the important parameters that determine products' costs (Erdil, 2015). Axsen and Kurani (2012) asserted that, consumers expect to derive functional benefits from the automobiles that they purchase. Some of these benefits include increased vehicle performance, cost-effectiveness, and reliability. Price refers to the financial amount that customers expend on a product or service. It is essentially the value relinquished by customers to acquire and use a firm's offerings (Kotler and Armstrong, 2010). In other words, price represents the value that customers are willing to forego to acquire a product or service (Kotler and Armstrong, 2010; Zeithaml, 1988). Additionally, price encompasses critical information for assessing the level of service, which can significantly impact purchasing behaviour (Shoemaker et al., 2005). Pricing has long been recognised as a key element in marketing of products (Borden, 1964), and among the mixes for marketing purposes, it stands out as the sole contributor to revenue (Al-Salamin and Al-Hassan, 2016). As Morris (1987) emphasised, one of the fundamental decisions a business faces is determining the appropriate pricing mechanisms. This decision becomes particularly crucial in what The Economist (2013) has termed the "age of austerity," characterised by stagnant sales, limited cost-cutting possibilities, and pricing as the remaining lever for action. In this fiercely competitive environment, the need for a well-defined pricing strategy becomes more critical than ever, as it facilitates the creation of value, shapes pricing decisions, and ultimately ensures profitability (Lancioni et al., 2005). A poorly conceived pricing strategy can lead to reduced sales volumes and consequential business challenges (Wasserman, 2010). Furthermore, an organisation's pricing strategy has a pervasive impact on its overall corporate strategy, influencing manufacturing, distribution, and sales promotion strategies.

Hsu and Pham (2015) who analysed price from a corporate perspective postulated that, a company must utilise price references to gauge its selling prices against both internal and external benchmarks. Dhanabalan et al. (2018) acknowledged the effect on pricing in influencing consumers' willingness to purchase. Most scholars and consultants concur that pricing is an exceedingly intricate function (Lancioni et al., 2005; Liozu, 2012). This complexity may arise from organisational pressures to implement innovative pricing approaches (Liozu et al., 2014), the requirement for cross-functional collaboration (Lancioni et al., 2005), or the absence of formal change management practices to support the implementation of progressive pricing strategies, resulting in irrational pricing decisions (Liozu, 2013). Consequently, many leaders find pricing to be a managerial headache (Dolan, 1995). Several firms developing pricing initiatives find themselves grappling with good intentions but are unsure about how to better manage pricing complexity (Hinterhuber and Liozu, 2012). Therefore, companies should place greater emphasis on effective pricing strategies (Wasserman, 2010). A single pricing strategy is unlikely to suit all products, it is therefore imperative for firms to develop varied pricing strategies to suit specific products based on factors such as customers, competitors, quality as well as overhead costs (Wasserman, 2010).

2.25.1 Price Sensitivity

Goldsmith and Newell (1997) defined price sensitivity as the total reactions that consumers exhibit towards prices of goods and services. It entails the feelings of consumers towards the payment of a particular price towards products and services. The reactions towards prices of goods and services vary from consumer to consumer and is therefore not constant (Ramirez, and Goldsmith, 2009). Price sensitivity refers to the degree to which consumers perceive or react to variations inherent in the prices offered by various brands (Monroe, 1973).

Price thresholds are important to marketers due to some reasons. It enables businesses to ascertain the least price that will have an influence in the choices that consumers make (Han, Gupta and Lehmann, 2001). Determining the level of prices will aid distributors obtain more favourable pricing regime for consumers. Price thresholds also enable marketers determine the right pricing strategy for different segments. Products with high prices may be an indicator of quality or premium service provider (Han, Gupta and Lehmann, 2001). Findings by Inglesi-Lotz (2014) in electricity consumption patterns in South Africa revealed a reduction in price sensitive from the 1980s to the 1990s. In the 2000s consumer behavioural patterns did not experience significant changes in prices. Another study in Africa by Adom (2017) determined the sensitivity of price among industrial and residential consumers. The results revealed that, industrial consumers were more sensitive to price than residential consumers in Ghana. Bhutto et al. (2022) conducted research in another developing economy, specifically Pakistan. The study sought to ascertain the relationship between attitude, subject norms and perceived behavioural control on the intention of green consumers to buy hybrid automobiles. The variables were moderated by price sensitivity. The results revealed that, price sensitivity moderated the relationship between attitude and consumers' intention to purchase green hybrid automobiles. However, price sensitivity did not moderate the relationship between perceived behavioural control and green purchase intention of consumers. Bhutto et al. (2022) concluded that, stronger intentions developed towards green products will result in higher intention to buy hybrid automobiles.

2.26 Perceptions

Perceptions are fundamentally shaped by a combination of factors, including familiarity, past experiences, personal values, and motivations (Schiffman and Kanuk, 1997). Consequently, perceptions represent a captivating and vital concept within the field of marketing. While there is a wealth of research on perceptions, it is noteworthy that few studies provide a clear definition or in-depth discussion of the concept before delving into its application. According to Moutinho (1993), perception is processes inherent selecting, organising, and assigning meanings to stimuli in a comprehensible manner. These stimuli can encompass sensory inputs from various modalities, including auditory, visual, tactile, olfactory, and taste. Individuals, in turn, engage in a selective organisation of these, creating meaningful connections, and their interpretation is significantly influenced by a blend of social and personal factors (Moutinho, 1993). As the concept of perception finds its way into the realm of individual and organisational behaviour from the domain of cognitive psychology, research focused on consumer perceptions predominantly examines the cognitive aspects inherent in the perceptual process (Axelsen and Swan, 2010). Disparities in perceptions often give rise to differences in conation, which relates to behavioural intent. One crucial implication of this phenomenon is that much like attitude, perception plays a pivotal role in shaping satisfaction levels and influencing assessments of service quality (Cohen et al., 2014).

2.27 Definitions of Perceived Value

Researchers such as Woodruff (1997), Falk and Dierking (2018), Sheng and Chen (2012) and Salehzadeh and Pool (2017) asserted that, perceived value is a concept that exhibits dynamism and can be experienced before buying products, during the purchasing of products, in the process of using products and when the products have been used. Many researchers of consumer behaviour have generated immense interest in conducting various studies on the issue of perceived value (Piyathasanan et al., 2015). Despite the interest, there is no consensus on the definition of the concept. The concept appears interdisciplinary in nature, and this has led to its observable numerous conceptualisations in the extant literature (Boksberger and Melsen, 2011). Kim et al. (2008) defined perceived value as the benefits that a consumer will derive from the purchase of good or a service. Despite the existence of different definitions for perceived value by different researchers, as observed in the literature, contemporary studies on the construct appear to favour the definition offered by Zeithaml (1988) which was adopted for this study. Zeithaml (1988) defined perceived value as the evaluation of utility inherent in products based on perceived delivery and expectations. Chang et al. (2009) intimated that the definition of Zeithaml (1988) indicated the reflection of customers' evaluation of the service or the value obtained from product as comparison of the cost involved in or the money the consumer paid, and the benefit obtained from the service or the product. It therefore reflects the comparison the consumer makes between what he or she gets (get component) and what he or she gives (give component). Perceived quality is defined based on customer perspective of what is quality (Mitra and Golder, 2006) which is derived from the definition of Zeithaml (1988) who viewed quality as subjective consumer assessment. Lieb et al. (2008) offered a contrary perspective of perceived quality and concluded that, it is an addition from an organisation. Lieb et al. (2008) dismissed the assertion that perceived quality lacks objectivity and the ability to be measured. There are other scholars who back the stance that, perceived quality should be recognised from a marketing philosophical perspective. Aaker (2009) for instance viewed perceived quality as superiority

inherent in an offering based on its purpose of purchase and competing options. Styliadis et al. (2015) concluded that, it is imperative that, the concept of perceived quality in key industries like automobile production needs to have an objective evaluation method despite its highly held subjective perspective. The over-reliance on the provision of quality from engineering perspective within the automobile industry in this contemporary global economic system is not sustained and there is therefore the need for automobile firms to develop products that satisfy customer requirements (Robinson, 2000; Petiot et al., 2009). In this study, perceived value is viewed from the pre-purchase stage.

2.28 Importance of Perceived Value

Babin and James (2010) have asserted that every meaningful marketing activity made about a product is directed purposefully at value creation. From his perspective as a practitioner, van Rensburg (2012) considered it as a “sine qua non for businessmen and marketers”. Studies by Yang et al. (2011), Ryu et al. (2012), Byon et al. (2013) and Kwon and Kwak (2014) have recognised perceived value as having direct and indirect association with many different attitudinal and behavioural attributes. As argued by Gallarza et al. (2012), perceived value may present a crucial benefit to a firm and therefore serves as a significant concept. One key importance of perceived value is the ability to aid manufacturers to identify customer needs and wants and tailor their offerings to satisfy them (Pandža Bajcs, 2015). Other studies such as Eggert and Ulaga (2002), Gale (1994) and Payne and Holt (2001) have concluded that firms that embrace perceived value in their business activities tend to have an edge over their competitors.

Perceived value serves as a tool that firms can explore in their quest to develop a lasting relationship with their customers (Cronin et al., 2000; Parasuraman and Grewal, 2000; Yang et al., 2011). Shapiro et al. (2019) observed that, perceived value is realised when consumers identify the benefits inherent in an offering whether financial or non-financial compared to the cost incurred in obtaining the offerings. Yang et al. (2011) have posited that consumer of a product, after the evaluation, must be satisfied to exhibit positive purchase behaviour towards the product. Chen and Chang (2012) also asserted that, firms must ensure that, their marketing activities are consistent with the values that consumers perceive from their offering obtain high sales. Salehzadeh and Pool (2017) also argued that perceived value is of more importance to the study of consumer behaviour than satisfaction because whereas satisfaction is obtained after usage of a product, perceived value can be assessed at various stages inherent in the purchasing decision-making process. Chattaras and Shukla (2015) asserted that, firms can be successful in their marketing activities when they perceive the value that consumers will derive from their offerings and respond appropriately. Malima and Moyo (2023) identified perceived value features such as engine capacity, low fuel consumption and vehicle sizes as features that were considered for vehicle choice. Low price was also an important factor in buying vehicles in Africa (Deloitte, 2018). Forbes Africa (2022) also argued that African automobile market, similar to that of Europe should possess quality and cost-effective spare parts, have competent experts, licensed workshop centres, efficient distribution channel system and able vehicle diagnostic systems.

2.29 Dimensions of Perceived Value

The conceptualisation of perceived value as a multidimensional or uni-dimensional construct demonstrate that two main approaches are involved (Ruiz et al., 2010). Concerning the uni-dimensional approach, researchers including Chi and Kilduff (2011), Dodds and Monroe (1985) and Monroe and Chapman (1987) have observed that it is highly dependent on consumer's price perceptions or the observable difference between consumers' perceived quality of the product and sacrifices in terms of payment they must make in order to obtain a product.

Although the literature showed that a stronger empirical underpinning exists concerning customer perceived value, uni-dimensional conceptualisation is viewed as simpler implementation and assessment (Sanchez-Fernandez and Iniesta-Bonillo, 2007). The findings of Leroi-Werelds et al. (2014) and Jamrozky and Lawonk (2017) have shown that scholars have favourable disposition towards the multidimensional proposition which has led to its wider acceptance. Previous studies, including Bolton and Drew (1991) and Dodds et al. (1991) which conceptualised perceived value simply as products' quality and price have been considered flawed in their findings by other studies that reported that perceived value being considered as mere trade-off between quality and price is not sufficient for firms in gaining competitive advantage (Rust and Oliver, 2000; Rintamaki et al., 2006). Consequently, the simplicity nature of the approach has led to its criticism. Chen and Hu (2010), Lin et al. (2005) and Sigala (2006) contended that the uni-dimensional conceptualisation approach failed to appreciate perceived value's multifaceted and complex nature.

The observable flaw of the uni-dimensional conceptualisation approach compelled researchers to advance the multidimensional approach to the explanation of perceived value, as they seek to offer a holistic explanation to the complexity of the construct (Chuah et al., 2014). In the study of Sweeney and Soutar (2001), it advocated for the development of a more sophisticated approach in the manner in which consumers assess goods and services. This implied that an integrated approach to the understanding of perceived value is required because the only way of obtaining a holistic understanding of the concept of value is taking into consideration all kinds of values (Holbrook, 1999; Sweeney and Soutar, 2001). The multi-dimensional approach appeared appealing in offering a more valid explanation as it captured customer perceived value's conceptual richness (Sweeney and Soutar, 2001).

In addition, Boksberger and Melsen (2011) reported that, perceived value has been studied dominantly in services than goods. It is argued therefore that because of certain characteristics of service marketing, including inseparability, intangibility, heterogeneity, and perishability, it has become more complex to undertake measurement of its perceived quality or value. In effect, it has become more adequate to consider the construct as a multi-dimensional instead of studying it as a single dimensional construct.

Despite the consideration of perceived value as multi-dimensional, researchers in the area have not agreed on the dimensions the construct comprised of (Gallarza et al., 2015; Leroi-Werelds et al., 2014; El-Adly and ELSamen, 2018; Gallarza et al., 2011) and the literature showed that only

a few scales have been accepted by researchers (Akkaya, 2021). Consequently, it is observable from the extant literature that researchers have employed diverse number of dimensions in their studies. For instance, in the research of Storbacka et al. (2012) and Zauner et al (2015) on perceived value applied two dimensions while in the study of Mathwick et al. (2001), six dimensions were adopted. The highest number of dimensions employed by a researcher to investigate consumer perceived values was thirteen as noted in the work of Lam et al. (2004).

The application of perceived value in various contextual situations have a strong effect on the proposed dimensionality or the number of dimensions required (Sánchez-Fernández and Iniesta-Bonillo, 2007 and Gallarza et al., 2011). The usage of hedonic and utilitarian approach of perceived value for example, was investigated by Holbrook and Hirschman (1982), Babin et al. (1994) and Jones et al. (2006) in the domain of service marketing, specifically in retailing. In other studies, Ryu et al. (2010) examined perceived value in hospitality with hedonic and utilitarian approach. The same construct of perceived value was researched by Babin and Kim (2001) in the domain of tourism. Holbrook (1999) was credited with the development of the classical hedonicutilitarian. In his approach, Holbrook (1999) developed three types of perceived value which were intrinsic and extrinsic, active and reactive as well as self-oriented and other oriented. These categories were further developed into eight types. These were efficiency, excellence (quality), play. The others included aesthetics, status, esteem, ethics, and spirituality. El-Adly and ELSamen (2018) reported that many different researchers have employed this framework in their assessment of value dimensions. In their research, social, perceived sacrifice and emotions were regarded as perceived value dimensions, and energy, time and effort as non-monetary factors were included by Wang et al. (2004). Epistemic, monetary, conditional, emotional, convenience, and social factors were used by Pura (2005) in defining the dimensions of perceived value.

Another categorisation of value as multi-dimensional was observed in the framework of consumption-value theory which was propounded by Sheth et al. (1991). According to the theory, the choices consumers make regarding brands comprised different forms of values. In their categorisation of consumer values that affect choices of brands, Sheth et al. (1991) identified conditional value, functional value, epistemic value, and emotional value. Others were conditional value and social value. In their categorisation, Sheth et al. (1991) posited that these various values played their respective roles independently and additive based on the situational context and product, or service involved. Zauner et al. (2015) and Sweeney and Soutar (2001) categorised the values of consumers according to social, emotional and functional values and suggested that the value for money and quality in the retailing context would be different from that of other contexts. Kim et al. (2011), following the argument of Sweeney and Soutar (2001) developed six forms of measuring perception of value of consumers. These included playfulness and aesthetics which was connected to emotional value. Social self-image expression and social support constituted social value. Quality and price utility were regarded as functional value. Another scale called MALLVAL was for measuring customer perceived value developed by El-Adly and Eid (2015). This scale had seven dimensions. Hedonic, self-gratification and utilitarian value were considered. The others were epistemic, social interaction, time convenience and transaction value.

This research adapted PERVAL scale by Sweeney and Soutar (2001) and considered three dimensions of value. These three dimensions were the social value, quality, and price. It has become clear from the discussions above that emotional, functional value (perceived quality and perceived price) and social value, adequately provide specificity of perceived value, as noted by Yeh et al. (2016). These dimensions of value were inculcated into the development of the Sweeney and Soutar (2001) scale (Slack et al., 2020; Hou and Sarigöllü, 2020 and Yeh et al., 2016).

In addition, Akkaya (2021) asserted that, there were not many widely accepted scales to measure perceived value in the research community. The PERVAL scale developed by Sweeney and Soutar's (2001) scale was adapted because it is widely used, and well-adopted multidimensional scale published to measure perceived value (Slack et al., 2020; Hou and Sarigöllü, 2020; Yeh et al., 2016; Akkaya, 2021) and include all the important variables (Slack et al., 2020; Hou and Sarigöllü, 2020 and Yeh et al., 2016). The PERVAL scale was also ideal because it captured the required items needed to measure the multi-dimensional perspective of perceived value that will serve as an intermediary link between brand attitude and purchase intention within the automobile industry. In the current study, the researcher adapted three dimensions of Sweeney and Soutar (2001) scale specifically price, -quality and social value because the emotional construct was recognised as a uni-dimensional conceptualisation of attitude in this study. Researchers such as Ajzen (1991), Salehzadeh and Pool (2017) and Um and Yoon (2020) viewed attitude as a uni-dimensional emotional variable, which can influence intention or actual behaviour. Below were the discussions of the dimensions of perceived value adapted for the study which were perceived price, perceived quality which constituted functional value and social value.

2.29.1 Functional Value

Functional value (utilitarian) has been the focus of researchers despite the existence of other aspects of value (Shapiro et al., 2019). Functional value to be the perceived benefits acquired for usefulness or physical performance (Sheth et al., 1991). Endurance, price and dependability may be examples of these dimensions. Regarding functional value perceptions, it has been reported by the findings of Buhalis (2000) and Lian Chan and Baum (2007) that administrative help, punctuality of the service provider, price, efficiency, security, information, available packages, quality places and amenities may be included. Patterson and Spreng (1997) also postulated that, the kind of widely accepted value conceptualisation is the kind of definition that is based on performance/quality and price. In the current study, the researcher focused on these two dimensions of functional value which were quality and price and social value.

2.29.1.1. Functional Value, Perceived Quality

In their research, Nyadzayo and Khajehzadeh (2016) described the quality of a product as the entirety of an evaluation of the performance that a product offers to a consumer. In order to achieve product quality, customers are interested in dealing with manufacturers and suppliers that will provide offerings that are consistent with their expectations (Brink and Brendt, 2004). Naseem et al. (2015) considered perceived quality to be the judgement of the consumer regarding the entire product excellence or superiority as projected by the judgment of the

consumers. According to Zeithaml (1988), the value of perceived quality may be differentiated from actual or objective quality. Regarding this, Naseem et al. (2015) explained that perceived quality portrayed the notion of a product's durability and reliability from a functional perspective. It has been explained that anytime the expectations of the customers are met or exceeded, it becomes a value for the customer (Mbango, 2019). Contrarily, the awareness of customers of low level of quality that a product possesses tends to make them start thinking of terminating the relationship they have with the supplier (Anton et al., 2007 and Hess et al., 2003).

2.29.1.2 Functional Value, Perceived Price

According Zeithaml (1988) consumers perception of price relate to the perception that they hold about products. In their definition of price, Zeithaml (1988) and Han and Ryu (2009) asserted that consumers view price as sacrifice to make to possess products needed to satisfy them. Naseem et al. (2015) contended that price models of perception consider the perceived sacrifices of the consumer, the non-monetary costs which include search effort, travel, time and psychic distance, either explicitly or implicitly. Even though Monroe and Krishnan (1985) exhibited evidence of positive correlation between price and product's quality, Zeithaml (1988) argued that there was no statistically significant relationship between a product's price and its quality. According to Calvo-Porrall and Levy-Mangin (2019), perceived price consists of the subjective form of a product's monetary value, which also include the consideration of customers perspective on the costly or less costly nature of goods and services and the purchasing power that is possessed. In their study, Sweeny and Soutar (2001) explained that the functional value that was identified with the price of a product involves the utility consumers obtained based on long-term and short-term perceived cost of products. In their research, Jacob and Olson (1977) differentiated between perceived price, which was the price that the consumer of the product encodes as either cheap or expensive, and objective price, which is the actual price the supplier marked on the product. Explaining price further, Han and Ryu (2009) asserted that customer use price to predict the expected performance that will be derived from the purchase and usage of a business offerings. It therefore serves as a yard of evaluating customer experience and forming attitude towards a seller or an establishment. Büyükdağ et al. (2020) argued that the actual price of a product is of less importance as compared to the consumers' perceived value of the price. From the perspective of product price, the findings of Ranaweera and Neely (2003) have shown that perceived price is a key component of customer value, since it was possible to relate the perceived customer value to the perceived benefits and less perceived costs. Thus, customers are interested in purchasing from a firm if the perceived benefits enjoyed outstrips perceived costs. Herrmann et al. (2007) concurred with Ranaweera and Neely (2003) by indicating that the perceived price has the ability to influence the holistic judgments of customers of a product.

2.29.2 Social Value

Since the 1990s, an increasing number of scholars have shifted their focus towards examining human behaviour from a sociological perspective, asserting that behaviours are not merely personal actions but are inherently intertwined with societal dynamics. The adoption of a specific behaviour is heavily influenced by the actions of others (Li et al., 2017). In essence, whether an individual chooses to adopt a particular behaviour or not, it is often contingent on the prevailing

behaviours of those around them. This perspective arises from the understanding that individuals frequently adjust their behaviour in response to societal norms and collective actions (Kollmuss and Agyeman, 2002). The rationale behind this is that a behaviour tends to be perceived as reasonable or acceptable when it aligns with the behaviours of the majority, as individuals often adapt their conduct in consideration of prevailing social opinions and norms (Kollmuss and Agyeman, 2002). Social value is the perceived benefits that customers enjoy from products that aligns and receives acceptability with their social circles which ultimately enriches their self-concept (Sheth et al., 1991). Naseem et al. (2015) advocated for the use of societal aspects such as pressures exerted on customers that influence their purchasing decisions although other aspects such as communicating and impressing members of a reference group will be complicated in researching on. Hultsman et al. (2015) postulated that, individuals develop social values via experiences within the society, demographic structure, culture or ethnic groups. Regarding this, Holbrook (1999) contended that consumers will be accepted within their societal space and enhance their social standing if they choose products that are appealing and conform to their societal expectations.

Transportation particularly vehicular are being assessed beyond the functional benefits that are derived from their usage (Schuitema et al., 2013). Vehicles are an indication of class or luxurious status or a symbol of status (Steg, 2003). The automobile in olden times was perceived to be for individuals who belonged to the upper class and vehicles were designed to meet the prestige and luxurious goals (Canzler, 1999). Katz (1999) also postulated that, automobiles in contemporary times have replaced jewellery and watches as symbols of identities. Girasek and Taylor (2010) concluded that, high-income earners are more likely to buy vehicles that have better safety characteristics and emphasise their societal status. As a result, automobile firms improve their market share by employing marketing strategies to position their vehicles as luxury brands that are of high status (Sovacool and Axsen, 2018). Automobiles are also being used as a social symbol which include means of identifying an individual, likely hobbies and ceremonial displays (Kent, 2014). Individuals' usage of vehicles is also affected by social and cultural trends such as educational background, habits exhibited at work, location of homes and courtship (Flink, 1980). Vehicles are used to demonstrate status which is reflected in the level of career attainment, speed, safety and security that it provides (Sheller, 2004). Axsen and Kurani (2012) postulated that, vehicles are purchased by consumers to demonstrate their self-identity and obtain acceptability in a group. For instance, if most people opt for conventional fuel vehicles (CFVs), those who choose to adopt battery electric vehicles (BEVs) may be viewed as unconventional or unsociable. This social influence becomes a pivotal factor in shaping consumers' intentions to embrace electric vehicles (Eppstein et al., 2011; Zhuge and Shao, 2019). Axsen et al. (2015) and Axsen et al. (2017) further asserted that, in contemporary times, the advent of electric vehicles has further developed the symbolic communications of vehicles in achieving social status. The Nissan-Leaf vehicle for instance is considered as environmentally friendly while Tesla vehicles reflect "success" or being "exotic". The behaviour of peers, friends, and family members can significantly impact the adoption of electric vehicles. Individuals are more likely to consider electric vehicles when they see others in their social circles adopting them. Social norms and trends related to environmental consciousness also contribute to the acceptance of electric automobiles (Zhuge and Shao, 2019). Societal influence, in this context, pertains to the significance that individuals attach to the recognition obtained from their relatives, peers, colleagues, close associates or other individuals with the society. Li et al. (2017) asserted that, social influence can make customers adopt a particular innovation or technology. Diagrammatic presentation below highlighted the dimensions of perceived value adapted for the study.

Figure 2. 1: Perceived Value Constructs for the Study

Adapted from Sweeney and Soutar (2001)

The Sweeney and Soutar (2001) model consisted of four dimensions which were emotional value, social value, perceived quality and perceived price. The study adapted the Sweeney and Soutar (2001) model because of the uni-dimensionality and emotional conceptualisation of brand attitude consistent with Fishbein (1967), Ajzen (1991) and Um and Yoon (2020). The uni-dimensional nature of attitude conceptualisation provided the basis on which other variables in the study were separated and tested.

2.30 Relationships Among Perceived Value Constructs

Rasoolimanesh et al. (2023) study in Iran revealed that, functional and social values which were two adapted values for this study influenced the satisfaction level of domestic tourists and their willingness to visit again. Ashton et al. (2010) research in Australia concluded that, perceived quality, perceived price influenced the intention of hotel restaurant dinners to buy. A study by Liu et al. (2023) on public hospital visit in China concluded that, patients developed perceived value in order to ascertain core values. The findings identified that the perception attached to quality, price and social value were some of the key determinants of the hospital's core values. Zhang et al. (2023) study of crowding funding projects revealed that, investors demonstrated willingness to participate in the project based on perceived price, perceived cost and social values. The results further indicated that, entrepreneurial efforts to enhance investment platforms also improved investors' perceptions of quality, price, and social values. The study further

indicated that, the provision of information to enhance transparency tend to have a positive effect on the perception of quality and price attached to the investment platforms. Jiang and Hong (2023) researched the tourism industry in China with Generation Z as consumers. The study concluded that various perceived value dimensions, quality, price, and social value did not have an impact on the attachment that Generation Z tourists exhibited towards a destination. Kashif et al. (2023) research in Pakistan about organic food consumption among students revealed that, social value, perceived price, and perceived quality affected their willingness to purchase. Research by DelVecchio and Puligadda (2012) in the United States among students who were consumers revealed that, lowering of prices of pasta sauce brand created the perception of a product with less quality. The study further revealed that, it was only when the brand was presented as a discounted offer that consumers did not perceive them as low in quality.

2.31 Purchase Intentions

It has become important that cognition is given to the purchase intention of consumers, since their actions could be predicted via their intentions (Kamalul Ariffin et al., 2018; Wu et al., 2011; Hsu et al., 2017). Purchase intention in this regard has a relation with their actual behaviour (Madan and Yadav, 2018). In the research of Wu et al. (2015), it was noted that purchase intentions served as the possibility of the product. This implies that the strength of purchase is strongly influenced by willingness to buy (Kamalul Ariffin et al., 2018; Lee et al., 2017; Martins et al., 2019; Wu et al., 2011). Consumers intention to buy a firm's offerings is strongly linked to attitude and the perception held towards a firm's brand (Beneke et al., 2016). The scale for purchase intention was adapted from Spears and Singh (2004) and Singh and Banerjee (2018) who conducted related study.

2.32 Brand Attitude and Purchase Intention

When individuals gain experience, they do not immediately translate that experience into an intention to adopt or reject a particular innovation. Instead, the formation of positive or negative attitudes occurs after careful consideration of these experiences (Li et al., 2017). If individuals develop positive attitudes, then the likelihood of purchasing electric automobiles is high. On the contrary, negative attitudes will negatively impact on the adoption of electric vehicles. Attitudes are consistently recognised as pivotal psychological factors influencing adoption intentions (Li et al., 2017).

Miniard et al. (1983) asserted that, the willingness to buy serves as an intermediary between attitude and purchases. Miniard et al. (1983) conclusion was based on a sample of women drawn from churches and hospital organisations in which their intentions to purchase soft drinks were monitored to ascertain their actual purchase in the United States. Other scholars have also identified that, brand attitude is a determinant of consumer purchase intention. Teng et al. (2007) conducted a study about advertisements in North America and the results indicated that, attitude exhibited towards brands impacted consumers likelihood to purchase those brands. Wu and Lo (2009) studied Taiwan customers behavioural patterns towards Microsoft personal computers and found that, their attitude towards the brand affected their willingness to buy. Another research was conducted by Wang et al. (2019) within social media in the South Korea. The study

sampled Facebook fan users and concluded that, the usage of advertising served as a source of improving brand attitude which tend to impact their willingness to buy. Jung and Seock (2016) study in the textiles industry in the United States proved that, consumers' brand attitude and purchase intention minimised after receiving negative information regarding the reputation of the company, America Apparel, a firm that previously enjoyed immense reputation due to their corporate social responsibility but subsequently experienced limited reputation when consumers realised that their products were sourced from third party contrary to information that the brands were produced in Los Angeles. Tang et al. (2011) study of Chinese customers revealed that, the attitude demonstrated towards a brand affect intention to purchase of customised desktop computers. Research by Nuzula and Wahyudi (2022) in Indonesia found that, social media users' attitude towards luxury brands had an impact on their intention to buy those brands. Another research was conducted by Pradhan et al. (2016) in India among student consumers of sports branded footwear. The results revealed that, consumers attitude developed towards footwear brands had a partial effect on their intention to purchase. Chuenban et al. (2021) also conducted a study among buyers in some retail supermarket in Thailand. The research concluded that, consumers in Thailand's attitude towards canned tuna brands played an influential role in developing the willingness to purchase those brands.

Plötz et al. (2014) conducted an analysis of attitude encompassing various aspects such as technology affinity, environmental concerns. The other aspects were comfort, and image. The findings also revealed that, attitude demonstrated by consumers towards electric automobiles were the strongest influences of consumers' willingness to buy. Beck et al. (2017) introduced a novel approach called best-worst scaling to examine relevant attributes. In this method, respondents in Australia were required to select attitudes based on statements. The study revealed that, accurate evaluation and prediction of consumer intentions will be challenging if attitudes are not properly considered. Moons and De Pelsmacker (2012) and Afroz et al. (2015) both conducted analyses of the impact of attitudes within the framework of the Theory of Planned Behaviour (TPB) in Belgium and Malaysia respectively. In the former study, attitudes toward battery electric vehicles were quantified as the sum of positive choices among dichotomous items like good/bad, like/dislike, clever/stupid, nice/not nice, useful/useless, suitable/unsuitable. In the latter study, attitude dimensions included consumers' beliefs about battery electric vehicles' fuel efficiency and their perceptions of battery electric vehicles as contributors to reducing oil consumption and greenhouse gas emissions. Both studies concluded that the intention to adopt battery electric vehicles' can be effectively explained by the Theory of Planned Behaviour (TPB) with attitudes having the most substantial direct impact among all the variables. Pop et al. (2023) also conducted a study among Millennials and Generation Z consumers who utilised mobile applications. The finding showed that, attitude towards brands played an influential role in the purchase intention of mobile application users in Romania. Kudeshia and Kumar (2017) also studied Facebook users in India. The research concluded that, consumers attitude towards desktop smartphone brands influenced their intention to buy. Abzari et al (2014) also researched social media and traditional media advertising users in Iran. The finding indicated that, attitude towards brands impacted customers who used both social media and traditional media advertising. Another research was conducted by Lee et al. (2017) in South Korea. The finding showed that brand attitude impacted the purchase intention of university students who watched smartphone advertising.

However, despite these other studies have established contrary results. Karamchandani et al.

(2021) who conducted research in India found that, brand attitude had no impact on the willingness of consumers to purchase hygienic products during the Covid-19 pandemic. Another research by Mazodier and Merunka (2014) into secondary brands which were a luxury brand and an event found that attitude towards the brands did not influence consumers intention to purchase.

The diagram below presented the relationship between brand attitude and purchase intention that the study developed.

Figure 2. 2: Brand Attitude and Purchase Intention

Despite the existence of these studies, there was a lacuna in relation to studies that evaluated brand attitude and purchase intention by comparing locally and imported vehicle brands. As part of novelty contribution, this study hypothesised that:

H1: Brand Attitude has a positive relationship with purchase intention with locally assembled vehicles compared to imported vehicles.

2.33 Brand Attitude and Perceived Value

Previous research works have demonstrated that attitudes towards brands had positive impact on perception of value (Riley et al., 2015). Hutchinson and Bennett (2012) studied attitudes and perceptions towards the athletic department in a university in the United States. The research adopted sample from both internal and external stakeholders. The internal stakeholders comprised of current students, members of staff, workers in the department in charge of athletics and boosters of the athletic department. The external stakeholders were the university's alumni. The investigation indicated that, intercollegiate athletics contributed to the formation of attitude that affected the perceived value of the university. Thus, the study of consumer behaviour will be enhanced if perceived value is prioritised (Ko et al., 2011). Lee and Hwang (2011) maintained

that consumers attitude and perception of value were instrumental in the realisation of profit and successes of organisations. Thus, positive attitude towards a brand significantly affects the perception of value attached to firms. Despite the existence of studies, there was a lacuna in literature of studies that tested the effect of brand attitude, perceived value and purchase intention in relation to locally assembled and imported vehicle brands. This study made novel contribution in bridging the gap.

Below was the diagrammatic presentation of the relationship.

Figure 2. 3: Brand Attitude and Perceived Value Constructs

Discussions on brand attitude and the perceived value constructs (quality, price, and social value) adopted for the study were highlighted below.

2.33.1 Brand Attitude and Perceived Quality

Scholars have asserted that that the attitude exhibited towards brands had an impact on the perception of quality. Research by José Sanzo (2003) in Spain for instance revealed that consumers attitude towards traditional product, honey specifically influenced their perception of quality that was attached to branded honey. Thus, consumers that had favourable predisposition towards generic honey tend to have high quality perceptions. The quality perception develops into positive, affective and pleasant feelings towards specific honey brands (José Sanzo, 2003). Homer (2008) used students as sample to undertake research in nine automobile firms in the United States of America. The research revealed that, perception of low quality inherent in a brand caused damages to the attitude that consumers demonstrated. Nuzula and Wahyudi (2022) identified that brand attitude had influence on perception of value of consumers who utilised social media platforms in Indonesia among luxury products. It is observable that Wang (2013) provided contributions to the array of research on brand attitude. In the conclusion of Wang

(2013), it was established that, attitude exhibited had an influential effect on perceived quality attached to food products among Taiwanese consumers. The attitude towards the brands were based on the product packaging features such as colour, logo, graphics, and typeface which consumers found attractive and as a result made them to perceive that, the food possessed quality. Esmailpour (2015) studied luxury fashion brands among Generation Y consumers in Iran. The research identified perceived quality as a better predictor of attitude towards brands. In addition, Dall'Olmo Riley et al. (2015) studied attitude towards premium brands which included cars and fashion brands of shoes among consumers in shops in the United Kingdom. The research found that, the brands adopted for the study influenced the perceived quality that consumers held. However, another study produced contrary result. by Huang et al. (2004) research into the Taiwanese gray market failed to establish a positive relationship between brand attitude and perceived quality.

The study therefore hypothesised that:

H2a: There is a positive relationship between brand attitude and perceived quality in the automobile industry.

2.33.2 Brand Attitude and Perceived Price

Pricing is noted to be a key component in the marketing activities of firms (Diallo, 2012). One of the most difficult and complicated tasks that businesses are confronted with is how to establish appropriate prices for products (Zielke, 2010). Some studies such as Baltas and Papastathopoulou (2003) and Desmet and Nagard (2005) have revealed that, a low-pricing strategy is effective in persuading and attracting customers to a business entity and its offerings. Hassan et al. (2010) advocated for the setting of pricing that are reasonable for customers.

A study by Salehzadeh and Pool (2017) in shopping malls in Iran revealed that, brand attitude tends to affect the perception that customers of luxury brands held. Research by Hwai Lee and Yuen Han (2002) employed experimental research using advertising in Singapore among brands from two product categories which were computer and stereo hi-fi. The research used students as respondents to compare their attitudes towards the perception of partitioned pricing which involved the treating of pricing as separate entities for good or service and an inclusive pricing. The finding showed that, consumers developed more favourable attitude towards an all-inclusive pricing than partitioned pricing. These results were contrary to the finding of Huang et al. (2004) whose research failed to identify a positive effect of attitude exhibited towards brands and the perception of price among customers in the Taiwanese gray market.

The research hypothesised that:

H2b: There is a positive relationship between brand attitude and perceived price in the automobile industry.

2.33.3 Brand Attitude and Social Value

Social value highlights the extent to which others should patronise and use a particular technology (Venkatesh et al., 2003). Social value therefore recognises that, social circles such as peers and families play a significant role in decision-making generally or specifically towards the adoption of technology (Hoang et al., 2022). Studies such as Sheth (1991) and Sweeny and Soutar (2001) revealed that, the presence of social value influenced buying decisions of customers. Customers decisions to buy gift items or products that can easily be identified such as clothes or jewelries are influenced by social value (Sheth, 1991). Sheth (1991) further asserted that, customers may Favor an automobile based on the social image that it will create than the functionality of it. Salehzadeh and Pool (2017) conducted research in Iran on customers of luxury brands in malls. The finding showed that, the attitude developed from various sources towards brands influenced their acceptability within the society. Another research by Ajitha and Sivakumar (2017) in India among luxury customers also proved that there was a positive relationship between brand attitude and social value in the cosmetics market.

The study, therefore, hypothesised that:

H2c: Positive relationship exists between brand attitude and social value in the automobile industry.

2.34 Perceived Value and Purchase Intention

Many research works have been done to investigate different variables that influence purchasing intentions of customers. The marketing literature has devoted substantial publications to the concept of perceived value. Customers will perceive that products have value when they meet their expectations (Bao et al., 2011; Jamal and Sharifuddin, 2015). Perceived value is based on the perspective of customers (Yoo and Park, 2016). Customers are likely to make the decision to buy products because they expect to obtain value from those purchases (Aghazadeh et al., 2014). Perceived value therefore correlated with purchase intention (Ponte et al., 2015). It has been reported by the findings of these studies that higher perceived value leads to positive consumer purchase behaviour regarding intentions and actual purchases. This implies that whenever there is a higher perceived benefit for a product, by the consumers of the product, the perceived value that the consumers attribute to the product also increases. This positively affects the purchase intention for the product, as the consumers' purchase intention is also raised accordingly (Zeithaml, 1988). Eggert and Ulaga (2013) and Yuan et al. (2020) contended that the likelihood of consumer perceived value triggering purchase intention is higher than that of consumer satisfaction. Evidence has been provided in the literature to the effect that perceived value played an influential role in affecting willingness to purchase in different contexts. For instance, in the study of Petrick (2004) sampled cruise passengers in the Caribbean voyages. The results revealed that consumer perceived value has a predictive power in cruise line industry. In another study, McDougall and Levesque (2000) established that perceived value had the potential of predicting consumer purchase intention in various primary service settings which were dentary, haircut, restaurant and auto service among members of a church in Canada. The research further recommended the incorporation of perceived value constructs to improve future purchase intentions due to its relevant in all the four services in the study. Durvasula et al. (2004) conducted research in Singapore and reported that, customers influenced by perceived value affected purchasing intention.

The literature showed that studies have been undertaken in relation to brand attitude and perceived value. Despite this, it was observable that only few research works applied various dimensions measuring perceived value. Based on this, this research examined perceived value by employing multi-dimensional constructs (quality, price and social) to ascertain its effect on purchase intention. The diagram below demonstrated the relationships between perceived value and purchase intention.

Figure 2. 4: Perceived Value Constructs and Purchase Intention

2.34.1 The Relationship between Perceived Quality and Purchase Intention

Eunju et al. (2008) also conducted research among students in two countries, South Korea and China. The results revealed that, the perception of quality held among consumers within these two countries played an influential role in their intention to buy sports footwear. Calvo-Porrall and Lévy-Mangin (2017) researched about store brands. The study sought to ascertain the relevance of perceived quality which were categorised into low and high product quality on the willingness of consumers in Spain to purchase. The results concluded that both high and low product quality influenced the intention to purchase store brands. Tsotsou (2005) also conducted a study in Greece among students to ascertain the impact of perception of quality on willingness to buy. The research identified that the perception held by the students influenced their decisions to purchase sports shoes. Das (2014) also researched perceived quality and purchase intention in India. The study which drew sample from retail consumers focused on the non-food category. The result indicated perceived quality among non-food retail shoppers had an impact on their willingness to buy. Wang et al. (2020) studied the Chinese meat market and identified that the perception among consumers played a significant influence in developing their purchase decision. Shukla and Purani (2012) research in four countries included two developed economies (United States of America and the United Kingdom) and two developing economies (India and Malaysia) concluded that, the perception of quality had an influential effect on consumers' intention to purchase. Another study by Chattalas and Shukla (2015) in two advanced countries,

United States of America and the United Kingdom also revealed that, the perception that consumers hold about the quality of an offering had an impact on intention to purchase. Similarly, Celik and Erciş (2018) research in Turkey confirmed the impact of quality as a value perception construct on consumers' willingness to buy. Another research which was conducted in a developing country, South Africa by Makhitha (2021) also postulated that, a key determinant of consumer purchase intention is the perception held about the quality of products. Despite the existence of these studies, others have also revealed contrary findings. Richardson et al (1994) investigated six products among shoppers in the United States. The research tested the effect of perceived quality and perceived price of national brands on purchase intention. The results revealed that, shoppers were more interested in their perceptions of price than perceptions of quality in determining their willingness to purchase. Reyes-Menendez et al. (2022) study in an advanced country, Spain did not find a positive relationship between perceived quality and consumers' willingness to buy. Another research conducted in an emerging economy, specifically, Angola also concluded that, perception of quality was not a key construct in determining the intention to buy luxury brands (Canguende-Valentim and Vale, 2022). A study by Wang (2010) in the food industry specifically snacks in Taiwan also found that perception of quality did not influence consumers intention to purchase.

The study therefore hypothesised that:

H3a: A positive relationship exists between perceived quality and purchase intention in the automobile industry.

2.34.2 The Relationship between Perceived Price and Purchase Intention

It worth mentioning that consumers hold different perceptions regarding price of products and services. What may be considered expensive for one consumer may not considered expensive by another consumer. Regarding this, it has been pointed out by Shirai (2017) that, in order to influence consumer purchasing behavioural patterns, firms must develop strategies and tactics that will positively affect the way consumers perceive prices of their offerings. Kim and Jang (2013) also argued that to effectively price goods and services, it is imperative for firms to appreciate and understand the perception that consumers attached to their pricing practices. There are a number of studies that related perceived price and purchase intention. A study by Eunju et al. (2008) in the sports footwear market revealed that, perceived price had a positive relationship with purchase intention in the South Korea market but a negative relationship in the China market among consumers. Bolton and Lemon (1999) investigated perceived price, purchase intention relationship among households who subscribed to interactive television entertainment service and cellular communications services in the United States. Bolton and Lemon (1999) explained that customer's evaluation of product price as fair or unfair had a significant influence on their intentions to repeat a purchase. Kim et al. (2012) also conducted an online study in South Korea. The research concluded that both potential customers and existing customers based on their perception of price to develop their willingness to purchase. Kim et al. (2012) research in Korea highlighted the impact of perceived price on consumers' intention to purchase. Ali and Bhasin (2019) conducted a study in India and reported that, the perception of price that consumers have played a crucial role in determining their intention to buy. In a study by Son and Jin (2019) in the United States of America, perceived price was identified as having impacted on the consumers' willingness to purchase. Pan et al. (2022) research in South Korea also reported that the perceived nature of price significantly influenced intention to buy. The

findings discussed were not consistent with a study by Yu et al. (2018) in the United States of America which indicated that, the perception of price did not play a major role in determining the willingness of consumers to buy luxury brands.

The study therefore hypothesised that:

H3b: A positive relationship exists between consumer perceived price and consumer purchase intention in the automobile industry.

2.34.3 The Relationship between Social Value and Purchase Intention

Mort and Drennan (2005) intimated that there was a need to take into consideration social value in research because consumers receive offerings within a social environment, which consisted of members of the social group. Researchers in the area of consumer behaviour have established that social value is an important variable in determining consumers' willingness to buy. Forgas-Coll et al. (2014), drew sample from cruise users in Spain. The research concluded that, the social value attached to the cruise lines affected the decision of customers to patronise their services again. Ha (2021) sampled young consumers in shoe stores and coffee shop in Vietnam to understand consumer behavioural patterns. The research maintained that consumers relied on products to enhance their societal standing, and this tend to influence their buying decisions. Chattalas and Shukla (2015) also researched luxury brands among customers of two developed economies, United States, and the United Kingdom. The study identified that social value had a stronger influence on customers' willingness to buy in the United States than in the United Kingdom. A study by Jain et al. (2021) in India further revealed that the likelihood to purchase battery electric vehicle brand is influenced by the opinions within the customer's social circle. Krishnan and Koshy (2021) also emphasised the role of social status in forming purchase decisions among Indian consumers in electric vehicle adoption. Research by Wu et al (2018) within the Chinese environment for instance revealed that, societal influence aided in forming consumers' intention to buy. Sanyal et al. (2014) study in India also recognised that social value played an important role in triggering purchase intention. Another research conducted in Turkey by Ozen and Engizek (2014) reported the significance of social value on intention to purchase. These findings were not consistent with Narang (2016) which did not establish any relationship between social value and the intention to buy Chinese products. Another research by Wang (2010) in the food industry also revealed that, social value did not have an influential effect on the intention of consumers to purchase. Other studies also provided contrary conclusions. Zhou et al. (2021) research in electric vehicles for instance concluded that social value was not considered in forming intention to buy among Chinese consumers. Thus, research was not conclusive on the role of social value influencing purchase intentions due to inconsistent results.

The study therefore hypothesised that:

H3c: A positive relationship exists between social value and consumers' purchase intentions in the automobile industry.

2.35 Brand Attitude, Perceived Value and Purchase Intention

There are few related studies to brand attitude, perceived value and purchase intention. Charton-Vachet et al. (2020) studied effects of attitude on the purchase intention of consumers towards regional products by considering the mediating influence of perceived value and preference in France. The researchers, in their analysis, considered perceived value as a uni-dimensional variable. In their findings, the researchers reported that, perceived value played a significant role in brand attitude and their intention to buy in hypermarkets. The research treated perceived value as a uni-dimensional variable, was not a comparative study, and employed the quantitative approach only. Salehzadeh and Pool (2017) also researched brand attitude and perceived value and purchase intention in Iran. The results established positive relationships among brand attitude, perceived value and purchase intention among customers who patronised global luxurious brands. The study treated perceived value as a multi-dimensional variable with personal, social and functional values but did not compare local and imported brands. The study also employed the quantitative approach only. A conceptual paper by Naseem et al. (2015) also recommended the empirical testing of variables, which include brand attitude, perceived value, consumer affinity, and purchase intention. The paper approached perceived variable from a uni-dimensional variable perspective. Based on the gaps in extant literature, this research quantitatively compared locally assembled vehicle brands to imported vehicle brands in relation to brand attitude, perceived value and purchase intention from a business perspective. The results obtained was used to conduct a subsequent qualitative study to explain the quantitative results which enhanced the novelty of the research. Diagrammatic relationships of the entire quantitative variables of brand attitude, perceived value and purchase intention were demonstrated below:

Figure 2. 5: The Conceptual Framework of the Research (Brand Attitude, Perceived Value Constructs and Purchase Intention)

This study which employed a mixed methodological approach, hypothesised that:

H4a: Brand attitude has a positive and significant influence on purchase intention with perceived quality as a mediating variable of locally assembled vehicle brands compared to imported brands.

H4b: Brand attitude has a positive and significant influence on purchase intention with perceived price as a mediating variable of locally assembled vehicle brands compared to imported brands.

H4c: Brand attitude has a positive and significant influence on purchase intention with social value as a mediating variable of locally assembled vehicle brands compared to imported brands.

CHAPTER THREE

THEORETICAL BACKGROUND

3.0 Introduction

This research was underpinned by the Nudge Theory which is deeply rooted in behavioural economics and emphasise on behavioural change. The study also had other four theories which are deeply rooted in psychology which stressed on intention and behavioural patterns. These theories were the Theory of Reasoned Action, Theory of Planned Behaviour, the Expectancy Theory and Means-End Theory. These relevant theories have attained high recognition in marketing literature and therefore formed the basis for their choice.

3.1. Nudge Theory

According to Thaler and Sunstein (2008), a nudge is a choice that provides behavioural change in an expectable manner without largely altering incentives that are economic centered. Thaler and Sunstein (2008) further explained that a nudge as an intervention should be inexpensive and less difficult to implement. The conceptualisation of nudge began in cybernetics where it was regarded as a role player in behavioural patterns irrespective of extent or degree (Hausman and McPherson, 2006). Nudge Theory gained popularity when it received prominence in the book publication of Richard Thaler and Cass Sunstein in 2008. Thaler and Sunstein (2008) received inspiration from the work of Daniel Kahneman and Amos Tversky which altered the psychological approach towards thinking.

According to the Nudge Theory, people provide feedback on information received through automatic and reflective processing systems. The automatic system takes into consideration the role of environmental cues while the reflective system is oriented towards intentions and attainment of goals (Thaler and Sunstein, 2008). The automatic system kicks in when people are faced with a highly complicated or challenging decision-making situation which the mental ability cannot contain. The automatic systems present a quick decision-making process characterised by simplistic and efficient regulations. Although the regulations are effective in most situations, they sometimes deviate from logical reasoning or rational options (Thaler and Sunstein, 2008). There is also the need for an intervention from external sources because individuals do not consistently make the right decisions. Inspired by psychological perspectives, Thaler and Sunstein (2008) who were economists argued that individual behavioural patterns can be changed, and this will have an impact on the perception held concerning choices to make. Thaler and Sunstein (2008) further advocated for the use of public policy in ways that enhances the interests of people without compromising their freedom to make choices instead of implementing regulations through force. Thaler and Sunstein (2008) used the term 'choice architecture' to mean developing nudges in a manner that will attract the desired behavioural pattern. Other ways of demonstrating 'choice architecture' is the application of default settings that enrolls individuals who do not activate steps to effect alterations (Brown and Krishna, 2004). Thaler et al. (2010) also highlighted on the use of other choice architecture techniques such as mapping information, error expectations and feedback loops.

Thaler and Sunstein provided instances where the implementation of this theory had chalked success. These included automatically enrolling people into a pension plan rather than providing exit options and the use of image of a fly to minimise the quantum of urine spillage. This was motivated by the notion that people change behaviour to conform to societal practices. Another instance is automatically enrolling people into organ donation schemes until they voluntarily opted out in order to boost the numbers of donors (Thaler and Sunstein, 2008). Nudges are employed to appeal to consumer minds to encourage behavioural change which serves as inputs in achieving outcomes or goals (Weijers et al., 2021). Thus, nudges encourage the adoption of behavioural patterns such as the walking to bin to trash a can which acts as a facilitator in achieving the goal such as a neat environment. The adopted behavioural patterns are often less focused on than the goal that is ultimately attained (Weijers et al., 2021). Due to its importance in contemporary times, various governments are increasingly adopting the nudge theory to influence policy. The government of the United Kingdom in 2010, established the British Behavioural Insights Team which was also referred to as the ‘Nudge Unit’. The theory is also credited with a 5% increase of timely tax payment due to the use of the inscription “9 out of 10 people in Britain pay their tax on time” on tax letters in the United Kingdom (Cabinet Office Behavioural Insights Team, 2012). United States government in 2014 also set up the Social and Behavioural Science Team (SBST) in the White House. All these establishments were to shape policies for the betterment of their economies. Australia is also continuously adopting Nudge Theory to improve legislation frameworks. The government of New South Wales employed Nudge Theory to achieve prompt tax payment through the setting up of Behavioural Insights community of practice in 2012 (Easton, 2014). In order to influence policy, the Behavioural Economics Team of the Australian Government was formed in 2015. The Nudge Theory is also widely gaining acceptance among business leaders. Nudge Theory has been embraced by Google to enhance output and happiness among staff (e.g. Bock, 2015; Ebert and Freibichler, 2017).

The Nudge Theory underpinned this study for some reasons. The theory explained the role of societal influences in making choices. The theory is relevant since the research sought to understand the influence of the choices of businesses in terms of automobile brands. The Nudge Theory explained that the choices that consumers make can be automatic or reflective. Thus, the Nudge Theory upholds that, consumer choice can be based on an individual’s decision or is influenced by environmental cues. The research sought to ascertain whether perceptions formed as a result of environmental cues (quality, price and social) influence the intention to purchase automobile brands by businesses.

In addition, the Nudge Theory also sought to explain the role of policy in changing behaviours. The government of Ghana is aggressively putting in place policies and laws that restrict the importation of old vehicles to encourage new vehicles and the growth of the local assembly of automobile brands. The government in its application of Nudge Theory can develop inexpensive incentives that will encourage behavioural change by highlighting benefits of using new vehicle brands such as long-term savings, cleaner environments and high safety and durability. These interventions can aid change the behaviour of individuals and business consumers as well as encourage more acceptability of new automobile brands.

3.2 The Theory of Reasoned Action

According to Fishbein and Ajzen (1975) and Ajzen and Fishbein (1980) who propounded the theory, it provides an understanding of human behavioural patterns. The theory is premised on assumption that individuals are rational, engage in conscious and step by step approach and utilise information. Thus, individual behavioural patterns do not occur without cognitive considerations and repercussions that are likely to be attained (Brodowsky et al., 2018). This is a popular and well- established theory that has existed over forty years. The theory which emerged from the psychological field has provided in-depth explanations and benefits to the marketing literature more especially in understanding choices (Brodowsky et al., 2018). The theory has provided understanding in consumer purchase decisions in the food industry (Lada et. al., 2009; Muktar and Butt, 2012). Theory of Reasoned Action has been applied in understanding the green behavioural patterns of consumers in recycling (Ha and Janda, 2012; Paul et. al., 2016).

The theory explained that behaviour is the end product after an intent has been developed to act in a particular manner. The theory further highlighted that, intention to engage in behaviour is based on attitude and subjective norms. Attitude is developed based on whether performing a particular act will result in favourable results. Subjective norm on the other hand is an indication of whether the social cycle of an individual such as friends, family members or colleagues at workplaces will endorse or approve a decision to conduct a particular action (Brodowsky et al., 2018). Regardless of this premise, the theory does not automatically draw the conclusion that, attitude and subjective norms will always be in an agreement. The theory also recognises that, the impact of attitude and subjective norms may vary due to differing behavioural patterns (Kan and Fabrigar, 2017).

This theory was ideal for the study because it provided explanations on issues of attitude, perception, and intention, which are consistent with this study. This research was premised on the basis that, attitude towards automobile brands can result in the formation of purchase intentions which can translate into actual behaviour. The study therefore sought to test the effect of attitude on purchase intention. Measuring intention provides an informative stance that can be used to guide the successful implementation of a venture. The theory also considered issues of perceptions and subjective norms which are regarded as social value, an important variable in ascertaining purchase intention.

3.3 Theory of Planned Behaviour (TPB)

According to Ajzen (1991), one of the theories that has received much attention due to its ability to predict behaviour patterns among individuals is the Theory of Planned Behaviour. This theory has received a lot of scholarly attention and this has led to an increase in publications (Ajzen, 2011). The Theory of Planned Behaviour is an improvement of the Theory of Reasoned Action since it provides a more holistic perspective towards behavioural patterns (Ajzen, 1991). The Theory of Planned Behaviour does not address behavioural change but seeks to provide explanations and make forecasts towards intentions and behavioural patterns. Regardless of this, the theory is instrumental providing guidance and directions in developing interventions that will result in behavioural change (Ajzen, 2015). The theory recognises that, intentions are key aspects

of behavioural patterns of individuals at specific moments and locations. The theory recognises that, apart from subjective norms and perceived behavioural control, attitude is a predictor of behavioural intentions which can result in behavioural change (Xu et al., 2017).

The Theory of Planned Behaviour was ideal for the study due to the presence of attitude, subjective norms, and behavioural intentions. Due to its relevance, the theory has been applied in the transport industry which was part of the context on which this study was premised. A study by Abrahamse (2019) for example revealed that, individuals engage in the behaviour of vehicle usage due to the intention to drive. These intentions did not occur in a vacuum but arise because of attitudes such as “I like the idea of driving to work”. Abrahamse (2019) further asserted that the social dimension in the theory which is referred to as subjective norms played an influential role in forming the intention to drive. Approval of work mates was regarded as a subjective norm that played an influential role in purchase intention of consumers. Many researchers have identified the usage of vehicles to connote social status, and this played an influential role in the choice made by consumers (see, e.g., Gatersleben and Uzzell, 2007; Steg, 2003). Abrahamse (2019) highlighted that, attitude that consumers demonstrated impacted the intention to use particular automobiles. In further explaining the role of the Theory of Planned Behaviour from the automotive perspective, Abrahamse (2019), concluded that, drivers that developed a more positive attitude towards the usage of automobiles, had more preference for the continuous usage of automobiles and relied on other means of transport less frequently.

3.4 The Expectancy Theory

The Expectancy Theory stipulates that, attitude is formed based on beliefs and values of an individual. These antecedents are key in the developments of attitude which predict intentions and action (Fishbein and Raven 1962; Ajzen and Fishbein, 2008). According to the Expectancy Theory, the manner in which an individual reacts to information transmission is deeply rooted in beliefs and values (Fishbein and Ajzen, 1975). Fishbein and Ajzen (1975) further argued that the presence of new information is likely to change an existing belief held by an individual. Afterwards, the individual attaches values to the beliefs adopted which ultimately results in creating attitudes (Fishbein and Ajzen 1975).

The Expectancy Theory was developed based on cognitive behavioural patterns of individuals (Vroom, 1964). Individuals have access to various options and make final decisions on outcomes that provide maximum pleasure and minimum pain (Abrate et al., 2021; Zboja et al., 2020). Baumann and Bonner (2017) and Weber et al. (2020) mentioned expectancy, instrumentality and valence as the three main composition of the theory. Expectancy is the belief that the required results will be attained due to the presence of the most desirable choice and corresponding efforts (Baumann and Bonner, 2017; Weber et al., 2020). Instrumentality on the other hand implies that, result is a reflection of performance. The higher the performance, the higher the expected results (Baumann and Bonner, 2017; Vroom, 2005). According to Weber et al. (2020) and Zboja et al. (2020), valence is the affective dimension of the theory. O’Keefe (1990) also added that, the formation of attitude should not be based only on the cognitive component of attitude, but affective or emotional components should also be considered. It refers to the differences identified

between the perceived value of results and the costs of undertaking a particular or set of activities (Weber et al., 2020; Zboja et al., 2020).

The Expectancy Theory has been widely used to study various topics in areas such as performance evaluations (Iqbal et al., 2019), pro-environmental behaviour (Kiatkawsin and Han, 2017) and online social media usage (Behringer and Sassenberg, 2015). Other areas include tourism (Abrate et al., 2021), cognitive understanding (Weber et al., 2020) and consumer boycotts (Barakat and Moussa, 2017). Talwar et al. (2021) advocated for the application of this theory in consumer behaviour due to its ability to appreciate differences in consumers preferences based on assessment of benefits and costs of products. This theory was ideal for this research because, it recognised that attitude, which also has an emotional dimension can affect intention and ultimately action. This was consistent with the study which sought to understand the impact of brand attitude on purchase intention in the automobile industry in Ghana. The theory also identifies perceived value also a key variable in consumer preferences. This was consistent with this research which sought to ascertain whether the perception of value held by consumers differ among locally assembled and imported automobile brands in Ghana.

3.5 Means-End Chain Theory

This theory has gained wide recognition and acceptance among scholars to understand the behavioural patterns of consumers (e.g., Olson and Reynolds, 2001; Wagner, 2007; Walker and Olson, 1991). The theory is based on three components which are attributes, consequences and values. Attributes are the characteristics inherent in a product. Attributes can be abstract or physical. It is derived from the manner in which products are perceived by consumers (Gutman, 1997). Consequences are the benefits or the results that consumers derived from engaging in the purchase behaviour (Gutman, 1982). Values on the other hand are a set of principles that are developed overtime and serve as guidance for behavioural patterns (Parks and Guay, 2009). These three components are referred to as the hierarchical levels that serve as a source of motivation for consumers (Jiang et al., 2015) and have been applied to the study of product adoption (Jiang et al., 2015) and travel preference (Wagner, 2007). The Means-End Theory originated from the studies of Olson and Reynolds (1983) and Gutman (1982). Oliveira, Souki and Vilas Boas (2024) stipulated that, the theory creates chronological levels of logical linkages of features of offerings to the benefits that consumers anticipate. Consumers choose product characteristics that are beneficial and meet their values (Reynolds and Gutman, 1988). Thus, purchasing decisions are based on product attributes, consequences and values (Oliveira, Souki and Vilas Boas, 2024).

According to the Means-End Theory, consumers favour products that provide maximum benefits or avoid offerings that generate unwarranted effects and ultimately meet their values (Oliveira et al., 2021; Barrena et al., 2017; Gutman, 1982). Thus, this theory therefore explains that consumers do not purchase products just because they are good but due to the benefits and the satisfaction of their personal values (Oliveira et al., 2021). The theory further stipulated that, attaining personal values is the ultimate objective of consumers (Oliveira et al., 2021). Consumers form purchase intention in relation to specific offerings before eventually achieving

the goal of personal value satisfaction (Fleşeriu et al., 2020; Ajzen, 1991). Purchase intention although important does not automatically result in actual purchases (Fishbein and Ajzen, 1975). The intention to purchase is influenced by factors such as personal values, past experiences, social influences, belief system, emotions, cognition and situational context (Kamboj and Kishor, 2022; Fleşeriu et al., 2020; Yilmaz and Ilter, 2017; Ajzen, 1991).

In this study, brand attitude which was conceptualised as an emotional construct was employed to ascertain its impact on perceived value and purchase intention of locally assembled automobiles compared to imported automobile brands. This theory underpinned this research because it recognises that consumers develop purchase decisions based on the perception of value that will be derived from the purchases. The theory further explained that factors such as personal values, social influences and emotions which were studied in this research are key in determining the purchasing behaviour of consumers.

CHAPTER FOUR

CONTEXT OF THE STUDY

4.0 Introduction

This chapter highlighted on contextual issues of the study which were linked to the automobile industry and the country where the research was undertaken, Ghana. Topics discussed were the vehicle infrastructure, impact of automobiles on the culture of road usage, evolution of the global automobile industry, the value chain within the automobile industry, the global automobile value provision (the upstream and downstream), productivity analysis of global automobile manufacturers, high capital intensity and large economies of scale, impact of Covid-19 on the automobile industry. Other topics included were internationalisation strategies in the automobile industry, the role of the automobile industry in economic development and the world's major global automobile producers. The context chapter also discussed vehicle policies and standards in Africa, automobile production and importation in Africa, automobile manufacturing challenges in Africa, used and new vehicle adoption in Africa, adoption of electric vehicles in Africa, profile and economy of Ghana and the automobile industry in Ghana.

4.1 The Vehicle Infrastructure

The manufacture of automobiles on a large scale is embraced due to the availability of systems and institutions such as road networks, parking, and road traffic regulations (Paterson, 2006). These components are called the 'car infrastructure'. This infrastructure showcases the public-sector contributions to the automobile industry (Docherty and Shaw, 2011). The establishment of a road network is the highest form of priority for automobiles. In order to achieve optimum value in the usage of automobile, there should be reliable road infrastructure to travel at a quick pace and arrive safely at locations (Mattioli et al., 2020). It is imperative to demarcate space on the roads for vehicles to ply on and expand prevailing ones as well (Mattioli et al., 2020). The history of road usage indicates that, there were variety of transportation means which included walking, horse-drawn vehicles, trams, and bicycles. The rise in road usage led to debates on its congestion nature, safety and modernity (Roberts and Geels, 2018). A key strategy to resolve such disagreements is the implementation of laws and to construct roads in a manner that satisfy various motorists (Mattioli et al., 2020).

The introduction of rules and regulations within the transport sector existed before the inception of automobile development (Docherty and Shaw, 2011). Rules after the advent of automobile were introduced to ensure that customers pay for the ownership of automobiles. These rules also ensure that state institutions develop systems and the infrastructure that will make them beneficial for road uses (Dupuy, 1995). There is an argument within the public domain whether the payment of taxes and fees correspond with the infrastructural development within the transport sector (Delucchi, 2007). Some transport experts are of the view that, the cost inherent in the usage of automobiles are not fully borne within the industry but are shifted to other sectors as well (Shoup, 2021). This leads to low cost of driving and makes it cheaper than other means

of transportation. Other scholars have also argued that there are hidden costs such as parking freely which have been implemented to reduce the cost of vehicle ownership (Shoup, 2021).

4.2 Impact of Automobiles on the Culture of Road Usage

Historical trend revealed that, vehicle usage on road networks was prioritised than other transportation modes irrespective of their level of popularity. The use of trams was very common in most places (Pooley, 2016) but were replaced by buses on the basis that they were partially responsible for crowding on the streets (Mees, 2009). The usage of cycles was also regarded as a dangerous means of transport and was considered as an obstacle to road traffic (Cox, 2012). This perception is currently making many emerging economies not interested in developing human-powered means of transportation such as cycles and carts (Stead and Pojani, 2017; Buliung et al., 2014). Trends in both developing and advanced countries indicated that the usage of vehicles exhibit modernity, forward-looking and is unavoidable. The perception that automobiles are ideal means of transportation is still generally accepted and this has inhibited the usage of other options of transportation (Hansen, 2017).

The culture that forms the basis for depending on automobiles transcends beyond travelling in vehicles but also appreciating travel as a desirable phenomenon. A lot of people did not engage in travelling much before the invention of travel structure such as railways and highways. The invention of railway specifically as a means of travel motivated people to embark on travel for economic reasons. This development resulted in novel tourism activities and motivated people to patronise railway managed resorts (Atkinson, 2012; Divall, 2010). The discovery of vehicles also influenced the tourism sector and led to creation of activities such as bus and car touring (Jeremiah, 2007; Moran, 2010). These occurrences linked with cultural aspects such as travelling domestically, adventure and self-sufficiency were regarded as patriotic activities in a lot of rich economies between in the 1920s and 1930s. Using vehicles as a means of transportation was not the sole objective of ownership but also served as a basis for building road networks and tourist facilities (Mattioli et al., 2020). This led to development centred on vehicles (Mattioli et al., 2020). This trend resulted to a popular practice called “auto camping” in the United States that increased the springing of motels (Belasco, 1973). A study by Torrie (2019) revealed a significant increase in travel patterns in the 1920s and 1930s to an extend never witnessed due to the presence of automobiles. In contemporary times, people sometimes travel by vehicles without necessarily having a location in mind, but it serves as a way of providing variation to their monotonous lifestyle (Garvey, 2020). Automobiles have become an integral part within our society (Sheller, 2018) and has served as a conduit for connecting people (Miller, 2001). Mattioli et al. (2016) and Davies and Weston (2015) also asserted that, vehicles are bought to undertake variety of activities such as conveying of heavy items, travelling for a longer duration, and developing vehicle-based leisure activities. This therefore explains that individual’s ownership of automobiles influences its usage (Schwedes et al., 2013; Van Acker and Witlox, 2010). The purchase of a vehicle makes a consumer hesitant in obtaining another source of transportation due to its influence on travel patterns (Mattioli et al., 2020).

4.3 Evolution of the Global Automobile Industry

Vehicles are not only identified as goods that last for a long period of time but can also undergo repairs works, maintenance and recycled. Automobiles are also regarded as a “metaphor for modernity” (Thomas et al., 1988) and are also recognised to provide temporary phases of modernity. This is because of the differentiation, styles and models that are produced to reflect current trends and consumer preferences (Chalfin, 2008). Virtuoso Leonardo da Vinci (1452–1519) is believed to have started the automobile industry through his invention of a steering driven tricycle in the 15th century (Dowlah and Dowlah, 2018). Although James Watt is accredited for the invention of a powerful steam engine in 1705, there are reports that, the real originator was a priest of the Catholic Church, Ferdinand Verbiest (1623–1688) who was the first to develop an automobile that thrives on steam engine in 1678 for an emperor in China at the time, Chien-lung (Dowlah and Dowlah, 2018). The automotive industry has gone through transformation over the years. Historically, it has been reported that Nicolas Cugnot (1725–1804), a French inventor introduced a steam-powered vehicle in 1796 and has resemblance to automobiles in contemporary times named *fardier à vapeur* which attained popularity and aided in the construction of roads (Dowlah and Dowlah, 2018). This prototype vehicle was huge and consisted of only three wheels. In terms of speed, it was noted that even human beings could move faster than the vehicle (Bharadwaj, 2018). Bharadwaj (2018) further asserted that, the relocation of cannons during times of war was considered the primary purpose of the vehicle.

The market for steam-powered vehicles which experienced an appreciable demand in England were used to convey goods and people from one location to the other (Nyamwange and Nyamwange, 2014). In France and the United States, they began to be used, with demand being motivated in part by developments which predominantly centred around its multi-speed characteristic, the usage of handbrake and the presence of a smoother steering device. Eventually, the usage of steam-powered automobiles on public roads began to receive negative reactions from people (Bharadwaj, 2018). The opposition was also from the producers of horse carriages who complained heavily on the colossal impacts of steam-powered vehicles on the then carts and horses. These people considered the use of steam-powered vehicles as competitors in the transportation industry at the time (Black, 2014). It needs to be mentioned that the promulgation of the Locomotive Act in 1865 was triggered by this agitation among transport operators within the time. Black (2012) explained that the Act stipulated that steam-powered vehicles could only be permitted to move on public roads when they are accompanied by a walking pedestrian who would be waving a red flag and blowing a horn in front of the vehicles. This effectively declined the steam-powered vehicle market in England. Competitive automobile industry began and developed in various parts of the world over the past two hundred years. Although vehicles had existed for many years, the worldwide demand began to grow due to the advent of engines powered by internal combustion (McNally 2017). In 1885, the automobile industry witnessed the development of an internal combustion engine for motorcycle. This innovation was developed by Gottlieb Daimler (1834–1900), a German engineer. The motorcycle also had the ability to travel with a speed of 1000 revolutions in a minute (Dowlah and Dowlah, 2018). The increase in demand was partly due to technological developments as well as advances in efficient manufacturing processes, which led to the availability of reasonably priced automobiles (Bharadwaj, 2018).

The automobile experienced increased growth in the United States despite its European roots. Subsequently, there was a shift to Europe to Japan and then to other parts of the globe (Maxton and Wormald, 2004). Another development within the automobile industry was the creation of the four-stroke internal combustion engine in 1876 by Nicklaus Otto (Hatheway, 2012). German engineer Karl Benz (1844–1929) is credited for the development of a flat engine for vehicular use in 1886. These two German engineers engaged in competition until their two firms merged and became known as Daimler-Benz, which was changed to Mercedes-Benz, a name that exist in modern times (Dowlah and Dowlah, 2018). The vehicle at the time was characterised with offensive odour, noise, excessive vibration emitting from the engines and engineers were able to provide solutions to these problems by the year 1904 (Saxena, 2009). This breakthrough served as huge pedestal that resulted in the growth and popularity of the vehicles which made it the most purchased automobile (Saxena, 2009).

In 1892, Rudolf Diesel, a German engineer and inventor developed the diesel engine which resulted into another major advancement in the automobile industry at the time. It was noted that diesel at the time was safer and cheaper than petrol (Mollenhauer and Schreiner, 2010). This gave huge advantage to the automotive machines developed by diesel over their competitors produced with Otto's engines. The introduction of the diesel engine did not initially have a positive impact on the market until later since the original design was undependable which meant that a petrol engine was the only obvious choice in the first mass-produced vehicle (Bharadwaj, 2018).

In order to avert the costs associated with importing automobiles into the United States, William Steinway (1835–1896) established the first assembling of automobile company, Daimler Motor Company in New York in 1888. The company specialised in assembling German vehicles (Dowlah and Dowlah, 2018). Henry Ford (1863–1947) who is generally recognised as the founder of the automobile industry in the United States established the Ford Motor Company in 1903. In 1903, Ford brought a lot of transformation into the industry through developing an assembling line for conveyor belt (Klier and Rubenstein, 2008). Ford expanded his activities across Europe and developed production infrastructure in England in 1911 and subsequently in Germany and Australia in 1925. Bharadwaj (2018) asserted that, Ford's philosophy was to achieve high sales by producing a high number of vehicles at affordable prices. Ford developed cost-effective and efficient strategies by developing production that centred on line assembly in 1914. The company crafted a system that ensured that assembling of automobiles was done within one and half hours. As a result of these strategies, the cost of Ford vehicles became cheaper and in 1916, the firm was able to sell its Model T in the United States for \$400 which was recognised as the cheapest vehicle brand (Carbaugh 2014).

Originally, Ford had planned to produce many different versions, but because of the popularity of the Model T, he scrapped these plans, concentrating all his energies on it. The Model T had a 60 percent share of the global car market by 1921 (Bharadwaj, 2018). Bharadwaj (2018) further revealed that, the diffusion of this technical marvel for public use in the developing world was made possible by the distribution of thousands of local assembly kits and a vast network of dealerships and agents. Ford discontinued production of the model in 1927 and recorded sale of 15 million vehicles worldwide. Parissien (2013) asserted that, the automotive market was also

patronised by the affluent who were primarily motivated at showcasing their wealth to other individuals within the society. The introduction of the Model T aided in changing the widely accepted perception particularly among markets outside Europe and the United States that vehicles were purchased to exhibit wealth. The Model T became a common brand among the masses (Bharadwaj, 2018).

Another key player in the development of the automobile industry is William Durant (1861–1947) who established General Motors in 1908 (Carbaugh, 2014). The firm subsequently engaged in international acquisition of Vauxhall Motors founded in England in 1925 (Dowlah and Dowlah, 2018). Durant also acquired the German company, Opel in 1929 and Holden, a firm established in Australia in 1931 (Dowlah and Dowlah, 2018). General Motors performed extensive market analysis to obtain a thorough understanding of each market's sales potential. Vehicle registration data was used to track market demand and ensure that vehicles were developed to meet the needs of customers (Bharadwaj, 2018). Bharadwaj (2018) further indicated that, General Motors tried to compete by selling a wide range of different vehicles and kept abreast of the latest tastes and developments of customers, while Ford implemented the low-cost strategy with just a single model. Because of the need to satisfy consumer needs, General Motors had to adapt its assembly techniques so that they could be changed regularly while allowing the large-scale manufacturing of vehicles (Bharadwaj, 2018). This necessitated the production of more adaptable machines capable of performing a wide range of tasks. Subsequently, competition emanated from Chrysler because of a disagreement between the founder of General Motors, William Durant and Walter Chrysler, a manager at General Motors. In 1920, Chrysler resigned from General Motors and established Chrysler Motor Corporation two years later (Bharadwaj, 2018). The advent of competition from General Motors and Chrysler in the United States of America in the 1920s challenged the global market leadership of the T Model (Carbaugh, 2014).

In terms of customer base, Chrysler competed with General Motors and Ford and distinguished itself by delivering a steady stream of revolutionary new components and accessories (Olson and Mendoza, 2015). The "Big Three" of Ford, General Motors and Chrysler dominated the global market for decades, ensuring that the United States stayed at the forefront of the automobile industry (Lucas and Furdek, 2009). Subsequently, another company which was based in Britain, F. Perkins Ltd., produced the more efficient diesel engine in 1930s. This firm became a competitor to the petrol engines that have been produced earlier (Jones, 2014). Citroen, a French automaker, was the first to use the new, improved diesel engine, introducing it into some of its models including Rosalie in 1934. Mercedes-Benz soon followed suit, launching the 260d the next year with a diesel engine (Bharadwaj, 2018).

Bharadwaj (2018) further asserted that, the use of diesel in naval vessels, planes, and other military equipment during wars was one of the key facilitators for its subsequent rise in popularity. This aided in a wide public acceptance of diesels vehicles, and this translated in its usage on road for transporting goods and for agricultural purposes. In the 1950s, various automobile firms notably Austin, Rover, and Standard who were British business and Fiat, an Italian business produced varied brands of automobiles powered by diesel. Isuzu Bellel, the leading Japanese manufacturer, joined them in the 1960s. Diesel vehicles also gained recognition

and was identified as a better option due to its energy efficiency levels. It was also identified as a less costly option to petrol, which had skyrocketed in price because of conflict in the Middle East (Long, 2013).

The automobile industry in the United States was recognised as the biggest globally in the 1920s and Ford became the market leader, a feat that was previously held by GM. The industry was led by three firms namely GM, Ford, and Chrysler by the end of the 1920s (Klier and Rubenstein, 2008). These three firms were popularly referred to as the 'Big 3' provided for markets across different locations in the world although there was lack of co-operation in various jurisdictions. The production was mostly concentrated in few locations specifically, Europe, North America, and Japan. Other parts of the world recorded 4.1%, 5.4 % and 5.5% in 1970, 1980 and 1990 respectively. Between 1970 and 1990, Japan dominated the automobile market share and recorded a rise of 18% to 30% in production figures while the number reduced from 32.4% to 28.4% for the United States. Europe also experienced a fall from 41.5% to 35.5% (Dowlah and Dowlah, 2018). The production output of Japan accounted for one-third of the global production figures while the automobile industry production figures in the United States were declining (Dowlah and Dowlah, 2018). The automobile producers in the United States started experiencing a fall in their market shares between 1980 and 1990. Ford had a fall from 46% to 35%. GM and Chrysler also recorded a decrease in their share of the markets to one-quarter and one-tenth respectively (O'Brien, 1992). As a result of the intense rivalry from Japanese auto makers in the 1990s, Western European and United States vehicle producers started adopting the Japanese investment strategy (Dowlah and Dowlah, 2018). The firms in line with the strategy began outsourcing components to other jurisdictions that produced at cheaper costs. The automobile industry experienced transformation due to the introduction of trade liberation policies by organisations such as the World Trade Organization (WTO)(Dowlah and Dowlah, 2018). These policies reduced the trade barriers imposed by many regimes and encouraged free trade within the automobile markets. These policies allowed automobile producers to situate in emerging economies which included East Asia, China, East and Central Europe, India, Mercosur area, and Mexico where they enjoyed low manufacturing costs (Lipsey et al., 1999). Another factor that influenced the automobile industry in the 1990s was the establishment of the global value chains (GVCs) which created integrated networks among the players in a fragmented space (Dowlah and Dowlah, 2018).

4.4 The Value Chain within the Automobile Industry

Research has shown that the automotive industry like many other industries in the world, is undergoing tremendous transition (Attias, 2017). The automobile industry experienced a paradigm shift in the mid-1980s from one that was country-focused to a more interrelated with global ties (Lung et al., 2004; Dicken, 2005, 2007). It is considered as one of the major industries and has also churned out a lot of products across the globe (Sturgeon et al., 2008). Despite the strides made in the industry, since the early 1990s, it is observable that certain aspects of the production of automobile products are peculiar to specific geographic regions. It has been reported by Wang et al. (2020) that after the 1990s, developing countries started experiencing rapid expansion of production. It is at this time that most developing countries witnessed automobile companies extending their manufacturing plants to their territories which resulted in the growth of sales. The move made the producers of the vehicles to have manufacturing plants

in developing countries leading to a reduction of the price of vehicles as the production levels increased. It also helped the companies to access ready market for their vehicles (Humphrey and Memedovic, 2003). The German-based auto-manufacturing companies, Volkswagen and Daimler AG are some of the prominent players within the industry. In Japan, auto-manufacturing companies cannot be discussed without mention being made of Honda, Toyota, and Nissan. In China, Shanghai Automotive Industry Corporation (SAIC) and Motor and Dongfeng Motor Corporation are the giant vehicle manufacturers in the country. In the Republic of Korea, Hyundai is a well-recognised automobile company. The rivals of these mentioned companies in the United States of America are Ford and General Motors (GM) (Wang et al., 2020).

The automobile industry is a specialised field that requires managerial expertise in supply chain and physical distribution. Supply chain is a broad process that range from the provision of raw materials to the assembly of complex electronic and computer-based technologies (Tang and Qian, 2008). According to Hugo (2010), the supply chain within automobile establishments consists of key players which are suppliers, Original Equipment Manufacturers (OEMs), distributors, dealers, and buyers. In terms of value creation, Original Equipment Manufacturers (OEMs) accounts for 30-35% and suppliers provide the rest (Dietz et al., 2004). Suppliers generally provide assembling units which comprise of vehicle doors, electronics, and power trains. Due to the demand for sub-assemblies, suppliers are constantly developing infrastructure that will be the backbone and provide the requisite assistance to the design, purchases and logistical framework established by manufacturers (Benko and McFarlan, 2003). To remain relevant, Tang and Qian (2007) advocated that automobile firms need to employ computerised systems that will enhance its operations in areas such as design, planning of processes, manufacturing, managing data and engineering. These systems will enhance innovation, fast-track vehicle production and minimise errors (Tang and Qian, 2008).

Porter (1991) asserted that, value chain comprises of all the practices that a firm engages in starting from the designing, manufacturing, marketing, and distributing to the consumption stage which includes providing services after sales (Porter, 1991). Players within these processes must provide value to a firm which will serve as likely avenue of creating an edge over competing businesses (Gorynia et al., 2019). The practices inherent in value chain were previously conducted by organisations but due to technological developments, the lowering of trade barriers and the reduction in the costs associated with supplies has resulted in the outsourcing of value by various firms in a particular jurisdiction or beyond territorial boundaries (Mudambi and Puck, 2016). The re-defining of value chain in relation to ownership and territorial boundaries (Asmussen et al., 2007) has broaden the concept to include a global perspective (Giroud and Mirza, 2015; Mudambi and Puck, 2016). This has led to the development of the term global value chain. Global value chain is the integration and creation of a network of various organisations both domestic and across the world based on contractual terms (Giroud and Mirza, 2015; Mudambi and Puck, 2016). According to Gereffi and Fernández-Stark (2016), global value chains consist of a series of practices that a firm engages in to develop and design products to its consumption and projected at the global level by at least a firm. Buckley and Ghauri (2004) developed a term global factory to mean a network of firms that are scattered around the world with differing objectives which come together to implement several activities previously done by a firm. The creation of value has shifted from a single firm and is now defined based on relationships established by multiple firms that form an industry with a worldwide outlook

(Buckley, 2009). The value chain within the automobile industry is characterised by firms with huge financial resources and have technological advancements that constantly improves products. This has made the industry have a high barrier of entry (Gorynia et al., 2019).

Another feature of the automobile industry's value chain is dependence on international networks. Most of these industries have huge funds support base from multinational firms assisted with enhanced domestic technology and is appealing to both suppliers in both international and domestic markets. The major stakeholders within the value chain are the producers of automobile and their parts (Gorynia et al., 2019). Specialists who undertake the task of assembling new automobiles are the assemblers also referred to as Original Equipment Manufacturer (OEM). The duties of the assemblers are to develop designs and engines, produce paints and assembly various parts of an automobile (ANFAC, 2017). Automobile producers in contemporary times are more preoccupied with designs and selling their products and as a result, have shifted some of the manufacturing responsibilities to the assemblers (Gorynia et al., 2019). One of the key requirements for an assembler is a firm's ability to enjoy economies of scale to neutralise the expenses occurred in the design and marketing of automobiles (Gorynia et al., 2019). There are nine Original Equipment Manufacturers in Spain for example that have been in business for a long time. These firms are Ford, GM, IVECO, Volkswagen, Nissan, Renault, PSA, Mercedes Benz and Seat. These Original Equipment Manufacturers have seventeen manufacturing facilities and can produce 40 variations of automobiles and 20 are produced specifically for the global market (ANFAC, 2017).

4.5 The Global Automobile Value Provision (The Upstream and Downstream)

The automobile industry has three categories of value creation entities. The first is the group referred to as original equipment manufacturers (OEM) or vehicle assemblers that generate sales from passenger and commercial automobiles. The second is the original equipment supply (OES) which gain sales through selling vehicle parts and components to official leaders of automobile manufacturers or assemblers. The final category is the independent aftermarket that is responsible for selling vehicle components to independent retail and repair outlets (Barnes and Morris, 2008). The automobile industry relies on a vibrant supply chain to create value. Supply chain is defined as upstream and downstream activities that characterise the production of goods and services which is eventually delivered to the end users (Christopher and Lee, 2004). Londe (1989) asserted that, within a supply chain in the automobile industry, there many businesses established to provide goods and services before the end-user. The supply chain involves manufacturers of raw materials and parts, assemblers, wholesalers and retailers and transportation firms. This definition of supply chain includes the end user of the product. The figure below depicted the supply chain of automobile industry.

Figure 4. 1: Supply chain of Automobile Industry

Source: Prakash et al. (2018)

Muhammad et al (2021) categorised the automobile supply chain into upstream and downstream.

4.5.1 Upstream Supply Chain

The upstream supply chain consists of three tiers of suppliers. Tier-3 Supplier's output serves as inputs for Tier-2 Supplier and its products also serves as inputs for Tier-1 Supplier whose outputs are provided to the Original Equipment Manufacturer (OEM) where the vehicle become a finished product and ends the upstream supply chain. The upstream stream supply chain in the automobile industry is long and complex made up of different suppliers found in many parts of the world (Dun and Bradstreet, 2020). Research finding by Dun and Bradstreet (2020) asserted that an estimate of 938 Fortune 1000 companies is at the tier-2 level of the supply chain which serves as inputs for 163 Fortune 1000 companies at the tier-1 level of supply chain in Wuhan. Dun and Bradstreet (2020) further estimated 51,000 firms worldwide that had a direct linkage with suppliers in Wuhan and an estimated figure of 5 million or more firms that have adopted the tier-2 level of supply chain in Wuhan. Dun and Bradstreet (2020) further asserted that, despite the awareness on the part of the suppliers in the tier-2 level, they do not frequently engage with them. There is an estimate of 5 million of other firms that have same experiences around the world. As a result of the complexities that characterise the global automobile industry (Couzin et al., 2001), the upstream supply chain is likely to be severely hit by disruptions such as natural disasters, geopolitical crises and diseases that easily spread like COVID-19 and SARS (Muhammad et al., 2021).

4.5.1.1 Supplier Selection Criteria in the Automobile Industry

The relationship that exists between suppliers and purchasers of their supplies in the automobile industry is recognised as one with futuristic focus and is deeply rooted in the sharing of information and trust. Suppliers account for about 80% of the value that is added in the production of an automobile (Clepa, 2017). Automobile firms are largely concentrating on performing functions that are directly related to their main business. These functions include managing brands, developing automobile style, producing some main parts and assembling (Calabrese, 2002; Calabrese and Erbetta, 2005).

Automobile makers assess suppliers based on two criteria. The first is the closeness of the supplier to the production facility. Scholars such Schmitt and Van Biesebroeck (2013) have concluded that, proximity is a criterion that automobile firms take into consideration when selecting a supplier. Secondly, automobile firms are more interested in obtaining suppliers that have a wide range of parts. Dealing with suppliers with diversified parts aids minimise the number of suppliers and the cost of procuring components (Shin et al., 2000).

There are various quantitative and qualitative criteria that are employed in identifying likely suppliers (Cengiz et al., 2017). Hebisch et al. (2022) study in the automobile industry highlighted that, firms that do not meet the requirements set by organisations are not awarded supply contracts. Research by Ho et al. (2010) revealed that, the most prioritised indicators for selecting suppliers are quality, delivery and cost. The less relevant requirements are production ability, technological status and financial capabilities. Other studies by Chen et al. (2016) and Taherdoost and Brard (2019) were also consistent with the findings of Ho et al (2010) but also highlighted the growing significance of other criteria which include environmental, social, and political. Other research works such as Haeri and Rezaei (2019), Kumar et al. (2014) and Luthra et al. (2017) corroborated the growing relevance of environmental, social, and political consideration in identifying suppliers. Awasthi et al. (2018) study broaden the scope and categorised supplier selection criteria into economic and relationship, environment, social and global risks.

In terms of the number of potential suppliers for selection purposes, a number of studies have made different recommendations. Having fewer suppliers with diversified components facilitates co-ordination and sharing of information (De Treville et al., 2004). Thus, a firm with more diversified components is more likely to be selected for a supply contract (Stern and Henderson, 2004). A study by Vyas and Woodside (1984) in six production firms identified that, there was high preference for the availability of three likely suppliers. Crow et al. (1980) researched into the electrical parts market and concluded that, firms in that sector were interested in having three to four suppliers. Research into service and non- profit businesses revealed the desire to have four to six alternative suppliers. Another study by Kauffman and Popkowski Leszczyc (2005) in the production industry recommended the availability of four to six suppliers. The diagram below illustrated the upstream and downstream of supply chain the automobile industry.

Figure 4. 2: Upstream and Down Stream of Supply Chain in Automobile Industry

Source: Mohammad et al. (2021)

4.5.1.2 Supplier Adaptation to Developments within the Automobile Industry

Long-term success in the automobile industry is heavily reliant on consistent innovation, strong branding, global supply chain efficiency and a skilled workforce (Wellbrock, 2020). The automotive industry is currently undergoing significant changes due to factors such as the quest for developing brands that are self-driven, have connectivity and mobility services and producing brands that also have minimal impact on pollution levels on the environment (Dannenbergh, 2017). Suppliers are also adapting to these trends, particularly in providing mobility that thrive on electricity and those that are self-driven (Wellbrock, 2020). In this context, vehicle interiors are being transformed into appealing living spaces using sustainable materials and innovative designs (Wellbrock, 2020). This transformation aims to enhance the emotional appeal, comfort, safety, functionality, and brand identity of the interior. However, balancing innovation with cost considerations remains a challenge (Dölle, 2013).

4.5.1.3 Additive Manufacturing and its Supply Chain implications

Automobile manufacturing firms that have gained global reputation such as GM, BMW, Ford, Daimler, and Volkswagen have employed additive manufacturing into the production of constituents. The supply chain inherent in automobiles requires many parts from several suppliers to produce a vehicle. There is therefore the need to achieve seamless flow of components globally to attain production. Additive manufacturing is the option that simplifies the complications by synchronising the entire process into a single system (Zijm et al., 2019; Knofius et al., 2021). Additive manufacturing aids minimise the number of parts needed to produce automobile via integration (Ford, 2017). The integration prevents the rusting of assembly points, minimise the weight due to the omission of tighteners such as screws, bolts and nuts and reduce the level of inventory of parts for automobile manufacturing (Zijm et al., 2019).

Addictive Manufacturing has the capacity to simplify the complicated processes inherent in the upstream supply chain sector during pandemic situations (Uffhausen, 2020).

4.5.2 Automobile Marketing Channels (Downstream)

Muhammad et al. (2021) further asserted that, the downstream automobile activities start with distributors who sell to retailers and then finally to the end user. Muhammad et al. (2021) acknowledged that, these steps might be followed rigidly. The figure below demonstrates the upstream and downstream activities as propounded by Mohammad et al. (2021) in the automobile industry. The essence of developing strong ties between producers and marketing channel members have been studied by scholars including Bloom and Perry (2001) and Amato and Amato (2009). Various studies have influenced a shift from the conventional product-centered perspective to a more customer- based perspective (Saccani et al., 2006; Gopalani, 2010). Automobile brands can achieve marketing outcomes if there is a productive and participatory atmosphere, incentives and sufficient empowerment (Chang et al., 2003). Retail outlets play an instrumental role in achieving competitive advantage through meeting customer expectations (Gopalani and Shick, 2011).

4.5.2.1 Criteria for Selecting Marketing Channel Members

Marketing channels which consist of distributors and retailers make up the downstream sector. There are a number of criteria that should meet customer requirements for selecting marketing channels for automobiles (Moyer and Whitmore, 1976). Customers assess marketing channels for vehicles based on choices relating to outlets and products, prices, information available about purchases as well as reliable and adaptable nature of suppliers (Bucklin and Stasch, 1970). In terms of outlet choice, consumers are interested in finding automobile dealers in locations that can easily be reachable. In order to increase accessibility, some automobile dealers have extended their hours of business into the evening and have Sunday business as well (Moyer and Whitmore, 1976). This has increased competition among automobile brands since research indicated that consumers consider several brand choices before finally purchasing an automobile (Time Marketing Research Report, 1971). One of the key considerations is product choice. Producers and distributors provide a wide range of varieties of products to customers (Automotive News, 1972). Purchasers of automobiles are no exception since they are provided with an increased opportunity to select from a broad options of vehicle types and models. In order to identified as the preferred option, automobile distributors and retailers are devising strategies that will augment their businesses by providing full services including spare components, financing schemes, insurance services, maintenance and repair works (Time Marketing Research Report, 1971).

Researchers have also identified lack of information about automobile purchase as a barrier to meeting customer demands (Vanderwicken, 1972). Consumers expect to have adequate information in relation to automobiles. The information should be prior, during and after the purchase of the vehicles. Some key information that consumers require should be related to product performance, price and warranty schemes as well (Moyer and Whitmore, 1976). Consumers are concerned about not only the cost involved in the purchase of vehicles but more

importantly, the cost of spare parts, insurance, replacements and repairs (Moyer and Whitmore, 1976). Consumers are also interested in automobiles that are reliable. The usage of a defective automobile may not only be expensive but can be life-threatening due to their accident-prone nature (Moyer and Whitmore, 1976). Marketing channels are also required to be flexible in order to meet the increasingly changing demands and needs of customers. Due to this, some shopping malls including Sears and K-Mart allowed servicing of automobiles (Moyer and Whitmore, 1976).

Prakash et al. (2018) identified some challenges inherent in the automobile supply chain that possess significant risks to the automobile industry. These were lack of quality materials for manufacturing, unavailability of automobile components, lack of financial resources, poor product design, expensive maintenance of stock, high cost of repairs and weak business relationships with suppliers among others.

4.6 Productivity Analysis of Global Automobile Manufacturers

The automobile industry is one of the world's giants when it comes to job offerings. In this regard, the automobile industry has been recognised by experts as having a multiplier effect on economic growth and development (Saber, 2018). China is the world's leading manufacturer and sales of automobiles since 2009. The country records a 5% increase in its Gross Domestic Product since 2002 (Yu et al., 2022). Yu et al. (2022) further asserted that, in terms of the number of passenger automobiles, the country experienced a growth of 21.69% and recorded 145.98 million in 2014. In the United States, mention can be made of original equipment manufacturers (OEMs), the company that is directly involved in the manufacturing of original vehicle parts employs directly, over 1.7 million people. Companies that serve as suppliers and distributors of the product of original equipment manufacturers (OEMs) are also noted for the creation of about 4.8 million job opportunities (Wang et al., 2020). Within the European Union, the automobile industry is also recognised as a key employment avenue. ACEA (2018) reported that, the industry has absorbed 3.5 million employees directly and 14 million people indirectly which accounted for over 6% of employment within the European Union. In 2015, Volkswagen had the highest number of staff which was more than 570,000. It was followed by 340,000 staff of Toyota and Daimler who had more than 270,000 employees (Wang et al., 2020).

The automobile industry invests heavily in research and development in order to be productive and competitive. In 2013 for instance, Toyota and General Motors invested \$8.1 billion and \$7.2 billion in research and development respectively. The expenditure reflected the importance and influence attached to the automobile industry in economies across the world (Kallstrom, 2015). Firms that engage in activities that sustain production enhance their technological capacities in production, materials and expertise in management (Motey, 2013; Barnes and Morris, 2008).

4.7 High Capital Intensity and Large Economies of Scale

One significant contributor to the structuring of the automobile industry is economies of scale (Orsato and Wells, 2007; Wells, 2010; Nieuwenhuis, 2015). The usage of steel body specifically (Nieuwenhuis, 2015; Nieuwenhuis and Wells, 2007) which started in the 1920s for automobile development overcame many challenges and aided the industry to obtain manufacturing on a large scale. This required automobile firms to invest immensely in the purchase of mass capacity equipment to produce vehicle type(s) (Nieuwenhuis and Wells, 2003). The huge investment required for the establishment of an automobile firms made it possible only for a small number of firms to enter the business. The huge investment also made it difficult for firms to exit the business (Wells, 2010; Nieuwenhuis, 2015). This has resulted in political support for automobile companies. Various governments have provided financial resources to automobile firms to ensure their continuity in business (Mattioli et al., 2020). According to Luger (2005), automobile firms enjoy opportunities in countries that practice capitalism due to their reliance for job opportunities, revenue and economic growth. Luger (2005) further postulated that governments rely on the automobile industry as a catalyst for not only economic progress but stability within the political space as well. Economies for instance generate revenues from Value Added Tax, income and profits from automobile firms. These benefits are largely influencing the development of favourable policies that result in the growth and survival of automobile business even in situations where lobbying does not exist (Mattioli et al., 2020). The financial support provided for automobile companies becomes immense usually during economic turbulent such as during and after the 2008 financial crisis. During difficult periods such economic recession, one of the areas of reduced family expenditure is the purchase of new vehicles. The resultant effect is a decline in automobile sales (Cascajo et al., 2018). In their quest to prevent the automobile industry from collapse, government provides financial incentives such as loan, reduced taxes and sales incentives during economic challenging times (Kumar, 2015; Stanford, 2010). Due to the job opportunities that the automobile industry creates, these incentives are generally accepted. Automobile firms can threaten to relocate manufacturing in other jurisdictions or have their investments in order countries to attract government assistance (Orsato and Wells, 2007).

Automobile manufacturing involves the usage of a small number of huge equipment and with a regional specialised manufacturing base system (Walks, 2015; Späth et al., 2016). This therefore implies that, the relocation of an automobile plant has a negative impact on availability of jobs compared to firms whose operations are scattered in various jurisdictions (Mattioli et al., 2020). This increases the bargaining power of individuals who favour the citing of automobile plants within their locations. Due to this, workers unions are likely to support automobile firms in attracting government incentives in situations where conflicts arise (Wells, 2010).

4.8 Impact of Covid-19 on the Automobile Industry

The COVID-19 pandemic has had a significant impact on the global automobile industry. These effects have been observed across various aspects of the industry, from manufacturing and supply chain disruptions to changes in consumer behaviour and the adoption of electric vehicles. Major automotive companies have faced significant challenges due to declining sales resulting from the pandemic (Belhadi et al., 2021). Several companies, such as Aston Martin Lagonda Global Holdings Plc, have announced workforce reductions in response to the pandemic's effects

(Philip, 2020). Government-imposed lockdowns forced factory and showroom closures across the European Union and other parts of the world leading to a substantial drop in sales (Philip, 2020). These challenges have also disrupted major projects, including the \$1.6 billion Mazda-Toyota joint venture and various construction projects by Fiat Chrysler Automobiles and Ford Motor Co. (Belhadi et al., 2021). Manufacturing plants, including those of General Motors were affected by safety and lock down protocols, resulting in slower production (Automotive News, 2020).

4.9 Internationalisation Strategies in the Automobile Industry

One of the developing trends of the automobile market is developing manufacturing and assembling plants in overseas markets. This trend was to increase financial growth after the world financial crises between 2008-2009 (Bharadwaj, 2015). The financial crises that occurred globally negatively affected the automobile industry. Sales figures were sharply declining, there was also difficult access to loan facilities and the cost of operations was also high (European Automobile Manufacturers Association, 2013). These trends also persisted after the crises. The demand for new automobile in 2012 witnessed an unprecedented fall since 1990 (European Automobile Manufacturers Association, 2013). Most European markets such as Spain, France and Italy recorded growth excluding the United Kingdom (European Automobile Manufacturers Association, 2013).

Developing economies such as China, India and Brazil are continuously regarded as attractive destinations (Bharadwaj, 2015). Managers from other jurisdictions who go into host countries must appreciate the laws, culture and values of the home countries in order not to jeopardise the operations of the firms that they represent (Ghillyer, 2012). Ferrell and Ferrell (2009) asserted that, it is the responsibility of an effective leader to create the necessary climate to be ethical based on the common belief systems and behavioural patterns. However, various host countries have different cultural and ethical trends, and this is making global managers consistently resolve ethical issues (Rodrigues, 2009). In order to obtain optimum performance among teams with various cultural backgrounds, McFarlin and Sweeney (2014) and Moussa and Somjai (2015) recommended that, global managers must blend many characteristics in identifying duties to be performed, consciously note the diversity inherent in various team players, develop an ambiguous mission statement and demonstrate equality and encourage frequent responses. Nelson and Quick (2006) also highlighted the need for managers to demonstrate integrity, be of good character and engage in ethical practices as requirements for managing diversity at the workplace. The main challenges in communications occur in global markets with languages and cultures because interactions vary from country to country (Rodrigues, 2009).

Due to the huge investment and the desire to achieve large economies of scale, automobile firms must generate huge volumes of manufacturing to compensate for costs with break-even points “at about 85 percent capacity utilisation” of equipment (Wells, 2010). The technological advancement utilised in automobile manufacturing is not only restricted to attainment of huge economies of scale but also large output which is commensurate to sales. It is imperative to also

note that, the size and cost components inherent in the purchase of advanced equipment makes it challenging to conform exactly to demand (Wells and Orsato, 2005). This situation results in producing vehicles that exceed demand which leads to reduction in prices of automobiles (Schäfer et al., 2009; Wells, 2013). Production beyond market demand has negatively affected the profitability of automobile firms (Wells, 2010). This business model existed at the early developmental stage of the automobile industry (Wells and Nieuwenhuis, 2012). At that stage, customers adopted automobiles that were low priced and regarded as standard (Wells, 2013). Subsequently, the automobile market became saturated and witnessed intense competition through product differentiation. This led to the development of new models, styles and unique features (Wells, 2010; Wells, 2015) which served the basis of categorising social class and consumer differences among various cultures (Mattioli et al., 2020). The revolution within the industry was quite expensive and it led to re-building of manufacturing plants and equipment, re-orienting staff relationships and re-strategies in a manner that provided more to engage in designing and marketing activities instead of production activities (Gartman, 2004). This also negatively affected profitability and break-even due to producing lower output of various models (Nieuwenhuis and Wells, 2003). Figures show a decline in profit margins overtime. An average profit margin in the 1920's was 20-30% which declined to 10% in the 1960s and experienced a further reduction to 5% in the 2000s (Nieuwenhuis and Wells, 2003; Wells, 2010). In order to reduce the challenges inherent in generating profits, Orsato and Wells (2007) asserted that, automobile producers focused on “general-purpose designs that approximate to several user needs”. This was a risk-mitigation strategy employed to ensure that automobile specifications and requirements attracted many customers (Mattioli et al., 2020). Automobile firms largely concentrate on producing five-seater passenger vehicles with speed limit of more than 160 km/h and an average range of fuel for 400 km (Orsato and Wells, 2007; Wells, 2013). The differentiated aspects in automobile markets are usually linked to minimal variations and choices (Orsato and Wells, 2007; Wells, 2010). Thus, the automobile industry has successfully blended the attainment of economies of scale, development of differentiation in brands and models and adhered to fundamental multi-purpose pattern such as five-seater vehicles (Mattioli et al., 2020). The main obstacle was designing a system that will embrace the changes required (Mattioli et al., 2020).

Market entry into emerging economies was also another strategy employed by automobile firms in their quest to maintain profit margins. The increased expansion into new territories was responsible for more of the automobile profits in contemporary times (Wells, 2015). The rippling effect of over-production of vehicles was an increased depreciation in value of both new and used automobiles and as a result, owners did not intent to put them on sale even in situations where their services were not required. This provided an explanation to the ‘hysteresis effect’ in vehicle ownership which indicated that, individuals have a higher intention to purchase a vehicle when there was a change in their circumstances than to get rid of it when there was no change in their circumstances (Bjørner and Leth-Petersen, 2004). In addition to this, the variety of automobile usage and the over-production of vehicles provided an explanation into their continuous usage as the major mode of travel once they were purchased (Mattioli et al., 2020).

4.10 The Role of the Automobile Industry in Economic Development

Vehicular transportation is one of the widely accepted and patronised means of transportation across the world (Zhang and Dong, 2023). Research has demonstrated that the automobile industry has been pivotal to economic growth among many countries (KPMG, 2023). Many economies have witnessed indigenous companies expand to access international markets, and this has been noted about the automobile industry. Rather than producing and selling automobile goods on international markets, automobile establishments started manufacturing diverse value activities outside their countries of establishment (Humphrey and Memedovic, 2003). Humphrey and Memedovic (2003) further observed that these automobile companies have identified and located their production activities strategically at locations that they consider high prospect markets.

The automobile industry experienced an incremental growth in its sales figures annually for the past decade except during the COVID-19 pandemic. The industry achieved sales of 82.1 million which was lower than 89.6 million before the COVID-19 pandemic. Although the figure declined, the amount involved was still high (Zhang and Dong, 2023). The contribution of the automobile industry to a nation's economy is dependent on the infrastructural development in a country. Globally, the significant contributions of the automobile industry cannot be underestimated (Saber, 2018). International Organisation of Vehicle Manufacturers (2023) reported that, a total of 85,016,728 vehicles were produced in 2022. The figure further revealed that, 61,598,650 were cars and 23,418,078 were commercial vehicles. Europe accounted for 21,531,339 of the global production output. America produced 2,016,401 and Asia-Ocean recorded 49,333,841 of automobile global production output. The African continent accounted for 1,095,151 of automobiles produced in 2022. The automobile industry records more than 2.7 trillion Euros as an average yearly sales (Aleksandrov, 2013) accounting for 3.65% of Gross Domestic Product (Saber, 2018). The industry is noted for generating innovation and injecting huge amount of money into the global economy. It accounts for the creation of a lot of employment and many individuals depend on it for their source of income. The industry employed almost 14 million people worldwide as at 2017 (International Labour Organisation, 2021).

Statistics also indicated an increase in the figures of worldwide automobile usage from 20 vehicles to 1000 dwellers as of 1950 to an average of 143 dwellers as at 2015 (Mattioli et al., 2020). The industry witnessed a surge since the end of the 19th century to become one of the leading industrial players in the world's economy (Mattioli et al., 2020). In 2005, the automobile industry achieved a turnover of €1.9 trillion worldwide which was more than the Gross Domestic Product obtained by a lot of economies. The industry also accounted for 5% of job creation in the manufacturing sector (des Constructeurs d'Automobiles, 2006). The automotive industry is connected to other sectors via both upstream and downstream. This connectivity is a further demonstration of the economic impact of the automobile industry (Sperling and Gordon, 2009; Paterson, 2006; Stanford, 2010). Key among the upstream players are the steel, rubber, and glass and the downstream impacted especially in the oil sector (Mattioli et al., 2020). The automobile industry is dominated by a few global giants due to the economies of scale advantages. In 2017, the industry was characterised by 10 leading producers that were responsible for 67% of global output (Mattioli et al., 2020). The automobile industry is also recognised as historically shaping

other sectors in their introductory stages by providing technological advancements and improving labour unions (Paterson, 2006). Countries that are developing such as Vietnam and India (Mattioli et al., 2020) recognised the automobile industry as an important avenue towards enhancing industrialisation drive due to its immense job creation potentials and other economic benefits (Hansen and Nielsen, 2016; Pojani and Stead, 2017). Governments in emerging economies are devising policies and programmes that encourage the development of industries (Organisation Internationale des Constructeurs d'Automobiles, 2014). This is part of a holistic approach that developing countries have adopted to champion their industrialisation drive and have chalked successes (Nieuwenhuis, 2015).

4.11 The World's Major Global Automobile Producers

The China is the leading automobile producer in the world (Trivedi, 2018). The country manufactures 30% of global automobiles which was more than the production of United States of America, European Union and Japan together (Statista Automotive Industry in China, 2019). The United States of America is also another powerhouse in the automobile industry. The country has generated over \$692 billion in exporting automobiles and components over the last five years. The industry contributes 3% of America's Gross Domestic Product and is the greatest job creation avenue in the economy (AAPC, 2018). Within the European Union, the industry provides 13.3 million jobs which accounted for 6.1% of jobs created (European Automobile Manufacturers' Association, 2018). The European Union also generated a surplus of €90.3 billion in trade (Dimsdale, 2019) and generated tax revenue of €413 billion on a yearly basis. Germany achieved revenue of €400bn in auto sales domestically (Statista, 2019). Two popular automobile brands, Hyundai and Kia originated from South Korea (Dimsdale, 2019) and the industry had a workforce of about 235,000 which represented 7% of the production sector and 7% of the Gross Domestic Product (Song Jung-a and Edward White, 2018).

4.12 Vehicle Policies and Standards in Africa

Vehicle producing firms are developing strategies for attracting new markets for automobiles (Klebaner and Ramírez Pérez, 2019). These firms are advocating for the payment of low taxes on new automobiles and improved laws that will make importation of old vehicles unattractive and the total prohibition of importation of vehicles and components that are more than ten years of age. There are instances of successful implementation of automotive policies across the world. Lechowski et al. (2023) study in the automobile industry in France and Germany revealed that, their governments designed policies geared towards reviving the automobile industry. These policies provided stimulus packages to cushion automobile firms during the COVID-19 pandemic. India for example adopted the phases of developing the automobile industry from some emerging economies such as Brazil, Mexico, and Thailand. The transformation of the industry was from the assembling of vehicle, then to huge production and then moved to selling automobiles abroad (Kale, 2012). The growth of the industry was initially slow after the country gained independence, but it increased in the 1970s when the country introduced restrictive policies on importation vehicles. In 1991, the industry introduced the liberalisation, privatisation and globalisation policy which attracted many global investors which resulted in joint ventures and large-scale export (Tyagi and Mahajan, 2022).

Automobile manufacturers emphasised that, the establishment of production facilities will improve a country's industrialisation drive and contribute towards the African developmental agenda. South Africa and Egypt are case studies that vehicle producers cite as African economies that implemented a ban on second-hand vehicles and have developed their local manufacturing base (Berthelot et al., 2020). One noted organisation that has contributed immensely to success stories of local automobile production on the continent is the African Association of Automotive Manufacturers (AAAM) which was founded in 2015. The association has been able to develop relationships among key stakeholders and liaised with Deloitte's automotive team for instance in organising programmes that have influenced automobile policies in countries in the African and European continents (Berthelot et al., 2020). Its aim is to aid vehicle manufacturers capitalise on opportunities in order to "jump-start the industry" because the continent possess the capabilities to be become next powerhouse in the automobile space (African Association of Automotive Manufacturers, 2020). The association is collaborating with other stakeholders such as the German government and car producers around the world (Venter, 2022) to realise this objective.

The African Association of Automotive Manufacturers together with automobile producers, German GIZ and Deloitte had influenced the crafting of the new automobile policy in Ghana which encourages assembling of automobiles and discourages the importation of used vehicles (Venter, 2020). There are only five countries that have placed a ban on the importation of second-hand vehicles. These countries are Algeria, Morocco, South Africa, Sudan, and Egypt (Baskin, 2018). Although Egypt has made a general ban on second-hand vehicles, it allows the importation of electric second automobiles. Kenya has developed a policy that is progressive in nature in reducing the importation of second-hand vehicles to the country (Ayeter et al., 2020). As of 2019, automobiles of five years of age or more were not allowed into the country. The age of allowed automobile importation was reduced to three years and above in 2021. The country aims to attain a target of zero second vehicle importation by 1st July 2024 (Ayeter et al., 2020). There are also African countries that ban the importation of second-hand automobiles or provide punitive charges for importing overage vehicles. Ghana for instance, initially banned vehicles older than 10 years but replaced it with a percentage charge on Cost Insurance and Freight (CIF) on vehicles in 2003. Vehicles aged between 10 and 11 received a charge of 5%, automobiles aged 12 and 14 years received a 20% charge of Cost Insurance and Freight (CIF) and vehicles that are aged 15 years and above attracted 50% of the charge. There are also countries within the Africa that have no rules regarding the importation of second-hand vehicles. These are Mali, Niger, Somalia, Togo, Zambia, Mali and others (Ayeter et al., 2020). The two countries are noted for leading the importation drive for second-hand vehicles are Kenya and Nigeria. In terms of percentage terms, West Africa is responsible for importing 49% of all second-hand automobiles found in Africa (Koener, 2018). There is clearly lack of integration and holistic policies within the automobile industry. As a result of that, World Economic Forum (2023) reported that, the African Association of Automotive Manufacturers together with Afreximbank are developing holistic policies that will guide the industry within the continent. Training programmes and financial assistance will be provided across the continent. Afreximbank is also providing financial support of \$1 billion to the industry.

South Africa introduced the Motor Industry Development Programme (MIDP) which provided an avenue for local automobile assemblers and components producers to competitive on the international market through export. The programme provided a tax-free incentive on

importation to automakers (Barnes et al., 2004). The successful implementation of the programme was greatly attributed to the intense competition among three major German automakers which were BMW, VW, and Daimler Chrysler. As part of its expansion, BMW allowed its subsidiary firm in South Africa to manufacture its 3-Series vehicles and this resulted in intense competition from VW and Daimler Chrysler (Barnes et al., 2004). The implementation of the Motor Industry Development Programme (MIDP) also resulted in other automobile big giants such as Ford and Toyota establishing automobile facilities that aided in automobile exportation from South Africa (Barnes et al., 2004). The Ghana has introduced automobile policy which has ten key areas. These include providing incentive and a framework for regulatory purposes, developing markets, and enhancing businesses, protecting the environment and adhering to standards and safety (Embassy of Ghana to Rome, 2023). The other key areas include providing business infrastructure, developing vehicular skills and enhancing technology, developing supply chain within the domestic market, enhancing industrial relations and productivity and enhancing legal regime. The policy also focused on encouraging automobile programme inclusion and enhancing institutional and state structures (Embassy of Ghana to Rome, 2023).

4.13 Importation of Vehicle in Africa

Different studies, including Pelletiere and Reinert (2002) have reported that the implementation of the Structural Adjustment Programmes in the sub-Saharan African countries in the 1980s led to the ineffectiveness of the policy that sought to protect infant automobile companies in most of the countries. In their findings, Beuving (2006) reported that the Structural Adjustment Programme contributed to the flooding of second-hand vehicles from developed countries into most African countries. It has been noted that, policies that discourage the use of old cars exist in some economies, which led to African countries becoming dumping site for used cars (Black and McLennan, 2016). Clerides (2008) explained that the Japanese 'shaken' is one such policies. With this policy, the law in Japan made it very costly for an old car to be thoroughly examined and certified as road worthy for its use on roads. In their study, Black and McLennan (2016) argued that policies of this nature and the lack of interest by nationals in purchasing cheap older model vehicles caused Africa to be at the receiving end as these used and old model vehicles were shipped into African countries. Different researchers, including Golub (2012) and Fadahunsi and Rosa (2002), have argued that Africa should be recognised as a regional market rather than focusing on the continent from a country perspective due to ease at which smuggling is undertaken across the borders of the continent. The research works of Beuving (2004), and Brooks (2012) have reported that many businesses import used vehicles into African countries that have lower cost of shipping and tariffs or countries that has no ban on the importation of over used vehicles.

The research findings Beuving (2006) have indicated that most of the importers of these used vehicles channel their imported vehicles via ports in Nigeria, Benin, and Togo into the West African region of the continent. Regarding Southern Africa, Brooks (2012) and Kaira (2014) have reported that the port of Durban serves as the major source for the importation of used and old-model vehicles into the Southern African region. The research of Kaira (2014) also found that, South Africa as a country has banned used cars from been driven through the country, a situation which has resulted in countries in East Africa becoming supply routes for used

imported vehicles. Brooks (2012) has observed that Japan is regarded as originating country of the importation of used cars into the Southern African region with countries in the Middle East playing subordinate roles. With regards to the importation of used cars into East Africa, Japan and the Middle East serve as the main source. The presence of used vehicles predominantly imported by traders who are supported by their families in their business (Brooks, 2012). It has been noted by Beuving (2006), for example that, used cars imported from Durban and Lebanon are facilitated by African families who live in these countries, by serving as arrangers of logistics for the cars to be shipped to their families in Africa. In other findings, researchers have revealed that some substantial numbers of cars have been imported by traders, including students. This means that the importation of the used cars is not limited to only gurus in the importation industry. Black and McLennan (2016) have also identified United States of America and Japan as two main sources of imported used vehicles.

4.14 Automotive Production in Africa

The demand for automobiles within Africa is increasing due to growth in disposable income, middle class and strong drive towards urbanisation. Averagely, Africa has a year demand for 2.4 million motor cars and 300,000 commercial vehicles which is largely provided through importation from other continents (World Economic Forum, 2023). Automobile manufacturing within the African continent has been growing on average of 7% over a couple of years. This revolution is led by South Africa and Morocco who account for 80% of automobile export in Africa (World Economic Forum, 2023). Black et al. (2017) also agreed that South Africa which is a powerhouse in Africa has made significant strides towards exporting vehicles to other parts of the continent. Apart from the European Union, South Africa regards the African automobile market as the second largest market of importance (Black et al., 2017). The country recorded an increase of automobile export to other African countries from 22.3% in 2010 to 27.3% in 2014 which amounted to \$2.9 billion (Black et al., 2017). The establishment of the African Continental Free Trade Area (AfCFTA) is expected to link markets of more than 1.3 billion and create a single entity which is likely to generate immense benefits for the automobile industry (World Economic Forum, 2023). The introduction of the African Continental Free Trade Agreement will make markets in Africa more competitive due to the benefits that economies of scale possess. It will also lead to easy accessibility of materials for vehicle manufacturing such as aluminium from countries such as Mozambique or rubber from Ivory Coast due to reduced taxes (World Economic Forum, 2023). There are eight regional blocs that have trade agreements within Africa that provide member states access to their markets. These are the Economic Community of West African States (ECOWAS), the Southern African Development Community (SADC), the East African Community (EAC), the Common Market for East and Southern Africa (COMESA), Arab Maghreb Union (AMU), the Community of Sahel Saharan States (CEN-SAD), Intergovernmental Authority on Development (IGAD) and East Africa Community (EAC) (United Nations Economic Commission for Africa, 2023).

Africa still records low levels of industrialisation in most of its countries. The total Gross Domestic Product (GDP) of Africa has only 11% being the contribution from the manufacturing sector in 2013. It has been noted that the continent has experienced a decline in the total Gross Domestic Product (GDP) in the manufacturing sector which was 12% as at 1980 (United Nations, 2016). Northern Africa has some of the prominent vehicle manufacturing plants with

the largest producing at the capacity of 400,000 vehicles per year. This vehicle assembly plant was built by Renault in Morocco at the total investment cost of €1 billion (Nissan News, 2007; Automotive News, 2020). In Egypt, another vehicle assembly plant exists, with production capacity of approximately 200,000 vehicles per a year. Although South Africa is the leading automobile assembling country in Africa, the volume of vehicles of 533,000 automobiles in 2014 is insignificant compared to worldwide output (Automotive Industry Export Council, 2015). It is worth mentioning that after the independence of some countries in the continent, between 1950 and 1970, vehicle assembling plants were established. Some of these African countries that boost of vehicle assembly plants include Ghana, Nigeria, and Kenya and then Rhodesia now referred to as Zimbabwe. The assembling plants that were in place were of a small scale and largely dependent on imported components. Arguably these industries added very little value (Black and McLennan, 2016). In the early part of the 1980s, most these assembly plants collapsed due to economic challenges and the Structural Adjustment Programmes which was introduced by the International Monetary Fund and World Bank. The Structural Adjustment programmes encouraged large scale importation and discouraged industrialisation due to a low tariff regime. Africa is now embracing automobile assembling and production.

There has been some stability in the level of growth in the economies of Africa and there is also incremental demand for automobiles in Africa. Secondly, the continent is encouraging inter-trade through the establishment of various associations which have engaged in policies that have led to tariff reduction. Thirdly, some sub-Saharan countries are designing policies aimed at reviving domestic production (Black and McLennan, 2016). Sub-Saharan African countries are many, usually have small economies but have an important yearly Gross Domestic Product (GDP) of \$1.66 trillion (Black et al., 2017). The economies in sub-Saharan African are largely import dependent apart from South Africa. Due to this, the region recorded a \$16.3 billion deficit in the automotive trade market (Black et al., 2017). In 2021, the value of the automobile industry in Africa was pegged at \$30.44 billion and is likely to increase to \$42.04 billion in 2027 representing almost 40% increase (World Economic Forum, 2023). The automobile makers are now venturing into foreign markets and are not only exporting but are adding value to their operations (Visser, 2011). Value chains that offer the development of the automobile industry within the African continent have not been strongly established unlike Asia regional block such as ASEAN (Association of Southeast Asian Nations) which have achieved incremental progress (Kobayashi et al., 2015).

DW Africa (2021) also revealed that, with the population of about one billion, only 1% of worldwide sales in the automobile industry is recorded in Africa. Apart from South Africa, which is well-established within the automobile industry, countries such as Morocco, Ghana, Kenya, Egypt, Rwanda, and Nigeria are establishing themselves as contenders within the automobile space in Africa (DW Africa, 2021). It has been observed that there is the need for a massive ecosystem to be developed in the continent. This will be crucial in contributing significantly towards the growth of the automobile market in the region (Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development, 2023).

4.15 Automobile Manufacturing Challenges in Africa

One of the major challenges that confront automobile production in Africa is unavailability of strong production potentials and infrastructure. The continent needs to surmount this challenge in order to become competitive (Black et al., 2017). Africa needs to develop strong infrastructural capabilities especially in electricity supply and transportation. Africa therefore needs to invest and spend 4.5% of its Gross Domestic Product on the expansion and accessibility of electricity supply. Some African countries which include Nigeria, Senegal, Kenya and Zimbabwe between 2010-2015 spent 1.3% of its Gross Domestic Product on electricity which did not meet the expected expenditure of 4.5% (Bughin et al., 2016). The lack of electricity infrastructure does not only lead to disruptions in the manufacturing of automobile processes but also huge investment in generators and plants (Black et al., 2017). The cost incurred for obtaining capital in Africa is high and this need to be address for the continent to be competitive in the global market. Although Africa has low cost of labour compared to countries in Eastern Europe and Latin America but there is the issue of high interest rate on capital. This makes the cost of manufacturing more expensive compared to countries in Asia for instance (Iarossi, 2009). There are also high collateral requirements that discourages businesses from seeking for loans (Black et al., 2017).

4.16 Used and New Vehicle Adoption in Africa

A used vehicle in Ghana is defined as an automobile that has been registered before and has travelled more than 500 km (MOTI, 2019). In Kenya, vehicles that had owners in the past are classified as used vehicles. A new vehicle based on these definitions can easily be classified as used in hours or days (Ayetor et al., 2021). Regulators within the African continent regard used vehicles as a threat to the environment and the health conditions of inhabitants due to the detrimental effects of the poisonous gases emitted from these vehicles (Ayetor et al., 2021). Although new vehicles also emit dangerous gases, it is argued that, used vehicles cause more harm. The detrimental effect of used vehicles on air quality accounts for the death of 1 in 8 deaths across the globe and the particles from emissions account for 4.2 million deaths that occur prematurely (Organisation, 2016).

New car importers and manufacturers are actively seeking to establish new markets for their products, employing various strategies. Much like their European counterparts, they are focused on creating these markets by developing technical standards (Klebaner and Ramírez Pérez, 2019). Their initiatives include efforts to reduce tariffs on new cars, tighten import regulations, and, in some cases, prohibit the import of old cars and spare parts. These endeavours are often accompanied by narratives promoting national industrialisation and its anticipated benefits for the African continent (Cohen, 2023). Manufacturers frequently cite successful examples, such as South Africa and Egypt, where the ban on second-hand vehicle imports facilitated the development of local automotive industries (Cohen, 2023). Central to these efforts is the African Association of Automotive Manufacturers (AAAM), established in 2015, which serves as a unifying force in the industry. The African Association of Automotive Manufacturers (AAAM) has leveraged the expertise of Deloitte's automotive team to organise forums and events aimed at influencing local, African regional, and European policies (Berthelot et al., 2020). The overarching objective of these endeavours is to empower car manufacturers to revitalise the industry, with Africa potentially becoming a global automotive powerhouse (African Association

of Automotive Manufacturers, 2020). This collaborative effort extends to partnerships with international car manufacturers' associations and enjoys support from the German government (Alade, 2021). Manufacturers have committed to addressing the issue of industrialisation (Black et al., 2017) by establishing local assembly chains, a move expected to generate employment and foster the growth of new formal businesses in the automotive industry and related services (Ewuzie, 2020). These initiatives have yielded notable success stories in various countries, including Kenya (Ayeter et al., 2020) and Côte d'Ivoire, where measures were introduced to restrict the import of cars older than ten years (Cohen, 2023).

4.17 Adoption of Electric Vehicles in Africa

Countries that have developed trading partnerships with Africa are increasingly shifting for the use of internal combustion engines to electric powered vehicles. A deadline of 2035 has been set to effectively ban the sale of engines powered by internal combustion (World Economic Forum, 2023). Most African countries are recognising the need to embrace electric vehicles as one of the avenues for attaining sustainable development goals which focuses on clean environment. This is because electric vehicles achieve zero emission rate and therefore largely contribute to meeting these goals (Ayeter et al., 2020). As a result, some African countries have gradually started producing electric vehicles in order to make it the main choice for its citizenry. Tunisia, Morocco and South Africa have started the production of electric bus although it represents less than 0.01% of the total number of new vehicle sales (International Council on Clean Transport, 2022). Other countries within the continent including Ghana, Nigeria, Seychelles, South Africa, Senegal, Kenya and Tanzania are encouraging automobile firms to engage in producing electric vehicles in commercial quantities (International Council on Clean Transport, 2022).

In order to fully embrace the adoption of electric vehicles, some economies within the Africa such as Mauritius since 2009 started providing a tax incentive of 50% off on excise tax on the importation of electric and hybrid electric vehicles (Barry and Damar-Ladkoo, 2016). This resulted in a rise in the importation electric vehicles. Between 2009-2019, the number of used electric vehicles increased to 11,841 from 43. In addition, the number of registered automobiles that were fully electric increased from 2 to 132 between 2011-2019 (Prithipaul, 2018). Electricity access to countries within the sub-Saharan Africa is estimated at 48% compared to the global average which stands at 90% (International Energy Agency, 2021). Ghana has electricity penetration of 85% and this makes the country one of the most attractive African markets for electric vehicles (Ayeter et al., 2022).

4.18 Electric Vehicle in Ghana

The African continent contributes to 7% of global emissions from vehicle usage every year Ghana is recognised as one of the seven countries that account for 70% of the African emissions (Ayeter, 2021). Dotse et al. (2019) also asserted that the main mode of transportation in Ghana is road, and this area is experiencing an increasing number of fatalities between 12-15% a year since 2008. The government of Ghana mentioned in its 2019 budget statement in 2018 that it will provide tax incentives for vehicles that are wholly electric (Ayeter, 2020). Agyemang et al. (2022) revealed that, consumers in Ghana are willing to adopt electric vehicles but there are three

main stumbling blocks. First, electric vehicles are expensive. In addition, vehicles that thrive on electricity and can be driven for a restricted a range and finally there are no infrastructural development that can provide the needed functionality of electric vehicles. Ayetor (2020) revealed that, even though most vehicles in Ghana do not travel beyond a day, an infrastructural development for electric vehicle will generate public confidence and generate much interest in electric vehicles. There will also be the need to have competent technicians who will fix and maintain various charging in homes of electric vehicle owners (African Association of Automotive Manufacturers., 2020).

4.19 Profile and Economy of Ghana

Ghana is situated at along the Gulf of Guinea in the Atlantic Ocean. The country is surrounded by Togo to the east, Burkina Faso to the north and Cote d'Ivoire to the west. The total land area of the country is 238,500 square kilometres (World Bank, 2014). Although the country has more than a hundred ethnic groups, with different languages, English is the official language due to the influence of British rule (Ghana Web, 2014), and the currency unit is the 'Ghana Cedi' (WorldData. Info, 2014).

It has a populace of roughly 29.6 million (World Bank, 2021). From 1471 to 1957, Europeans ruled Ghana (then known as the Gold Coast). During this time, native tribes were engaged in various business and missionary activities with the Portuguese who were the first Europeans to arrive from 1471 to 1642. The Dutch were in the Gold from 1580 to 1872 followed by the Swedes from 1640 to 1663. In 1674, the Danes arrived 1674 and left in 1850. Brandenburgers of then Prussia also came in 1682 and departed in 1721. The last Europeans, the British who were in the Gold Coast from 1631 and left the shores in 1957. The presence of the Europeans influenced the Ghanaian culture and traditions (Charway and Houlihan, 2020) just like other anglophone countries (Ndee, 2000). In the 18th century, educated locals were required to engage in colonial trade to serve as interpreters (McWilliam and Kwamena-Poh, 1975), as well as missionaries to propagate Christianity (Graham, 1976). The Europeans introduced sports and games, and this attracted the natives into colonial educational institutions and Christianity (Scanlon, 1964). The English educational systems, sports activities, Christianity, health systems and others (Zweiniger-Bargielowska, 2006) were predominant in the Ghanaian physical culture (Charway and Houlihan, 2020).

Ghana experienced political upheavals and unstained economic growth since the country gained independence until the 1990s. By the turn of the century, the country had made significant progress in a number of sectors. In 2010, Ghana was placed 5th in terms of stability, 17th in terms of governance, and 13th in human capital development (Nesbitt, 2012). It had made significant progress in democracy under a multi-party system over the last two decades, with popular confidence in the independent judiciary (World Bank, 2021), and is regarded as one of the continent's most vibrant democracies (CIA World Fact Book, 2014). Ghana's economy was also ranked sixth largest on the African continent in 2010 due to purchasing power parity and nominal Gross Domestic Product (Nesbitt, 2012). Ghana was adjusted as the 7th best in terms of economic development in Africa by Ibrahim Index of African Governance. The recognition also indicated that, foreign investments were secure in the country. The country has achieved high

rankings in terms of press freedom and was identified as an attractive destination for engaging in business activities (Mo Ibrahim Foundation, 2021). The country was also recognised as one of the world's fastest-growing economies, with the tenth highest per capita Gross Domestic Product in Africa and the highest per capita Gross Domestic Product in West Africa in 2013, while having a rate of unemployment of 5.20 percent (World Bank, 2016). However, these achievements began to fade. Economic growth in the country fell from 11.25 percent in 2011 to 1.52 percent in 2015 (World Bank, 2016).

Ghana's economic growth has fluctuated dramatically during the last four decades. Figures indicated that the country's economic growth stayed reasonably constant at an average of 4.98 percent after swinging from -14.45 percent in 1975 to 4.98 percent in 1984. Over the period 1985 to 2007, the country's economic growth was relatively constant at an average of 2%. Following the global financial crisis, there was a period of unpredictability. The rate of growth fell in 2015 to 1.52%, the lowest level in two decades Domestic Product in 2021 increased to more than 90% in 2022. As part of measures to improve the macroeconomic performance, Ghana is currently under an International Monetary Fund programme and has secured a 3 billion credit facility as well as undertaking holistic measures to restructure its debts (World Bank, 2023). Ghana's economy is divided into three major sectors: agriculture, manufacturing and services. The country's economy is based on cocoa exports, and the country is the world's largest producer after overtaking Ivory Coast (Ghana Web, 2023). Ghana is also one of Africa's largest gold miners and the continent's newest oil producer (British Broadcasting Corporation, 2014). The country which initial had 10 regions now has additional 6 regions created by the government due to a successful implementation of a Constitutional Instrument. The initially regions were Greater Accra, Ashanti Region, Eastern Region, Central Region, Northern Region, Upper East Region, Upper West Region, Volta Region, Brong Ahafo Region, and Western Region. The additional regions are Bono East Region, Ahafo Region, North-East Region, Oti Region, Savannah Region and Western North Region (The Permanent Mission of Ghana to the UN, 2019). Below is the map of Ghana showing all the 16 regions with their capital cities in brackets.

Figure 4. 3: Map of Ghana

Source: (The Permanent Mission of Ghana to the UN, 2019)

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4.20 The Automobile Industry in Ghana

The automobile industry in Ghana is at its infancy state. Despite the expectation of enhancing economic growth, not many of the employable labour force has been absorbed by the sector (Motey, 2013; Industrial Global Union, 2020). Even though the industry, is at its infant stage, it has been able to offer appreciable social and economic development over the years in the country. The industry has provided tax revenues and has also been one of the avenues for creating employment opportunities (Motey, 2013). There are three main players around which the automotive industry in Ghana is structured. Companies such as Mac Ghana, Mahindra, Mechanical Lloyd, Toyota Ghana, Auto Parts, Nissan, Mitsubishi, and Universal Motors among others are household names in car dealerships. Some of these companies also offer after sales services to their clients. There are also a plethora number of garages that deal in the sale of both new and used cars. It has been observed about the automobile industry in Ghana that there is a huge business in sales of spare parts. These spare part dealers are involved in the sale of new and genuine vehicle spare parts. Most Ghanaians consider these spare parts as very expensive (Myjoyonline, 2022). However, the country, Ghana boasts of a very flamboyant and flourishing used spare part trade and is among the most lucrative businesses. The domestic demand for engines, tyres, batteries, ball bearings, headlights and lubricants among others is on the rise. Like the vehicles, the bulk of imported parts are used parts (Industrial Global Union, 2020). Mordorintelligence (2023) reported that the automobile market in Ghana has a value of about USD 4 billion annually, and this value is expected to rise to the range of USD 11 billion by the

year 2026, as the market registered a Compound Annual Growth Rate of 15% in the period of the forecast, between 2020-2026. Industrial Global Union (2020) reported that the majority of the consumers of the automobile products in Ghana belong to the affluent class component of the populace. The automobile industry has a bright future as the country's middle-class people are yet to be fully tapped into the consumer category of the automobile products (Mordorintelligence, 2023).

4.20.1 Importation of Vehicles into Ghana

Ghana's automobile market is still flooded with used vehicles (Obeng-Odoom, 2015). It is worth noting that Ghana's second-hand car value chain is primarily driven by importers and repairers, in contrast to new cars, where producers or consumers play more central roles (Freidberg, 2001). These combined efforts, spearheaded by the African Association of Automotive Manufacturers (AAAM) and other manufacturers, have demonstrated success in several countries, contributing to the reshaping of the automotive landscape in Africa (Ayeter et al., 2020; Cohen, 2023). However, it is believed that with time, the economic situations in the country will improve to enable the growing middle class and young population have purchasing power that will significantly develop the automobile market in the near future (Obeng-Odoom, 2015). In the creation of a favourable automobile market, new investors are expected to take advantage of the market for huge investments that will also affect other ancillary businesses in the industry across the country (Graphic Online, 2023).

Records on Ghana's importation indicated that in the year 2018, the importation of vehicles into the country constituted 12.5 percent of the country's overall importation, which was noted as the highest value among all imported goods. The percentage of vehicle importation as a ration of all imported commodities saw an increase from the 12.5% in 2018 to 14% in the year 2019 (UN Comtrade, 2020). The country spends averagely, a whopping amount of USD 1.8 billion annually on the importation of vehicles since 2016. Among these imported vehicles, the majority fall under the category of used or pre-owned vehicles. Research has shown that about 70 to 80 percent of the imported vehicles that were registered in the country are used or pre-owned vehicles (Industrial Global Union, 2020). The figure of imported vehicles into the country was over 100,000 every year. Out of this number of imported vehicles that were registered in the country, 90 percent were used vehicles which constituted for 12 percent of the total importation in Ghana. Imported vehicles and spare parts arrive at Tema Harbour before clearance into various places (Beuving, 2006). The topmost three countries that are sources of importation are the United States, Japan and Germany (Mordorintelligence, 2023).

4.20.2 Automobile Assembling Vehicles in Ghana

Oxford Business Group (2020) reported that, the automobile market in Ghana was witnessing growth in a positive direction as favourable conditions have been created for industrialisation. History makes it clear that assembling of cars in the country started back in 1960s. On 2nd February 1962, Ghanaians witnessed the commissioning of the first vehicle assembly plant, called Auto Parts Vehicle Assembly Plant, in the country (Daily Graphic, 1969). The vehicle assembly plant was located at the then Ring Road North Industrial Area with the capacity to

produce 600 cars, 600 buses, pick-ups, and trucks per annum. The plant imported Nissan parts from Japan and assembled Nissan vehicles (Daily Graphic, 1969; Industrial Global Union, 2020). According to Industrial Global Union (2020), UAC Motors, SCOA, RT Briscoe/ATS/KOWUS, GHAMOT and Neoplan Ghana Limited were also into the business of assembling vehicles in the country. It is worthy to note that the rugged Bedford trucks were also assembled in the country. At the time, an assembling plant and vehicle workshop was established by the National Investment Corporation (NIC), with the mandate to drive the industrialisation plan of the government (Industrial Global Union, 2020). According to Modern Ghana (2019), assembling plants in the automobile industry faded out of business as there were no substantial government policy and commitment in their favour. In the same period that witnessed the collapse of the private automobile assembling plants, also witnessed the sale of state-led National Investment Corporation under the initiative of privatisation.

Various vehicle brands convey unique national values based on various commitments of governments in establishing the automobile industry which reflected economic development (Holden, 2016). The African Association of Automotive Manufacturers (AAAM) and automakers have made significant strides in Ghana, actively contributing to the development of a new industrial policy with the support of the German GIZ and Deloitte (Cohen, 2023). The head of Volkswagen Group South Africa and president of the African Association of Automotive Manufacturers played a pivotal role in initiating discussions with Ghana's president during a visit to Germany. The discussions centred on formulating a supportive policy and addressing the challenges posed by second-hand car imports, which were hindering the development of a local automotive assembly industry (Venter, 2020).

The introduction of the Ghana Automotive Development Policy in 2019 has created an opportunity to attract players in the industry to channel their investment into Ghana in the form of original equipment manufacturing (OEM) and foreigners forming investment partners in the industry (Ministry of Trade and Industry, 2023). It is worthy of mention that one of the objectives of the formation of Ghana Automotive Development Policy in 2019 was the creation of favourable environment for the development of automobile plants that would manufacture quality and affordable new vehicles to feed the automobile market in the country. This is hoped to cause a decline in the country's over-reliance on the importation of used cars, which have led to the creation of serious environmental and safety concerns for the nation (Ministry of Trade and Industry, 2023). Under the Ghana Automotive Development Policy, it is required that the vehicle assembly plants in the country would produce vehicles of all ranges including those for both domestic and industrial purposes (Ministry of Trade and Industry, 2023). According to Ghana Auto Development Centre (2023), some of the original equipment manufacturers (OEM) have appended their signatures, agreeing to set up their vehicle assembly plants in the country. These companies include Nissan Motor Company, Volkswagen AG, that have committed to assembling vehicles in Ghana are Volkswagen, Nissan, Toyota, Sinotruk, Suzuki Motor Company and Toyota Motor Company. These companies are additions to the already existing local company, Kantanka Automobile. Mordorintelligence (2023) asserted that the demand for both private and commercial vehicles in the country is expected to rise.

As part of this policy, manufacturers are expected to relocate their factories to enable local assembly, rather than import fully assembled automobiles. On April 30, 2020, new policies that largely provided tax reliefs to vehicle assembly firms were introduced in Ghana (Ernst and Young, 2023). This aligns with the Ghana Automobile Development Policy, which aims to establish an industrial hub, generate employment, and create an asset-based vehicle financing scheme to enhance affordability for vehicle buyers (Cohen, 2023). Importantly, this policy includes bans on cars older than 10 years and wrecks. Although importers initially appeared to disregard these bans, they underscore the delicate balance within transatlantic trade agreements and raise questions about the government's dual approach (Cohen, 2023). Below were discussions on vehicles manufacturers engaging in local assembling in Ghana.

4.20.2.1 Volkswagen

In the year 2018, the country witnessed another stride towards the transformation of the automobile industry in the country with Volkswagen (VW) signing a Memorandum of Understanding (MoU) with the Ghanaian government to begin vehicle assembling in the country (Volkswagen AG, 2023). The Memorandum of Understanding (MoU) led to the establishment of the company's local subsidiary, VW Ghana (Volkswagen AG, 2023). This made VW Ghana, a subsidiary of VW, a German automotive company the first to be registered under the Ghana Automotive Development Policy which seeks to encourage locally assembly vehicles in the country (Graphic Online, 2020). According to the MoU that was signed between the government of Ghana and company, VW Ghana was to release its first assembled vehicle in the year 2019 (Myjoyonline, 2018). The first assembled vehicle that was produced by VW Ghana was launched in August of 2020 (Africa Business Insider, 2020). VW-Ghana is assembling six of its vehicle models, including Teramont, Passat, Tiguan, T-Cross, Caddy, and Polo, in the country (The bftonline, 2022). What the company does is that it imports partially disassembled parts of these car models and re-assemble them in the country. This implies that, VW-Ghana is operating as Semi-Knocked Down (SKD) in the production of the VW brands (Myjoyonline, 2023). In 2020, Volkswagen took a significant step by opening assembly lines near Tema. The firm has committed USD 22 million in Ghana and is expected to assemble between 10,000 and 20,000 automobiles per annum (Ghana Web, 2020). The firm has been able to sell 1,00 vehicles within two years of operating the assembling plant in Ghana (The bftonline, 2022).

4.20.2.2 Nissan

Nissan, a Japanese firm went into an agreement with the government of Ghana to establish a plant that would assemble vehicles in the country (Graphic Online, 2018). In November 2018, a Memorandum of Understanding (MoU) was signed between the two parties, making the company the second major automobile company to commit to the assembling of vehicles in the country (Graphic Online, 2018). According to the Memorandum of Understanding (MoU) signed between the company and the government of Ghana, the assembly plant would be in Tema, specifically at Tema Industrial Area, which is a short distance from Tema Harbour (Japan Motors Trading Corporation Limited, 2022). It is indicated in the Memorandum of Understanding (MoU) that the first quarter of 2020 would commence the period when Nissan would start the assembly of the vehicles. It was the intention of the company to actualise the moving of their first assembled vehicle on road by the end of 2020 (Myjoyonline, 2022). It is in

line with this aspiration that the company in the year 2019 established its centre for the training of sales and after-sales technicians to serve clients within the West Africa sub-region (Citinewsroom, 2021). The company has established a 9-million-dollar assembly plant with the capacity of assembling 31,666 vehicles in a year (Japan Motors Trading Corporation Limited, 2022). Nissan has begun assembling two of its brands in Ghana which are Nissan Navara and the Peugeot 3008 sports utility vehicle (SUV) (Japan Motors Trading Corporation Limited, 2022).

4.20.2.3 Toyota

In March of 2019, senior managers of Toyota and the government of Ghana signed a Memorandum of Understanding (MoU) in Accra, Ghana to establish a vehicle assembling plant in the country (Graphic, 2020). The company is 100% owned by Toyota Tsusho (Toyota-Tsusho, 2021). Toyota was the second automobile company to establish an assembling plant after Volkswagen (Reuters, 2023). The assembling plant is in Tema which is noted as the hub for industrial activities (Thebftonline, 2021). The \$7 million assembling plant is expected to have an estimated output of 1,330 units per annum (Reuters, 2023). Toyota is the first Japanese company to establish an assembling plant in Ghana. Toyota Hilux pickup will be the first model to assembled before the Suzuki Swift model (Thebftonline, 2021). The decision by Toyota to assemble Suzuki vehicles is based on a Memorandum of Understanding (MoU) between Toyota and Suzuki (Toyota-Tsusho, 2021).

4.20.2.4 Sinotruk

Among the companies that have come to Ghana to boost the automobile industry with vehicle assembling plants is Sinotruk, a Chinese company. The company is noted for the manufacturing of minibuses, heavy-duty trucks, and other vehicles such as lifting and earth-moving machinery (Reuters, 2018). In the year 2018, the government of Ghana went into an agreement with Sinotruk during the Ghana-Shandong business conference in September, which saw both parties sign a Memorandum of Understanding (MoU) with the Sinotruk given the mandate to establish an assembly plant in the country, Ghana (The Presidency, Republic of Ghana, 2018). The company will assemble about 1500 trucks every year for the automobile market in Ghana and that of the entire West African Region (Reuters, 2018). Regarding the company's absorption of the labour force in Ghana, it was hoped that about 250 auto technicians and engineers would be employed directly by the company (News Ghana, 2018). In addition to providing employment to the Ghanaian people, Sinotruk is also expected to provide training opportunities and technology transfers in the area of automobile assembly and other related auto manufacturing activities (Graphic Online, 2018). Sources at the presidency of Ghana indicated that the company has started its operations by assembling trucks in Ghana (Myjoyonline, 2020).

4.20.2.5 Kantanka Automobile

The automobile assembly in the country, Ghana, was revived by Kantanka Automobile, a subsidiary of Kantanka Group in the 1990s by assembling its first vehicle in the country (Oxford Business Group, 2021). Kantanka Automobile was founded in 1994 by Apostle Dr. Ing.

Kwadwo Safo Kantanka and became a limited liability firm in 2005 (Kantanka Automobile, 2023). The firm's automobile assembly plant is located at Gomoa Mpota in the Central Region (Al Jazeera, 2014; New African Magazine, 2015). Even though the company produced its first assembled vehicle in 1994, it was in 2016 that the firm started assembling on a large scale (Kantanka Group, 2021). The first assembled vehicle comprised of 75% of local materials including the engine (Kantanka Automobile, 2023). The company has the capacity of producing eight vehicles every day (Ghana Web., 2014). Some of the notable Kantanka automobile assembled vehicle brands are Kantanka Otumfuo, Kantanka Nsoromma and Kantanka Dassebre, which are sports utility vehicles (SUVs). During the launching of the modern vehicle assembly plant, Kantanka Motors inaugurated its three flagship car models comprising the Kantanka Omama, which is a pickup truck, Kantanka Onantefuo, which is a sports utility vehicle (SUV), and the Kantanka K71, a mini-SUV (Ghana Web, 2015; Oxford Business Group, 2021). Apart from the conventional vehicles, Kantanka is working on introducing electric automobiles to its markets as well (GhanaWeb, 2015). It is reported that Kantanka Automobile has assembled Kantanka Odeneho I, which is a prototype electric car (Myjoyonline, 2017). The company is currently enjoying fiscal incentives that the government of Ghana has offered to foreign automobile manufacturers. Base on the policy of the government regarding the establishment of automobile assembling plants, Kantanka Automobile has been given a 10-year tax holiday and is also exempted from paying duties on imported equipment meant for assembling of its vehicles (Ghana Financial Markets, 2019).

CHAPTER FIVE

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

5.0 Introduction

The previous chapter reviewed extant literature relevant to this study. Research methodology provides assumptions and procedural choices and techniques that were adopted in collecting and analysing data for a particular study (Creswell, 2009; Lapan et al., 2012; Creswell and Creswell, 2017). The methodology was based on the purpose and objectives that a researcher seeks to achieve (Ying et. al, 2009 and Saunders et al., 2011). The chapter discussed research philosophies and paradigms, research approaches, strategies, time horizon as well as and techniques and procedures. The chapter further discussed research philosophies and paradigms, approaches, strategies, methods, population, sampling techniques, sample size, time horizon as well as and techniques and procedures (data collection instruments, validity and reliability testing and pre-testing of data collection instruments, analysis of data (data screening, factor analysis, structural equation modelling, thematic analysis), data integration and ethical consideration.

5.1 Philosophical Assumptions and Research Paradigms

Philosophical assumptions are the conceptual pillars that solidifies our apprehension of the world (Lim, 2023). Within every paradigm, there are philosophical assumptions which include ontological, epistemological, and methodological stances that provide direction and guidance and form the basis of distinction from one another (Creswell, 2014). This therefore implies that ontological, epistemological, and methodological assumptions are inherent in every paradigm and provides underlying explanations. According to Creswell and Creswell (2017), epistemological assumptions is concern with the sources of obtaining knowledge, the legitimacy of the knowledge and the requirements for assessing the adequate nature of the knowledge. Ontological assumptions on the hand, is concerned about issues of reality that exist within the social context, the nature of the reality and the relationship that such realities have with others (Creswell and Creswell, 2017). The very specific means by which work is empirically and logically performed is construed as the methodological assumption (Creswell and Creswell, 2017). According to Creswell (2014), a paradigm serves as the foundation for a study and dictates the philosophical assumption. A paradigm is of importance due to the direction that it provides in identifying the right methodology for particular research (Creswell and Creswell (2017). There are five main paradigms of a research: positivism, post-positivism, interpretivism, constructivism and pragmatism.

Positivists believe in the objective perspective of reality and advocate for the reliance on methods which include experiments instead of the application of subjective methods such as reflection, sensation or intuition (Babbie, 2012; Saunders et al., 2012; Creswell and Clark, 2018). The paradigm is premised on deductive and hypothetical statements which are quantitatively inclined and takes into consideration causal relationships between independent and dependent

variables (Park et al., 2020). Positivism has objective perspective of reality as its ontological philosophy. The paradigm also regards discovering knowledge as its epistemological philosophy and the application of quantitative methods as its methodological philosophy (Lim, 2023). Unlike positivism which emphasise on objectivity in research, post-positivism postulate that, objectivity of knowledge cannot be entirely obtained. The ontological philosophical stance is inclined towards the acceptability of “probable” truth (Bunniss and Kelly, 2010). The epistemological philosophical position is that knowledge could have subjective elements in objective truths and relies on both quantitative and qualitative methods as its methodological philosophy (Lim, 2023). In terms of interpretivism, this paradigm does not subscribe to the objective view of research which makes them likely to value subjectivity rather than objectivity (Willis, 2007). Naturally, interpretivists fail to seek out answers for their research in rigid ways; instead, they adopt more personal and flexible research structures (Ataro, 2020; Thanh and Thanh, 2015). According to Lim (2023), interpretivists ontological philosophical position is varied realities based on epistemological stance that, knowledge is experienced and has qualitative method as methodological philosophy.

The next paradigm is constructivism. According to this paradigm, reality is built on experiences of individuals and social interactions (Lim, 2023). Whereas interpretivists focus more on developing multiple realities based on individual experiences and perspectives, constructivists focus more on developing realities based on individuals’ social context or social dynamism. The Pragmatism is the next paradigm. According to pragmatism, there are single and multiple realities and prescribes a practical approach in solving problems (Creswell and Clark, 2007; Rorty, 1999). Other scholars such as Creswell and Poth (2017) and Mackenzie and Knipe (2006) also added that, a pragmatist researcher’s major motivation is how to answer research questions and solve problems irrespective of the approaches involved. The ontological philosophical view of pragmatism is problem-based realities. The epistemological philosophical stance is that knowledge is the adoption of practical approaches to solving problems. The methodological philosophical position is based the questions and problems that a study seeks to provide solutions (Lim, 2023).

The study employed the pragmatist paradigm which was considered ideal. The research was therefore not restricted to a particular methodological stance and therefore utilised quantitative and qualitative approaches to provide findings that contributed to the filling of the research gaps and answering the research questions. This was employed to provide different practical approaches to solving research problems without being confined by a particular ideological stance. This is consistent with Creswell (2018) who asserted that, the pragmatic paradigm views the research problem as key and applies all approaches to understanding the problem. Most studies conducted on brand attitude, perceived value and purchase intention focused only on qualitative and quantitative perspectives. The literature also viewed indicated that, there was a lacuna in terms of the application of mixed methods in relation to brand attitude, perceived value and purchase intention that compared locally assembled vehicle brands and imported vehicle brands. The study therefore employed a multifaceted approach to answer research questions to obtain a practical approach to solve problems, hence the adoption of the pragmatist paradigm which aided in generating novel results.

5.2 Research Approaches

Research involves the use of theory that may be made explicit in the design of the research or may not although it will usually be made explicit in the presentation of findings and conclusions (Saunders et al., 2007). Janiszewski and van Osselaer (2022) asserted that, research approaches include inductive, deductive, and abductive approaches. Studies that adopt inductive reasoning approach aim at building theories by initiating the process with observation of instances (Hyde, 2000; Bucher, 2021). Inductive reasoning is linked to qualitative studies and seeks to make general conclusions based on the perceptions and experiences of study participants (Thomas, 2006). Deductive approach focuses on confirming or dis-confirming a hypothetical statement and leans towards quantitative research which is backed by objective research stance (Cooper and Schindler, 2006). It is also referred to as top-down process and focuses on generalisation of research findings (Janiszewski and van Osselaer, 2022). The next approach is abductive. This approach combines two approaches, which are deductive and inductive. It also embraces the skills-sets, competence and experience of scholars who undertake studies in order to draw conclusions based on findings (Wheeldon and Ahlberg, 2012).

According to Janiszewski and van Osselaer (2022), pragmatism forms the basis for the abductive reasoning. This reasoning was linked to mixed methods and encourages theoretical and empirical testing (Wheeldon and Ahlberg, 2012). The study was a mixed method research and adopted the pragmatic paradigm and therefore the abductive reasoning is the appropriate choice. According to Morgan (2007) and Christensen (2022), pragmatism relies on the abductive approach that allows for the application of both qualitative and quantitative approaches. Results of quantitative studies could serve as inputs for qualitative study and vice-versa. The study relied on qualitative findings to explain quantitative results in order to provide divergent and holistic appreciation of the research objectives and the phenomenon under study.

5.3 Research Strategies

A research strategy is the processes through which data is collected, analysed, interpreted, and presented. Research strategy is of much importance because it presents a practical way of conducting research (Creswell, 2012). Experiments and survey are the research designs suited for quantitative studies. Research strategies used for qualitative studies include narrative, ethnography, grounded theory, case study, phenomenological research, and archival studies (Creswell and Creswell, 2017). Narrative research aids the development or contribution to a theory through an analysis of events in a sequential manner (Saliya, 2023). Narrative research is most suitable when the research evolves around linguistics, cultural, historical and identity stories about the lives of a people (Riessman, 2005). Ethnography is often time consuming, and it occurs over an extended period. This strategy is used to study a phenomenon of an intact cultural group within their natural setting (Creswell, 2009) through extended participant observation and interviews that allow the participants to tell their stories about the complexities of their everyday life (Saunders et al., 2009). Grounded theory is often used when the researcher seeks to predict and explain the behaviour of participants with the intention to develop theory grounded in the views of participants (Creswell, 2009). Grounded theory relies on data collected to develop a theory based on observations made by the researcher (Creswell, 2009; White and Cooper, 2022). Through case studies, the researcher can explore an event, process or activity in depth and within

its context (Creswell, 2009; Yin, 2003). Though both surveys and case studies are situated within context, the latter differs from surveys in that surveys place a limitation on the number of variables that can be employed and used for engaging in data collection (Saunders et al., 2009). Archival Research draws upon information that is derived from documentation and have been stored over a period, although the data is not necessarily restricted to only historical documents (Bryman and Bell, 2011). This study is employed when researchers need information that exist in archival materials (Rhee, 2015). Surveys chronologically observe and ask questions that a study seek to answer (Bryman and Bell, 2015). Common data collection methods include questionnaires and interviews. Surveys are employed in research to collect data and produce statistical results in quantitative studies (Creswell, 2012). In qualitative research, interview is the main approach for data collection (Creswell, 2012; Myers and Newman, 2007). The flexibility inherent in semi structured interviews for example allows participants to provide responses based on personal experiences within the confines of the research (Yin, 2009).

Survey strategy was adopted for the study. This study mixed methodological approach and employed both questionnaire and interview approaches. Survey was employed to collect large data based on quantitative objectives using questionnaires and interviews were conducted to generate qualitative data to meet study objectives.

5.4 Methods

The methods that are ideal to a researcher are linked to the objectives and not based on the preference of the researcher (Babbie, 2004). Research choices range from wide assumptions to elaborate methods that are applicable in collecting, analysing, and interpreting data in a study (Creswell, 2014). Three types of research methods are available. These are qualitative, quantitative, and mixed methods. Qualitative research according to Maxwell (2012) seeks to attain narrative, rich insights and detailed data that serves as a source of knowledge from the phenomenon understudy. Creswell, 2009; Silverman (2013) asserted that qualitative research uncovers deep knowledge, experiences, and opinions from the perspectives of the participants to provide an understanding of the research problem and answer objectives. This method relies on varied tools such as the use of documentation, observations, and the conduct of interviews (Creswell and Plano Clark, 2011; Easterly-Smith et al., 2012). Thus, qualitative research occurs in a natural environment and brings interpretations of a phenomenon (Lincoln and Denzin, 2003). Studies conducted qualitatively are based on exploring issues in their natural settings (Creswell, 2009).

Boateng (2016) argued that researchers need to consider the context, timing, and experience in undertaking such a study. Quantitative research on the other hand is associated with theory testing of variables and seeks to assess the linkages between variables and constructs to ascertain whether a relationship exist or not (Creswell, 2014). Quantitative study is geared towards providing results that are objective and can be generalised (Ponterotto, 2005; Creswell and Clark, 2007; Leedy and Ormrod, 2001; Agyekum-Mensah et al., 2020). The third method is mixed method is the collection and integration of both qualitative and quantitative data to provide interpretations and findings in order to understand problems of a study (Creswell and Clark, 2007; Creswell, 2018). The method provides in-depth appreciation of a phenomenon and improves the quality of a study due to the reliance on both qualitative and quantitative methods

compared to studies that employ only one method (Creswell, 2014). Mixed method has gained prominence due to the criticisms of adopting either a qualitative or a quantitative approach. Qualitative has been criticised for its lack of generalisation of findings (Gelo et al., 2009) and being subjective and therefore lacking objectivism (Nagel, 1986). Quantitative research on the other has been criticised for lack of voice of respondents and lack of deeper insights and substantive interpretation of results (Toomela, 2008). Regardless of the significance attached to mixed method, there are some difficulties. The method will require more funding, more space to interview, administer a questionnaire or other data collection instruments. Researchers who adopt this method should also be knowledgeable in both quantitative and qualitative approaches (McKim, 2017).

The study employed mixed method because of a number of reasons. According to Hurmerinta-Peltomaki and Nummela (2006), mixed method makes research finding more valid and aid in creating more knowledge through the usage of a second data. The adoption of a mixed method enables a study to gain broader and deeper understanding compared to investigating a phenomenon using either quantitative or qualitative research approach. In another study, it was reported that, research works that were conducted with mixed method had more citations than their counterparts that were conducted using other approaches (Lopez-Fernandez and Molina-Azorin, 2011). In the findings of O’Cathain et al. (2010), it was revealed that, the integration component is another value of mixed method. This is because, integration raises the confidence level in the results and conclusions that are drawn based on the findings.

5.5 Research Population

Before results are achieved in a research, data is collected from a sample. The sample used in research is obtained from research population. Three concepts are used to categorise a population under study. These three concepts are general, target, and specific population. According to Banerjee and Chaudhury (2010), the totality of the set of people that the researcher conducts the investigation is the general population. General population has been explained by Bartlett et al. (2001) as constituting all individuals that the researcher gathers information or data in efforts to address or find answers to a study. Saunders (2012) postulated that, the general population is the universe population in which two other populations, target and specific are drawn from. The target population on the other hand, is distinct from the general population includes individuals who possess the requisite characteristics. These characteristics might include the number of years that staff, for example should have before taking part in the research. These characteristics therefore represent the criteria by which target population members are selected (Banerjee and Chaudhury, 2010). The specific population may be obtained from the target population. The specific population is the number of individuals within the target population who have demonstrated their preparedness to respond to questions during data collection process related to a study (Allwood, 2012). In this current research, the general population was travel trade (car rental, travel, tour, and tours) in Ghana. The target population was travel trade (car rental, travel and tours, and tour operating agencies) staff in Ghana with at least one year experience and the specific population were those within the travel trade in Ghana (car rental, travel and tours, and tour operating agencies) who were prepared to take part in the study. The usage of automobiles was a key component in the travel trade business hence their choice as the population of this research.

5.6 Sampling Technique

In research, sampling is the mechanism that is employed in selecting a subset of a population. By sampling, the researcher can obtain the group of participants for the administration of the research instrument (Creswell, 2003). Individuals within the population that are selected to be part of the study constitute the sample (Saunders, 2012). Researchers engage in sampling due to the impracticability of obtaining data from an entire population in social sciences (Sarker and AL-Muaalemi, 2022). In order to obtain sample for the study, the researcher accessed information about travel trade from the Ghana Tourism Authority website. Trade travel trade within the Greater Accra Region were physically contacted by the researcher who was in Ghana for data collection purposes. Before data collection, respondents in firms that agreed to partake in the research were introduced to participant consent form and participant information sheet. Data was collected on the premises of the firms of the respondents and was for a period of 2 months and 2 weeks.

Two main techniques are employed by researchers in obtaining the sample for a study. These are probability and non-probability (Neuman, 2007; Malhotra and Das, 2010; Sekaran and Bougie, 2016). With probability sampling, there is the likelihood that each individual within the population for a research stand a chance of being selected to constitute the sample (Malhotra and Krosnick, 2007). There are a number of sampling techniques that are probabilistic in nature. These include systematic sampling, stratified sampling, cluster sampling and simple random sampling. On the other hand, non-probability sampling draws sample based on the judgement of the researcher (Malhotra, 2019). Scholars have identified quota sampling, snowball sampling, convenience, and purposive sampling as non-probability sampling techniques (Neuman, 2007). This study employed convenience sampling and purposive sampling to select respondents. Convenience sampling technique focuses on choosing respondents who can easily be reached and are ready to be part of a study. The researcher employed convenience sampling because it provided a faster and efficient means of identifying respondents and obtaining data since the study was time bound and cross-sectional in nature (Sarker and AL-Muaalemi, 2022). This sampling method provides generalisation to the population from the sample of the study (Andrade, 2021; Creswell and Clark, 2007). Research by Bendixen et al. (2004) that employed quantitative analysis that found that branding affected purchasing of medium-voltage electrical equipment derived sample from members of the buying centre. Consistent with the previous study, the sample for the quantitative study comprised of owners, managers, supervisors, and workers of travel trade (car rental, travel and tour and tour operating agencies) with at least one year experience who played various roles in the buying centre. Forman (2014) also added that organisations are expanding the boundaries of individuals who make input in purchasing decisions to include low-level staff to enhance the level of involvement. This is due to the expertise that such staff possess (Prior et al., 2021). A qualifying question was used to ensure that respondents were familiar with issues related to automobile brands. This was consistent with Herbst and Merz (2011) who used of qualifying question to enhance sample selection.

Another sampling technique employed was purposive sampling. Hair et al. (2010), Hibberts et al. (2012) and Sarker and AL-Muaalemi (2022) asserted that purposive sampling seeks to identify individuals or respondents who have specialised knowledge pertaining to a study. Hibberts et al.

(2012) further suggested that purposive sampling aids in obtaining rich detail for a study but findings from the use of purposive sampling should not be generalised. Andrade (2021) also postulated that generalisation of purposive sampling should be limited to the population that the sample was obtained from. Andrade (2021) stressed on the application of exclusion and inclusion criteria to obtain the relevant respondents during purposive sampling. The exclusion criteria of this study were individuals who were not part of the travel trade as well as operatives of trade travel and supervisors. The participants that were purposively sampled were selected based on ownership, occupancy of lower or upper managerial position and at least one year experience in the position in a travel and trade firm. These criteria were employed in order to obtain more insights from those who ensure that purchasing decisions are implemented in organisations (Dawes et al., 1996; Laing et al., 1998). The sample drawn for the study was due to their knowledge and experience not only as individuals who make inputs but also ensure that brand-related issues and purchasing decisions are implemented in the automobile industry.

5.7 Sample Size

It is the responsibility of a researcher to devise strategies that would help determine the appropriate number of respondents for a study. The sample size is therefore the number of participants who respond to questions in a study (Malhotra, 2010; Malhotra and Dash, 2011). In the process of conducting research, it becomes a necessity for a researcher to obtain a sample from a population because, a population is too large to reach and administer a data collection instrument (Blumberg et al., 2014). There are different factors that play a role in determining the sample size. Among these factors are nature of the study, the approach employed, nature of analysis, the sample sizes that were used in previous studies that share similarity with current study and the resources that are available to undertake the study (Malhotra and Krosnick, 2007). Various researchers have also made recommendations for determining the sample size for quantitative study. Roscoe (1975) advocated for a larger sample size of a minimum of 10 times of the number of variables used for a study. Hair et al. (2006) also mentioned that a sample size of 100 or more respondents is ideal for a quantitative study. Based on the assertions of various scholars, this study obtained a larger sample size of 654 respondents for the quantitative part of the study. Exploratory factor analysis was conducted on the 310 responses and confirmatory factor analysis was undertaken on 344 responses of the study. The respondents were owners, managers, supervisors, and staff of travel trade firms in Accra and Tema in the Greater Accra Region.

In relation to the qualitative study, Creswell (2003) asserted that, the choice of the sample size should be between five (5) to twenty-five (25) respondents based on data saturation. The qualitative aspect of the study constituted a sample size of 15 respondents due to saturation of data. The sample were owners and managers of travel and trade firms within the Greater Accra Region who were part of the quantitative study. The Greater Accra Region, which hosts the capital city has the nation's highest urban population of around 90.5 per cent (Anuwa-Amarh, 2015). In addition, Ghana Tourism Authority Report (2021) indicated that, the highest number of licensed travel trade firms in Ghana is in the Greater Accra Region. The capital has 254 licensed travel trade firms out of a total of 408 across the country.

5.8 Horizon

Time frame is critical for the successful completion of a research. According to Rindfleisch et al. (2008), longitudinal and cross-sectional studies are the options available for researchers in terms of time horizon. Longitudinal studies are conducted over a phenomenon for a long period of time. It could be years or a decade. With longitudinal studies, participants are usually observed without interference from researchers (Plano Clark et al., 2015; Caruana et al., 2015). Cross-sectional on the other hand, undertakes research over short period of time (Taris, 2021). Cross-sectional studies are conducted within a specific time frame and can investigate multiple variables at the same time (Caruana et al., 2015). This study was cross-sectional in nature. The study was for academic purpose and data was collected at one point in time and there is no intention to collect data in the future.

5.9 Techniques and Procedures

This section highlighted on the data collection instruments that were employed to undertake the research and their piloting.

5.9.1 Data Collection Instruments

The researcher employed two data collection instruments. Structured questionnaire was used to collect data for the quantitative part of the study. In terms of the qualitative aspect of the research, semi-structured interview guide was employed. Burns and Bush (2012) and Haydam and Mostert (2013) asserted that, questionnaires have the potential to eliminate bias from respondents. It also has the potential to reach many respondents and obtain a high rate of responses. Despite the strength of a questionnaire, the use of media such as mail, e-mail or online to disseminate it may result in low responses (Bhattacharjee, 2012). In order to avoid this, the researcher administered the questionnaire on a face-to-face basis. Another weakness of employing a questionnaire is the challenge of obtaining huge volume of information if it is complicated (Dickey and Blumberg, 2004). Due to this difficulty, the researcher simplified the questionnaire and assured respondents of taking some few minutes of their time. Questionnaires can be unstructured, structured, and semi-structured. Unstructured questionnaires are the type that provides non-restrictive responses (Chowdhury et al., 1998). Structured questionnaires are developed with fixed questions and uses close ended questions. Unlike structured questionnaires, semi-structured questionnaires have some open-ended questions that elicit more responses (Bowling, and Ebrahim, 2005). Although structured questionnaires have been criticised for limiting responses, the researcher employed semi-structured questionnaires due to its ability to obtain unambiguous data that enhances quantitative data analysis (Bowling, and Ebrahim, 2005). To obtain more explanations and deeper perspectives, the researcher conducted a qualitative study with the support of a semi-structured interview guide.

Interviewing is a technique that is mostly employed by researchers to collect data that provides insights of respondents' perspectives and opinion in a social phenomenon (Kvale, 1996). Interviews therefore unearth deeper understanding of a phenomenon unlike quantitative techniques such as questionnaires which seeks to ascertain casual relationships among variables

and constructs (Denzin and Lincoln, 2000). Interviews have an advantage over other qualitative data collection methods such as participant observation and archival analysis due to its ability to ask questions and probe further to generate greater understanding and insights (Bryman, 2015). Interviews also enables participants to freely express their opinions even on sensitive topics unlike focus groups where respondents sometimes become reluctant (Kaplowitz and Hoehn, 2001) and may conform to social dynamics (Geuens et al., 2018) as well as rely on vociferous individuals and high ranked position holders to influence their thoughts (Belzile and Öberg, 2012). There are three types of interviews that are used to undertake research. These are unstructured interview, structured interview and semi-structured interview (Stuckey, 2013). Unstructured interview are usually narratives by participants based on life experiences (Stuckey, 2013). DiCicco-Bloom and Crabtree (2006) also asserted that, unstructured interviews are usually conducted after collecting observational data. Structured interview also follows questions that are determined in advance and provides opportunity for restrictive responses that are brief and does not require follow-up (Stuckey, 2013). Semi-structured interview allows interviewers to ask questions determined in advance and accommodates questions and answers based on interactions (DiCicco-Bloom and Crabtree, 2006). The researcher employed semi-structured interviews due to identified benefits. Galletta (2012) acknowledged that, it enhances interactions. Semi-structured interviews also embrace follow-up on questions, and this leads to the provision of unanticipated data that enrich a study (Rubin and Rubin, 2011; Polit and Beck, 2010) and encourages respondents to verbally express their positions and opinions (Olsen et al., 2022).

Kallio et al. (2016) recommendations for developing a semi-structured guide were adopted for this study. According to Kallio et al. (2016), scholars need to understand the requirements for opting semi-structured interviews and utilise already existing knowledge. Kallio et al. (2016) further encouraged the development of an initial semi- structured interview guide which should be tested and then develop the final semi-structure interview guide. There are several books on how to adequately semi-structure an interview guide (e.g. Wengraf, 2001; Morrow, 2005; Kvale, 2007; Galletta, 2012; Rubin and Rubin, 2012) although the main goal of a qualitative work is to provide deeper insights (Polit and Beck, 2010). This is due to the possibility of designing semi-structured interviewer guide in less user-friendly manner through making it complicated and providing too much detail (Gibbs et al., 2007). This concern informed the researcher to design the data collection instrument in a simplistic manner devoid of excessive details. The interview sessions had an average time of 30 minutes.

5.9.2 Validity and Reliability in Quantitative Studies

Validity and reliability are conducted quantitatively to achieve rigour and soundness of results (Heale and Twycross, 2015). Below was a discussion on validity and reliability employed in the study.

5.9.2.1 Validity

Validity in quantitative terms is the degree to which variables employed in a study are precisely measured (Fitnzer, 2007) or the extent to which a data collection measures what it is supposed to measure (Polit and Hungler, 1989). To obtain validity, the study employed criterion validity and

content validity. Criterion validity seeks to ascertain the extent to which a data collection instrument is designed to reflect others used in similar studies (Fitnzer, 2007). The researcher adapted questionnaires from previous similar studies. Thus, questionnaires that were used in previous studies were fine-tuned to suit the study. Content validity was also employed. Content validity is defined as the ability of a research instrument to measure the variable or the construct. An approach of attaining construct validity is seeking the opinions of experts. In order to achieve this, the researcher received feedback from supervisors, lecturers, and PhD students on the nature of the questionnaire which was employed to collect data (Heale and Twycross, 2015). In addition to this, the researcher conducted a pilot testing among respondents. The feedback was used to improve the wording and understanding of the data collection instrument.

5.9.2.2 Reliability

Reliability on the other hand refers to the extent to which data collection instrument produces quality results (Heale and Twycross, 2015). Fitnzer (2007) asserted that, reliability emphasises on the consistency of results. One of the techniques that was adopted by the study to achieve reliability was the Cronbach's α that test the internal consistency of a data collection instrument employed in a quantitative study. The Cronbach's α test outcome ranges between 0 and 1 (Heale and Twycross, 2015). To achieve reliability, the value for Cronbach alpha testing should be 0.7 or higher (Cronbach, 1951). The questionnaire employed for the research was subjected to Cronbach alpha test and questions which did not meet the requirements were deleted. Kim et al. (2022) also advocated for the use of confirmatory factor analysis to conduct reliability and validity tests. In line with this, the study employed conducted confirmatory factor analysis that focused on fit indices.

5.9.3 Reliability and Validity of Qualitative Studies

Reliability and validity of qualitative studies had its roots in quantitative studies. These tests are conducted to enhance the quality, significance, and the applicability of qualitative studies (Rose and Johnson, 2020).

5.9.3.1 Reliability

Reliability is the sound nature of a study which is mostly based on the selection and implementation of the right methods in undertaking studies qualitatively. Reliability seeks to ascertain the consistency of the procedures that are employed in research (Miles et al., 2014). Creswell (2013) also advocated for studies to be consistent and clear in their methodological choices in order not to only provide understanding but also serve as a basis of which other studies can adopt the methods. To attain reliability, the researcher provided a written methodological process which will serve as an example for other researchers to follow (Yin, 2012). Transcripts were also inspected to identify errors which were corrected (Gibbs, 2007). The codes and themes were clearly identified and discussed (Rose and Johnson, 2020).

5.9.3.2 Validity

Validity is concerned with the fidelity or the accuracy of the results of studies (Creswell and Miller, 2000; Lincoln et al., 2011). To ensure validity, the study adopted rich, thick description, crystallisation and searching for disconfirmation as recommended by Rose and Johnson (2020). To achieve rich, thick description study provided detailed information and explanations on the qualitative findings based on the transcripts (Furman et al., 2006). Crystallisation was also employed and as result, the study provided strong themes and the voices of participants who have rich insights were presented in the form of quotations (Alvesson and Skoldberg, 2000). The research also provided instances of not only confirmations, but contrary results conducted by similar studies (Maxwell, 2013).

5.9.4 Pre-Testing of Data Collection Instruments

The structured questionnaire and the semi-structured interview guide were pre-tested to ascertain accuracy and reliability (Du Plooy, 2009; Bhattacharjee, 2012). The scale of the questionnaire was 1-5 (1= Strongly Disagree 2= Disagree 3= Neutral 4= Agree 5=Strongly Agree) (Balakrishnan et al., 2014). The structured questionnaires were initially tested among 20 respondents and the semi-structured interview guide tested among 5 respondents that constituted the sample for quantitative and qualitative aspects of the study. The pilot testing aided the researcher to obtain feedback from the respondents in terms of the structure and content of the data collection instruments. It therefore assisted in identifying questions that were not clear and difficult to understand. The responses were used to fine-tune the final data collection instruments that were used for the research.

5.10 Data Analysis

This section highlighted on the analysis of both quantitative and qualitative data. Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS) software was used to undertake Exploratory and Amos Software was used to conduct Confirmatory Factor Analysis and Structural Equation Modelling. Qualitative data on the other hand was subjected to Thematic Analysis manually. The subsections below provide detailed explanations.

5.10.1 Data Screening

In terms of the quantitative aspect of the study, primary data was gathered using a questionnaire that was developed by the researcher. The collected data was entered into the Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS) software which is a very popular software for quantitative analysis due to its precision (Banerjee and Roy, 2012). Data was cleaned and errors and missing values were removed. The data was checked to ensure consistency between the data gathered from the field and the one in the software. The researcher followed the recommendations by Pallant (2011) who postulated that data should be checked for errors, these errors found should either be deleted or corrected. Factor analysis which included Exploratory Factor analysis (EFA) and Confirmatory Factor Analysis (CFA) were undertaken as part of the process in achieving quantitative research objectives.

5.10.2 Factor Analysis (FA)

Factor analysis which can be categorised into exploratory and confirmatory is recognised as a very important component in quantitative studies (Tabachnick and Fidell, 2007; Pallant, 2011). Exploratory Factor Analysis conduct various analysis among variables and establishes groups of items (Bryman and Bell, 2011). Hair et al. (2010) and Tabachnick and Fidell (2013) further asserted that, it eradicates multicollinearity and enhances data quality via minimising large data sets into manageable sets. According to Pallant (2011), there are three processes that are requirements for Exploratory Factor Analysis. These are determining the suitability of data, extracting of factors, undertaking factor rotation and interpreting the results. Confirmatory Factor Analysis on the other hand is undertaken to determining inter-relationships among variables via testing of hypotheses established in a study (Tabachnick and Fidell, 2007; Pallant, 2011). Thus, a clear and simplistic distinction between these two-factor analysis is that, as the name suggests, exploratory factor analysis “explores” while confirmatory factor analysis “confirms”. Due to the relevance of factor analysis, the researcher conducted both Exploratory and Confirmatory Factor Analysis on a sample size of 310 and 344 respectively. The decision to use two separate data sets is based on the assertion by Brown (2015). The usage of the same data would not undergo rigour and would merely fit the Exploratory Factor Analysis (EFA) results directly to the Confirmatory Factor Analysis (CFA) (Hatcher and O'Rourke, 2013). Therefore, an Exploratory Factor Analysis (EFA) was conducted on an initial sample, and Confirmatory Factor Analysis (CFA) was performed on a subsequent, separate sample.

5.10.3 Structural Equation Modelling

As part of undertaking Confirmatory Factor Analysis, the quantitative data was analysed using Structural Equation Modelling (SEM) techniques with AMOS version 21. Structural Equation Modelling (SEM) is a robust comprehensive technique that is employed in multivariate data analysis in determining relationships among variables (Ullman, 2006). It is a potent analytical method that test hypothetical situations irrespective of whether functional, predictive or causal (Lomax and Schumacker, 2004) and ascertain the fitness of data (Byrne, 2013). There are three benefits that makes Structural Equation Modelling (SEM) more preferred to other analytical techniques. Structural Equation Modelling (SEM) can assess errors inherent in measurement (Byrne, 2013; Novikova et al., 2013), compute unobserved variables from observed variables and test model and evaluate data fitness (Novikova et al., 2013). Fabrigar et al. (2010) and Ramlall (2016) asserted that Structural Equation Modelling (SEM) is highly powerful compared to other forms of analysis such as Regression Analysis in terms of controlling for measurement errors. Regression Analysis assumes that the observed proxies constitute exact measures of the latent variables/constructs which may not be the case in practice due to measurement errors. Structural Equation Modelling (SEM) obviates such a problem by giving due consideration to latent variables. Alternatively, Regression Analysis assumes that the observable proxies are exact measures or perfect substitutes of the theoretical constructs/attributes, which may not hold true due to measurement errors (Ramlall, 2016). By using latent variables, SEM effectively controls for measurement errors so that more valid coefficients are obtained (Fabrigar et al., 2010). Scholars have developed fit indices that must be satisfied in conducting Structural Equation Modelling using covariance structure. Weston and Gore (2006) advocated for the testing of

Comparative Fit Index (CFI) and Tucker Lewis Index (TLI; non-normed fit index) with an acceptable value of 0.90 or above for a model to be acceptable as fit. Hu and Bentler (1999) and Schermelleh-Engel et al. (2003) also factored in the test of Standardised Root Mean Residual Value which should be 0.08 or less as part of obtaining model fit.

5.11 Thematic Analysis

The researcher employed Thematic Analysis to obtain qualitative findings. According to Scharp and Sanders (2019), this type of data analytical technique seeks to identify, analysis, interpret and report patterns. Thematic Analysis an analytical technique that provide findings in a robust and detailed manner (Elhajjar, 2023). Unlike other qualitative analytical techniques such as conversation analysis and interpretative phenomenological analysis, thematic analysis obtains richer insights from data in a more flexible manner (Braun and Clarke, 2006). Thematic Analytical technique also provides unanticipated details (King, 2004; Braun and Clarke, 2006). Another benefit of Thematic Analysis is that it is a well-structured manner means of analysing data and which leads to the development of a more clarified and organised final report (King, 2004). According to Braun and Clarke (2019), there is the need for researchers to pose questions regarding the composition of a theme. To meet the qualitative objectives of this study, the researcher followed the six processes outlined by Braun and Clarke (2020) in conducting Thematic Analysis. The first step was familiarising with the data. This entailed persistently listening to audio recordings and transcribing and reading transcripts to obtain meanings and patterns. The second step is generating codes for the collected data. Due to the anonymity and confidentiality of the research, the respondents who were 15 were assigned codes. The coding process required the researcher to attach labels which were BAP1, BAP2, BAP3, BAP4, BAP5, BAP6, BAP7, BAP8, BAP9, BAP10, BAP11, BAP12, BAP 13, BAP14 and BAP15.

The next step entailed defining and providing names for themes. This was followed by developing themes from the data set. The fifth stage was the review of theme generated. The final stage was to locate examples or extracts which formed evidence related to the study. The likely themes were also identified. At this stage the researcher thoroughly examined the data to identify patterns among the responses in the transcripts. This process aided the researcher to identify themes that were most likely to suit the research question and the entire study. The next stage finalised on the identified themes. The researcher then concluded on the occurring opinions that were identified within the data set after continuous reading. The next stage reviewed the themes. The review ensured that the themes were clear. Themes that did not have enough evidence to support them were dropped. Themes that had commonalities were also merged as stipulated by Braun and Clarke (2020). The next step was providing summary of each theme and providing a theme name. The researcher at this stage, concluded on the specific names assigned to each theme and ensured that, the themes were a good fit for the data set. The final stage was writing the report entailed providing analytical narrative and clear data extracts. At this stage, the researcher developed the analysis and provided in-depth information about the themes that were initially identified and provided in-depth narratives to reflect the content of the data set. Extracts from the transcripts were provided to support the themes that were developed.

Thematic Analysis was conducted manually. The usage of software packages such as Nvivo,

ATLAS.ti, MAXQDA has been recognised as a fast and simpler means of analysing qualitative data (Morison and Moir, 1998; Richards and Richards, 1994). However, the application of manual qualitative data analysis has some advantages over software packages. Manual data analysis provides greater flexibility in handling, managing and providing results unlike software packages. Researchers have questioned the handling of large data sets by software packages. The usage of software packages limits the richness and in-depth analysis and perspectives of qualitative data but rather provides more volume and less depth. Thus, software packages are regarded as quantifying qualitative data (Seidel, 1991) and create a distance between the researcher and the research (Baarry, 1998; Hinchliffe, Crang, Reimer and Hudson, 1997).

The application software packages to undertake qualitative data analysis requires the structuring of data that produces rigid and inflexible outputs (John and Johnson, 2000). A situation which Holbrook and Butcher (1996) referred to as ‘straight jacket’. The usage of software packages can therefore minimise the creativity in undertaking analysis due to its rigidity (Welsh, 2002). Unlike manual data analysis, John and Johnson (2000) postulated that, qualitative software packages can restrict the researcher’s ability to design data collection instruments that suit the study. Researchers might therefore develop questions that suit software packages and not necessarily based on answering research questions. The researcher therefore employed manual thematic analysis to generate responses that answers the research question. The study also adopted the manual thematic analysis because of its flexibility. This was because the study adopted a mixed methodological approach which resulted in the generation of unanticipated data.

5.12 Data Integration

Data integration is defined as a carefully planned endeavour that provides a conduit for connecting, combing, and merging data from qualitative and quantitative methods to generate findings (Creswell and Clark, 2018). Scholars have identified that, integrating data provide highest quality and robustness in research rather solely relying on either qualitative or quantitative approach (Bazeley, 2018; Creswell and Clark, 2018; Fetters et al., 2013; Fetters and Freshwater, 2015). Researchers can apply three basic types of integration which include exploratory sequential, explanatory sequential and convergent designs (Fetters et al., 2013). Researchers who use exploratory sequential design, in the first place, gather and analyse qualitative data. The findings from the analysis of the qualitative data serves as the basis for the collection and analysis of quantitative data (Onwuegbuzie et al., 2010; Creswell and Clark, 2018). In most of the mixed method studies, the researcher obtains qualitative data for the investigation into a phenomenon. After the qualitative study has established the results, quantitative study is adopted to enable generalisation (that is, exploratory sequential design) (Creswell and Clark, 2018). The use of an explanatory sequential design involves the collection and analysis of quantitative data, with the results informing the collection and analysis of qualitative data (Ivankova et al., 2006; Creswell and Clark, 2018). Unlike the two previously mentioned approaches, researchers who employ convergent design which is also referred to as concurrent design, utilises both qualitative and quantitative data collection methods to obtain and analyse quantitative and qualitative data simultaneously (Creswell and Clark, 2018; Fetters et al., 2013). Integration occurs after the collection of both qualitative and quantitative data distinctly and then merged (Fetters et al., 2013). The study adopted the explanatory sequential design. Quantitative data was initially collected, and the results informed the collection and analysis of

qualitative data. Explanatory sequential design was ideal for the study due to initial quantitative objectives that sought explanation through the development of qualitative objectives.

5.13 Ethical Consideration

Malhotra and Birks (2006) contended that, ethics deserves an attention due to its significance in an entire study. Ethics provides an assurance that makes participants or respondents provide genuine responses freely without tailoring their opinions on a phenomenon to reflect socially acceptable requirements or shelve their actual perspectives (Podsakoff et al., 2003). The study sought and received the approval from the Ethics Committee of University of the West of Scotland before data was collected. The researcher also adhered to ethical principles outlined by Pietilä et al. (2020). Pietilä et al. (2020) advocated that studies should adhere to autonomy, beneficence and non-maleficence and justice ethical principles.

The principle of autonomy is the ability of individuals to freely make decisions without any external influences (Beauchamp and Childress, 2013). Pietilä et al. (2020) asserted that, obtaining the consent of respondents is respecting the right of an individual to either engage in a study or not. Beauchamp and Childress (2013) further asserted that, the respondents should also be well-informed about the study. Based on that, the researcher allowed respondents to freely take decisions to participate in the research and informed the participants about the aim and objectives of the research and the methodologies employed as well. The researcher also assured the respondents about the confidentiality of the data and the identities of the respondents were not disclosed as a way of ensuring confidentiality which was consistent with Narteh (2013) and Pietilä et al (2020). The researcher did not only verbally seek the consent of participants but also filled a written consent form without any influence. Consistent with Emanuel et al. (2008), the respondents were also made aware of their right to withdraw from the study at any point in time.

The next principles discussed were beneficence and non-maleficence principles. Beneficence provides an ethical duty to the researcher to ensure that a study has maximum likely benefits whereas non-maleficence ethically charges researchers to ensure that, studies have minimum detrimental impacts (Beauchamp and Childress, 2013; Pietilä et al., 2020). To attain this, the researcher did not have topics or engage in conduct that will bring psychological trauma to the respondents but rather explained that the research was conducted to benefit not only respondents but the society as well. The next ethical principle is justice. Justice is the provision of fair and equal treatment for participants in a study (Beauchamp and Childress, 2013). Rawls (1971) advocated that, the two aspects of fairness are liberty and equality. Rawls (1971) further explained that liberty means the provision of same rights for all respondents and equality means providing each member selected an opportunity to partake. The respondents were treated fairly and equally irrespective of position or social status.

CHAPTER SIX

QUANTITATIVE DATA ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

6.0 Introduction

This study focused on brand attitude, perceived value, and purchase intention in the automobile industry in Ghana for new product category. This chapter revealed the results that were generated after collecting and analysing quantitative data. The various quantitative techniques employed were Exploratory Factor Analysis and Confirmatory Factor Analysis using structural Equation Modelling.

6.1 The Demographic Profile of Respondents

This section presented the demographic details of the quantitative aspect based on 344 respondents used to undertake Confirmatory Factor Analysis. The results were highlighted in the table below.

Table 6.1: Descriptive Statistics: Demographic Profile of Respondents

Profile of Respondents 1		Freq.	%
Gender	Male	212	61.6
	Female	132	38.4
Age	18-27	101	29.4
	28-37	124	36.0
	38-47	81	23.5
	48-57	32	9.3
	58 and +	6	1.7
Educational Level	Senior High School	195	56.7
	Diploma	43	12.5
	Degree	72	20.9
	Post-Graduate	34	9.9
Position	Owners	10	2.9
	Managers	41	11.9
	Supervisors	55	16.0
	Operatives	238	69.2
Experience	1-3 Years	160	46.5
	4-6 Years	118	34.3

	7-9 Years	36	10.5
	10 and +	30	8.7
Firm Category	Car Rentals	183	53.2
	Travel and Tours	101	29.4
	Tour Operating Agencies	60	17.4

Source: Field Data, 2022

The demographic data was based on 344 respondents used to undertake Confirmatory Factor Analysis. In terms of gender, there was 212 males representing 61.6 % and 132 females representing 38.4%. There were 101 respondents indicating 29.4% who were aged between 18-27 years. The statistics further revealed that, there were 124 respondents between the ages of 28-37 years representing 36.0%. Respondents aged between 38-47 were 81 representing 23.5%. There were also 32 respondents aged 48-57 constituting 9.3%. Respondents who were 58 and over were 6 indicating 1.7%. In terms of education, 195 respondents constituting 56.7% were Senior High School graduates. 43 of the respondents representing 12.5% were Diploma holders. The number of Degree graduates was 72 indicating 20.9% of the respondents. Post-Graduate graduates were 34 in number constituting 9.9%. Owners of firms sampled were 10 representing 2.9%. 41 of the respondents representing 11.9% were managers. The data also indicated that, 55 of the respondents indicating 16.0% were supervisors and 238 workers representing 69.2 %. With regards to experience within the automobile industry, 160 of the respondents had experienced between 1-3 years representing 48.5% of the respondents. A total of 118 of the respondents constituting 34.3% had 4-6 years of experience. The statistics also indicated that, 36 of the respondents indicating 10.5% had experience between 7-9 years. Respondents who had experience of 10 years and above were 30 representing 8.7%. Within firm category sampled for the study, Car Rentals firms had 183 respondents accounting for 53.2%. There was 101 respondents of the Travel and Tours firms constituting 29.4% respondents. The statistics also revealed that, Tour Operating Agencies had 60 respondents representing 17.4% respondents.

6.2 Automobile Brands Preferences of Respondents

The study sought to identify the brand preferences for locally assembled and imported vehicle brands in new product category. In addition to that, the researcher sought to identify the specific automobile vehicle brands whether locally assembled or imported were preferred by the respondents.

The table below provided details of the brand preferences of automobiles by the respondents.

Table 6.2: Descriptive Statistics: Automobile Brands Preferences of Respondents

Automobile Brand Preferences		Freq.	%
Brand Preference of Vehicles	Locally Assembled	185	53.8
	Imported	159	46.2
Specific Brand Preference of Vehicles	Toyota (LA)	65	18.9
	Toyota (I)	59	17.2
Locally Assembled (LA) Imported (I)	Kantanka (LA)	48	14
	Nissan (LA)	35	10.2
	Nissan (I)	33	9.6
	Volkswagen (LA)	14	4.1
	Volkswagen (I)	11	3.2
	Peugeot (LA)	10	2.9
	Peugeot (I)	8	2.3
	Suzuki (LA)	9	2.6
	Suzuki (I)	6	1.7
	Sinotruk (LA)	4	1.2
	Sinotruk (I)	3	0.9
	Other Imported	39	11.3

Source: Field Data, 2022

In terms of brand preference of vehicles, the statistics indicated that 185 of the respondents representing 53.8% preferred Locally Assembled Vehicle Brands to Imported Vehicle Brands. On the other hand, 159 of the respondents constituting 46.2% preferred Imported Vehicle Brands to Locally Assembled Vehicle Brands. In terms of the specific vehicle brand preference, the data indicated that, 65 respondents representing 18.9% preferred Toyota Vehicle Brands Assembled in Ghana. Other respondents who were 59 in number indicating 17.2% also preferred Imported Toyota Brands. This was followed by 48 respondents accounting for 14.0% who preferred Kantanka Vehicle Brands Assembled in Ghana. 35 of the respondents indicating 10.2% preferred Nissan Brands Assembled Locally in Ghana to 33 of the respondents indicating 9.6% for Imported Nissan Brands. The data further indicated that, 14 of the respondents accounting for 4.1% preferred Locally Assembled Volkswagen Brands to 11 respondents who had preference for Imported Volkswagen Vehicle Brands representing 3.2%. 10 of the respondents representing 2.9% preferred Locally Assembled Peugeot Brands compared to 8 respondents representing 2.3% who had preference for Imported Peugeot Brands. The statistics further showed that, 9 of the respondents indicating 2.6% preferred Suzuki Locally Assembled Brands as compared to 6 of the respondents representing 1.7% of Imported Suzuki Brands. 4 of the respondents indicating 1.2 % of the sample size preferred Locally Assembled Sinotruk Brands compared to 3

respondents representing 0.9 who had preference for Imported Sinotruk Brands. The statistics also revealed that 39 of the respondents indicating 11.3% had preference for other Imported Brands of Vehicles.

6.3 Exploratory Factor Analysis (EFA)

Exploratory Factor Analysis was employed due to its ability to reduce data by ensuring the attainment of more manageable and accurate data before undertaking further empirical analysis (Reio and Shuck, 2015). This aided the redesign of the questionnaire for further data collection and the conduct of Confirmatory Factor Analysis. Exploratory Factor Analysis (EFA) was conducted on a sample size of 310. The number supported the assertion by Tabachnick and Fidell (2007) and Field (2009) that, a sample size of at least 300 is needed to conduct Exploratory Factor Analysis (EFA). Exploratory Factor Analysis was undertaken to reduce the number of scales (questions) that were deemed as not fit for undertaking the next stage of analysis (Watson, 2017).

Before the conduct of Exploratory Factor Analysis (EFA), a Kaiser–Meyer–Olkin (KMO) which measures the adequacy of a sample (Kaiser, 1974) and Bartlett’s Test which is conducted to determine the factorability of the data were undertaken. In order for factor analysis to be conducted to achieve data reduction, the value of the test should be significant (Bartlett, 1954). According to Kaiser (1974), the required value after conducting KMO and Bartlett’s Test should be 0.5 or above. The KMO Measure was 0.946. The Bartlett’s Test of Sphericity should have a significant value of not more than 0.05. The test result was significant with a value of 0.000. This is consistent with Bartlett (1954). These tests were conducted in order to determine suitability of data for Exploratory Factor Analysis (EFA) (Howard, 2016). The table below showed the results.

Table 6. 3: KMO and Bartlett’s Test

KMO and Bartlett's Test

Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin Measure of Sampling Adequacy				.946
Bartlett's Test of Sphericity	Approx. Chi-Square			6530.669
	Df			378
	Sig.			0.000

Source: Field Data, 2022

Principal Components, a method of Factor Analysis: Extraction was used to undertake data reduction in Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS) based on the responses of 28 scales with 3 variables. These variables were Brand Attitude, Perceived Value with 3 constructs (Perceived Quality, Perceived Price and Social Value) and Purchase Intention. Items for Brand Attitude were AT1, AT2, AT3, AT4, AT5, AT6, and AT7. In terms of Perceived value, the construct Perceived Quality had PQ1, PQ2, PQ3, PQ4, PQ5 and PQ6 as items (questions).

Perceived Price as a construct was represented by PP1, PP2, PP3, and PP4 as items. Social Value had SV1, SV2, SV3, SV4, SV5 and SV6 as items. Purchase Intention also had PI1, PI2, PI3, PI4 and PI5 as items. As part of the process of conducting Factor Analysis, Eigen Values were greater than 1. Varimax Rotation was also conducted and smaller coefficients with absolute value less than 0.5 were suppressed. These requirements are consistent with Kamri and Radam (2013) whose procedure to conducting factor analysis prescribe the elimination of smaller coefficients, that is coefficient less than 0.5 in order to have accurate scales (questions) that will be used for further data collection and analysis. As part of the process of conducting factor analysis, a rotated component matrix was selected in Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS) in order to obtain outputs. Rotated Component Matrix provided a table that highlighted the various scales (questions) that survived based on values greater than 0.5.

The table below showed the results of the Exploratory Factor Analysis after conducting Rotated Component Matrix

Table 6. 4: Rotated Component Matrix

	Rotated Component Matrix ^a				
	Component				
	1	2	3	4	5
AT5- This vehicle brand is attractive	.771				
AT4- This vehicle brand is good	.737				
AT1-Information about this vehicle brand is appealing	.721				
AT6- This vehicle brand is likable	.697				
AT2-This vehicle brand brings joy	.681				
AT7- This vehicle brand is favourable	.659				
AT3- This vehicle brand is loveable	.616				
SV3- This vehicle brand has good performance in relation to the price		.766			
SV2- This vehicle brand creates good perception to others		.745			
SV4- This vehicle brand has good approval by others		.728			
SV6- This vehicle brand is considered reputable by others		.664			
SV5- This vehicle brand creates good social image in the society		.587			
SV1- This vehicle brand creates good impression to others		.570			
P15- I am likely to recommend this vehicle brand for the firm			.769		
PI3- I want this vehicle brand to be considered for purchase by the firm			.728		
PI4- I definitely want this vehicle brand purchased for the firm			.715		
PI2- I will be interested to get this vehicle brand purchased for the firm			.702		
PI1-There is information about this vehicle brand			.665		
PP1-This vehicle brand is reasonably priced				.845	
PP2- This vehicle brand offers value for money				.841	
PP3- This vehicle brand has good performance in relation to the price				.793	
PP4- This vehicle brand is economical				.761	
PQ3- This vehicle brand has accepted standard					.764

PQ4- This vehicle brand functions well					.745
PQ6- This vehicle brand has excellent features					.637
PQ5- This vehicle brand lasts longer					.621
Eigenvalues	13.439	2.106	1.661	1.173	1.038
% of Variance	47.997	7.522	5.934	4.191	3.706
Cumulative %	47.997	55.519	61.453	65.644	69.350

Source: Field Data, 2022

After conducting Exploratory Factor Analysis, two items from Perceived Quality, which were PQ1 and PQ2, dropped when a Rotated Component Analysis was conducted, and the items reduced from 28 to 26. The remaining items had values greater than 0.5 and fell within the right components. These scales were deemed fit for the next stage of the analysis which was Confirmatory Factor Analysis. The Cronbach Alpha Test was also conducted to test the reliability of the scales of Brand Attitude, Perceived Value and Purchase Intention after conducting Principal Component Analysis.

The table below showed the results:

Table 6. 5: Cronbach Alpha Test

Variable	Loadings	Cronbach's Alpha	Corrected Item-Total Correlation	Cronbach's Alpha if Item Deleted
AT5-This vehicle brand is attractive	.771	.901	.777	.878
AT4-This vehicle brand is good	.737		.753	.881
AT1-Information about this vehicle brand is appealing	.721		.690	.888
AT6-This vehicle brand is attractive	.697		.740	.883
AT2-This vehicle brand brings joy	.681		.720	.885
AT7-This vehicle brand is favourable	.659		.614	.896
AT3-This vehicle brand is loveable	.616		.669	.891
SV3- This vehicle brand makes one feel accepted in the society	.766	.927	.843	.906
SV2- This vehicle brand creates good perception to others	.745		.853	.905
SV4- This vehicle brand has good approval by others	.728		.836	.907
SV6-This vehicle brand is considered reputable by others	.664		.764	.917
SV5- This vehicle brand creates good social image in the society	.587		.693	.926
SV1- This vehicle brand creates good impression to others	.570		.742	.920
PI5- I am likely to recommend this vehicle brand for the firm	.769	.904	.806	.872
PI3- I want this vehicle brand to be considered for purchase by the firm	.728		.790	.877
PI4- I definitely want this vehicle brand purchased for the firm	.715		.781	.878
PI2- I will be interested to get this vehicle brand purchased for the firm	.702		.702	.896
PI1- There is information about this vehicle brand	.665		.731	.889

PP1-This vehicle brand is reasonably priced	.845	.906	.774	.886
PP2- This vehicle brand offers value for money	.841		.813	.870
PP3- This vehicle brand has good performance in relation to the price	.793		.815	.871
PP4-This vehicle brand is economical	.761		.760	.889
PQ3- This vehicle brand has accepted standard	.764	.764	.623	.677
PQ4- This vehicle brand functions well	.745		.631	.676
PQ6- This vehicle brand has excellent features	.637		.592	.698
PQ5- This vehicle brand lasts longer	.621		.455	.787

Field Data, 2022

In order to attain reliability, Cronbach (1957) asserted that items should meet the threshold of 0.70 or above. Reliability is defined as the degree to which measurement duplicates outcomes that are consistent if the procedural measurement steps are repeated (Malhotra and Birks, 2006). The reliability revealed the extent to which a data collection instrument such as a questionnaire is free from random error (Pallant, 2011). This provided an indication of the extent to which the researcher can rely on the data collected. The items that were retained after Principal Component Analysis on the various factors were regarded as reliable because the thresholds were above 0.70. Brand Attitude had a Cronbach Alpha of 0.901 and Social Value was 0.927. Perceived Price had a value of 0.907, Perceived Quality was 0.764 and .906 was the value for Purchase Intention.

6.4 Confirmatory Factor Analysis (CFA)

The data collection instrument was re-structured and the two items (questions) that did not undergo Exploratory Factor Analysis successfully were eliminated. A new data set of 344 respondents was used to undertake Confirmatory Factor Analysis. This is consistent with Blunch (2012) and Byrne (2013) who asserted that, Confirmatory Factor Analysis (CFA) should be used to validate data using separate data. One key advantage of Confirmatory Factor Analysis (CFA) is the tendency to determine multiple interrelated dependence relationships (Hair et al. 2010; Bagozzi and Yi, 2012). Various tests which included direct relationships, mediator, multi-group analysis and mediated-moderated relationships were conducted. Confirmatory Factor Analysis was used to validate the various items (questions) (Jennifer and Jung, 2023). To conduct Confirmatory Factor Analysis using Structural Equation Modelling, another sample size of 344 was collected. Structural Equation Modelling was chosen over other analytical techniques such as Regression because of its ability to significantly reduce errors and variances in measuring relationships among variables (Nunkoo and Ramkissoon, 2012).

6.4.1 Measurement Model

Measurement Model was the first stage of Confirmatory Factor Analysis. A number of fit indexes were used to assess how well the data collected fit the measurement model. These included Root Mean Squared Error of Approximation ($RMSEA \leq 0.08$), Goodness of Fit Index

(GFI \geq 0.90), Normed Fit Index (NFI \geq 0.90) and Comparative Fit Index (CFI \geq 0.90) (Hu and Bentler, 1999; Bagozzi and Yi, 2012; Hair et al., 2014). These fit indices were employed to assess the strength and acceptability of the construct measurements. The selection of these fit indices was based on the classification proposed by Kline (2005) and Byrne (2013) as being the most accepted criteria in social sciences in ensuring data accuracy and reducing errors. The Original Model did not meet the acceptable values of the fit indices. The acceptable values were obtained after deletion of some items.

The table below highlighted the results:

Table 6. 6: Improvement in Fit of Measurement Model

Phase	Modification	Fit		Indices			
		GFI	RMSEA	NFI	CFI	AGFI	χ^2/df
I	Original Model	0.842	0.074	0.806	0.863	0.812	2.875
II	Deleted:	0.966	0.044	0.962	0.984	0.939	1.650

Source: Field Data, 2022

The table above indicated the fit indices about after deleting some items. These results were consistent with Hu and Bentler (1999); Bagozzi and Li (2012) and Hair et al. (2014) for model fit who mentioned that the acceptable criteria to ensure robustness and accuracy of results should meet certain thresholds. These scholars prescribed Root Mean Squared Error of Approximation ($RMSEA \leq 0.08$) and Root Mean Squared Error of Approximation ($RMSEA = 0.44$) was obtained. In addition to this, Goodness of Fit Index should be ($GFI \geq 0.90$) and Goodness of Fit Index ($GFI = 0.966$) was obtained. Normed Fit Index ($NFI \geq 0.90$) was required, and the result indicated Normed Fit Index ($NFI = 0.962$). In addition, scholars recommended Comparative Fit Index ($CFI \geq 0.90$) and Comparative Fit Index ($CFI = 0.984$) was obtained. The figure below showed the measurement model after deletions in order to obtain figures that were used to undertake the structural model.

Figure 6. 1: Measurement Model After Deletion

Source: Field Data, 2022

After deletion, Brand Attitude (ATT) had two items, Perceived Value with three constructs had two items for Perceived Quality (PQQ), two items for perceived Price (PPP) and three items for (SVV) for Social Value. Purchase Intention (PII) also had three retained items. The diagram below shows the final measurement model after deletion to meet fit indices.

6.4.1.1 Validity and Reliability Tests

The table below provided details of the validity and reliability tests of the various constructs used for the study.

6.4.1.1.1 Validity Test

The correlation matrix below explained the validity test.

Table 6. 7: Validity Test

	ATT	PQQ	PPP	SVV	PII
ATT	0.785				
PQQ	0.159	0.824			
PPP	0.669	0.112	0.778		
SVV	0.573	0.217	0.475	0.838	
PII	0.456	0.257	0.493	0.399	0.809

Source: Field Data, 2022

Convergent validity was conducted. According to convergent validity determines the extent to variables or construct assemble to explain variance (Hair et al., 2021). One of the key methods of undertaking convergent validity is the use of Average Variance Extracted (AVE) which focus on the commonality of construct which should be above 0.5 or above (Hair et al., 2021). The results indicated that there were no validity concerns. Thus, there were no error concerns. The data was deemed to be valid. Brand Attitude, the independent variable was represented by ATT with AVE of 0.785, Perceived Value had three constructs. These included Perceived Quality (PQQ) had AVE 0.824, Perceived Price (PPP) with AVE OF 0.778 and Social Value (SVV) had AVE of 0.838. Purchase Intention, the dependent variable was represented by PII had an AVE OF 0.809.

6.4.1.1.2 Reliability of Final Model

The table below provided details of the test results of the final model.

Table 6. 8: Reliability Test

	Items	Standardised Loadings	CR	AVE	Cronbach α
ATT	AT5	0.85	0.761	0.616	0.756
	AT6	0.72			
PQQ	PQ2	0.83	0.809	0.68	0.809
	PQ3	0.82			
PPP	PP1	0.74	0.754	0.605	0.752
	PP4	0.81			
SVV	SV2	0.81	0.876	0.703	0.874
	SV3	0.89			
	SV4	0.81			
PII	PI2	0.67	0.849	0.655	0.838
	PI3	0.90			
	PI4	0.84			

Source: Field Data, 2022

The results were deemed reliable because the figures fell within acceptable levels as stipulated by Fornell and Larcker (1981) and Vandebosch (1996) recommendations of Cronbach (1951) alphas > .70, Average Variance Extracted > .50, composite reliability > .70). The factor loadings between 0.67 and 0.90 indicated good convergent validity. The results of the correlations, validity and reliability showed that the model adequately fits the data of the study.

6.4.2 Confirmatory Factor Analysis without Mediator

The figure below showed the structural model that tested the relationship between Brand Attitude and Purchase Intention.

Figure 6. 2: Structural Model: Testing Independent and Dependent Relationship

This model tested the direct relationship between Brand Attitude (ATT) and Purchase Intention (PII). The table below showed the fit indices that were obtained.

Table 6. 9: Fit Indices for Final Measurement Model

Relationship	Fit Indices					
	GFI	RMSEA	NFI	CFI	AGFI	χ^2/df
ATT_PII	0.994	0.017	0.993	0.999	0.978	1.244

Source: Field Data, 2022

The fit indices are consistent with recommendations by Hu and Bentler (1999); Bagozzi and Li (2012) and Hair et al. (2014) for model fit.

6.4.2.1 Significance Testing Results

The table below presented the results of the direct relationship between Brand Attitude and Purchase Intention

Table 6. 10: Significance Results

Hypothesis	Relationship	β Estimate	SE	T-Value	P-Value	Outcome
<i>Hypothesis: Brand Attitude has a Positive Relationship with Purchase Intention</i>	ATT--> PII	0.46	0.069	6.175	***	Supported

Source: Field Data, 2022

Research hypothesis is an unambiguous statement that is tested in research to determine results (Kalaian and Kasim, 2008). The table above showed the direct relationship between brand attitude and purchase intention within the automobile industry. In order for a relationship to be supported, a construct or variable should have a t-value ≥ 1.96 and p-value ≤ 0.05 . A supported outcome meant the hypothesis failed to be rejected (accepted). The results indicated that, brand attitude had an impact on purchase intention within the automobile industry since the t-value is ≥ 1.96 and the P-value shows a significant relationship. The outcome is therefore supported.

6.4.3 Confirmatory Factor Analysis with Mediator

A mediator served as an intermediary link between two variables (Woody, 2011). In this study, the researcher tested the relationship between brand attitude and purchase intention within the automobile industry with perceived value as the mediator. The earlier result proved that brand attitude had an impact on purchase intention within the automobile industry. Further testing was conducted to determine if perceived value mediated the relationship between brand attitude and purchase intention. The researcher therefore ascertained the impact of perceived value on brand attitude and perceived value. The figure below showed the relationships between the three variables, Brand Attitude, Perceived Value and Purchase Intention used in the study.

Figure 6. 3: Structural Model: Testing Independent, Dependent and Mediating Variable Relationships

Brand Attitude (ATT) is the independent variable, Purchase Intention (PII) is the dependent variable. The mediating variable where Perceived Value was represented by three constructs which were Perceived Quality (PQQ), Perceived Price (PPP) and Social Value (SVV).

The study hypothesised that, there is a positive relationship between Brand Attitude and Purchase Intention mediated by Perceived Value.

The results of the fit indices were consistent with Hu and Bentler (1999); Bagozzi and Li (2012) and Hair et al. (2014) for model fit.

The table below showed the fit indices that were obtained.

Table 6. 11: Model Fit Indices

Relationship	Fit Indices					
	GFI	RMSEA	NFI	CFI	AGFI	χ^2/df
ATT_PV_PII	0.969	0.035	0.962	0.989	0.949	1.410

Source: Field Data, 2022

6.4.3.1 Structural Model Assessment Results

The researcher applied the approach stipulated by Preacher and Hayes (2004) in obtaining the indirect effects required for determining mediation results. The table below presented the results for the Structural Model Assessment.

Table 6. 12: Structural Model Assessment Results

	Direct Without Mediator		Direct With Mediator		Indirect Effect		Outcome
	β Estimate	P-Value	β Estimate	P-Value	β Estimate	P-Value	
ATT--PV—PII	0.46	***	0.37	0.751	0.41	***	Full Mediation

Source: Field Data, 2022

The results indicated a significant indirect effect of Perceived Value (Perceived Price, Perceived Costs and Social Value). Thus, Perceived Value (Perceived Price, Perceived Costs and Social Value) fully mediated the relationship between Brand Attitude and Purchase Intention. Perceived Value therefore played a significant role in ensuring that brand attitude affect purchase intention in the study.

6.4.3.2 Relationships Among Variables and Constructs

These results examined the relationships among the various variables used for the study which included Brand Attitude (ATT), Perceived Value represented by Social Value (SVV), Perceived Price (PPP) and Perceived Quality (PQQ) as well as Purchase Intention (PI).

The table below indicated the relationships among the variables and constructs used in the study.

Table 6. 13: Structural Model Assessment Results

			β Estimate	S.E.	t-Value	Sig.	Outcome
ATT	--->	SVV	0.63	0.073	8.679	***	Supported
ATT	--->	PPP	0.684	0.082	8.37	***	Supported
ATT	--->	PQQ	0.473	0.099	4.758	***	Supported
SVV	--->	PII	0.136	0.067	2.015	0.044	Supported
PPP	--->	PII	0.31	0.093	3.331	***	Supported
PQQ	--->	PII	0.232	0.09	2.582	0.01	Supported
ATT	--->	PII	0.037	0.117	0.317	0.751	Not Supported

Source: Field Data, 2022

The table above indicated that Brand Attitude (ATT) had a positive and significant relationship with Social Value (SVV) ($\beta= 0.63$, t-value= 8.679). The outcome was supported which indicated that, the hypothesis was not rejected. Brand Attitude also had a positive and significant relationship with Perceived Price (PPP) ($\beta=0.684$, t-value= 8.37). The relationship between Brand Attitude (ATT) and Perceived Quality (PQQ) was also positive and significant with ($\beta=0.473$, t-value=4.758). The outcome was supported which indicated that, the hypothesis was not rejected. Social Value (SVV) also had a positive and significant relationship with Purchase Intention (PII). The outcome was supported which indicated that, the hypothesis was not rejected. The relationship between Perceived Price (PPP) and Purchase Intention (PII) was positive and significant with ($\beta=0.31$, t-value=3.331). Perceived Quality (PQQ) had a positive and significant relationship with Purchase Intention (PII) ($\beta= 0.232$, t-value= 2.582). The outcome was supported which indicated that, the hypothesis was not rejected.

The relationship between Brand Attitude (ATT) and Purchase Intention (PII) was insignificant with ($\beta=0.037$, t-value=0.317). With the inclusion of Perceived Value constructs (Perceived Quality Perceived Price and Social Value) the outcome was not supported. These findings indicated that, perceived value constructs (Perceived Quality, Perceived Price and Social Value) played a critical role in the relationship between brand attitude and purchase intention within the automobile industry. This therefore supported the earlier finding that Perceived Value fully mediated the relationship between Brand Attitude and Purchase Intention.

6.4.4 Multi Group Analysis

The multi group analysis was conducted to assess the role of locally assembled vehicle brands and imported vehicle brands in the study. According to Gaskin and Lim (2018), the multi group plugin is used to conduct causal relationships and multiple chi-square differences tests to ascertain whether path-wise differences exist between groups.

The research hypothesised that, brand attitude and purchase intention have a stronger positive relationship with locally assembled vehicle brands compared to imported vehicle brands.

Plugin for multi group analysis was used to compare data for locally assembled and imported vehicle brands in Amos 24 as part of Structural Equation Modelling.

6.4.4.1 Global Test

The table below showed the results for the Global Test

Table 6. 14: Global Test Results

	X²	DF
Unconstrained	15.008	8
Constrained	18.121	9
Difference	3.113	1
P-Value	0.039	

Source: Field Data, 2022

The global test tends to indicate whether significance exist among the models that are being analysed. The test results indicated that, the p-value of the chi-square difference test was significant; the model differs across groups. There is therefore a difference between brand attitude and purchase intention towards locally assembled brand of vehicles and imported brand of vehicles. This is reflected in the P-Value of (0.039) which was an indication of significance. The finding was based on Gaskin and Lim (2018).

6.4.4.2 Local Test Results

The local test provided further information and revealed that locally assembled vehicle brands had a stronger relationship in terms of brand attitude and purchase intention than imported brands in the automobile industry. The table below presented the local test results.

Table 6. 15: Local Test Results

Path Name	Locally Assembled Beta	Imported Beta	Difference in Betas	P-Value for Difference	Interpretation
ATT→PII	0.514***	0.384**	0.130	0.039	The positive relationship between ATT and PII is stronger for Locally Assembled Vehicle Brands.

Source: Field Data, 2022

The table indicated that, in terms of the impact of Brand Attitude and Purchase Intention, there was a stronger positive relationship for Locally Assembled Vehicle Brands than Imported Vehicle Brands. This was demonstrated by a higher beta and significance of 0.514 (***) for Locally Assembled Vehicle Brands and a lower beta and significance of 0.384 (***) for Imported Vehicle Brands. The test also revealed beta difference of 0.130 and a P-value of 0.039. The finding was based on Gaskin and Lim (2018).

6.4.5 Moderated Mediation (MyModMed) Relationship

This analysis is conducted when a mediating variable is introduced into a causal relationship with a moderator to determine its impact. According to Gaskin and Lim (2018), moderated mediation occurs in two different groups or same group with multiple indirect paths.

An earlier analysis indicated that Perceived Value fully mediated the relationship between Brand Attitude and Purchase Intention. A further analysis also indicated that, the positive relationship between Brand Attitude and Purchase Intention of Locally Assembled Vehicle Brands was stronger than Imported Vehicle Brands. The Moderated Mediated tested the impact of Perceived Value Constructs (Perceived Quality, Perceived Price, and Social Value) on the relationship between Brand Attitude and Purchase Intention between Locally Assembled Vehicle Brands and Imported Assembled Vehicle Brands. The test was conducted to determine whether there was a difference in perceived value of locally assembled vehicle brands and imported brands.

The study hypothesised that, there was a significant difference of perceived value in the relationship between brand attitude and the purchase intention of locally assembled vehicle brands compared to imported brands.

6.4.5.1 Perceived Value

The results of the impact of Perceived Value constructs (Perceived Quality, Perceived Price and Social Value) on the relationship between Brand Attitude, Perceived Value and Purchase Intention of Locally Assembled Vehicle Brands compared to Imported Vehicle Brands were explained below.

6.4.5.1.1 Perceived Quality, Moderated Mediation Relationship

Perceived Quality (PQQ) was introduced to determine whether differences exist in terms of the relationship between Brand Attitude, and Purchase Intention of Locally Assembled Vehicle Brands compared to Imported Vehicle Brands.

The table below indicated the results for the moderated mediation relationship of Perceived Quality.

Table 6. 16: Perceived Quality, Moderated Mediation Relationship

User-defined estimands: (Locally Assembled and Imported)

Parameter	Estimate	Lower	Upper	p-Value
(A x B)- (C x D)	0.112	-0.110	1.331	0.242

Source: Field Data, 2022

Perceived Quality did not have a significant relationship among the two variables which were Brand Attitude and Purchase Intention. Thus, Perceived Quality did not differ among the two groups (Locally Assembled and Imported Vehicle Brands). This therefore indicated that, no difference was found in terms of the Perception of Quality of Locally Assembled Vehicle Brands and Imported Brands. This is reflected in a P-Value of 0.242 which is greater than 0.05.

6.4.5.1.2 Perceived Price, Moderated Mediation Relationship

The table below indicated the results for the moderated mediation relationship of Perceived Price.

Table 6. 17: Perceived Price, Moderated Mediation Relationship

User-defined estimands: (Locally Assembled and Imported)

Parameter	Estimate	Lower	Upper	p-Value
(A x B)- (C x D)	0.225	-0.185	0.558	0.210

Source: Field Data: 2022

Perceived Price did not have a significant relationship among the two variables which were Brand Attitude and Purchase Intention. Thus, Perceived Quality did not differ among the two groups (Locally Assembled and Imported Vehicle Brands). This therefore indicated that, the Perception of Price of Locally Assembled Vehicle Brands and Imported Brands did not differ. This was reflected in a P-Value of 0.210 which was greater 0.05.

6.4.5.1.3 Social Value, Moderated Mediation Relationship

The table below indicated the results for the moderated mediation relationship of Social Value.

Table 6. 18: Social Value, Moderated Mediation Relationship

User-defined estimands: (Locally Assembled and Imported)

Parameter	Estimate	Lower	Upper	p-Value
(A x B)- (C x D)	-0.045	-0.315	0.138	0.576

Source: Field Data, 2022

The results revealed that, social value did not have a significant relationship among the two variables which are Brand Attitude and Purchase Intention. Thus, Perceived Quality did not differ among the two groups (Locally Assembled and Imported Vehicle Brands). This therefore indicated that, Social Value of Locally Assembled Vehicle Brands and Imported Brands did not differ. This was reflected in a P-Value of 0.576 which was > 0.05 . These results were therefore an indication that perceived value (quality, price and social value) did not differ among the two groups (locally assembled and imported automobile brands). The hypothesis that, *there was a significant difference of perceived value in the relationship between brand attitude and the purchase intention of locally assembled vehicle brands compared to imported brands* was therefore rejected.

The diagram below depicted and summarised the various quantitative tests:

Figure 6. 4: Summary of Quantitative Results

CHAPTER SEVEN

QUALITATIVE DATA ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

7.0 Introduction

This chapter highlighted on the analysis of qualitative data and the provided a presentation of the results. To analyse qualitative data, Thematic Analysis was employed to answer the research question. Thematic analysis was employed because it provides richer insights from data in a more flexible manner compared to other qualitative analytical techniques such as conversation analysis and interpretative phenomenological (Braun and Clarke, 2006). The qualitative chapter of the thesis analysed data from 15 interviewees who constituted the travel trade. These included vehicle rentals, travel and tours and tours operating agencies.

7.1 Thematic Analytical Process

The researcher employed Braun and Clarke (2020) process of analysing thematic data. These include data familiarisation, coding, ‘searching’ for themes, reviewing likely themes, identifying, and naming themes as well as writing the report. In applying Braun and Clarke (2020) thematic analytical process, data was familiarised through reading and re-reading of the transcripts, listening to audio-recordings, and making notes of observations. Thus, the recording for the data was listening to and transcribed. The next stage which was coding. The respondents were assigned various codes. The codes assigned to the interviewees were BAP1, BAP2, BAP3, BAP4, BAP5, BAP6, BAP7, BAP8, BAP9, BAP10, BAP11, BAP12, BAP 13, BAP14 and BAP15. These codes were assigned to the interviewees due to anonymity and confidentiality of the research. The likely themes were also identified. The next stage finalised on the identified themes. The next stage reviewed the themes. The review ensured that the themes were clear. The next step was providing summary of each theme and providing a theme name. The final stage which is writing the report entailed providing analytical narrative and clear data extracts. This section highlighted on the demographic profile of participants, attitude towards automobile vehicle brands, the role of perceived value in the automobile industry and provided reasons why there was a stronger attitude towards intention to purchase locally assembled vehicle brands than imported vehicles (A Stronger Preference for Locally Assembled Vehicle Brands).

7.2 Demographic Profile of Participants

The table below provided details of the 15 interviewees who participated in the qualitative data collection process.

Table 7. 1: Demographic Profile of Participants

Code:	Gender:	Age:	Position:	Experience:
BAP1	Male	38	Sales Manager	3 Years
BAP2	Male	45	Owner	8 Years
BAP3	Male	51	Owner	6 Years
BAP4	Male	31	Customer Service Manager	4 Years
BAP5	Male	38	Sales Manager	2 Years
BAP6	Male	39	Owner	10 Years
BAP7	Female	27	Procurement Manager	3 Years
BAP8	Male	29	Procurement Manager	4 Years
BAP9	Male	32	Financial Manager	6 Years
BAP10	Male	36	Chief Accountant	8 Years
BAP11	Male	32	Sales Manager	5 Years
BAP12	Female	33	Owner	9 Years
BAP13	Male	39	Sales Manager	6 Years
BAP14	Female	46	General Manager	12 Years
BAP15	Male	41	Marketing Manager	9 Years

Source: Field Data, 2022

The qualitative findings were discussed below.

7.3 Attitude towards Automobile Vehicle Brands

The quantitative aspect of the study revealed that, brand attitude had a positive relationship with purchase intention. The participants were of the view that, both locally assembled and imported automobile brands were valuable based on their knowledge and experiences of customers, their firms, and the automobile industry. Thus, although, perceived value matters in the automobile industry, both locally assembled and imported brands were perceived as valuable. The research probed further to compare attitude towards locally assembled vehicle brands and imported vehicle brands. The study identified a more positive attitude towards locally assembled vehicle brands than imported vehicle brands. The interviewees mentioned that locally assembled vehicle brands were more likable, attractive, and more favourable than imported vehicle brands.

7.3.1 Likability of Locally Assembled Vehicle Brands

The interviewees demonstrated more likability towards locally assembled vehicle brands than imported vehicle brands. The respondents liked automobile brands and indicated much preference for the Ghana assembled brands. They indicated their willingness to purchase the locally assembled brands since they perceived both locally assembled and imported brands as having the same level of value. Participant BAP3 mentioned that *“I mean, I like to have it made here. More of the companies should come in. I’m happy in the change in the way this whole car business is going. I like it, and I like the assembled ones here the more. That’s how I feel about it”*. This was an indication of an embracing posture towards the acceptance of local assembling in Ghana. This was based on previous quantitative finding which revealed that, perceived value attached to locally assembled brands were no different from imported vehicle brands and businesses indicated their readiness to embrace the inclusion of local assembling of vehicles. Another respondent BAP5 also stated, *“Ghana is a developing country, and we have a lot of resources, but we haven’t been able to, as it were, do a lot. I will like us to do more so if the cars can also be made in this country, for me, I like it and support the idea, we will get somewhere when we put in the effort”*. This was also a demonstration that, the likeness for locally assembled vehicles was not influenced by the perception of value since imported brands were also considered valuable. The likability was based on the benefits that the country will derive from it. *“So far, I know some countries are using the vehicles that are assembled or done there. So why not? These firms know what they are doing. It takes a lot to set up so they can’t just come in like that. I will go for the one here. Definitely”*- Respondent BAP12. This response was a clear indication that, the respondents did not expect to receive inferior value because the firms involved in assembling locally are noted to be industry players with established reputation and will not want to jeopardise it. Local assembling of vehicles generates likeness and value will not be compromised.

7.3.2 Attractiveness to Locally Assembled Vehicle Brands

The participants also felt more attracted to locally assembled vehicle brands than imported vehicle brands. Participant BAP2 mentioned that *“The vehicles being done in the country catch my attention; our customers ask about it also”*. The respondents found locally assembled vehicles attractive and were therefore interested and receptive to information that will aid in their growth and development. Respondent BAP14 also mentioned that *“The cars and the business around it look more attractive. We will have a lot to benefit from it”*. The respondents felt attracted to the locally assembled vehicle brands and were expectant of some benefits. “I follow the news. Last time, I heard there will be more coming in. The assembling plants are going on and all that. It will help rather than always importing”- Respondent BAP14. The response demonstrated that, due to attraction to locally assembled vehicle brands, information is being searched to ascertain the progress of it.

7.3.3 Favourability Towards Locally Assembled Vehicle Brands

The responses from the interview conducted also indicated that, the participants had a more favourable posture towards locally assembled vehicle brands than imported brands. Excerpts of the responses are stated below:

“All what we want is that the government should not just promise them that, oh we will do this and that and that’s all. Some of us are hoping that it will grow very big for us” - Respondent BAP6. The interviewees demonstrated the need to have government support to grow the local assembling market and not just rely on importation of finished automobile brands. Another Respondent BAP8 also mentioned that *“I will want to buy the vehicles if they are made here. Why not? I feel it’s a positive thing. We can also do it just like the rest. The imported cars are also okay. We should move ahead of that”*. The respondents also recognised the possibility of building automobiles in Ghana since there are successful examples across the globe. *“I will surely convince my colleagues that we go for it. Why import if we can find them here. It is the same quality that we will get”*- BAP13. Thus, the respondent therefore does not see the need to buy imported brands since the value attached to locally assembled ones were same.

7.4 The Role of Perceived Value in the Automobile Industry

The quantitative results also indicated that, perceived value fully mediated the relationship between brand attitude and purchase intention within the automobile industry. Thus, perceived value played a significant role within the automobile industry irrespective of it been locally assembled or imported automobile brands. The researcher therefore explored to ascertain the reasons why perceived value (perceived quality, perceived price and social value) played a critical role within the automobile industry.

7.4.1 Perceived Quality

Most of the respondents mentioned that perceived quality was a very important component that affected attitude towards automobile brands that they intent to purchase. Quality attributes such

as durability, conformance to specifications and customer requirements were mentioned. The respondents also mentioned that the performance of vehicles was also very important particularly the quality of vehicle engines. Below are some extracts that indicated that quality played a major role in the automobile industry.

Respondent BAP5 mentioned that *“We definitely need good cars because some of our customers travel to far places outside Accra. If we don’t buy cars that can last, we will be out of business. Some of the roads are rough and have potholes so if the car is not quality, we will have problems on the road.”* This response was clearly an indication that, the quality of vehicles in terms of durability was key towards the intention to purchase automobiles. The vehicles needed to engage in travel trade had to be strong to withstand frequent travels and bad road networks. The purchase of automobile vehicles was seen as a huge investment and as such the interviewees who constituted travel and trade perceived quality as automobiles with strong engines that can have a long-lasting lifetime. The travel trade which constituted vehicle rentals, travel and tours and tour operating agencies were interested in purchasing vehicles that can last longer and withstand the pressures of poor road networks in some parts of the country, Ghana.

In addition to that, the interviewees also defined quality from the perspective of vehicles that customers were interested in hiring or travelling in. Respondent BAP15 mentioned that *“So, when the customers tell us about how good some cars are we try to buy more of such ones. Those that they don’t like we don’t buy”*. Quality therefore played a very instrumental role in forming the intention to purchase new automobile vehicles. The interviewees were likely to purchase automobiles that have the capacity to last longer and were also preferred by customers that they serve.

7.4.2 Perceived Price

The perception of the cost of automobile vehicle was also a major influence that affected brand attitude and the purchase intention of automobile brands. Pricing determined if the customers will be in the position to buy the vehicle brands. In order to buy automobile brands, customers must have the purchasing power. The respondents mentioned that vehicle brands were purchased based on affordability which should be commensurate with the benefits that can be derived from their usage. Below were some of the extracts:

Participant BAP2 mentioned that *“With the price, it’s always not easy. You need to see the strength of the business before you try to buy. See...hmmm...it’s not easy, getting a loan to buy is not easy and you don’t always have ready cash. ... So, if we think that the prices that some of these car sellers are charging are too high, we try and get the ones that we can afford”*. This was an indication that, players in the travel and trade business were not only interested in the quality of automobile but in the price as well. Customers of car rentals, travel and tours and travel agencies (travel trade) tend to have interest in certain automobiles and this interest must translate to purchase intention and ultimately into purchase. But one obstacle that travel trade participants who were respondents must overcome is obtaining the necessary financial resources

which was difficult task. Affordability was therefore key consideration in the formation of purchase intention of buyers.

In addition, the travel trade business was expensive to operate. Some of the costs were rental of premises, utility payments, fuel, maintenance of premises and vehicles, insurances, road worthy and labour. Due to the cost burden on travel trade, there was the need for prudent financial management to generate profits. The interviewees were therefore very much concerned about prices of vehicles. Respondent BAP8 for example mentioned that *“Pricing is very key, you know, If the prices are high, we can’t do this business. Don’t forget that, once they are vehicles there are extra costs once you buy them. You need to do insurance, road worthy, pay for fuel and maintain it too. So, we go for automobiles that we can afford and the quality as well”*.

7.4.3 Social Value

Most the respondents were of the view that social value influenced their attitude and intention to buy vehicle brands. The interviewees (car rentals, travel and tours and tour operators) considered the social acceptability of vehicles. The participants paid attention to vehicles brands that will make customers feel accepted and/or appreciated within the society. Vehicle brand must conform to how friends, neighbours and the society perceive them.

Participant BAP4 mentioned that *“some of the customers when they come, they tell us that, their friends told them of how comfortable our cars are. So, they also want to experience the same service. Some also move with their families to tour certain areas so when they rent some of these cars, so they want a family sort of thing, something more spacious and accommodating”*. Family, friends, and acquaintances tend to influence customers of travel trade and the type of vehicles to hire for various reasons including tourism and leisure. The car rental, travel and tours and travel agencies in their quest to buy new vehicles also take into consideration the type of vehicles that meet the expectations of their customers.

Customers have also enjoyed vehicle hires and made recommendations to their partners to share similar positive experiences. Participant BAP12 stated that *“Partners for example play a role in choosing vehicles. It does matter. Once they travel in cars that they find valuable, they want their partners to also have such an experience you know. Some people also want to visit some places with their friends so when they are renting, they take that into consideration, yes, a car that their friends also want to ride in”*.

7.5 A Stronger Preference for Locally Assembled Vehicle Brands

Based on quantitative analysis, there was a stronger attitude towards intention to purchase locally assembled vehicle brands than imported vehicles. Thus, the respondents had more preference for locally assembled vehicle brands than imported vehicle brands. This part of the analysis provided reasons why there was a stronger attitude towards intention to purchase locally assembled

vehicle brands than imported vehicles. Although the results revealed that, perceived value was a key component in forming brand attitude and purchase intention in the automobile industry, there was no difference in the perception of value (quality, price and social) among locally assembled and imported new automobile brands. This was demonstrated below.

Both locally assembled vehicle brands and imported vehicle brands were identified to be of same quality. Participant BAP4 mentioned that *“We know that the companies that are here have international standards, their cars will be good just like anywhere”*. Another respondent also stated that: *“I don’t think that they will want to sacrifice their quality because they are doing the vehicles in Ghana”*- BAP7. In terms of social value, the interviewees regarded locally assembled brands and imported brands as socially accepted. We buy the cars so that customers will use them as well. *“Most of these customers look out for brands and some features that their people will be happy with”*- Respondent BAP6. Respondent BAP8 also stated that, *“we hire cars to people, and they come here because their friends and loved ones expect some benefits out of them”*. In terms of price, the respondents mentioned same pricing whether locally assembled or imported brands. The respondents were of the view that, a disparity in pricing will negatively affect the purchase intention of locally assembled vehicle brands or imported vehicle brands. Participant BAP12, mentioned that *“For us, we won’t be able to buy these local assembled vehicles if they are expensive, so we expect that, the ones that are from outside and the ones are same”*. Another interviewee also stated that, *“You know, because of competition you can’t say simply because yours is made here in Ghana, it will be more expensive, where are we going to get the money. The customers will not want to pay high prices because they made them here”*- Respondent BAP13.

A number of themes emerged from the qualitative research that demonstrated the preference for locally assembled vehicle brands although the perception of value for vehicle brands (locally assembled and imported brands) were the same. The researcher therefore probed further to identify the reasons for the preference of locally assembled automobile brands. The themes that emerged were broadly categorised into economic factors that affect the marketing environment and marketing improvements.

7.5.1 Economic Factors that Affect Marketing Environment

A number of economic issues that were external environmental factors were identified as the reasons why the responses indicated that there was a stronger brand attitude towards the intention to purchase locally assembled brand of vehicles than imported brands. These factors are part of the macro-environmental forces which tend to affect the purchasing power of businesses and the broader economic outlook of Ghana. These included high inflation, high interest rates and foreign exchange.

7.5.1.1 High Inflationary Rate

Most of the respondents mentioned that inflation was one of the challenges that the Ghanaian economy was facing because of over-reliance on imported vehicles and other commodities. The country experiences rapid increase in general prices of goods and services. The respondents were

of the view that, inflation can reduce if there were more production activities domestically. Local vehicle assembling firms can capitalise on raw materials that can be sourced within the country to support the industrialisation drive in the country. Below are some of the responses from the interview:

“It’s good to have these firms in the country. The government and our support are needed to ensure that this is sustained. Ghana can’t build the vibrant economy we always talk about if we’re always importing”- Respondent BAP3. The response above revealed the over-reliance on importation of finished products which was identified as a driver of high inflationary rate in Ghana. There was therefore a good recognition that the presence of locally assembled firms and the government promise to provide iron ore together with other industrial activities can contribute to the government’s quest to reduce inflation which will not only transform the economy but also bring economic relief to the country, Ghana. The locally assembled automobile industry started with Kantanka which used some materials that were sourced locally. The influx of foreign firms in Ghana to assemble automobile will lead to increased partnerships with local suppliers. Participant BAP9 mentioned that *“Kantanka is doing its best to use raw materials here. It’s not everything but we can see that some of the parts are produced right here”*. The travel trade business has negatively been affected by inflation and the resultant effect is increase in prices of vehicles. Thus, a lot of money is spent on the purchase and maintenance. This is reflected in the response of interviewee BAP12 who stated that, *“I have one of the cars here, the last two months, I bought it for GHC 400, 000, after I finished paying, following month, I was going to buy, they said GH 500, 000. So, can you imagine? Just within 30 days?”*.

7.5.1.2 High Interest Rates

Most of the respondents asserted that, the volatility of the economy due to factors such as high inflation makes the cost of borrowing expensive. This because the country over-relies on importation. The rippling effect is that it makes banks demand for high interest rates which makes it difficult for businesses to access loan facilities. Businesses that do obtain loan facilities also struggle to pay. The participants were of the view that assembling of local vehicles will support other business activities to lessen the pressure on the importation of goods and services. Excerpts of responses were indicated below:

Respondent BAP1 mentioned that, *“we went to the bank to get some money to buy more cars for our business, but the interest was too much. A loan of 30% interest... When we buy things outside with the dollar or other currencies, our currency weakens more, and things shoot up which affects the interest on loans”*. Locally assembled vehicles will contribute to the general economic structure due to the utilisation of some local resources and aid in the stabilisation of the cedi, the Ghanaian currency. Stability in the currency will reduce the pressure and the resultant effect will be stable or reduced interest rates. This can aid the trade travel (car rentals, travel and tour and travel agencies) have greater purchasing power that can enhance their businesses. Ghana is experiencing high inflationary rate and one of the notable contributing factors was high importation. A locally assembled automobile brands with local participation and content together with other business activities locally will lead to improved economy activities, reduce the cost of borrowing, and enhance their business abilities. The participants were very concerned about the

high interest rates and the need to localise more business ventures. Participant BAP8 for instance stated that *“We start doing stuff here, the inflation will slow and there will be confidence so we can borrow money easily and pay as well”*.

7.5.1.3 Foreign Exchange

The respondents mentioned that the citing of local assembling plants will aid the country to export vehicles to other parts of Africa generally and particularly to other West African Countries. Ghana is noted to be the country in West Africa that has attracted a lot of foreign investors into assembling of vehicles in addition to Kantanka, an indigenous based vehicle assembling company. This development will provide the country with the required capacity to have large scale assembling of vehicles and export to neighbouring countries. This will support the country with the needed foreign exchange. Thus, complementing the existing foreign exchange reserve and reducing the pressure on the local currency, the cedi. Ghana will also save foreign currencies that would have been used to import vehicles in other countries due to the presence of local automobile assembly.

Strong partnership between the government and the locally assembled vehicle firms will lead to a large-scale production which can result in export and bring in the requisite revenue. Respondent BAP9 mentioned that *“We export electricity to Togo and other countries. We can do same with automobiles too. It’s a good investment. The government must see how the country can benefit when we export so that it’s not only the companies that will enjoy”*.

The influx of foreign automobile firms was a demonstration that the country was well-positioned and can capitalise on this to generate more foreign exchange. Respondent BAP15 indicated that, *“We have a lot of countries around us, so for the Toyotas and others to come here, it means they have seen something good. So, we can also export and get some foreign currencies that will be good for the country”*.

7.5.2 Marketing Improvements

The respondents also mentioned activities geared towards improving marketing in the automobile industry and the country as a theme. This theme was sub-divided into competitiveness and market share as well as creation of good national image. Below were discussions on the sub-themes.

7.5.2.1 Competitiveness and Market Share within the Automobile Market

The locally assembled brands are expected to occupy a substantial market share within the Ghanaian market. The presence of locally assembled will generate more competition and offer more choices since the automobile market has been dominated by imported brands. The participants were of the view that such competition will lead to continuous improvements and

innovations that will enhance their businesses and the automobile industry. The automobile industry is dominated by the imported brands and the development in the locally assembling will transform the business. Respondent BAP13 mentioned that *“We definitely need new competition. The market is now flooded with a lot of imported cars. When we accept assembling here. We will see that there are choices available and new things will come up”*.

The local assembling of automobiles will provide a greater market share and likely dominate the automobile industry. According to Respondent BAP15 *“There will be market share for the local industry. Something that’s not been around. It’s only Kantanka that has been around so if others from outside want to support, why not? We can all do it. Let everybody play his role and there will be results”*. Ghana has relied on large scale importation of vehicles across the world. Until recently, Kantanka Automobile, which is a local firm has been the only firm engaged in assembling of vehicles in Ghana before the influx of foreign companies. The warm reception that has been received by these firms will lead to dominance of assembling of automobiles in Ghana.

7.5.2.2 Good National Image

Most of the respondents mentioned that the image of Ghana will be projected globally. The success of local automobile assembling will therefore enhance the image of the country. This will attract other entities and individuals to invest more within the sector which will lead to growth and expansion of the automobile industry. The country can also leverage on the success of local assembling of automobiles to attract foreign and local investors to inject more capital that will boost business activities in the country.

Football and cocoa exportation are among notable things about Ghana. The addition of automobile assembling can also aid in the projection of a good image. According to Participant BAP1 *“Some people got to know of us because of football. Some people know us because of the cocoa that we export. Once we are able to come up with new things, the country’s name becomes well-known, and people will say good things about us”*.

Some of the countries within the sub-Saharan African are characterised with political instability and unresolved electoral conflicts. Ghana is regarded as a country with stable democratic credentials and the development of local automobile industry will enhance its image. Participant BAP8 stated that *“We know that Ghana is a peaceful country, but we need to do more so that we can be more recognised internationally and across the world. These cars will definitely make a positive statement about the country and people will know the good things here”*.

CHAPTER EIGHT

DATA INTEGRATION

8.0 Introduction

This thesis sought to research into issues of brand attitude, perceived value and purchase intention within the automobile industry in Ghana. To achieve the study objectives, hypotheses and themes were developed consistent with the mixed methodological approach of the study. Explanatory sequential model was employed to connect quantitative and qualitative data. Data was analysed in two phases. The first phase analysed quantitative data. The second phase was the analysis of qualitative data. This was followed by integrating both quantitative and qualitative results which was accomplished by providing qualitative data to explain the quantitative results. The analyses were conducted based on the research objectives of the thesis. Explanatory sequential model, a mixed methodological approach that focused on the usage of qualitative data to explain quantitative findings was utilised. The method tends to provide more detailed, in-depth, and holistic understanding of research problems or a phenomenon with an initial quantitative and a subsequent qualitative data (Ivankova et al., 2006; Younas et al., 2020).

8.1 Data Integration

Studies have identified five means of integrating data. These include connecting, building, merging, and embedding (Creswell et al., 2012; Creswell and Clark, 2018; Fетters et al., 2013). The explanatory sequential model that was employed subscribed to integrating data using qualitative results to explain quantitative findings based on connection as the integration option. The study therefore linked the quantitative data results into the qualitative study. The explanatory sequential model was adopted because although there were some quantitative studies on the concept of brand attitude, perceived value and purchase intention, there was the need for further studies in the area due to lacuna identified. The processes started with the development of quantitative research objectives. The objectives were derived from review of extant literature and identified gaps. These objectives included to determine the impact of brand attitude and the purchase intention of automobile brands in Ghana, to determine the mediating role of perceived value in the relationship between brand attitude and purchase intention of automobile brands in Ghana, to ascertain the impact of brand attitude and purchase intention of locally assembled vehicle brands compared to imported vehicle brands in Ghana and to determine if there was a significant difference of perceived value in the relationship between brand attitude and the purchase intention of locally assembled vehicle brands compared to imported brands in Ghana.

In order to obtain quantitative data without complications in analysis and ambiguity of results, a structured questionnaire was employed. This study conducted exploratory factor analysis to identify questions that were ideal for the next stage of analysis which was confirmatory factor analysis. Confirmatory factor analysis using Structural Equation Modelling, a rigorous quantitative analytical tool was also employed to establish casual relationships among various variables and constructs. Various Structural Equation Modelling Tests were conducted. These included testing significant levels of direct relationships, multi-group analysis, mediation test and moderated-mediation relationships. Direct relationship testing indicated that brand attitude

influence purchase intention in the automobile industry. Mediation test revealed that, perceived value fully mediated the relationship between brand attitude and purchase intention. Multi-group analysis also indicated that, the impact of brand attitude on the purchase intention of locally assembled vehicle brands was stronger than imported brands. A further test which was moderated mediation was to ascertain whether there was any difference in perceived value among two groups which were respondents who preferred locally assembled automobile compared to imported automobile brands. The result indicated that, was no difference in the perception of value between brand attitude and purchase intention of locally assembled vehicle brands and imported brands.

The figure below demonstrated the steps in conducting the quantitative research.

Figure 8. 1: Steps in Conducting Quantitative Aspect of the Study

In order to provide explanations to the quantitative findings which was consistent explanatory sequential model, qualitative research was conducted.

The quantitative study which conducted multi-group analysis revealed that, brand attitude and purchase intention towards locally assembled automobile brands was stronger. The researcher developed an objective which was to investigate the perspectives of attitude developed towards brands within the automobile industry (locally assembled and imported brands) in Ghana. The qualitative result revealed that, the respondents found locally assembled automobile brands more likable, attractive, and favourable than imported brands. Another quantitative result revealed that, perceived value constructs (perceived quality, perceived price and social value) fully mediated brand attitude and purchase intention. The qualitative objective which was to investigate the dimensions of perceived value that are relevant to the automobile industry (locally assembled and imported brands) in Ghana was developed. The qualitative aspect of the study explained that perceived quality attributes such as durability, conformance to specifications and customer requirements and the performance of vehicles particularly the quality of vehicle engines were important to the respondents. The qualitative research further revealed that, purchasing power was an important consideration in the purchase of automobile brands. The study further revealed that, automobile brands that were affordable and have benefits commensurate with price will be considered for purchase. In terms of social value, the qualitative aspect of the study revealed that, vehicles that conform to how customers want to be perceived by their social circle such as family, friends and neighbours will be considered in the purchase decision in the automobile industry.

Further quantitative study revealed that, there was no differences in perceived value whether the automobile brands were locally assembled or imported brands. Despite this result, an earlier finding revealed that, business customers have more positive attitude towards locally assembled automobile brands than imported automobile brands. The research therefore sought to find out the factors driving the preference for locally assembled automobile brands if perceived value did not differ. The research revealed that, the firms assembling, except for Kantanka which is an indigenous company also imported automobile brands into Ghana and will therefore not compromise on standards. In addition, that, Kantanka is a brand with high standards and due to that has penetrated markets in West Africa. In addition to this result, external environmental factors which affected the business performance were identified as the factors driving the preference for locally assembled automobile brands since the perception of value did not differ among locally assembled and imported brands. These included high inflation, high interest rates and foreign exchange. The study revealed that, local assembling together with other industrialisation can improve these external environmental factors and ultimately business performance. The study further identified marketing improvement factors such as competitiveness, creating market share for local assembling brands and improving the national

image of the country as considerations for the preference of locally assembled automobile brands. These results were achieved through the application of Thematic Analysis.

Figure 8. 2: Integrating Quantitative and Qualitative Findings

The quantitative results served as the basis to conduct the qualitative research based on the usage of Explanatory Sequential Model. The figure below depicted the conduct of quantitative and qualitative studies and provided a pictorial representation of the integration, using connecting.

CHAPTER NINE

DISCUSSION OF RESULTS

9.0 Introduction

This chapter discussed both the quantitative and qualitative findings of the research based on the research question and objectives. The results obtained from the quantitative study was used to collect qualitative data to explain the quantitative findings. Thus, whereas the quantitative findings established the causal relationships between the variables, brand attitude, perceived value and purchase intention in the automobile industry, the qualitative results provided in-depth insights into issues related to brand attitude, perceived value and purchase intention in the automobile industry. The chapter highlighted consistent and contrary findings with the results of this research.

9.1 Discussion of Quantitative Results

This section discussed the results of the research based on the objectives and the development of hypotheses. The research objectives and hypotheses were developed from Naseem et al. (2015), Salehzadeh and Pool (2017) and Charton-Vachet et al. (2020) who conducted similar studies in relation to brand attitude, perceived value and purchase intention. Structural Equation Modelling was applied to test the casual relationships among the various constructs and variables.

The first research objective was to determine the relationship between brand attitude and the purchase intention of automobile brands. Based on this objective, the hypothesis below was developed.

H1: There is a positive relationship between brand attitude and purchase intention in the automobile industry.

The findings of the study revealed that, there was a positive relationship between brand attitude and purchase intention. The relationship was therefore supported. Thus, attitude towards brands had an impact on the intention to purchase automobiles. The result was consistent with a number of studies into brand attitude and purchase intention across different context. Wu and Lo (2009) and Tang et. al (2011) research in personal computers and Pop et al. (2023) fast fashion mobile apps finding all in the computing industry. Kudeshia and Kumar (2017) research into consumer electronics specifically smartphones; Abzari et al. (2014) study of social media and traditional media advertising; Lee et al. (2017) research into smartphones advertising industry. The research finding confirmed other similar studies- as well. Nuzula and Wahyudi (2022) research work on social media. Another research was conducted by Pradhan et al. (2016) in the sports branded footwear and Chuenban et al. (2021) in retail supermarket. However, the study result was contrary to Karamchandani et al. (2021) who found that, brand attitude did not affect the intention to buy hygienic products during the lock down periods because of the Covid-19 pandemic. The finding of this research was also inconsistent with Mazodier and Merunka (2014) research into secondary brands which were luxury brands. The study found that attitude of the brands did not influence consumers intention to purchase.

Another objective was to determine the relationship between brand attitude and perceived value constructs (perceived quality, perceived price, and social value). Based on the objective, the following hypotheses and results were discussed.

H2a: There is a positive relationship between brand attitude and perceived quality in the automobile industry.

The finding of the research revealed that, a positive correlation existed between brand attitude and perceived quality. This result was consistent with some studies. Wang (2013) research in Taiwan for instance reported that, a positive relationship existed between brand attitude and the perception of food quality among Taiwanese consumers. In their study of Chinese and American consumers, Juan et al. (2007) reported that, attitude towards brand tend to affect the perception of its quality. José Sanzo (2003) research in Spain also found that consumers attitude towards traditional product, particularly honey affected their perception of quality that was attached to attitudes of branded honey. Another research by Homer (2008) study among students in the United States found a positive relationship between brand attitude and perceived quality among nine automobile firms. Also, Nuzula and Wahyudi (2022) identified that brand attitude influenced perception of value of consumers who utilised social media platforms in Indonesia among luxury products. Esmaeilpour (2015) researched luxury fashion brands among Generation Y consumers in Iran and found that perceived quality was a better predictor of brand attitude. Dall'Olmo Riley et al. (2015) researched also identified attitude towards premium brands influenced perceived quality specifically cars and fashion brands of shoes among consumers in shops in the United Kingdom. The result was however inconsistent with a study by Huang et al. (2004) in the Taiwanese gray market which showed a negative relationship between brand attitude and perceived quality.

H2b: There is a positive relationship between brand attitude and perceived price in the automobile industry.

The research revealed that, firms within the Ghanaian automobile industry recognised that, the attitude demonstrated towards automobile vehicle brands had a positive effect on their intention to purchase those brands. This finding however corroborated other studies. Carpenter and Moore (2006) research in the United States of America among grocery retailers reported that attitudes formed about brands positively impacted on the perception of price held by consumers. Similarly, Salehzadeh and Pool (2017) study conducted in Iran showed a positive relationship between brand attitude and perceived price among luxury customers. Another research by Hwai Lee and Yuen Han (2002) in electronic products among students in Singapore revealed that, consumers had more favourable attitude towards an all-inclusive than partitioned pricing. The result was however contrary to Huang et al. (2004) research in Taiwan on gray market goods which reported that, there was no positive relationship between attitude exhibited towards brands and the perception of price held by consumers.

H2c: There is a positive relationship between brand attitude and social value in the automobile industry.

The study results also indicated that, attitudes which were demonstrated towards automobile brands affected the value attached to it within the societal landscape. The finding was consistent

with other studies. Research by Ajitha and Sivakumar (2017) in India for instance concluded that, brand attitude and social value had a positive relationship among customers of cosmetics market. In addition, a study by Salehzadeh and Pool (2017) in Iran also identified that brand attitude had an impact on social value of consumers of luxury products.

The study had another objective which was to ascertain the relationship between perceived value constructs (quality, price, and social value) on purchase intention. Based on the objective, the following hypotheses were tested.

H3a: There is a positive relationship between perceived quality and purchase intention in the automobile industry.

This research's conclusion recognised that the perception of quality held by businesses was an important factor in forming their intention to purchase. Thus, perceived quality influenced the intention to purchase automobile brands in Ghana. This finding corroborated other similar studies. Shukla and Purani (2012) research in United States of America, the United Kingdom, India, and Malaysia concluded that, the perception of quality had an influential effect on consumers' intention to purchase. Another study by Chattalas and Shukla (2015) in United States of America and the United Kingdom also revealed that, the perception that consumers held about the quality of an offering had an impact on intention to purchase. Similarly, Celik and Erciş (2018) study in Turkey concluded that, there was an impact of quality as a value perception construct on consumers' willingness to buy. Another research by Makhitha (2021) in South Africa also postulated that, a key determinant of consumer purchase intention was the perception held about the quality of products. Eunju et al. (2008) also revealed that, the perception of quality held among consumers within these two countries, South Korea and China impacted purchase intention of sports footwear.

Calvo-Porrall and Lévy-Mangin (2017) finding indicated also that both high and low product quality impacted the intention to purchase store brand in Spain. Another study by Tsiotsou (2005) in Greece revealed that students' perception of quality played an important role in forming the decision to purchase sports shoes. Das (2014) research also indicated that, perceived quality among non-food retail shoppers had an impact on their willingness to buy. Wang et al. (2020) researched the Chinese meat market and identified that the perception among consumers played a significant influence in developing their purchase decision. However, these findings were contrary to other studies. Richardson et al. (1994) research in the United States revealed that, shoppers were more interested in their perceptions of price than perceptions of quality in forming buying intention. Reyes-Menendez et al. (2022) research in Spain did not find a positive relationship between perceived quality and consumers' willingness to buy. Another study by Canguende-Valentim and Vale (2022) in Angola also concluded that, perception of quality did not determine the intention to buy luxury brands. In addition, Wang (2010) in Taiwan concluded that perception of quality did not influence intention to purchase among snack consumers.

H3b: There is a positive relationship between perceived price and purchase intention in the automobile industry.

The results of the research indicated that, the perception of price positively influenced the intention to buy automobile vehicles brands. Consumers were therefore likely to purchase automobile vehicles based on how they perceive their prices in Ghana. The finding was consistent with similar studies. Kim et al. (2012) research in Korea highlighted the impact of perceived price on consumers' intention to purchase. Ali and Bhasin (2019) conducted a study in India and reported that, the perception of price influenced consumers' intention to buy. In a study by Son and Jin (2019) in the United States of America, perceived price influenced consumers' willingness to purchase. Pan et al. (2022) research in South Korea also reported that the perceived nature of price significantly influence intention to buy. A study by Eunju et al. (2008) in the sports footwear market revealed that, perceived price had a positive relationship with purchase intention in the South Korea market but a negative relationship in the China market among consumers. Bolton and Lemon (1999) customer's evaluation of product price as fair or unfair had a significant influence on their intentions to repeat a purchase among interactive television entertainment service and cellular communications service users in the United States. Kim et al. (2012) research also concluded that prospects and customers based on their perception of price, developed their willingness to purchase in an online study in South Korea. The finding was contrary to Yu et al. (2018) in the United States of America which highlighted that, the perception of price did not influence the intention of customers to buy luxury brands.

H3c: There is a positive relationship between social value and purchase intention in the automobile industry.

The study found that, social value played a significant role on the intention to buy automobiles in Ghana. This finding corroborated other studies. Research by Wu et al. (2018) within the Chinese environment for instance revealed that, societal influence aided in forming consumers' intention to buy. Sanyal et al. (2014) study in India also recognised that social value played an important role in triggering purchase intention. Another research conducted in Turkey by Ozen and Engizek (2014) reported the significance of social value on intention to purchase. Forgas-Coll et al. (2014), also concluded that, the social value attached to the cruise lines affected the intention of customers to re-purchase services in Spain. Ha (2021) shoe stores and coffee shops study in Vietnam reported that consumers social value impacted on their buying decisions. Chattalas and Shukla (2015) also researched luxury brands and highlighted that, social value had a stronger influence on customers' willingness to purchase in the United States than in the United Kingdom. A study by Jain et al. (2021) in India further revealed that the likelihood to purchase battery electric vehicle brand was influenced by social value. Krishnan and Koshy (2021) also stressed the influence of social value in affecting purchase decisions among Indian consumers in electric vehicle adoption. Other studies also provided contrary conclusions. Zhou et al. (2021) research into electric vehicles did not identify any positive effect of social value on intention to buy among consumers in China. A study by Narang (2016) did not establish any relationship between social value and the intention to buy. Another research by Wang (2010) in the food industry also revealed that, social value did not have an influential effect on the intentions of consumers to purchase.

Additional objective of the research was to ascertain the role of perceived value in the relationship between brand attitude and purchase intention. Based on this objective, the hypothesis below was developed.

H4: There is a positive relationship between brand attitude, perceived value and purchase intention in the automobile industry.

The results of the study indicated that perceived value fully mediated the relationship between brand attitude and purchase intention within the automobile industry. Thus, perceived value played a significant role in ensuring that brand attitude had an impact on consumers' intention to purchase. This finding was consistent with other studies in different contexts. Salehzadeh and Pool (2017) studied global luxury brands and revealed that, perceived value had an impact on brand attitude and purchase intention. Another research by Charton-Vachet et al. (2020) on food products also concluded that, perceived value had a full mediating effect on brand attitude and purchase intention. The finding was however contrary to Dall'Olmo Riley et al (2015) study in premium brands that discovered that, perceived value partially mediated attitude towards brands and the intention of consumers to buy.

Another objective of the study was to ascertain the impact of brand attitude and purchase intention of locally assembled vehicle brands compared to imported vehicle brands. Based on this objective, the hypothesis below was developed.

H5: There is a positive relationship between brand attitude and purchase intention of locally assembled vehicle brands compared to imported brands.

The research had already established that, the attitude towards brands influenced the intention of consumers to purchase automobile brands. The study further probed to ascertain which of the automobile brand categories (locally assembled brands or imported brands) had a stronger brand attitude on intention to purchase. The finding revealed that, there was a stronger brand attitude towards purchase intention of locally assembled automobile brands than imported brands. This was an indication that, in terms of automobile brands, locally assembled brands were more likely to be purchase than imported brands. Thus, there was stronger appeal for vehicles brands that were assembled within the Ghanaian market than imported vehicle brands. This was a novelty and contributed towards filling the lacuna in the literature.

The research probed further to determine whether there was a difference in the perception of value in the relationship between brand attitude and purchase intention.

The study therefore hypothesised that:

H6: There is a significant difference of perceived value in the relationship between brand attitude and the purchase intention of locally assembled vehicle brands and imported vehicle brands

The study conducted further analysis to ascertain the effect of perception of value in the relationship between brand attitude and purchase intention among locally assembled vehicle brands and imported vehicle brands. The test was conducted to determine whether there was difference in the manner in which the value of locally assembled and imported brands were perceived. Thus, the key question behind this hypothesis was, were locally assembled brands perceived as more valuable than imported vehicle brands? or were imported brands perceived to

be more valuable than locally assembled brands? or were locally assembled brands and imported vehicle brands perceived to have the same level of value. The results indicated that, there was no differences of perception of value among locally assembled vehicle brands and imported vehicle brands in relation to brand attitude and the intention of customers to buy. Consumers therefore preferred locally vehicle brands and the perception of value of both locally assembled and imported vehicle brands were same. This finding that assessed perception of value in relation to brand attitude and purchase intention among locally assembled vehicle brands and imported vehicle brands was novel.

Quantitatively, this study exhibited novelty by assessing brand attitude, perceived value and purchase intention in diverse ways. The study ascertained the relationship between brand attitude and purchase intention within the automobile industry in Ghana. Furthermore, this research also assessed the impact of perceived value on brand attitude and purchase intention. In addition, the study determined the relationship between brand attitude, perceived value and purchase intention of locally assembled vehicle brands compared to imported vehicle brands in Ghana. The research also ascertained the impact of brand attitude and purchase intention to determine whether locally assembled vehicle brands or imported vehicle brands had the stronger effect. The study also determined if a significant difference existed between perceived value in the relationship between brand attitude and purchase intention of locally assembled vehicle brands compared to imported vehicle brands.

9.2 Discussion of Qualitative Results

The qualitative results were used to explain the quantitative results that were obtained during the study. The first qualitative research objective was to provide insights into the attitude of brands within the automobile industry (locally assembled and imported brands). The respondents indicated more likeness, attractiveness and favourability towards locally assembled vehicles brands than imported vehicle brands. These findings were consistent with similar studies. Research by Kim (2000) among female consumers in the United States identified differences among clothing brands. The result concluded that, favourable brands received more competent ratings. Fullerton et al. (2007) conducted research about brand attitude among students in Australia, Hong Kong, and Singapore. The findings showed that, Singaporean students had more favourable attitudes towards brands from the United States. International students also regarded Coke, Nike and McDonald's as the most liked and disliked brands which was referred to as "lovemark" and "loathemark" positions. Another study by Hong and Ahn (2023) in the food service sector in the United States identified that, the attractiveness of coffee house brands led to the formation of intention to buy from them.

The second qualitative objective sought to explain the role of perceived value within the automobile industry (locally assembled and imported brands). The respondents identified perceived quality, perceived price, and social value as key influencers of intention to purchase automobile brands. Customer requirements, durability and conformance to specifications were identified as key quality attributes that influenced the perception of customers towards the likelihood to purchase of automobile brands. Thus, quality was recognised as a strong influence for intention to purchase automobile brands whether locally assembled automobile brands or imported automobile brands. This finding corroborated a study by Yeboah (2023) in the hotel industry in Ghana which identified food quality as a key value that did not only differentiate one

hotel from the other but also recognised the need for the inclusion of intangible value elements in creating superior customer experiences. The result was also consistent to Carvalho and Alves (2023) who explored value creation in the hospitality and tourism industry. The study concluded that perceived quality was one of the key components of perceived value that led to outcomes in customer co-value creation.

Perception of price was also key in forming the intent to purchase automobile brands. The respondents mentioned that prices set should reflect the quality of the automobiles that were intended to be purchased. Prices that were perceived to be higher than quality would not be considered. The participants were interested in the purchase of automobile brands that reflected value for money. This result was consistent with previous studies. A study by Carvalho and Alves (2023) in the tourism and hospitality industry revealed the importance of perceived price. The authors who employed systematic literature concluded that, perceived price was an important dimension of perceived value that was attained after engaging in value co-creation. Another research by Ali and Bhasin (2019) in electronic commerce in India also revealed that, perception of price held by customers played an influential role in determining whether to buy using electronic commerce among shoppers. The result also confirmed research by Bolton and Lemon (1999) who concluded that, the assessment of price component by consumers who patronised interactive television entertainment service and cellular communications services in the United States informed their intention to repeat their purchase. Eunju et al. (2008) conducted research across two countries, China and South Korea in the footwear market and generated contradictory findings. Although the perception of among South Korea consumers influenced price, perceived price did not influence consumers in the Chinese market.

Social value was also regarded as key component of perceived value. As a result of that, participants intended to purchase automobile brands that society viewed as valuable. Family members, colleagues and friends were recognised as individuals who influenced the purchase of specific automobile for business activities. The respondents were therefore interested in buying automobile brands that suited the social influences of their customers. This result was consistent with other findings. Carvalho and Alves (2023) research provided similar finding in the tourism and hospitality industry. Social value was recognised as a significant component in forming perceptions of value after co-creation experiences. Wu et al. (2018) research among online shoppers also identified social value as an important component of perceived value which had been underestimated. The authors further explained that perceived value of shoppers in China resulted in the formation of their willingness to buy. Ha (2021) research among young shoes and coffee consumers concluded that, the value attached to social status played an influential role in encouraging purchasing decisions. Contrarily, a study by Zhou et al. (2021) revealed that, electric vehicle consumers in China did not consider social value in determining their willingness to purchase.

Despite these findings which also highlighted the importance of perceived value in the automobile industry, the respondents were also of the view that, there was no difference between the perception of value between locally assembled vehicle brands and imported vehicle brands. The perception of value among locally assembled vehicle brands and imported brands were the same is due to the likely collapse of either locally assembled or imported vehicle brands if value offered to customers were reduced or varied. The study therefore further probed to identify the

reasons why consumers preferred locally assembled brands of vehicles to imported brands of vehicles if the perception of value was the same across these two groups. Two themes emerged as a result of the analysis. These were economic factors and marketing improvements. The sub-themes that emerged under economic factors which affected marketing environment include high inflationary rate, high interest rates and attracting foreign exchange.

The respondents indicated that, Ghana's rapid increase in inflation is a disturbing trend and one of the solutions to the problem is industrialisation of which developing the local automobile market is no exemption. The persistent increases in goods and services due to wide scale importation of automobile brands brings excessive pressure on the local currency due to high demand of foreign currencies such as the dollar and the pound. The finding was consistent with Kantur and Özcan (2022) study in Turkey which relied on secondary data and identified the importation and consumption of products as one of the causes of inflation. In another study, Khan and Gill (2010) who employed secondary data also posited that, the reliance on importation and lack of local production were major drivers of high inflationary rate in Pakistan. The respondents mentioned that government's support to provide raw materials such as iron ore to local automobile assembling firms and support from local partners and suppliers will enhance the development of the locally assembled area of the automobile industry in Ghana. This will eventually reduce importation since Ghanaians were embracing the local automobile assembling market. This was recognised as one of the means of enhancing economic growth and stability.

Another theme that emerged from the study was high interest rates. The participants identified that the cost of borrowing was expensive due to the economic challenges in the country such as inflation. As a result, the participants mentioned that, assembling vehicle brands in Ghana together with other industrialisation drives will reduce the pressure on the local currency and eventually aid in its sustained appreciation. Such an occurrence will bring relief to automobile vehicle players and the business community. This finding corroborated with Horvath (2018) who researched the effect of interest rate among emerging economies using secondary data. The research concluded that, an increase in interest rates in Mexico and Argentina reduced formalised economic activities, purchases, and investment due to high savings and a reduction in investment. The result was contrary to a study of Berdin and Gründl (2015) who concluded that, an increase in interest rate threatened the survival of insurance firms in the German economy because it was not attractive for investment.

The interviewees also mentioned that Ghana can earn foreign exchange through the automobile assembling. This can be achieved through exporting locally assembled vehicles to neighbouring countries, within Africa and some parts of the world as well. The automobile industry can therefore support earnings from other exports such as cocoa, gold and oil. This finding was consistent with Cardoso and Helwege (2018) who researched into import substitution in Latin America. The authors concluded that "domestic production would have to substitute for nonessential imports, freeing foreign exchange for needed inputs". Irwin (2023) study which was based on secondary data in Taiwan also supported the research finding. Irwin (2023) further revealed that, one of the key successes attributed to the improvement of foreign reserves was government policy that provided tax reliefs on the importation of raw materials which were transformed into finished products and exported to other countries. Economic conditions within

the environment therefore played a significant role in business success (Chittithaworn et al., 2011).

Apart from the economic factors, two marketing improvement sub-themes which were competitiveness and market share within the automobile market and creation of good national image were identified. The participants were of the view that, competition within the automobile industry will increase since the industry was dominated by imported brands. Competition can lead to more improved vehicle brands. The presence of the locally assembled vehicle will also create a market share and aid to shape and grow the automobile industry domestically and satisfy future international markets as well. The finding was supported by Dalmoro (2013) who concluded that, Brazilian and Uruguayan firms produced wine domestically and successfully attain improved market share, international recognition, and competitiveness. Also, a review by Thoburn (2022) among five Asia economies which included Thailand, Indonesia, Malaysia, the Philippines, and Vietnam concluded that, automotive industrialisation resulted in competition and domestic market share acquisition. Industrialisation was therefore key in resolving economic difficulties and it was a pre-requisite to economic transformation (Poloz, 2021).

In addition, the presence of locally assembled automobile brands on a large scale also creates a good image for the Ghana brand. Countries all over the world will identify Ghana as a hub for business development. The image will also propel businesses to invest in different sectors of the economy and boost international tourist activities as well. This result collaborated Halkias et al. (2016) study in Austria which focused on six products categories of soft drinks, laptops, clothing, chocolate bars and automobiles and their corresponding country of origin. The results revealed that, consumers were likely to purchase brands due to the image of the country of origin. Suter et al. (2021) conducted research in relation to country-of-origin image among Brazilians. The study conclusion identified that a country that has favourable image has an advantage over others. Thus, good brand image served as a source of attraction to country (Meng and Meng, 2020).

Qualitatively, this research's novelty is based on the explanation of quantitative results in relation to brand attitude, perceived value and purchase intention in the automobile industry which compared locally assembled vehicle brands to imported brands. The qualitative research provided into insights and explanations to the quantitative results. Another novelty also lied in the emergence of themes and sub-themes related to the external marketing environment and marketing improvements.

CHAPTER TEN

CONCLUSIONS OF THE RESEARCH

10.0 Introduction

The previous chapter discussed the results obtained after analysing the data of the research. This chapter provided conclusions based on the findings. The topic of the study which was brand attitude, perceived value and purchase intention conducted within the automobile industry in Ghana.

The study objectives included the following:

- i. To determine the impact of brand attitude on purchase intention of automobile brands
- ii. To determine the mediating effect of brand attitude and purchase intention of automobile brands
- iii. To ascertain the impact of brand attitude and purchase intention of locally assembled vehicle brands compared to imported vehicle brands
- iv. To determine if there was a significant difference of perceived value in the relationship between brand attitude and the purchase intention of locally assembled vehicle brands compared to imported brands
- v. To investigate the perspectives of attitude developed towards brands within the automobile industry (locally assembled and imported brands) in Ghana
- vi. To investigate the dimensions of perceived value that are relevant to the automobile industry (locally assembled and imported brands) in Ghana
- vii. To identify reasons for the quantitative outcomes of brand attitude, perceived value and purchase intention in the automobile industry in Ghana

Literature reviewed highlighted on the various aspects of the topic. Issues related to the concept of brand and brand orientation, branding perspectives, conceptualisation of brand attitude, benefits derived from brand attitude, components of brand attitude, definitions of perceived value, benefits of perceived benefits, components of perceived benefits and purchase intention as well were discussed. In addition to this, literature linkages on various variables within the topic which were brand attitude, perceived value and purchase intention were highlighted. These linkages resulted in the identification of gaps and the setting of hypotheses for the study. These hypotheses were subjected to testing at the analysis stage.

The context chapter was discussed after the literature review. The chapter focused on contextual issues which included the automobile industry and Ghana. The chapter provided information of the evolution of the global automobile industry, the value chain inherent in the automobile industry and productivity analysis of global automobile manufacturer. It also discussed the trends

within the automobile in Ghana, the profile, and the economy of Ghana as well as the automobile industry in Ghana.

The next chapter was the methodology. This chapter outlined the various techniques and approaches that were adopted to achieve the research objectives. The study adopted the pragmatic philosophy which does not subscribe to objectivity or subjectivity but is concerned about the application of varied approaches in solving research problems. The pragmatism was ideal since the research was a mixed and did not rely on objectivity or subjectivity but a blend of them and therefore required a varied technique. The abductive approach was adopted since it does not give credence to objective or subjective perspectives but embraces both objectivity and subjectivity. The research employed survey and interviews. Structured questionnaires and semi-structured interview guides were used to collect both quantitative and qualitative data to answer the research questions. Mixed method was chosen because the research had both quantitative and qualitative research objectives. Mixed method provided comprehensive and in-depth understanding of the study. The research was cross-sectional in nature since it was conducted for a specific period and the researcher had no intention to continue the same studies in the future.

The sample for the research was drawn from the travel trade which included car rentals, travel and tours as well as tour operating agencies within Accra and Tema located within the Greater Accra Region where most commercial activities in Ghana are conducted. The researcher employed convenience sampling to obtain respondents who were readily available for the quantitative aspect of the study. Purposive sampling was employed to obtain respondents who had rich understanding of the automobile sector in Ghana. In terms of the quantitative aspect of the study, a sample size of 310 was used to conduct Exploratory Factor Analysis and 344 respondents for Confirmatory Factor Analysis using Structural Equation Modelling. Exploratory Factor Analysis aided to reduce the number of questions that were not fit for further analysis. Confirmatory Factor Analysis was employed for further validation and add rigour to minimise errors in analysing data. In terms of qualitative data analysis, 15 participants based on data saturation were used to undertake thematic data analysis to identify various patterns. The analyses were conducted based on the objectives and hypotheses of the research.

The conclusions of the research were based on the objectives. The objectives were categorised into quantitative and qualitative objectives as guided by explanatory sequential model. The conclusions of the study based on quantitative objectives were discussed below:

The first quantitative objective was to determine the relationship between brand attitude and the purchase intention of automobile brands. The results indicated that, there was a positive relationship between brand attitude and purchase intention. Thus, the attitude towards brands had an impact on the intention to purchase automobile brands.

The second quantitative objective was to determine the relationship between brand attitude, perceived value, and the purchase intention of automobile brands. The findings of the research revealed that, perceived value fully mediated the relationship between brand attitude and

purchase intention. This result revealed that, perceived value played a significant role in ensuring that brand attitude had an impact on purchase intention. Perceived value was therefore a variable that was taken into consideration in the brand attitude, purchase intention relationship. It was a major influence of brand attitude and purchase intention within the automobile industry.

The third quantitative objective was to compare brand attitude and the purchase intention of locally assembled vehicle brands and imported brands. The results revealed a stronger brand attitude and purchase intention towards locally assembled vehicle brands than imported vehicle brands. This was therefore an indication that, the respondents had more preference for locally assemble brand of vehicles than imported vehicle brands.

Another quantitative objective was to determine if there was a significant difference in perceived value in the relationship between brand attitude and the purchase intention of locally assembled vehicle brands and imported brands. The study revealed that, there was no difference in the perception of value among locally assembled vehicle and imported vehicle brands. This therefore indicated that the respondents consider both locally assembled vehicle brands and imported vehicle brands as having the same level of perceived value. In line with explanatory sequential model, using the connection option, the study probed further with qualitative objectives to explain the quantitative findings. The conclusions based on the qualitative objectives were discussed below:

The first qualitative objective was to investigate the perspectives of attitude developed towards brands within the automobile industry (locally assembled and imported brands). The findings indicated that, the respondents had a more positive attitude towards locally assembled automobile brands than imported brands. The respondents found automobile brands assembled in Ghana as likable, attractive, and favourable than imported vehicle brands.

The second qualitative objective was to investigate the dimensions of perceived value that are relevant to the automobile industry (locally assembled and imported brands). The respondents recognised perceived value as a key influence in the purchase of automobile brands. The three aspects of perceived value which were social value, perceived price and perceived quality were identified as key dimensions.

Another qualitative objective was to identify reasons for the quantitative outcomes of brand attitude, perceived value and purchase intention in the automobile industry. The quantitative result revealed that, perceived value did not differ among the two groups (locally assembled vehicles and imported vehicle brands). Thus, although the respondents recognised that perceived value played a critical role in the relationship between brand attitude and purchase intention, perceived value was same among both locally assembled vehicle brands and imported vehicle brands. Perceived value was recognised in vehicle brands irrespective of being locally assembled or imported brands although it was recognised as important. The researcher therefore probed further to identify reasons why the respondents had preference for locally assembled vehicle brands and not imported vehicle brands. Since the perception of value was same across all two

groups, the respondents attributed their preference for locally assembled vehicle brands to economic issues that affect marketing environment and marketing improvements. The economic issues included high inflation, high interest rates and attracting foreign exchange. Marketing improvement reasons were enhancing competitiveness and market share as well as good national image of Ghana.

Ghana engages in a lot of importation of products. As a result of that, the cedi which is the currency experiences a lot of depreciation and the resultant effect is high inflation, the rapid increase of goods and services. In addition to this, the cost of borrowing is high. The Ghanaian economy is import dependent and as the rate of inflation increases, the interest rates on loans also increases. This situation increases the cost of borrowing and the cost of doing business. Furthermore, due to high demand for foreign currencies such as the dollar and the pound, the cedi tends to depreciation on a regular basis. This situation reduces the value of money since more cedis will be required to engage in businesses activities. Due to these factors, a shift in import dependent economy to local production will provide a healthy economy and promote business growth and survival.

Apart from these factors, the respondents revealed that, Ghana will attract a lot of foreign exchange by engaging in local assembling of vehicles. When the assembling of vehicles is done on a large scale, the country can engage in exportation to neighbouring West African countries and other countries in Africa and some parts of the world. This will provide some of the needed financial inflows that will improve the economic situation in the country. This research further revealed that, since locally assembled brands and imported brands were regarded as valuable, there was therefore the need to have positive economic factors to drive the success of locally assembled automobile brands. A successful local automobile industry can contribute to economic progress. A feat that Ghana is currently struggling to attain. One of the factors that is impending the attainment of economic progress is attributed to over-reliance on importation.

Marketing improvements which included competitiveness and market share as well as good national image were also identified as reasons why there was preference for the locally assembled automobile brands. In terms of competitiveness and market share, the participants were of the view that, imported automobile brands have dominated the automobile market for a long time. The presence of locally assembled vehicles will bring competition in the market and create market share for those brands. Such situation can bring immense benefits to the Ghanaian market. There will be varied offerings to meet the tastes and preferences of customers and it can also drive other benefits such as product improvements.

Ghana will also benefit from having a good brand image if the local automobile market was sustained. The country can be identified as the hub for vehicle assembling. This will generate a lot of attention and interest in the country and eventually lead to immense job opportunities, an increase in the flux of tourists and investment potentials as well. This will make Ghana more attractive which can translate into business and investment opportunities that will improve standard of living and aid in transforming the economy.

10.1 Research Contributions

The contributions of this research were in three strands. These were contributions to theory, practice and knowledge.

10.1.1 Contributions to Theory

The study utilised the Nudge Theory which is deeply rooted in behavioural economics. Other four theories specifically Theory of Reasoned Action, Theory of Planned Behaviour, the Expectancy Theory and Means-End Theory which originated from the psychology literature were adopted. These theories were significant to the topic made theoretical contributions. The study was underpinned by five theories which provided detailed explanations to the topic brand attitude, perceived value and purchase intention. It therefore expanded the theoretical base and encourage future researchers to incorporate these theories and other relevant theories in similar studies to enhance theoretical basis of research.

10.1.2 Contributions to Knowledge

PhD research may demonstrate originality in different perspectives. This study demonstrated originality through original approach, empirical (understudied area) and method as proposed by scholars such as Phillips (1994), Winter et al. (2000), Mullins and Kiley (2002), Delamont et al. (2004), Guetzkow et al. (2004), Cryer (2006), Phillips and Pugh (2010) and Wisker (2012).

10.1.2.1 Original Approach

Originality can be demonstrated when a new approach is devised to conduct a study in an already existing topic. The new approach includes developing new perspective, new arguments and posing new research questions. This study adopted the original approach to brand attitude, perceived value and purchase intention. The researcher approached the concept of perceived value from a multi- dimensional construct due to the lack of literature about it in the automobile industry and ascertained the level of differences in perception of value among locally assembled and imported automobile brands. The research answered questions about brand attitude, perceived value and purchase intention from an organisational perspective which made it distinct from other studies. In addition, the study also tested brand attitude, perceived value and purchase intention in order to ascertain their strength in relation to locally assembled vehicle brands and imported automotive brands which further demonstrated the novelty of this study.

10.1.2.2 Empirical (Understudied Area) Contribution

According to Guetzkow et al. (2004), research is regarded as making original contributions if it focused on an area which is understudied. The authors categorised understudied area into region and within a time duration. This is distinct from original topic since understudied contribution does not focus on the topic of the research. Guetzkow et al. (2004) further postulated that, a

study that contributes to a research gap contextually usually from a non-western perspective is regarded as understudied in nature. This research contributed empirically to branding and organisational behavioural within the automobile industry in a developing country, Ghana. Extant literature revealed that most studies on the automobile industry have focused on developed economies. The study also contributed to the understudy area in terms of time duration. This is because, apart from the presence of an existing locally assembled vehicle company, Kantanka Automobile, the country is currently witnessing an influx of global automobile brands who have ventured into locally assembling. This study was timely because it provided insights into the reception of the locally assembled vehicles in Ghana, an area that has scarce literature.

10.1.2.3 Method Contribution

The research has originality in method. Original methods are tools linked with a discipline, a project's research design, or a researcher's basic methodologies and research techniques (Cryer, 2006; Phillips and Pugh, 2010). Guetzkow et al. (2004) highlighted that, one of the means of demonstrating method contribution is by designing an innovative research design which highlights on concepts and demonstrate comparison. This research contributed to that aspect by comparing locally assembled automobile brands to imported brands in relation to brand attitude, perceived value and purchase intention. Another manner of attaining originality is the way collected data is synthesised (Guetzkow et al., 2004). The study employed the mixed methodological approach. Convenience sampling method was employed to collect quantitative data while qualitative data was purposively collected. Covariance structural equation modelling and thematic analysis were employed to analyse quantitative and qualitative data respectively. In order to integrate the findings, the study employed explanatory sequential model in which qualitative results were used to explain initial quantitative findings. Thus, causal relationships between independent and dependent variables were not only established but further explanations were obtained through thematic analysis. This aided in the presentation of a holistic and in-depth appreciation and understanding of the topic and made the research different from other studies. The application of the various methodological approaches is a novelty in relation to brand attitude, perceived value and purchase intention.

10.1.3 Original Results Contribution

Guetzkow et al. (2004) advocated that the inclusion of original results is one of the criteria for determining originality of a PhD thesis. Original results refer to findings that are new and unique nature. This research made an original contribution to results by setting new research objectives and questions. Thus, the research objectives for the study were different from those of previous studies. The research assessed the strength of brand attitude and purchase intention in relation to locally assembled and imported vehicle brands. In addition, the study was able to determine the level of differences of perceived value among locally assembled and imported vehicle brands. The study also generated themes and insights from brand attitude, perceived value and purchase intention in the automobile industry. The themes for the preference for locally assembled vehicle brands were external factors that affected marketing environment and marketing improvements. The sub-themes for external environmental factors were high inflationary rate, high interest rates and attracting foreign exchange. Themes for marketing improvements included competitiveness

and market share as well as good national image. These themes and sub-themes can be converted into variables and constructs and tested quantitatively to ascertain their relevance to other industries and countries. This makes the research novel since it had identified themes that can be adopted in other studies. The research will generate more interests and provide more information and knowledge to scholars who will conduct similar studies.

10.1.4 Contributions to Practice

The study makes contributions based on the findings. The contributions were geared towards improving the automobile industry and was directed towards the automobile firms particularly the locally assembled ones and the government. The government is currently encouraging the locally assembling of vehicles in Ghana and therefore this study can provide the needed impetus that will influence policy direction. The study can also serve as a guide for government to shape and implement policies that will strengthen the automobile industry and make it more attractive to both local and foreign investors and ultimately support the industrialisation drive, economic growth and development since the country largely depends on importation of raw materials and finished products. Based on the findings, the following recommendations were highlighted.

The locally assembled automobile firms must ensure that, vehicles produced meet the needs and requirements of customers. There should be consistency in products to instil trust and confidence in prospects and customers. The locally assembled firms must also provide packages that will motivate customers to buy. After-sales service, repairs and spare parts should be readily available and flexible payment terms can also increase patronage.

Industries should also engage in productive business activities that will enhance positive brand attitudes and increase the perception of values attached to local production so that, customers do not regard locally produced products as inferior.

Furthermore, celebrities and opinion leaders should be used to endorse the brands that are assembled in Ghana. Locally assembled firms should engage in providing sponsorship packages for needy and brilliant students for instance. They should also support hospitals, schools and provide job opportunities to create more favourable opinions about their brands.

The government must form partnerships to aid provide the locally assembled automobile brands the requisite resources to enhance their business activities. One key necessity is for the government to fulfil its promise of providing a major resource for the development of locally assembled vehicles, iron ore as a catalyst to stimulate growth and development within the sector. The government should also provide more incentives in the form of tax reliefs to support the local vehicle assembling sector. This will make Ghana a more attractive destination for foreign firms to invest more. There is also the need to for the government to have a directive in place to purchase only locally assembled vehicle brands to encourage others to patronise more locally assembled vehicle brands.

There should also be continuity and improvements in government policies and programmes that have been developed to assist the local automobile sector. Ghana has a history of abandoning policies, programmes and developments started by previous governments. This situation stifles initiatives and hinders developmental agenda of the country. A continuity will enhance the progress and expansion of the sector. Periodic performance within the sector also needs to be conducted and improved to obtain optimum benefits for the automobile industry, businesses, individuals, and the country.

The government should also encourage and provide a conducive environment that will create partnerships between automobile firms and tertiary institutions to build and develop the capacity of students. One key deficiency among technical students and graduates is the lack of practical knowledge, insights, and expertise. The government can enhance the skill development potentials through encouraging automobile firms to have technical students as interns in their businesses. The government can also build practical centres and liaise with automobile firms to regularly provide pragmatic training that will aid in developing the much need technical capacities.

The government should also develop a policy that should transcend beyond the automobile industry aimed at reviving ailing firms as well as encourage the setting up of new manufacturing businesses to enhance the industrialisation drive in Ghana. This will boost the local content production of other products that transcends beyond the automobile sector. This can be realised when the government, educational institutions, local and foreign investors as well as industries liaise and form strong partnerships. The government should provide the requisite policies and financial support that will not only aid establish businesses but also groom infant industries. These policies should provide incentives to both local and foreign investors to find establishment of businesses in Ghana more attractive. The government should support the universities to provide the right educational content to broaden the horizon of students and liaise with industries to build training centres and encourage internships and other placements that will equip them with the skills required for business activities.

10.2 Limitations of the Study

The study conceptualised perceived value from a pre-purchase stage and did not focus on actual purchase because local assembling of vehicles in Ghana is at its embryonic stage. The research did not include moderating variables such as age or gender to ascertain the variations of responses among any of these groups in the quantitative aspect. In terms of the qualitative aspect of the study, the researcher focused on the usage of in-depth interviews and did not consider other qualitative data collection techniques such as focus groups. The research also concentrated on new automobiles only and the study was also cross-sectional and not longitudinal since it was time bound.

10.3 Directions for Future Research

This research focused on issues of brand attitude, perceived value and purchase intention within the automobile industry in Ghana. Since this study was cross-sectional, longitudinal studies that apply time series can be employed in order to ascertain the impact of brand attitude, perceived value on purchase of locally assembled and imported automobile brands in Ghana.

This research can be conducted in other countries that are experiencing new developments within the automobile industry or other industries to provide rich insights and finding comparisons. Other studies can also adopt other mediating variables and moderating variables such as age and gender in other to ascertain variations among various groups of consumers.

In addition, since the automobile industry is evolving, future studies can take into consideration actual purchase and firm performance as key research variables related to the local automobile industry. Furthermore, future studies can also be conducted in different product categories since this research was limited to the automobile industry. This study also tested the perception of value at the pre-purchase stage, future research can test the perception of value at the post-purchase stage.

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APPENDIX A
QUESTIONNAIRE

SCHOOL OF BUSINESS AND CREATIVE INDUSTRIES
QUESTIONNAIRE

Dear Respondent,

The questionnaire is designed to help undertake research in order to ascertain the impact of Brand Attitude, Perceived Value and Purchase Intention of automobile brands for business activities. Please note that the questions relate to only new automobiles. This questionnaire is strictly for academic purposes and all answers will be held confidential. Kindly take some time to complete it. Thank you.

SECTION A: DEMOGRAPHIC PROFILE

1. Gender: 1. Male 2. Female 3. Prefer Not to Say
2. Age Group: 1. 18-27 2. 28-37 3. 38-47 4. 48 -57 5. 58+
3. Educational Level: 1. Senior High School 2. Diploma c. Degree 3. Post-Graduate 4. Others ...
4. Position: 1. Owner 2. Manager 3. Supervisor 3. Worker
5. Work Experience: 1. 1-3 Years 2. 4-6 Years 3. 7-9 Years 4. 10+ Years
6. Firm Category: 1. Car Rentals 2. Travel and Tours 3. Tour Operating Agencies

Qualifying Questions

7. Are you familiar with automobile companies and their brands? 1. Yes 2. No

Please answer the rest of the questions only if your answer is “Yes”.

8. Brand preference for business activities: 1. New Vehicle Brands Assembled in Ghana 2. New Vehicle Brands Imported

SECTION B: Please kindly indicate your level of agreement or disagreement with the following statement below, ranking from the lowest **1** – Strongly Disagree (**SD**), **2** – Disagree (**D**), **3** – Neutral (**N**), **4** – Agree (**A**), and to the highest **5**- Strongly Agree (**SA**) based on your preference of vehicle brands indicated above.

QUESTIONS	SD 1	D 2	N 3	A 4	SA 5
BRAND ATTITUDE					
9. Information about this vehicle brand is appealing					
10. This vehicle brand brings joy					
11. This vehicle brand is loveable					
12. This vehicle brand is good					
13. This vehicle brand is attractive					
14. This vehicle brand is likable					
15. This vehicle brand is favourable					
PERCEIVED VALUE					
Perceived Quality					
16. This vehicle brand has consistent quality					
17. This vehicle brand is well made					
18. This vehicle brand has accepted standard					
19. This vehicle brand functions well					
20. This vehicle brand lasts longer					
21. This vehicle brand has excellent features					
Perceived Price					
22. This vehicle brand is reasonably priced					
23. This vehicle brand offers value for money					
24. This vehicle brand has good performance in relation to the price					
25. This vehicle brand is economical					
Social Value					
26. This vehicle brand creates good impression to others					
27. This vehicle brand creates good perception to others					
28. This vehicle brand makes one feel accepted in the society					
29. This vehicle brand has good approval by others					
30. This vehicle brand creates good social image in the society					
31. This vehicle brand is considered reputable by others					
PURCHASE INTENTION					
32. There is information about this vehicle brand					
33. I will be interested to get this vehicle brand purchased for the firm					
34. I want this vehicle brand to be considered for purchase by the firm					
35. I definitely want this vehicle brand purchased for the firm					
36. I am likely to recommend this vehicle brand for the firm					

APPENDIX B

INTERVIEW GUIDE

SCHOOL OF BUSINESS AND CREATIVE INDUSTRIES

INTERVIEW GUIDE

Dear Interviewee,

This interview guide is designed to help undertake research in order to ascertain the impact of Brand Attitude and Purchase intention, the role of Perceived Value in the Automobile Industry in Ghana. Please note that the questions relate to only new automobiles and should be based on your knowledge and experiences. This interview guide is strictly for academic purposes and all answers will be held confidential. Kindly take some time to fill it. Thank you.

SECTION A

1. Gender: a. Male b. Female
2. Age Group: a. 18-27 b. 28-37 c. 38-47 d. 48-57 e. 58+
3. Educational Level: a. Senior High School b. Diploma c. Degree d. Post-Graduate
e. Others ...
4. Position: a. Owner b. Manager
5. Work Experience: a. 1-3 c. 4-6 d. 7-9 e. 10+
6. Firm Category: a. Car Rentals b. Travel and Tours c. Tour Operating Agencies

Qualifying Question

7. Brand Preference: a. New Vehicle Brands Assembled in Ghana b. New Vehicle Brands Imported

SECTION B

Brand Attitude

8. What is your attitude towards automobile brands assembled in Ghana compared to imported brands? What are the reasons for your answer?

9. What interventions do you think should be put in place in order to improve the brand attitude within the automobile industry in Ghana?

Perceived Value

10. Do you think automobile brands assembled in Ghana has more perceived value in terms of costs, quality and social value compared to imported brands? What are the reasons for your answer?

11. What interventions do you think should be put in place in order to improve the perception of value within the automobile industry in Ghana?

Brand Attitude and Perceived Value

12. Does your attitude towards automobile brands assembled in Ghana makes such brands to be perceived to be more quality than imported ones. What are the reasons?

13. Does your attitude towards automobile brands assembled in Ghana makes such brands more socially valuable than imported ones. Provide reasons

14. Does your attitude towards automobile brands assembled in Ghana makes such brands to be perceived as more affordable than imported ones. Provide reasons

Brand Attitude and Purchase Intention

15. Does your attitude towards automobile brands assembled in Ghana makes such brands more likely to be purchased than imported ones? Provide reasons

Brand Attitude, Perceived Value and Purchase Intention

17. Does your attitude towards automobile brands assembled in Ghana makes such brands more likely to be purchased than imported ones as a result of your perception of quality? Provide reasons

18. Does your attitude towards automobile brands assembled in Ghana makes such brands more likely to be purchased than imported ones as a result of social value? Provide reasons

19. Does your attitude towards automobile brands assembled in Ghana makes such brands more likely to be purchased than imported ones as a result of you perception of costs? Provide reasons

20. What interventions do you think should be put in place in order to improve brand attitude, perception of value and purchase intention within the automobile industry in Ghana?

Thank you for your participation

**APPENDIX C
MAIN RELATED STUDIES**

Author	Year	Geographical Area	Journal of Publication	Title of Research Paper	Type of Study (Conceptual/ Empirical/Review)	Methodological Approaches (Qualitative/ Quantitative/Multi-Method/Mixed)	Key Findings
Charton-Vachet, Lombart and Louis	2020	France	International Journal of Retail & Distribution Management	Impact of attitude towards a region on purchase intention of regional products: the mediating effects of perceived value and preference	Empirical	Quantitative	Perceived value influenced consumers attitude exhibited towards the intention to buy food products in a region
Balaji and Maheswari	2021	India	Sage Open	Impact of store image dimensions on shopper's attitude, perceived value, and purchase intention	Empirical	Quantitative	Attitude of shoppers affected intention to purchase
Salehzadeh and Pool	2017	Iran	Journal of International Consumer Marketing	Brand attitude and perceived value and purchase intention toward global luxury brands	Empirical	Quantitative	Brand Attitude impacted perceived value and purchase intention among luxury brands of

							consumers
Alexander, Bick, Abratt and Bendixen	2009	South Africa	South African Journal of Business Management	Impact of branding and product augmentation on decision making in the B2B market	Empirical	Quantitative	Mining companies prioritised brand, followed by durability and price as most important factors in purchasing tyres for business activities
Michell, King and Reast	2001	United Kingdom	Industrial Marketing Management	Brand values related to industrial products	Empirical	Quantitative	Branding influenced premium price by accounting firms who provide services to other organisations in the United Kingdom
Hien and Nhu	2022	Vietnam	Cogent Business & Management	The effect of digital marketing transformation trends on consumers' purchase intention in B2B businesses:	Empirical	Quantitative	Attitudes towards digital marketing affected purchase intention

				The moderating role of brand awareness			
Glynn, Motion and Brodie	2007	New Zealand	Journal of Business & Industrial Marketing	Sources of brand benefits in manufacturer-reseller B2B relationships	Empirical	Quantitative	Attitude towards digital marketing impacted on the purchase intention
Herbst and Merz	2011	Germany	Industrial Marketing Management	The industrial brand personality scale: Building strong business-to-business brands	Empirical	Multi-Method	Brand personality an important variable in measuring brand management activities in business markets
Chang, Lin, Yen and Hung	2020	Taiwan	Computer Standards & Interfaces	The trust model of enterprise purchasing for B2B e-marketplaces	Empirical	Quantitative	Perceived value influenced the intention to purchase by procurement personnel
Kumar and Kapoor	2017	India	British Food Journal	Do labels influence purchase decisions of food products? Study of young consumers of an emerging market	Empirical	Quantitative	Labels impacted the purchasing intention of food among young Indians
Osei-Frimpong,	2019	Ghana	Journal of	The impact of	Empirical	Quantitative	Celebrity

Donkor and Owusu-Frimpong 2019			Marketing Theory and Practice	celebrity endorsement on consumer purchase intention: An emerging market perspective			characteristics which included attractiveness, trust-worthiness and familiarity affected consumers' intention and loyalty towards brands
Anaza, Kemp, Osakwe and Adeola	2023	Nigeria	Industrial Marketing Management	B2B brand marketing in Africa? An exploratory investigation of B2B buyers' perception of supplier brands	Empirical	Qualitative	Brands are the most important consideration in organisational purchases
Ahn and Back	2018	United States	International Journal of Contemporary Hospitality Management	Beyond gambling: mediating roles of brand experience and attitude	Empirical	Quantitative	Brand attitude impacted on brand reputation and customers' intention to re-visit a resort
Pongjit and Beise-Zee	2015	Thailand	Journal of Product & Brand Management	The effects of word-of-mouth incentivization on consumer brand attitude	Empirical	Quantitative	Prospects might have negative attitude towards a brand due to financial

							benefits from peers and family members through enticement
Lee, Cheng and Shih	2017	South Korea	Asia Pacific Management Review	Effects among product attributes, involvement, word-of-mouth, and purchase intention in online shopping	Empirical	Quantitative	Context awareness about mobile phone advertisements had a strong impact on advertising and brand attitude
Ahn, Back and Lee	2019	United States	International Journal of Hospitality Management	A new dualistic approach to brand attitude: The role of passion among integrated resort customers	Empirical	Quantitative	Extrinsic motivation and obsessive passion minimised the impact on affective attitude. Intrinsic motivation and harmonious passion increased affective attitude. A direct relationship between

							intrinsic and affective attitude
Park and Jeon	2018	United States and South Korea	International Marketing Review	The impact of mixed eWOM sequence on brand attitude change: Cross-cultural differences	Empirical	Quantitative	The order of presentation of information influenced attitude towards consumers in the United States but there was no significant differences among South Korea consumers
Rhee and Jung	2019	United States	Journal of Marketing Communications	Brand familiarity as a moderating factor in the ad and brand attitude relationship and advertising appeals	Empirical	Quantitative	Attitude exhibited towards advertisement tend to affect the development of consumers' attitudes towards the advertised brand
Foroudi	2019	United Kingdom	Journal of Business Research	Perceptual components of brand equity:	Empirical	Quantitative	Brand signature had a positive

				Configuring the Symmetrical and Asymmetrical Paths to brand loyalty and brand purchase intention			relationship with brand attitude. Brand attitude also impacted on brand reputation and brand awareness also influenced brand attitude
Waiguny, Nelson and Marko	2013	Online (Not specific)	Journal of Advertising	How advergame content influences explicit and implicit brand attitudes: When violence spills over	Empirical	Quantitative	Game players exhibited negative content towards the game brand (Scion) that they were not familiar with. There was positive content for the brand that they were familiar with (LEGO).
Renton and Simmonds	2017	New Zealand	Journal of Product & Brand Management	Like is a verb: exploring tie strength and casual brand use effects on brand attitudes and consumer online goal	Empirical	Qualitative	Strength of relationships were reflected in variations in attitudes, the social media platforms

				achievement			selected and in brand usage
Banerjee and Pal	2023	United Kingdom	Internet Research	I hate ads but not the advertised brands: a qualitative study on Internet users' lived experiences with YouTube ads	Empirical	Qualitative	Consumers disliked YouTube advertisements but their displeasure did not extend to the advertised brand
Danes, Hess, Story and York	2010	United States	Qualitative Market Research: An International Journal	Brand image associations for large virtual groups	Empirical	Qualitative	More favourable brands received free association than brands that were less favourable
Yoon and Park	2012	South Korea	Journal of Business Research	Do sensory ad appeals influence brand attitude?	Empirical	Multi-Method	Olfactory and auditory senses significantly affected brand attitude; Brand logo and interior colour were important elements in developing brand attitude among consumers
Hsu, Chang and	2019	Taiwan	British Food	Triple bottom line	Empirical	Quantitative	Consumers

Lin			Journal	model and food safety in organic food and conventional food in affecting perceived value and purchase intentions			attitude affected purchase intention of green skincare consumers
Abzari, Ghassemi and Vosta	2014	Iran	Procedia-Social and Behavioural Sciences	Analysing the Effect of Social Media on Brand Attitude and Purchase Intention: The Case of Iran Khodro Company	Empirical	Quantitative	Brand attitude had a significant effect on the willingness of customers to buy from Khodro Company
Signh and Banerjee	2018	India	Global Business Review	Exploring the influence of celebrity credibility on brand attitude, advertisement attitude and purchase intention	Empirical	Quantitative	Celebrity endorsement positively affected customers intention to purchase
Lee, Lee and Yang	2017	South Korea	Industrial Management & Data Systems	Effects among product attributes, involvement, word-of-mouth, and purchase intention in online shopping	Empirical	Quantitative	Brand attitude has a stronger effect on purchase intention than advertising
Augusto and	2018	Portugal	Journal of	Effects of brand	Empirical	Quantitative	Brand attitude

Torres			Retailing and Consumer Services	attitude and eWOM on consumers' willingness to pay in the banking industry: Mediating role of consumer-brand identification and brand equity			influenced the purchase intention of customers
Park, Jeon and Sullivan	2015	South Korea	The International Review of Retail, Distribution and Consumer Research	How does visual merchandising in fashion retail stores affect consumers' brand attitude and purchase intention?	Empirical	Mixed Methods	Brand attitudes and purchase intentions were affected by visual merchandising in fashion retail shops
Karjaluoto, Shaikh, Saarijärvi and Saraniemi	2019	Finland	International Journal of Information Management	How perceived value drives the use of mobile financial services apps	Empirical	Quantitative	Perceived value had a stronger positive effect on satisfaction and commitment of banks customers
Lee, Yoon and Lee	2007	South Korea	Tourism Management	Investigating the relationships among perceived value, satisfaction, and recommendations:	Empirical	Quantitative	Perceived value influenced satisfaction

				The case of the Korean DMZ			
Lo and Lee	2011	Hong Kong	Tourism Management	Motivations and perceived value of volunteer tourists from Hong Kong	Empirical	Qualitative	One of the reasons of volunteering by travellers was to obtain value based on their perceptions
Chopy, Winkler, Schwartz-Barcott, Melanson and Greene	2015	United States	Journal of Parenteral and Enteral Nutrition	A qualitative study of the perceived value of membership in The Oley Foundation by home parenteral and enteral nutrition consumers	Empirical	Qualitative	Individuals subscribed to the Oley Foundation due to the perception of value which manifested in the programmes, capabilities, inspiration, normalcy and advocacy
Coutelle-Brillet, Riviere and Des Garets	2014	France	Journal of Business & Industrial Marketing	Perceived value of service innovation: a conceptual framework	Empirical	Qualitative	Elements of perceived value identified were economic, functional, interactional, emotional, symbolic and

							altruistic
Sedzro, Amewu, Darko, Nortey and Dasah	2014	Ghana	Journal of Transnational Management	Determinants of automobile purchase and brand choice in Ghana: Multinomial logit approach	Empirical	Quantitative	Consumers considered safety, value for money, interior satisfaction, modernity and affordability when determining to buy a specific vehicle
Zhu, Mou and Benyoucef	2019	China	Journal of Retailing and Consumer Services	Exploring purchase intention in cross-border E-commerce: A three-stage model	Empirical	Quantitative	Platform situational involvement, trust beliefs as well as platform enduring involvement influenced the intention of customers to buy
Yuan, Tsao, Chyou and Tsai	2020	Taiwan	Soft Computing	An empirical study on effects of electronic word-of-mouth and Internet risk avoidance on purchase intention: from the perspective of big	Empirical	Quantitative	Electronic word of mouth and Internet risk avoidance influenced consumers' willingness to buy

				data			
Watanabe, Torres and Alfinito	2019	Brazil	Revista de Gestão	The impact of culture, evaluation of store image and satisfaction on purchase intention at supermarkets	Empirical	Quantitative	With the exception of culture, store image and satisfaction influenced customers intention to buy again in supermarkets
Wang, Shahzad, Ahmad, Abdullah and Hassan	2022	Systematic Literature Review	Sage Open	Trust and consumers' purchase intention in a social commerce platform: A meta-analytic approach	Empirical	Quantitative	Trust had an influential effect on the intention of consumers to buy
Hosseinikhah Choshaly	2019	Malaysia	International Journal of Innovation Science	Applying innovation attributes to predict purchase intention for the eco-labelled products: A Malaysian case study	Empirical	Quantitative	Relative advantage, trialability and observability influence the willingness of consumers to buy eco-friendly products
Kazancoglu and Aydin	2018	Turkey	International Journal of Retail & Distribution Management	An investigation of consumers' purchase intentions towards omni-channel shopping:	Empirical	Qualitative	Performance expectancy, effort expectancy, facilitating

				A qualitative exploratory study			conditions, hedonic motivation, habit, price value and perceived trust were considerations for purchase intention. Others were situational factors, perceived risk, anxiety, need for interaction and privacy concern played influential roles in forming the intention of customers
Hwai Lee and Yuen Han	2002	Singapore	Marketing Letters	Partitioned pricing in advertising: Effects on brand and retailer attitudes	Empirical	Quantitative	Attitude exhibited towards computer and stereo brands also influenced perceived value in terms of prices
Gan and Wang	2017	China	Internet	The influence of	Empirical	Quantitative	Perceived

				Research	perceived value on purchase intention in social commerce context			value components which were utilitarian, hedonic and social values positively affected purchase intention of customers
Zhang, Zhang and Pang	Liu, and	2021	China	Data Science and Management	The impact of consumer perceived value on repeat purchase intention based on online reviews: by the method of text mining	Empirical	Quantitative	The impact of consumer perceived value on repeat purchase intention based on online reviews: by the method of text mining. Customers had the intention to purchase accommodation services again due to the perceived value obtained from the services
Liu	and	2007	China	International	A qualitative	Empirical	Quantitative	Chinese

Murphy			Journal of Wine Business Research	study of Chinese wine consumption and purchasing: Implications for Australian wines			consumers drank made-in China alcoholic beverages regularly but reserved red wine for special occasion such as holidays or New Year
Amatulli and Guido	2011	Italy	Journal of Fashion Marketing and Management: An International Journal	Determinants of purchasing intention for fashion luxury goods in the Italian market: A laddering approach	Empirical	Quantitative	Consumers were likely to patronise fashion brands in order to satisfy their perception of value, specifically their lifestyle
Sharma, Pradhan and Srivastava	2021	India	Asia-Pacific Journal of Business Administration	Understanding the luxury purchase intentions of young consumers: a qualitative analysis	Empirical	Qualitative	Perceived value themes which were functional, social and emotional values significantly influenced purchase intentions of

							India young consumers among luxury brands
Hung, Huiling Chen, Peng, Hackley, Amy Tiwsakul and Chou	2011	Taiwan	Journal of Product & Brand Management	Antecedents of luxury brand purchase intention	Empirical	Quantitative	Although functional value influenced purchase intention, symbolic value did not
Eunju, Kim and Zhang	2008	China and South Korea	Journal of Global Academy of Marketing Science	A cross cultural study of antecedents of purchase intention for sports shoes in Korea and China	Empirical	Quantitative	Although perceived value specifically price had an influence of intention to buy in the Chinese, it did not influence intention to purchase in the South Korean Market
Roy, Basu and Ray	2020	India	Global Business Review	Antecedents of online purchase intention among ageing consumers	Empirical	Quantitative	Brand loyalty and social influence which were constructs of electronic word-of-mouth

							had a significant impact on the willingness to buy online
Miniard, Obermiller and Page Jr	1983	United States	Journal of Marketing Research	A further assessment of measurement influences on the intention-behaviour relationship	Empirical	Quantitative	Intentions to purchase soft drinks influenced actual purchase
Teng, Laroche and Zhu	2007	North America	Journal of Consumer Marketing	The effects of multiple-ads and multiple-brands on consumer attitude and purchase behaviour	Empirical	Quantitative	Attitudes exhibited towards advertised brands impacted consumers likelihood to purchase those brands
Wu and Lo	2009	Taiwan	Asia Pacific Journal of Marketing and Logistics	The influence of core-brand attitude and consumer perception on purchase intention towards extended product	Empirical	Quantitative	Customers attitude towards Microsoft personal computers brands affected their willingness to buy
Wang, Cao and	2019	South Korea	International	The relationships	Empirical	Quantitative	The usage of

Park			Journal of Information Management	among community experience, community commitment, brand attitude, and purchase intention in social media			social media advertising served as a source of improving brand attitude which tend to play an influential role in their quest to buy
Jung and Seock	2016	United States	Fashion and Textiles	The impact of corporate reputation on brand attitude and purchase intention	Empirical	Quantitative	Brand attitude and purchase intention minimised after receiving negative information
Tang, Luo and Xiao	2011	China	Journal of Product and Brand Management	Antecedents of intention to purchase mass customised products	Empirical	Quantitative	Attitude demonstrated towards a brand affect intention to purchase customised desktop computers
Nuzula and Wahyudi	2022	Indonesia	Innovative Marketing	Effects of brand attitude, perceived value, and social WOM on purchase intentions in luxury product marketing	Empirical	Quantitative	Social media users' attitude towards luxury brands had an impact on their intention to

							buy those brands
Pradhan, Duraipandian and Sethi	2016	India	Journal of Marketing Communications	Celebrity endorsement: How celebrity-brand-user personality congruence affects brand attitude and purchase intention	Empirical	Quantitative	Consumers attitude developed towards footwear brands had a partial effect on their willingness to buy
Chuenban, Sornsaruht and Pimdee	2021	Thailand	Heliyon	How brand attitude, brand quality, and brand value affect Thai canned tuna consumer brand loyalty	Empirical	Quantitative	Consumers attitude developed towards footwear brands had a partial effect on their willingness to buy
Plötz, Schneider, Globisch and Dütschke	2014	Germany	Transportation Research Part A: Policy and Practice	Who will buy electric vehicles? Identifying early adopters in Germany	Empirical	Quantitative	Attitudes were the most influential predictors, surpassing demographic and situational factors of a consumer's intention to adopt battery

							electric vehicles
Beck, Rose and Greaves	2017	Australia	Transportation	I can't believe your attitude: a joint estimation of best worst attitudes and electric vehicle choice	Empirical	Quantitative	Without proper consideration of the role of attitudes, accurate evaluation and prediction of consumer intentions were challenging
Moons and De Pelsmacker	2012	Belgium	Journal of Marketing Management	Emotions as determinants of electric car usage intention	Empirical	Quantitative	Attitude and emotions were strongest determinants for electric automobile adoption
Afroz, Masud, Islam and Duasa	2015	Malaysia	Environmental Science and Pollution Research	Consumer purchase intention towards environmentally friendly vehicles: an empirical investigation in Kuala Lumpur, Malaysia	Empirical	Quantitative	Attitudes significantly influenced purchase intention
Pop, Hlédik and Dabija	2023	Romania	Technological Forecasting and Social Change	Predicting consumers' purchase intention through fast fashion mobile	Empirical	Quantitative	Attitudes influenced purchase intention of mobile

				apps: The mediating role of attitude and the moderating role of COVID-19			application users
Kudeshia and Kumar	2017	India	Management Research Review	Social eWOM: does it affect the brand attitude and purchase intention of brands?	Empirical	Quantitative	Consumers attitude towards desktop smartphone brands influenced their intention to buy
Karamchandani, Karani and Jayswal	2021	India	Vision	Linkages between advertising value perception, context awareness value, brand attitude and purchase intention of hygiene products during COVID-19: a two-wave study	Empirical	Quantitative	Brand attitude did not influence the intention of consumers to purchase hygienic products during the Covid-19 pandemic
Mazodier and Merunka	2014	Not stated	Journal of Business Research	Beyond brand attitude: Individual drivers of purchase for symbolic cobranded products	Empirical	Quantitative	Attitude towards the brands did not influence consumers intention to purchase luxury brands

Hutchinson and Bennett	2012	United States	Sport Management Review	Core values brand building in sport: Stakeholder attitudes towards intercollegiate athletics and university brand congruency	Empirical	Quantitative	Intercollegiate athletics contributed to the formation of attitudes that affected the perceived value of the university
José Sanzo, Belén del Rí, Iglesias and Vázquez	2003	Spain	British Food Journal	Attitude and satisfaction in a traditional food product	Empirical	Quantitative	Consumers that had favourable predisposition towards generic honey tend to have high quality perceptions
Homer	2008	United States	Journal of Business Research	Perceived quality and image: When all is not “rosy”	Empirical	Quantitative	There is a positive relationship between brand attitude and perceived quality among nine automobile firms.
Wang	2013	Taiwan	International Journal of Retail & Distribution Management	The influence of visual packaging design on perceived food product quality, value, and brand	Empirical	Quantitative	Attitude towards the brands were based on the product packaging

				preference			features influenced the perception of food quality
Esmailpour	2015	Iran	Journal of Fashion Marketing and Management	The role of functional and symbolic brand associations on brand loyalty: A study on luxury brands	Empirical	Quantitative	Perceived quality as a better predictor of attitude towards brands
Dall'Olmo Riley, Pina and Bravo	2015	United Kingdom	Journal of Marketing Management	The role of perceived value in vertical brand extensions of luxury and premium brands	Empirical	Quantitative	Brands influenced the perceived quality that consumers held
Huang, Lee and Hsun Ho	2014	Taiwan	International Marketing Review	Consumer attitude toward gray market goods	Empirical	Quantitative	A negative relationship existed between brand attitude and perceived quality
Ajitha and Sivakumar	2017	India	Journal of Retailing and Consumer Services	Understanding the effect of personal and social value on attitude and usage behaviour of luxury cosmetic brands	Empirical	Quantitative	There was a positive relationship between brand attitude and social value in the cosmetics market
Petrick	2004	Caribbean	Journal of	The roles of	Empirical	Quantitative	Consumer

			Travel Research	quality, value, and satisfaction in predicting cruise passengers' behavioural intentions			perceived value has a predictive power in cruise line industry
McDougall and Levesque	2000	Canada	Journal of Services Marketing	Customer satisfaction with services: putting perceived value into the equation	Empirical	Quantitative	Perceived value influenced future purchase intentions
Durvasula, Lysonski, Mehta and Tang	2004	Singapore	Journal of Financial Services Marketing	Forging relationships with services: the antecedents that have an impact on behavioural outcomes in the life insurance industry	Empirical	Quantitative	Customers influenced by perceived value affected purchasing intentions
Calvo-Porrall and Lévy-Mangin	2017	Spain	European Research on Management and Business Economics	Store brands' purchase intention: Examining the role of perceived quality	Empirical	Quantitative	Both high and low product quality influenced the intention to purchase store brands
Tsiotsou	2005	Greece	Marketing Bulletin	Perceived quality levels and their relation to involvement, satisfaction, and purchase intentions	Empirical	Quantitative	Perceived quality of students played an important role in forming the decision to

							purchase sports shoes
Das	2014	India	Journal of Retailing and Consumer Services	Linkages of retailer personality, perceived quality and purchase intention with retailer loyalty: A study of Indian non-food retailing	Empirical	Quantitative	Perceived quality among non-food retail shoppers had an impact on their willingness to buy
Wang, Tao and Chu	2020	China	Food Control	Behind the label: Chinese consumers' trust in food certification and the effect of perceived quality on purchase intention	Empirical	Quantitative	Perception among consumers played a significant influence in developing their purchase decision
Shukla and Purani	2012	US, UK, India and Malaysia	Journal of Business Research	Comparing the importance of luxury value perceptions in cross-national contexts	Empirical	Quantitative	Perception of quality had an influential effect on consumers' intention to purchase
Chattalas and Shukla	2015	US and UK	Luxury Research Journal	Impact of value perceptions on luxury purchase intentions: a developed market comparison	Empirical	Quantitative	Perception that consumers hold about the quality of an offering had an impact on intention to

							purchase
Celik and Erciş	2018	Turkey	Press Academia Procedia	Impact of value perceptions on luxury purchase intentions: Moderating role of consumer knowledge	Empirical	Quantitative	The impact of quality as a value perception construct on consumers' willingness to buy
Makhitha	2021	South Africa	International Journal of Research in Business and Social Science	Black consumers perceptions towards luxury brands in South Africa	Empirical	Quantitative	A key determinant of consumer purchase intention is the perception held about the quality of products
Richardson, Dick and Jain	1994	United States	Journal of Marketing	Extrinsic and intrinsic cue effects on perceptions of store brand quality	Empirical	Quantitative	Shoppers were more interested in their perceptions of price than perceptions of quality in determining their willingness to purchase
Reyes-Menendez, Palos-Sanchez, Saura and	2022	Spain	European Management Journal	Revisiting the impact of perceived social value on consumer	Empirical	Quantitative	There was no positive relationship between

Santos				behaviour toward luxury brands			perceived quality and consumers' willingness to buy
Canguende-Valentim and Vale	2022	Angola	Journal of Global Marketing	The Effect of Value Perceptions on Luxury Purchase Intentions: An Angolan Market Perspective	Empirical	Quantitative	Perception of quality was not a key construct in determining the intention to buy luxury brands
Wang	2010	Taiwan	Journal of Food Products Marketing	Impact of multiple perceived value on consumers' brand preference and purchase intention: a case of snack foods	Empirical	Quantitative	Perception of quality did not influence consumers intention to purchase
Bolton and Lemon	1999	United States	Journal of Marketing Research	A dynamic model of customers' usage of services: Usage as an antecedent and consequence of satisfaction	Empirical	Quantitative	Customer's evaluation of product price as fair or unfair has a significant influence on their intentions to repeat a purchase
Kim, Xu and Gupta	2012	South Korea	Electronic Commerce Research and Applications	Which is more important in Internet shopping, perceived price or	Empirical	Quantitative	Prospects and customers based on their perception of

				trust?			price to develop their willingness to purchase
Ali and Bhasin	2019	India	Jindal Journal of Business Research	Understanding customer repurchase intention in e-commerce: role of perceived price, delivery quality, and perceived value	Empirical	Quantitative	Perception of price that consumers have played a crucial role in determining their intention to buy
Son and Jin	2019	United States	Asia Pacific Journal of Marketing and Logistics	When do high prices lead to purchase intention? Testing two layers of moderation effects	Empirical	Quantitative	Perceived price was identified as having impact on the consumers' willingness to purchase
Pan, Liu and Ha	2022	South Korea	International Journal of Contemporary Hospitality Management	Perceived price and trustworthiness of online reviews: different levels of promotion and customer type	Empirical	Quantitative	Perceived nature of price significantly influence intention to buy
Yu, Hudders and Cauberghe	2018	United States	Journal of Electronic Commerce Research	Selling luxury products online: The effect of a quality label on risk perception, purchase intention and attitude toward	Empirical	Quantitative	Perception of price did not play a major role in determining the willingness of consumers

				the brand			to buy luxury brands
Forgas-Coll, Palau-Saumell, Sánchez-García and Maria Caplliure-Giner	2014	Spain	Management Decision	The role of trust in cruise passenger behavioral intentions: The moderating effects of the cruise line brand	Empirical	Quantitative	Social value attached to the cruise lines affected the decision of customers to patronise their services again
Ha	2021	Vietnam	Cogent Business & Management	The impact of product characteristics of limited-edition shoes on perceived value, brand trust and purchase intention	Empirical	Quantitative	Consumers relied on products to enhance their societal standing, and this tend to influence their buying decision
Jain, Bhaskar and Jain	2022	India	Research in Transportation Business & Management	What drives adoption intention of electric vehicles in India? An integrated UTAUT model with environmental concerns, perceived risk and government support	Empirical	Quantitative	The likelihood to purchase battery electric vehicle brand is influenced by the opinions within the customer's social circle
Krishnan and Koshy	2021	India	Case Studies on Transport	Evaluating the factors influencing	Empirical	Quantitative	Social status influenced

			Policy	purchase intention of electric vehicles in households owning conventional vehicles			purchase decisions among consumers in electric vehicle adoption
Sanyal, Datta and Banerjee	2014	India	International Journal of Indian Culture and Business Management	Attitude of Indian consumers towards luxury brand purchase: an application of 'attitude scale to luxury items'	Empirical	Quantitative	Social value played an important role in triggering purchase intention
Ozen and Engizek	2014	Turkey	Asia Pacific Journal of Marketing and Logistics	Shopping online without thinking: being emotional or rational?	Empirical	Quantitative	Social value influenced intention to purchase
Narang	2016	China	Journal of Retailing and Consumer Services	Understanding purchase intention towards Chinese products: Role of ethnocentrism, animosity, status and self-esteem	Empirical	Quantitative	Social value did not influence intention to buy
Zhou, Long, Kong, Zhao, Jia and Campy	2021	China	Transportation Research Part A: Policy and Practice	Characterizing the motivational mechanism behind taxi driver's adoption of electric vehicles for living: Insights from China	Empirical	Quantitative	Social value was not a taken into account in forming intention to buy among Chinese consumers
Naseem,	2015	Not stated	International	Global brand	Conceptual	Quantitative	No results

Verma and Yaprak			Marketing in the Fast-Changing World	attitude, perceived value, consumer affinity, and purchase intentions: A multidimensional view of consumer behaviour and global brands			presented
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APPENDIX D

PARTICIPANT CONSENT FORM

UWS UNIVERSITY OF THE
WEST of SCOTLAND

Participant Consent Form

Name of Investigator: Frederick Okyere Asiedu

Research Title: Brand Attitude, Perceived Value and Purchase Intention in the Automobile Industry

1. I..... voluntarily agree to participate in this research study.
2. I confirm that I have read and understood the Participant Information Sheet for the above project and the researcher has answered any queries to my satisfaction.
3. I understand that even if I agree to participate now, I can withdraw at any time or refuse to answer any question without any consequences of any kind.
4. I agree that my participation in the research will be filling of a questionnaire and/or an interview.
5. I understand that I can withdraw permission to use data at any time during the research task.
6. I have had the purpose and nature of the study explained to me in writing and I have

had the opportunity to ask questions about the study.

7. I understand that I will not benefit directly from participating in this research.
8. I understand that all information I provide for this study will be treated confidentially.
9. I understand that in any report on the results of this research, my identity will remain anonymous. This will be done by changing my name and disguising any details of my information which may reveal my identity or the identity of people I speak about.
10. I understand that if I inform the researcher that I or someone else is at risk of harm they may have to report this to the relevant authorities - they will discuss this with me first but may be required to report with or without my permission.
11. I understand that signed consent forms will be retained by the researcher under the act of the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) until the exam board confirms the results of the thesis.
12. I understand that my responses in the questionnaire and/or interview guide which all identifying information has been removed and will be retained under the GDPR policy until the exam board confirms the results of the thesis.
13. I understand that under freedom of information legislation I am entitled to access the information I have provided at any time while it is in storage as specified above.
14. I understand that I am free to contact any of the people involved in the research to seek further clarification and information.

Signature of participant

Signature:

Date:

Signature of researcher

I believe the participant is giving informed consent to participate in this study

Signature:

Date:

APPENDIX E

PARTICIPANT INFORMATION SHEET

Name of School: University of the West of Scotland

Degree: PhD in Marketing

Title of Dissertation:

BRAND ATTITUDE, PERCEIVED VALUE AND PURCHASE INTENTION IN THE AUTOMOBILE INDUSTRY

I would like to invite you to take part in a research study that involves a distribution of questionnaire and interview of participants. Before you decide you need to understand why the research is being done and what it involves. Please take time to read the following information carefully. Please feel free to ask questions if anything you read is not clear or if you would like more information. Take time to decide whether you want to take part.

1 Confidentiality, Anonymity and Protection Agreement

In this research, all participants will be anonymous, and any information given by the participants will not be revealed such as names. Any information given by the participant will be encrypted and contain password access and only the researcher who will have access.

2 Please read all details below to take part

My name is Frederick Asiedu. I am a PhD student at University of the West of Scotland (UWS). I am carrying out a research about my dissertation, I have chosen a mixed study, and the topic is Brand Attitude, Perceived Value and Purchase Intention in the Automobile Industry. The University of the West of Scotland, School of Business and Creative Studies is allowing me to carry out the research.

3 What is the investigation purpose?

The aim of this study is to determine the impact of Brand Attitude on Perceived Value and Purchase Intention within the Automobile Industry in Ghana

4 Do you have to take part?

Participation in this research is voluntary. Therefore, participants are not obliged to answer the questions. A consent form will be included to sign showing participants have agreed to take part of the research with their willingness to withdraw anytime they choose to without any constrictions.

5 How will you take part?

The researcher will personally send a copy of the questionnaire and conduct a face-to-face interview with participants.

What is your role in this project?

Questions will focus on determining the impact of brand attitude, perceived value and Purchase Intention within the Automobile Industry in Ghana. The questions will take a maximum of 50 minutes. With the guidelines of the Social Research Association (2003), privacy, confidentiality, preventing risk and harm to both sides (interviewer and interviewees), and information integrity have been taken into consideration to follow. Moreover, if any un-convenience is to appear in questions, the participants do not need to give any answer.

6 Why have you been invited to take part?

You have been considered the main participants of the research because you play a key role in the automobile industry in Ghana

and you appear to have the knowledge and experience to answer those questions.

7 What are the potential risks you may face in taking-part?

The questions follow a structure which guarantees your privacy and status will be protected, and no restrictions on you to answer all or any question you may not fancy. Furthermore, during the research no physical, legal or psychological issue will be exposed.

8 What happens to the information you give?

The information given will be in a secure and password protected file. Any references to individuals will be removed unless the participants want it to appear. As well as the whole information which has been carried out in the research will be destroyed as soon as the research has been submitted successfully.

The University of the West of Scotland is registered with the Information Commissioner's Office who implements the Data Protection Act 2018. All personal data on participants will be processed in accordance with the provisions of the Data Protection Act 2018.

Thank you for taking your time to read the whole information. If you have any questions concerning the form, you are welcome to ask.

9 What happens next?

If you agree to be a participant in this research, a consent form will be sent to your email and you can please sign it to confirm your participation and send it back. However, if you do not wish to take any participation, you do not need to sign and thank you for the time you have spent going reading the whole form. If you have any feedback, you are free to send it as soon as the investigation is complete.

The research was given ethical approval by the University of the West of Scotland, School of Business and Ethics committee. If there is, during or after the research, any question, concern, or you would wish to contact an independent body who part of the university Ethics Committee is, you may feel free to contact the following address:

School Ethics Committee

University of the West of Scotland

Paisley Campus

Paisley

PA1 2BE

Scotland, UK

Personal details withheld.